

Brexit And Intergovernmental Relations: A Comparative Case Study of Scotland and Wales and the New Common Framework for Agricultural Support

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Declaration

I declare that, except where explicit reference is made to the contribution of others, this thesis is the result of my own individual work and has not been submitted for DBA, DProf, EngD or PhD or comparable academic award at the University of the West of Scotland or any other institution.

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Abstract

The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) is a key European Union (EU) policy that the UK has participated in since joining the European Community (EC) in 1973. After 1999, Scotland and Wales's devolved administrations (DAs) were responsible for delivering this policy. Following the UK's withdrawal from the EU, the CAP no longer applied, necessitating a replacement agricultural support policy framework. A Joint Ministerial Communiqué (2017) stipulated that these new common frameworks (NCF) would be designed jointly by the UK government and the devolved administrations, underpinned by coordination, cooperation, and respect for the devolution settlements. The Provisional Common Framework for Agricultural Support was published in February 2022.

This thesis examines how the intergovernmental relationship (IGR) enabled the devolved governments in Scotland and Wales to participate in designing a new common framework for agricultural support. It explores the fundamental principles and structures underpinning the UK's IGR, examining their development since devolution's introduction. It also investigates how previous engagement with the UK government in agricultural support policy has shaped the current intergovernmental relationship. Since 1999, devolution in Scotland and Wales has been enhanced through the Scotland Acts of 2012 and 2016, the Government of Wales Acts of 2006 and 2014, and the Wales Act 2017, granting more power to the devolved administrations. Several reviews commissioned by the UK government raised concerns about the IGR's formal machinery and informal relationships, recommending improvements. In 2018, the UK and devolved governments agreed to commission another intergovernmental review, published in January 2022.

A comparative case study was conducted on the experiences of the Scottish and Welsh governments. This thesis draws on literature from historical institutionalism and path dependency to perform a historical analysis using process tracing spanning from 1999 to 2022. Data from official documents and parliamentary and committee meeting transcripts were analysed using critical realism thematic analysis. This study contributes to the burgeoning literature on common and agricultural support frameworks. It enriches the existing literature on intergovernmental relations, providing historical contextualisation of UK government-commissioned reviews of IGR. Additionally, this research advances the study of historical institutionalism by offering a nuanced understanding of how institutional arrangements adapt and persist over time.

List of Abbreviations

CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
DAs	Devolved Administrations
DEFRA	Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs
EEC	European Economic Community
EU	European Union
FOA	Framework Outline Agreement
HI	Historical Intuitionism
HoL	House of Lords
IGF	Intergovernmental Framework
IGR	Intergovernmental Relations
IMG	Inter-ministerial Group
IMG EFRA	Inter-ministerial Group for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs
IMSC	Inter-ministerial Standing Committee
JMC	Joint Ministerial Committee
JMC EN	Joint Ministerial Committee European Union Negotiations
MA	Member of the Assembly
MAFF	Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food
MLG	Multi-Level Governance
MMG	Market Monitoring Group
MOU	Memorandum of Understanding
MP	Member of Parliament
MS	Member of the Senedd
MSP	Member of the Scottish Parliament

NCF	New Common Frameworks
NCF AS	New Common Framework for Agricultural Support
NI	New Institutionalism
NFU	National Farmers Union
PCG	Policy Collaboration Group
PD	Path Dependency
RC	Rational Choice Institutionalism
SI	Sociological Institutionalism
SG	Scottish Government
SNP	Scottish National Party
SOPB	Senior Officials Programme Board
UK	United Kingdom
UKG	United Kingdom Government
UKIMA	United Kingdom Internal Market Act (2020)
WA	Welsh Assembly
WG	Welsh Government

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Chapter 1

1.1 Introduction

This thesis aims to critically examine the pivotal role of the intergovernmental relationship in enabling the Scottish and Welsh Governments to participate with the UK government in developing a new common framework for agricultural support. This chapter introduces the rationale for this study, detailing its aims, research questions, and theoretical and methodological approaches and underscoring their relevance. It concludes with a comprehensive thesis outline, establishing the foundations of this in-depth exploration of the intergovernmental relationship between the Scottish, Welsh and UK administrations.

1.2 Context for the Study

The United Kingdom (UK) has been a member of the European Community since 1973 but in 2016 voted to leave. The UK is the first member state to leave the European Union (EU), a process commonly referred to as Brexit, signifying this unique departure. The UK was an EU member state, but the devolved governments of Scotland and Wales were responsible for implementing EU directives that fell within their competency. To leave the EU, the UK government began by introducing legislation into the House of Commons, passing the European Union (Withdrawal) Act, 2018. The Act included provisions stating that powers previously exercised by the EU in devolved areas would be transferred to the devolved administrations after the transition period. However, the Act gave UK ministers the power to temporarily freeze the devolved governments' powers to prevent them from legislating in areas where common frameworks were necessary (Paun, 2017). It was agreed that a common approach would be required where powers returned from the EU fell within areas of devolved competence (Cabinet Office, 2018). In October 2017, the UK, Scottish, and Welsh governments gathered at a Joint Ministerial European Negotiations (EN) meeting and agreed that a new common framework (NCF) would replace the EU policy frameworks. A communiqué stated that all parties agreed that this would be a collaborative and cooperative effort underpinned by respect for devolution (Cabinet Office, 2017).

1.2.2 Intergovernmental Relations

When the UK joined the European Community, the Scottish, Welsh, and Northern Ireland Offices oversaw European policy delivery. These offices were directed by Secretaries of State who are government ministers. During the UK's time as a member of the EU, devolved administrations (DAs) were established. In 1999, the Scotland Act 1998 created a Scottish

Parliament with a reserved power model of executive and legislative authority over policy areas, except for specific areas explicitly reserved by Westminster (Keating, 2018). The Government of Wales Act 1998 created the National Assembly for Wales, granting devolution based on a conferred power model. This model gave the Assembly only secondary legislative powers over specific policy areas, while Westminster retained authority over all other areas. The Government of Wales Act 2006 restructured the Assembly from a corporate body to a separate legislature, the National Assembly for Wales and established a new executive Welsh Assembly government (Trench, 2007). The Wales Act 2017 granted primary legislative powers aligning with Scotland's devolution settlement and enabled the assembly to change its name (Moon & Evans, 2017). In 2019, the assembly voted to change its name to the Senedd Cymru or Welsh Parliament.

The introduction of devolution in 1999 demanded a new intergovernmental framework, enabling interaction between the UK government and the institutions of these new administrations (Keating, 2005; Cairney, 2012). With its primarily unwritten constitution and devolved administrations established by an Act of Parliament, the UK is distinct from a federal state. It is common for a federal state to have a constitution that clarifies its role, the sub-states within it, and how the relationship between the two should function in areas where crossover occurs (Keating, 2005; Cairney, 2012). The intergovernmental framework reflects the political system in place, with the UK as a union state and a crossover of competencies (Keating, 2010).

Due to the lack of clear boundaries and the potential for crossover over who holds responsibility, significant cooperation and coordination between governments are necessary (Keating, 2010). Institutional interactions can occur through both formal and informal processes and mechanisms. Formal mechanisms include intergovernmental agreements such as Memorandums of Understanding (MOU) and concordats that set out arrangements for joint working. However, these are not legally binding agreements (Cairney, 2006; Horgan, 2004). Another aspect of the intergovernmental relationship (IGR) was the Joint Ministerial Committee (JMC). The JMC was a mechanism to discuss shared competence areas, coordinate policy initiatives, and deal with disagreements. These JMCs take several formats, such as plenary meetings, European affairs, and European Negotiations, to address the UK's exit from the EU (McEwen, 2017).

However, the UK government abolished the JMC in 2021, and Chapter 7 will discuss this change to the intergovernmental machinery in more detail. The UK government commissioned

several reviews of devolution and the intergovernmental framework throughout the devolution settlement. These reviews have recommended increased power for devolved governments and improvements to intergovernmental machinery. The recommendations contributed to the Scotland Acts of 2012 and 2016, the Government of Wales Acts of 2006 and 2017, and the Wales Act 2014. The review's criticism of the intergovernmental relationship found an overreliance on informal relationships and a lack of transparency (Hol, 2002). The Calman Commission (2007) reviewed devolution and called for an enhanced JMC and changes to the civil service. The Smith Commission (2014) also criticised the informality of the intergovernmental framework, finding that most disputes were dealt with through unofficial discussions with civil servants and ministers (Cairney, 2012). The Smith Commission (2016) recommended that a more explicit system was required to ensure further devolution and power-sharing would function and that a more effective method of conflict resolution would reduce the potential for future conflict. While each review instigated a new Act that granted powers, the UK resisted significantly reforming the IGR to resolve these criticisms.

At the start of the new common framework process at a Joint Ministerial Committee (plenary) in 2018, the UK government and the devolved administrations agreed to conduct another review of the IGR. It was decided that a good working relationship that enabled cooperation and coordination between the UK government and devolved administrations was desirable for developing and designing new common frameworks (Cabinet Office, 2021). There were concerns about how the existing intergovernmental framework might perform once the UK was no longer under EU law (Cabinet Office, 2021). Policy crossover and institutional interdependence might become more apparent after Brexit, so replacing frameworks must be a coordinated, co-owned process based on consent (McEwen, 2021). The House of Lords' New Common Frameworks scrutiny committee report emphasised that this process must underpin the principle of building a cooperative union for the future (House of Lords, 2021). The intergovernmental review was published in 2022, a month before the common framework for agricultural support.

1.2.3 Common Frameworks

The Joint Ministerial European Negotiations (EN) communiqué sets out common frameworks' agreed purpose and principles. Their purpose was to enable the functioning of the UK internal market while allowing some degree of divergence, ensuring compliance with international obligations, enabling the UK to enter trade deals without impediments, ensuring that

international commitments are met, and protecting the security of the UK (Cabinet Office, 2017; Cabinet Office, 2019). The agreed principles that underpin the frameworks are:

- **Respect the devolution settlement and democratic ability of the devolved legislatures.**
- **Be based on established conventions and practices, including the fact that the competence of the devolved institutions will not normally be adjusted without their consent.**
- **Maintain, as a minimum, equivalent flexibility for tailoring policies to the specific needs of each territory as is afforded by current EU rules.**
- **Lead to a significant increase in decision-making powers for the devolved administrations. (Cabinet Office, 2017).**

In the early stages of common framework development, the number of frameworks required was undecided. However, the UK government agreed they would only be developed in policy areas where necessary (Cabinet Office, 2017). Also, it was undecided how each framework would be regulated.

"Frameworks may be implemented by legislation, by executive action, by memorandums of understanding, or by other means depending on the context in which the framework is intended to operate" (Cabinet Office, 2017, p.2).

The Cabinet Office mapped out policy areas that might require a common framework. It was decided that a common framework would be necessary to replace the EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). The CAP is a key European Union (EU) policy in which the UK government has participated in development and implementation since it joined the European Community (EC) in 1973. In 1999, Scotland and Wales's devolved administrations (DAs) became responsible for implementing this policy. Since the UK's withdrawal from the EU renders the CAP obsolete, the UK government and the devolved administrations agreed to develop a new common framework for agricultural support.

Since 1999, the UK's devolved administrations have been responsible for delivering agricultural policy directives from the EU (Gravey, 2019). Designing a new common framework for agricultural support that harmonises standards while maintaining flexibility to fit the needs of each territory would be challenging. The CAP is designed to accommodate a wide range of environments (nine biogeographical regions within Europe) and allows each member to create strategies to achieve the best outcomes (Cole, 2020). The UK is an excellent

example of a member state that has benefited from this flexible approach. For example, Scotland has specific challenges and different types of farming from other parts of the UK, as 73% of Scotland's landmass is classified as agricultural. Still, only 10% is suitable for crops, and 55% is classified as only appropriate for rough grazing (Scottish Government, 2016). England is 70% farmed, and 55% is classified as cropland (DEFRA, 2019). Wales comprises the most significant proportion of agricultural land (84%). Only 14% of the land is classified as suitable for crops, while the rest is classified as grassland (70%) or rough grazing (10%) (Armstrong, 2016). The CAP recognised these differences, and Scotland, England, Wales, and Northern Ireland had to submit separate reports to the EU Rural Development Programme (RDP) (Keating & Stephenson, 2006).

Because of the level of diversity across the UK, each part can determine its priorities within the EU directive; thus, the policy has evolved differently across the UK. "There are four CAPs across the UK" (Scott, 2013, p.17694). English agricultural policy focuses on diversification and agro-environmental schemes. Scotland and Wales's farming sectors predominantly focus on Less Favoured Land (LFL), mainly supporting sheep and cattle hill farming. The problematic nature of terrain limits the possibility of diversification (Gelan & Schwarz, 2008; Gray, 2010; Bunce, 2018). The CAP support falls into two categories: pillar 1, Rural Funding, which provides direct funding to support farmers' income, including the Less Favoured Areas Support Scheme (LFASS), which has been crucial for Scottish and Welsh hill farmers and crofters who farm in Less Favourable Areas (LFA) (House of Commons Library, 2018), and pillar 2, which funds environmental and rural development (UK Government, 2018).

Less favourable areas (LFA) include moorlands, grasslands, and peatlands. It is important not to disturb peatlands, as they function as carbon storage. Moorlands and grasslands protect biodiversity. Over 40% of agricultural land has a high natural value (HNV) (NFUS, 2019). Therefore, changes in support for hillside farming will be highly relevant to Scotland and Wales but less relevant to England. The National Farmers Union of Scotland (NFUS) called for the UK government to respect the need for policy divergence:

"The UK Government must fully commit to a multi-annual, ring-fenced agricultural and rural development budget and the Bew Review while ensuring proper independent governance of commonly agreed UK regulatory frameworks." (NFUS, 2019).

While designing the new common framework, the UK government released a new policy plan for agricultural support in England, *Health and Harmony: The Future for Food, Farming, and the Environment in a Green Brexit* (DEFRA, 2018). This new policy direction focuses on future

agricultural support based on 'public money for public goods.' This policy eventually leads to subsidies or support for unprofitable farms being phased out (Dwyer, 2018; Gravey, 2019). The National Farmers Union for Scotland and Wales have voiced concern that replacing CAP quickly or removing all subsidies is unrealistic and should be moderated and simplified.

"The Scottish Government must use the full extent of its devolved powers to enable the continued, but improved, delivery of a package of existing policy measures that meet the needs and profile of Scottish agriculture, as well as the development and implementation of new measures that will allow Scottish agriculture to establish a firm foundation for more meaningful change from 2024." (NFUS, 2020).

Concerns about Scotland and Wales's ability to continue having similar control over agricultural policy and their support within the EU were crucial factors in designing the new common framework. There is potential for conflict if divergence is restricted or if policy decided in England sets the basis and priorities of the framework for agricultural support across the UK.

1.2.4 Exploring the Factors Behind Political Tensions

This thesis examines how the intergovernmental relationship enabled the Scottish and Welsh administrations to participate in designing a new common framework for agricultural support with the UK government. However, this process occurred during a tumultuous period in UK political history. Consequently, it is important to consider the political context to understand how some events overshadowed joint discussions while developing the new common framework.

The first event that instigated political tensions between governments began in 2016 with the outcome of the referendum to withdraw from the European Union. The referendum result was 52% in favour of leaving. The result was not without controversy, with England (53.4%) and Wales (52.5%) voting to leave, but Scotland (62%) and Northern Ireland (55.8%) voting in favour of remaining in the EU (The Electoral Commission, 2019). Prime Minister David Cameron resigned immediately after the referendum. The First Minister of Scotland, Nicola Sturgeon, gave a speech on the result, stating:

"The vote across England and Wales was a rejection of the EU, and it was a sign of divergence between Scotland and large parts of the rest of the UK in how we see our place in the world. Furthermore, as things stand, Scotland faces the prospect of being taken out of the EU against our will. I regard that as democratically unacceptable" (Sturgeon, 2016).

McHarg and Mitchell (2017) argued that different territorial results indicated a shift in constitutional politics and produced divergent outcomes. The UK would now have to establish replacement policy frameworks with two devolved governments whose citizens voted against Brexit.

A second event that increased tensions and raised concerns in the devolved administrations arose when the UK government, with Theresa May as the new Prime Minister in July 2016, introduced the first draft of the European Union (Withdrawal) Bill to the House of Commons. This Bill aimed to repeal the European Communities Act of 1972 and incorporate all existing EU laws into UK statute books. Once passed, the Bill would grant ministers 'Henry VIII' powers, allowing the UK government to amend or repeal retained EU law with less parliamentary scrutiny, facilitating a swift transfer and avoiding a legal gap. Additionally, the Bill included provisions, notably in Section 12, enabling the UK government to temporarily 'freeze' devolved competencies until new policy frameworks could be agreed upon to replace EU frameworks. The devolved administrations accused the UK government of a 'power grab.' As agriculture is a devolved policy, Angus Robertson (SNP) asked the Prime Minister directly in the House of Commons about powers being returned to devolved governments.

"Ministers could not answer basic questions about the Government's plans for agriculture and fisheries. These are important industries for the rural economy and are devolved to the Scottish Government and Parliament. With Brexit ending the role of Brussels in those areas, will all decisions about agriculture and fisheries be made at Holyrood—yes, or no?" (Robertson, 2017).

The Prime Minister responded by stating that the UK government discussed common frameworks with the devolved governments, but the single market of the United Kingdom was a more important issue (May 2017). The Scottish and Welsh governments initially refused to grant a Legislative Consent Motion (the Sewel Convention) that would consent to the UK government passing legislation on devolved policy areas. The Welsh Government was concerned because the Bill had the power to alter the Government of Wales Act 2006, constraining devolution and shifting the balance of power further in favour of the UK government. The Welsh Government eventually consented to the EU (Withdrawal) Bill when a modified version of the Act was agreed upon. However, David Rees (LAB), Member of the Senedd and Chair of the External Affairs and Additional Legislation Committee, still had concerns:

"We remain particularly concerned that the Assembly's ability to pass laws in devolved policy areas such as agriculture could be constrained by the UK Parliament, even in circumstances where the Assembly has refused consent for such constraints to be imposed" (Rees, 2018, p. 172).

The Scottish Government refused to grant consent, and in a debate in the Scottish Parliament on the European Union (Withdrawal) Bill, Bruce Crawford (SNP) expressed concerns:

"While the Bill may be complex, there is no doubt that it represents a fundamental challenge to the devolution settlement and that, as currently drafted, it undermines the principles upon which this Parliament was established" (Crawford, 2018, p. 27).

Bruce Crawford, the Finance and Constitution Committee convener, had engaged with academics and legal experts on the Bill, concluding that two significant issues with the Bill prevented the Scottish Government from issuing a legislative consent motion. The first issue was Clause 11. The Scottish Government had a similar concern as the Welsh Government and believed that this would enable powers to be taken from the devolved governments and returned to Westminster:

"The evidence that the committee took was remarkably consistent in emphasising that clause 11 not only undermines the devolution settlement but would result in a fundamental shift in the structure of devolution from a reserved-powers model to a conferred-powers model. This shift inevitably creates an increasingly complex boundary between devolved and reserved powers" (Crawford, 2018, p. 28).

Despite the Scottish government's refusal to provide a legislative consent motion, the European Union (Withdrawal) Act received royal assent in June 2018. The possibility that the UK government would use the European Union (Withdrawal) Act 2018 to 'freeze' devolved powers overshadowed the development of the common frameworks and introduced further unease.

The third issue during this period occurred with the UK government's attempt to bypass Parliament and invoke Article 50 of the Treaty on the European Union. This action prompted a legal case in the High Court of England and Wales to prevent the Government from triggering Article 50 without the consent of Parliament. A separate court case in Northern Ireland ruled that the UK government did not require the consent of devolved governments to consent to the EU withdrawal (Fabbrini, 2017). These outcomes led to an appeal in the Supreme Court R (Miller) v Secretary of State for Exiting the European Union. In its decision, the Supreme Court reached three conclusions: a parliamentary agreement was required to invoke Article 50, the UK Parliament was sovereign, and a fundamental principle of the UK constitution, and devolved consent was not needed in this matter (Fabbrini, 2017). Therefore, the UK

government had to introduce the European Union (Notification of Withdrawal) Act 2017 so that Parliament could grant permission for the Prime Minister to instigate Article 50 of the Treaty of the European Union to start negotiations to withdraw from the EU. However, the Legislative Consent Motion (Sewel Convention) in the Memorandum of Understanding established that the UK government would not legislate in the devolved policy area without the consent of the devolved governments. This court ruling affirmed the ineffective legal status of the Sewel Convention, allowing the UK government to pass legislation on devolved competencies: "Since the convention is simply constitutional, political convention and accordingly non-justiciable" (Engel & Petetin, 2018, p. 26). The Supreme Court judgment established that devolved governments held no power to prevent the UK government from passing legislation on devolved matters.

The UK experienced more upheaval, leading to political instability. The Fixed-term Parliaments Act 2011 ensured that the next election would not occur until 2020. However, Theresa May called for a snap election in 2017 to increase Conservative Party support and bolster the Government's Brexit mandate (Hobolt, 2018). The Conservatives won but fell short of a majority and relied on a confidence and supply agreement with the DUP. The UK government struggled to obtain the House of Commons approval for a withdrawal agreement with the EU. This increased concerns that the UK might leave the EU without a deal, causing significant issues, especially for Northern Ireland, which borders the EU's Republic of Ireland.

Under pressure from further defeats in reaching an agreement in the House of Commons, May requested an extension of Article 50 to prevent the UK from leaving the EU without a deal, extending the leave date to April 2019. Theresa May could not reach an agreement in Parliament, so she had to seek another extension until October 2019. After experiencing several votes of no confidence, May announced her resignation in July 2019 to be replaced by Boris Johnson as Prime Minister. Johnson also failed to reach an agreement and had to request another Article 50 extension. The UK government attempted to prorogue Parliament in September 2019, but the Supreme Court blocked this action. A third extension was accepted in October 2019, with a new deadline of January 2020. In the 2019 election, Johnson's Conservative Party won an 80-seat majority. The SNP won 48 of the 59 seats, making it the third-largest party in the Commons (ONS, 2020). An agreement was reached, the European Union (Withdrawal Agreement) Act 2020 passed, and the UK left the EU on the 31st of January 2020.

Amidst the political turmoil, the Covid-19 pandemic occurred. Health is a devolved matter, so the UK and its devolved governments had to collaborate. Whitehall departments had to cooperate with ministers and officials from Holyrood and Cardiff. During the pandemic, many officials were reassigned from common frameworks. Lesley Griffiths (MS) reported to the Climate Change, Environment, and Rural Affairs Committee that 300 of her 800 officials were reassigned to the Covid-19 response (Griffiths, 2020, p. 171). This also occurred in the Scottish and UK Governments, impeding the progress of common frameworks for agricultural support. As a result, the Common Framework for Agricultural Support should have been available in January 2020 as soon as the UK withdrew from the EU. However, the provisional document was not published until February 2022.

1.2.5 New UK Legislation on Intergovernmental Agreement

As the common framework development program began, the UK government introduced two pieces of legislation: the Agriculture Act 2020 and the UK Internal Market Act 2020. A third piece of legislation, the Subsidy Control Act 2022, was introduced after the Provisional Common Framework for Agricultural Support was published. These pieces of legislation would generate significant tension in devolved governments and are repeatedly mentioned by ministers and officials in the following findings. A brief outline of these Acts is provided below.

The Agriculture Act 2020 received royal assent on the 11th of November 2020. Most of the Act pertains only to England. However, some small sections apply across the UK. The UK government claimed that this legislation would be transformative for English agriculture, and the purpose of the Act was to "establish a new agricultural system based on the principle of public money for public goods for the next generation of farmers and land managers" (UK Government, 2020). The seven-year phase of direct support payments began in 2021. Funding was available only for the Environmental Land Management Scheme (ELMS). The legislation was introduced before completing the common framework for agricultural support, raising concerns about the implications of removing subsidies in England for direct support payments in Scotland and Wales.

The Internal Market Act 2020 contains two key market access principles: mutual recognition and non-discrimination. Mutual recognition allows businesses to sell goods made or imported in one part of the UK without complying with equivalent regulations. The second principle, non-discrimination, is a regulatory requirement that prevents discrimination against a good produced by one part of the UK that cannot be directly or indirectly enforced. These principles

affect all devolved administrations wishing to diverge from UK policy. Some exclusions are included, but most only apply to Northern Ireland because it shares a land border with the EU.

The Subsidy Control Act 2022 is part of the new UK government subsidy control regime that will begin in 2023, after the period covered in this thesis. However, the impact this Act could have was a concern for those who participated in designing a common framework for agricultural support. The UK left the EU and was no longer subject to EU State Aid rules. The subsidy control regime replaces this, enabling central, devolved, and local administrations to introduce subsidies. This Act could have a significant impact on future subsidies for agricultural support.

1.3 Research Aims

This thesis examines how intergovernmental relations enabled the Scottish and Welsh administrations to participate in designing a new common framework for agricultural support. So far, no other state has left the EU; therefore, there is a lack of knowledge about how a member state negotiates with devolved or regional administrations to replace EU policy frameworks, and no state has had to create an alternative to the CAP. This unique and complex process raises important questions about the effectiveness of the intergovernmental framework during such a challenging and unprecedented transition. The Joint Ministerial Communiqué established that the principles of cooperation, coordination, and respect for devolution would underpin the process. So good intergovernmental relations are, therefore, crucial. However, the IGR has faced criticism for its limitations in enabling joint discussions, decision-making, and dispute resolution.

Furthermore, the common frameworks aim to replace EU policy frameworks such as the Common Agricultural Policy, which previously enabled the devolved governments to develop and implement a tailored agricultural support framework. This research seeks to understand whether the intergovernmental relationship will allow the devolved governments to maintain the potential for policy divergence in the new agricultural support framework.

1.3.2 Research Questions

This section presents the primary research and supplementary questions that this study aims to address.

Primary Research Question:

To what extent does the intergovernmental relationship enable the Scottish and Welsh administrations to participate in designing a new common framework for agricultural support?

Supplementary Questions:

- What are the fundamental principles and structures underpinning the UK's intergovernmental frameworks?
- To what extent have they developed since the introduction of devolution?
- To what extent has previous engagement with the UK government in developing agricultural support policy shaped the current intergovernmental relationship?
- To what extent is the experience different for the Scottish and Welsh administrations?

The primary research question aims to understand how the devolved administrations and the UK government collaborated to develop a new common framework for agricultural support between 2016-2022. The purpose of the supplementary questions is to construct a historical context of intergovernmental relationships from 1999-2016. The first supplementary question seeks to understand the principles that underpin the IGR and how they have evolved, which could contribute to understanding how they might perform under unprecedented and potentially challenging circumstances. The second question examines how the IGR enabled the Scottish and Welsh administrations to develop and implement the CAP. Understanding how the UK and devolved governments managed policy divergence might contribute to understanding how they will approach divergence within the common framework. The third question builds on the first and second questions by asking how the experience differs between Scotland and Wales. The devolution settlement granted power to Scotland and Wales at different times. These circumstances meant that institutions, government departments, ministers, and officials in Scotland and Wales operated and interacted with their UK counterparts in distinct ways.

The fundamental concern of the three questions on which this thesis is based is how well the intergovernmental framework supports power sharing, joint decision-making, and dispute resolution to ensure institutional stability across the UK, enabling the devolved administrations to participate in designing new common frameworks for agricultural support. By exploring the mechanisms that influence stability and change between the devolved administrations of Scotland, Wales, and the UK government, how the dynamics of power relationships, other events, or more subtle processes may present themselves differently, creating a similar or different outcome, will be critically examined.

1.3.4 Delimitations

After explaining the scope of this research project, it is helpful to set the boundaries of the extent to which this project will stretch. Although three devolved administrations exist in the UK, this project will focus only on the Scottish and Welsh administrations and exclude Northern Ireland (NI). Northern Ireland's situation during this period was so complex that it would make the research project unmanageable. The Brexit settlement in NI differs significantly from that in Scotland and Wales. The NI Executive was also closed during essential parts of this thesis's timeframe, making it highly challenging to study how they interacted with the UK government.

1.3.5 Research Approach: Unit of Analysis, Comparative Analysis, and Theoretical Framework

In qualitative research, the unit of analysis is the primary object of examination in a study. It is the focal point for data collection, analysis, and interpretation. Understanding the unit of analysis is essential as it defines the study's boundaries and guides the methodological approach (Grunbaum, 2007). This study centres on the intergovernmental framework between the UK government and the devolved administrations of Scotland and Wales as its primary unit of analysis. This framework encompasses formal and informal structures, processes, and interactions that direct these governmental institutions' relationships and collaborative efforts. Formal mechanisms include joint ministerial committee meetings and guidance documents such as the Memorandum of Understanding, Concordats, and Devolution guidance notes. Meanwhile, informal interactions occur between officials through regular communication through phone calls, emails, and unofficial meetings. Civil servants from different administrations often engage in regular, unofficial discussions to share information, coordinate policy approaches, and address emerging issues promptly (Cairney, 2012). Such informal engagements allow for more flexible and responsive decision-making, fostering a collaborative environment where issues can be addressed quickly without formal procedures (Parry, 2004).

The choice of the intergovernmental framework as the unit of analysis is driven by the need to understand the dynamics and effectiveness of intergovernmental relations in a decentralised governance system, particularly in the context of developing new common frameworks post-Brexit. This focus is essential for several reasons. Firstly, examining the intergovernmental framework provides insights into how governmental institutions collaborate and resolve conflicts, which is crucial for effective governance. Secondly, the new common frameworks emerging post-Brexit significantly affect intergovernmental relations, making this study timely

and pertinent. Thirdly, the informal nature of many intergovernmental interactions requires a detailed and nuanced examination to understand their impact on governance fully.

This study employs a qualitative comparative case study approach augmented by process tracing to analyse the intergovernmental framework. This methodology is chosen for its ability to capture detailed interactions and trace processes over time. Case studies allow for an in-depth exploration of specific intergovernmental interactions, capturing the complexity and subtleties of these relationships. Process tracing helps identify and understand the sequence of events and interactions that shape intergovernmental relations, providing a comprehensive view of how these dynamics evolve (Checkel, 2008).

Given the complexity and informal nature of intergovernmental relations, operationalising this study presents inherent challenges. Existing data and literature are scarce, particularly those addressing the intricacies of informal intergovernmental relationships. This scarcity underscores the necessity of innovative research methods and comprehensive data collection strategies. The study employs process tracing and qualitative comparative case studies to address these challenges and gather in-depth and representative data. Data sources, including official documents, parliamentary debates, and committee transcripts, will be utilised to ensure a thorough understanding of intergovernmental relations. This research project analyses from 1999 to 2022, encapsulating the evolution of intergovernmental relations from devolution to the implementation of new common frameworks. This time frame is crucial for examining how historical contexts and institutional legacies shape current policy choices and intergovernmental dynamics.

Therefore, this study's primary unit of analysis is the intergovernmental framework between the UK government and the devolved administrations of Scotland and Wales. By focusing on this unit, the study aims to clarify the dynamics and effectiveness of intergovernmental relations in a decentralised governance system, particularly in the context of post-Brexit developments. The chosen methodologies and comprehensive data collection strategies are designed to address the inherent challenges and provide a detailed understanding of these complex interactions.

By employing a comparative case study approach, the study explores variations in experiences and outcomes between the Scottish and Welsh administrations within the intergovernmental framework. Comparing these contexts allows for identifying commonalities, divergences, and underlying factors influencing decision-making processes and policy outcomes. This

comparative analysis is critical for understanding how different devolved administrations navigate their relationships with the central UK government and implement new policies in the wake of Brexit. The study uses critical realist thematic analysis to evaluate the data collected. This method is well-suited for identifying and interpreting patterns within qualitative data, allowing for a nuanced understanding of how intergovernmental dynamics operate within different contexts.

The theoretical lens of path dependency guides this study's analysis, exploring how past decisions and institutional structures influence current policy trajectories and the maintenance of stability under stress. Path dependency theory is particularly apt for examining how historical legacies and initial conditions shape the development and evolution of intergovernmental relations and policy frameworks over time (Pierson, 2000). This theoretical framework helps to explain the persistence of specific patterns of interaction and the challenges of implementing new governance structures in a context of significant political and constitutional change.

By integrating these elements, this research implements a comprehensive approach to studying the intergovernmental relationships between the UK government, Scotland, and Wales, addressing inherent data access challenges. Through innovative research methods and a robust theoretical framework, this study aims to contribute nuanced insights into the dynamics of governance and institutional interactions in a decentralised political system.

1.4 Thesis Outline

Chapter One: Introduction

This chapter explains why Brexit necessitated the UK government's design of a new policy framework for agricultural support to replace the EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). Since devolution in 1999, Scotland and Wales have designed and managed their agricultural support policies. The UK and devolved administrations agreed to collaborate on a new policy framework, highlighting the importance of good intergovernmental relationships. However, there are longstanding concerns about the effectiveness of the intergovernmental framework. This chapter outlines these concerns and introduces the research questions and their rationale.

Chapter Two: Literature Review

This chapter reviews literature relevant to the research question. The chapter begins by discussing academic debates on the historical context of devolution, its evolution in Scotland

and Wales, and intergovernmental relations in the UK. The chapter then discusses conceptual debates on autonomy, shared rule and the decentralisation of power. Also, the UK's governance structures are changing. It concludes with an examination of recent literature on the impact of Brexit and common frameworks on intergovernmental relations.

Chapter Three: Theoretical Framework

This chapter presents the theoretical framework, focusing on historical institutionalism and path dependency. It explores how institutional change becomes challenging once an institution is established and "set on a course." The chapter examines power asymmetries to determine if a status quo bias allows one group to dominate and hinder genuine cooperation and collaboration in inter-institutional relationships.

Chapter Four: Methodology

This chapter justifies the study's methodological approach and operationalisation. It explains the selection of a comparative case study between Scotland and Wales to address the research question and details the application of case-oriented process tracing. The chapter also discusses the data collection and analysis technique of critical realist thematic analysis and concludes with a discussion of ethical issues.

Chapter Five: Historical Context (1999-2016)

This chapter covers the period from the establishment of devolution until the vote to leave the EU. It examines the intergovernmental relationship through UK government-commissioned reviews and House of Lords Scrutiny Committees.

Chapter Six: Agricultural Policy (1999-2016)

This chapter focuses on agricultural support policy from 1999 to 2016. It explores how the devolved administrations assumed responsibility for agricultural policy and developed and implemented the CAP.

Chapter Seven: Post-Brexit Developments (2016-2022)

This chapter covers the period from the Brexit vote until 2022, when the Provisional Common Framework for Agricultural Support was published. It examines this document and the latest intergovernmental review, presenting evidence from Scottish, Welsh, and UK government ministers and senior officials on their experience developing common frameworks.

Chapter Eight: Discussion and Conclusion

This chapter synthesises Chapters Five, Six, and Seven data, addressing the research questions and findings. It evaluates the performance of the intergovernmental framework and how it enabled the devolved governments to participate in designing the new common framework for agricultural support.

Chapter Nine: Concluding Remarks

This chapter concludes the thesis by summarising the aims and research questions and outlining its conclusion, contributions to knowledge, limitations and recommendations for future research.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

This chapter builds on the ideas presented in the introduction and provides an overview and critical analysis of the pertinent literature, thus laying the groundwork for this project. The purpose of this chapter is to situate this study in the context of existing research, identify any gaps in the literature, and explain how this thesis addresses these gaps.

The UK's withdrawal from the European Union (EU) is unprecedented, meaning no previous study has investigated this process. Consequently, there is no existing literature on how the UK government and the devolved administrations of Scotland and Wales have developed new overarching common frameworks to replace EU frameworks. This thesis focuses on the effectiveness of the intergovernmental architecture in enabling the devolved governments of Scotland and Wales to negotiate the process with the UK government. Therefore, this review must examine the literature on intergovernmental relations (IGR), including the factors contributing to the need for IGR, their development, and their purpose. Additionally, it situates the literature within the broader conceptual discussions of power and autonomy, the decentralisation of power, the dynamics between autonomy and shared decision-making, and the impact this has on the governance structures of the UK.

To achieve this, the chapter is structured into several sections. First, the conceptual framework introduces essential concepts such as power and political authority, autonomy and regional authority, and the dynamics between self-rule and shared rule. These concepts are crucial for understanding the forces shaping devolution and intergovernmental relations in the UK. The following section details the implementation of devolution and its evolution over time, focusing on the asymmetrical nature of UK devolution and the role of New Labour in advancing the devolution process. The chapter then explores intergovernmental relations, including formal mechanisms and informal relationships that facilitate cooperation and coordination between different levels of government in the UK. This section examines the factors that necessitate IGR, their development, and their purpose. It uses Scotland and Wales as a case study to illustrate devolution's varied experiences and outcomes.

The broader context of decentralising power, changes in governance structures, and parliamentary sovereignty is also examined. This includes the implications of devolution for the nature of the state, the shift from traditional government structures to modern governance approaches, and the concept of multi-level governance. Finally, the chapter addresses the

significant impact of Brexit on the UK's constitutional arrangements and intergovernmental relations. This section explores the development and implementation of common frameworks post-Brexit and speculates on the future directions for IGR, considering the emerging trends and challenges that Brexit presents for devolution and governance in the UK.

2.2 Conceptual Foundations

2.2.1 Introduction

Understanding the literature on power, autonomy, and the dynamics between central and devolved regions is essential for analysing the complexities of devolution and intergovernmental relations in the UK. In governance, power refers to the ability of an entity to influence or control the behaviour of others, shaping decisions and outcomes (Dahl, 1957). Autonomy denotes the extent of self-governance a political entity can exercise, managing its internal affairs without external interference (Raz, 1986). Decentralising power involves redistributing authority and decision-making responsibilities from central governments to lower tiers, such as regional or local authorities. This process aims to enhance autonomy at the subnational level, allowing regions to govern themselves more independently while remaining part of a larger political entity (Smith, 2018). The dynamics of power and autonomy are central to understanding how decentralised institutions operate and their impact on governance structures and intergovernmental relations. These concepts are particularly relevant in the UK's asymmetrical devolution, where different regions possess varying legislative and administrative powers, and this asymmetry is crucial to understanding the dynamics of power and autonomy. The balance between self-rule and shared rule is critical to this dynamic, where regions seek to govern themselves while participating in broader national decision-making processes.

This section examines definitions of power and political authority, the extent of autonomy and regional authority, and the interplay between self-rule and shared rule. It lays the foundation for the subsequent analysis of the UK's devolution arrangements. It highlights how these concepts are operationalised within the UK's governance framework and their implications for the effectiveness of devolved institutions and intergovernmental relations. This conceptual framework plays a crucial role in evaluating the UK's intergovernmental architecture and the dynamics of power and autonomy that shape its governance structures. This analysis is crucial for understanding the broader context of devolution and the challenges and opportunities it presents for regional and national governance.

2.2.2 Foundations and Dynamics of Political Authority

Political authority, a fundamental concept in political theory and governance studies, refers to the legitimate power held by governments or political entities over individuals or groups within a specific territory (Weber, 2009). Weber (2009) classified political authority into three types: traditional, charismatic, and rational-legal. Traditional authority is rooted in longstanding customs and traditions, charismatic authority arises from a leader's exceptional qualities, and rational-legal authority is based on formal rules and institutions (Weber, 2009). Insight has been sought by examining the role of institutions, norms, and practices in shaping political authority and power dynamics within and between states. Through these analyses, scholars seek to offer insights into the operation of political systems and governance structures (Gordon & Foucault, 1980; Beetham, 2012). Dahl (1991) proposed that political authority is closely linked to legitimacy, defined as the perceived legality or morality of a government's actions by its citizens (Dahl, 1991). Legitimacy can derive from various sources, including historical traditions, religious beliefs, social consensus, and adherence to legal and constitutional norms (Beetham, 2012). A government viewed as legitimate is more likely to garner respect and compliance from its citizens, promoting political stability and social cohesion (Beetham, 2012). It has been argued that exercising political authority involves navigating between coercion and consent, and governments use force, persuasion, and incentives to maintain order and ensure compliance with policies and laws (Gordon & Foucault, 1980). However, political authority ultimately relies on the consent and acceptance of the governed. Without legitimacy and popular support, political authority may face challenges or be overthrown, leading to political instability or regime change (Gordon & Foucault, 1980).

2.2.3 The Scope and Significance of Political Autonomy in Governance Systems

Political autonomy is the degree of self-governance or independence a political entity enjoys in making decisions and managing its internal affairs without external interference or control (Benz, 2005). It encompasses the authority of a political unit, such as a state, region, or community, to govern its policies, structures, and resources within a defined territory (Benz, 2005). Raz (1986) characterises political autonomy as the capability of individuals or groups to govern themselves according to their laws and values, free from external coercion or domination (Raz, 1986). Political autonomy is closely linked to concepts such as sovereignty and self-determination, which safeguard the rights of political entities to determine their fate and pursue their interests (Wolff & Weller, 2007). Political autonomy manifests in various

forms within different political frameworks, ranging from full sovereignty enjoyed by independent states to partial autonomy granted to subnational regions within a federal or decentralised state (Keating, 2001). In federal systems, regions typically have significant authority over policy areas. In unitary states, regional authority may be more limited and subject to central oversight (Keating, 2001). Political autonomy is often associated with decentralisation, devolution, and federalism, which aim to empower subnational units and grant them greater control over local governance and decision-making (Watts, 2008). Devolved administrations in countries such as the United Kingdom, Spain, and Canada exemplify varying degrees of political autonomy, with regional governments enjoying legislative, executive, and sometimes fiscal powers within their jurisdictions (Kincaid, 2003). In the United Kingdom, devolution refers to decentralising political authority and granting varying levels of self-governance to subnational regions within a centralised state framework (Mitchell, 2009). The devolved governments in Scotland, Wales, and Northern Ireland exercise political autonomy within their respective jurisdictions, with authority over competencies such as education, healthcare and transport (Mitchell, 2009).

2.2.4 Global Trends and Theoretical Perspectives on Decentralisation and Regional Autonomy

In addition to the debates for more autonomy in Scotland and Wales, Holtmann and Rademacher (2016) noted a broader trend in the discussion of the decentralisation of power beyond the UK, reaching across Europe, from the late 1980s. The fall of the Soviet Bloc initiated many Eastern European countries to embark on reform and restructuring processes. In some instances, power was decentralised as former autocracies shifted to democracies and implemented political systems and institutions that represented legitimacy and effectiveness (Holtmann & Rademacher, 2016). The European Union (EU) also implemented new principles that promoted the decentralisation of power by member states to regional and local governments. As a member, the UK was required to abide by EU directives and regulations (Bulmer & Burch, 2009). The Single European Act 1986 and the Maastricht Treaty 1993 included the principle of subsidiarity. The objective of subsidiarity is for the central Government to delegate as much responsibility as possible to local authorities (Morphet, 2013). Similar decentralisation trends can be observed in other parts of the world beyond Europe. Canada's federal structure, particularly Quebec's quest for greater autonomy, provides a North American parallel to the European experiences (Turp, 2022). Quebec has consistently sought greater control over its affairs, pushing for constitutional recognition of its distinct society and

additional powers, mirroring the autonomy movements in Scotland and Catalonia. In Australia, states and territories have navigated complex intergovernmental relationships to achieve a balance of power, echoing the dynamics seen within the EU (Grant, Grant & Drew, 2017). Australia's federal system involves significant cooperation between the federal and state governments, particularly in healthcare and education, which requires constant negotiation and adjustment of responsibilities.

In attempting to understand why some regions seek autonomy while others do not, Tijmstra (2009) explains that it may be common for people in a region to think of themselves as distinct from other parts of the much larger state. However, it does not necessarily follow that they wish for their territory to be devolved. However, ideological differences exist in areas that demand devolution, creating a schism between the state and the region. The region lacks political legitimacy, and a devolved government can better represent its needs (Tijmstra, 2009).

Building on these global and historical perspectives on decentralisation and regional autonomy, exploring the theoretical concepts of self-rule and shared rule is crucial. Understanding the balance and interaction between self-rule, where regions govern themselves, and shared rule, where they cooperate with a central authority, provides a foundational framework for analysing decentralisation. The following section delves into these concepts, examining their definitions, implications, and dynamics when regions seek autonomy and integration within the broader political system.

2.2.5 Dynamics of Self-rule and Shared Rule

A comprehensive understanding of the dynamics between self-rule and shared rule is imperative in regional governance. This duality encapsulates the essence of regional authority, where self-rule allows subnational entities to govern independently, while shared rule necessitates cooperation with higher levels of government (Hooghe & Marks, 2001). Various factors, such as constitutional frameworks, intergovernmental relations, and policy domains, shape this relationship (Hooghe & Marks, 2001). Understanding these dynamics is essential for effective governance and is particularly relevant in the context of devolution and power distribution in the UK.

Constitutional frameworks are pivotal in delineating the powers and responsibilities between central and regional governments (Watts, 2008). These frameworks define the extent of self-rule that subnational entities enjoy and the mechanisms through which they coordinate and cooperate with the central government (Watts, 2008). This legal structure sets the stage for the

interplay between autonomy and interdependence. Intergovernmental relations further influence the dynamics between self-rule and shared rule. Positive interactions characterised by cooperation, dialogue, and mutual respect facilitate shared decision-making and effective policy implementation (Peters, 2018). Robust institutional mechanisms for consultation, negotiation, and dispute resolution are essential for managing conflicts and fostering collaboration between different levels of government (Peters, 2018).

Understanding the allocation of competencies across various policy areas is crucial to grasping the power dynamics between the central and regional governments. Competencies, which refer to the specific powers and responsibilities designated to different levels of government, play a crucial role in determining how effectively governance is implemented. Some competencies may be entirely under the authority of regional governments, while others require significant coordination with central authorities (Elazar, 1987). For example, Scotland's education and health systems are prime examples of such independent control in the UK, allowing the Scottish government to tailor policies to its population's specific needs without central approval. Conversely, other competencies necessitate significant coordination between regional and central authorities. Transportation infrastructure, for instance, often requires a blend of regional planning and national funding or regulatory oversight, necessitating robust mechanisms for consultation, negotiation, and cooperation (Mitchell, 2009).

Achieving a balance between self-rule and shared rule is crucial for inclusive and effective governance at both regional and national levels (Hooghe & Marks, 2001). The work of scholars such as Hooghe, Marks, McEwen, and Schakel provides critical insights into understanding the complexities of regional authority. The Regional Authority Index (RAI) offers a comprehensive framework for assessing regional authority, enabling comparative analysis of regional governments' degree of autonomy and influence (Hooghe & Marks, 2016). The RAI evaluates regional authority across several dimensions: institutional depth, policy scope, fiscal autonomy, and representation. Institutional depth measures the extent of autonomous policymaking authority regional governments possess, while policy scope assesses the range of policy areas under regional legislative control. Fiscal autonomy evaluates the financial independence of regional governments, and representation examines the presence of regional representation in the central government (Hooghe & Marks, 2016). By identifying distinct authority domains of self-rule and shared rule, the RAI facilitates a deeper analysis of the power distribution between central and regional governments.

McEwen and Schakel's (2016) research further explores the complex relationship between self-rule and shared rule within multi-level governance systems, challenging the conventional view that these concepts are mutually exclusive (McEwen & Schakel, 2016). They analyse the conditions under which sub-state governments exercise varying degrees of shared rule, emphasising the impact of political, constitutional, and institutional factors. Their findings reveal that regions with high levels of self-rule prioritise decision-making autonomy but remain constrained by central government authority in critical policy areas such as foreign affairs and taxation. They also identify important variables, such as constitutional asymmetry and the strength of nationalist parties, which shape the dynamics of shared rule (McEwen & Schakel, 2016).

Effective decentralisation involves transferring powers to regional governments and ensuring that these governments have the resources and institutional support necessary to exercise their authority effectively (Watts, 2008). Whether in federal or unitary systems, governance structures significantly affect how power is shared and exercised. Understanding these frameworks helps design systems responsive to the needs of both central and regional authorities (Keating, 2001). In the UK, the principle of parliamentary sovereignty traditionally means that the central government retains ultimate authority (Mitchell, 2009). However, the devolution of powers to Scotland, Wales, and Northern Ireland has introduced significant changes to this principle, creating a more complex and dynamic governance landscape (Smith, 2018). The ongoing debates about the UK's state structure and intergovernmental relationships highlight the challenges and opportunities presented by devolution (Bulmer & Burch, 2009).

Examining how power is redistributed and how different governance frameworks influence the relationship between central and subnational governments is crucial for understanding the UK's unique position as a devolved state (Hooghe & Marks, 2016; McEwen & Schakel, 2016). The work of Hooghe, Marks, McEwen, and Schakel provides a comprehensive framework for assessing regional authority, enabling comparative analysis of the degree of autonomy and influence exerted by regional governments (Hooghe & Marks, 2016). Their research underscores the importance of balancing autonomy and interdependence, providing policymakers and researchers with the insights needed to navigate the complexities of regional authority and ensure effective governance in a devolved system (McEwen & Schakel, 2016).

Understanding these dynamics is crucial for evaluating the effectiveness of the UK's intergovernmental architecture (Peters, 2018). By analysing the practical implications of

devolution and power distribution, we can better understand the broader context of devolution and the challenges and opportunities it presents for regional and national governance (Elazar, 1987). This deeper understanding is essential for ensuring that governance structures are inclusive, responsive, and effective at all levels, ultimately promoting political stability and social cohesion across the UK (Beetham, 2012).

2.3 Historical Overview of Devolution in the UK

The Scottish Parliament and the National Assembly for Wales were established in 1999. However, debates surrounding the ideas of autonomy and the consequences of decentralising power in Scotland, Ireland, and Wales have been growing since the nineteenth century. According to Dicey (1973), the decentralisation of power should be resisted. He asserted that devolution would not meet the aspirations of the devolved regions and would eventually lead to the disintegration of the UK (Dicey, 1973, 2013). "England was the 'linchpin' of this Union, and the Union and Empire were necessary because they increased England's heft on the world stage" (Dicey, 1973, p. 281; Wincott, Murray & Davies, 2022, p. 710). Concerns about the Empire might have decreased, but it does not diminish that much of the literature surrounding the relationship between territories in the UK is shaped by their historical relationship with England (Bogdanor, 2001). In 1284, England annexed Wales and formally incorporated it in 1536 (Jenkins, 2014). In 1603, England and Scotland were united by the Scottish King (O'Neil, 2014). The political Union was formalised in 1707. Ireland joined in 1801, but in 1922, twenty-six counties formed the Irish Free State, separating from the Union. The remaining six counties of Northern Ireland formed the UK with Scotland, Wales, and England.

Upon the founding of the Union, Westminster became the legislative body for the entire UK, taking England's uncodified constitution as its basis. This constitution has largely remained unwritten, and the UK is one of the few countries with an uncodified constitution (O'Neil, 2004). Under the Union Act, Scotland preserved several significant institutions, including the Church, the legal system, education, and some local government structures (Paterson, 1994; Judge, 2005). While the debate around self-rule may have increased, the desire for home rule in Scotland was not universal: some sought autonomy, while others wanted Scotland to play a more significant role in Westminster. Jeffrey (2007) contended that the UK government responded to these demands by creating a more structured role for a Secretary of State for Scotland in 1885, which eventually evolved into a cabinet position in 1892. This role was designed to demonstrate that Scottish interests were represented in Westminster, and their views were considered (Jeffrey, 2007). The Scottish Office was in London until it relocated to

Edinburgh in 1939 (Dardanelli, 2006). Its purpose was to modify the UK policy within the framework of Scots law and consider Scottish 'distinctiveness' (Jeffrey, 2007).

The Scottish Office operated a form of administrative decentralisation, which, according to Mitchell (2003), became an important institution within Scotland to manage public affairs and promote Scottish interests at the UK level (Mitchell, 2003). Mitchell identified the unique dichotomy of the Scottish Office as a decentralised institution but also as part of the central Government and highlighted the features that enabled it to achieve those ends, which were the UK government's acceptance of the 'distinctiveness' of Scottish identity within a part of the central state and its representation of Scottish interests in the UK government. The Scottish Office may represent the characteristics of the devolved administration. However, this does not necessarily indicate an increase in autonomy if the function of the Office is only to deliver central government policies. Mitchell (2003) concludes that the only autonomy available to Scotland was the "autonomy to ask for and often receive more favourable treatment. That would, in time, prove a frustrating limitation" (Mitchell, 2003, p.8).

Academic debates on the early Welsh administration and its relationship with the UK government have centred on its historical ties with England. In many ways, Wales was treated as a part of England. Unlike Scotland, which retained its religious, educational, and legal systems, no distinct Welsh institution has survived. Therefore, Wales and England continued to share legal jurisdictions, which has had significant implications for devolution in Wales (Jenkins, 2014; Watkin, 2012). As part of the Union, Wales lagged behind Scotland in achieving a specific representation of Welsh needs in Westminster. A Minister for Welsh Affairs was not appointed until 1951, becoming a Secretary of State for Wales in 1964, and the Welsh Office was established in 1965 and transferred to Cardiff in 1971 (Jenkins, 2014; Davies, 2007). As Wales lacked distinct institutions or legal systems from England, there was only a limited need for the Welsh Office to perform administrative devolution. Most policymaking remained the responsibility of the UK government to design and implement on behalf of Wales before and after the creation of the Welsh Office (Jeffrey, 2006).

The discourse on decentralising power expanded with the Labour Party's rhetoric of restoring faith in institutions, bolstering democracy, and responding to growing grievances about democratic deficits, particularly in Scotland (Barnett, 1997; Curtice & Jowell, 1998). Academic literature has connected this rhetoric to the growing support for pro-independence political parties such as the Scottish National Party (SNP), which called for a new constitutional

arrangement for Scotland, and Plaid Cymru (PC), or the Party for Wales (Bogdanor, 1999; Balsom, 1979; McAngus, 2016). The Labour Party's response was establishing The Royal Commission of the Constitution, commonly known as the Kilbrandon Commission (Mitchell *et al.*, 1998; Wright, 2020). In 1973-75, the Kilbrandon report failed to reach a consensus on which constitutional action should be taken, but some recommendations were made (Barendt, 1974; Wright, 2020). The report dismissed the idea of federalism, as England was too large and powerful. Federalism would require considerable institutional restructuring, so devolution was recommended (Barendt, 1974; Kellas, 1990). Some form of Assembly was proposed for Scotland and Wales, but legislative powers were limited for Wales (Trice, 1974). The disparity in the recommendations for delegating powers to Scotland and Wales reflects the differences between the devolved administrations—the proposed new assemblies transferred power from the Scottish and Welsh Secretaries of State.

The Scotland Act 1978 established a new assembly in Scotland. Burrows (1999) argued that the Act shifted from administrative devolution to a restricted constitutional power transfer and only granted the proposed Assembly limited legislative powers or 'Measures.' Moreover, the Act stipulated that the Assembly could only be set up if the referendum vote exceeded 40%. In 1979, the referendum for Scottish devolution was passed by a slim margin. However, since it did not receive the support of more than 40% of the electorate, the Conservative Government blocked its implementation and forced the repeal of the Scotland Act 1978 (Pattie *et al.*, 1999; Wright, 2020). In Wales, the turnout was only 20%, which suggests that the Welsh had a different attitude towards devolution than the Scots (McAllister, 1998; Wyn & Lewis, 1999). However, the devolution question remained unresolved.

Increasingly, academic discussions have focused on the actions and diminishing support for the Conservative Party to drive debates on democratic deficits and political legitimacy in Scotland and Wales. Beland and Lecours (2005) claim that in the first half of the 20th century, support for the Conservative Party was similar across England and Scotland; by the 1980s, support had dropped by half in Scotland. The literature reports the perception of a Conservative government as centralising and the dismantling of Scottish institutions, which was viewed as an attack on Scotland (Beland & Lecours, 2005). This belief led to claims that Scotland suffered from a democratic deficit, as it was outsized by the English electorate, which voted for Conservatives (Dardanelli, 2005; Trench, 2007; McHarg, 2016). As Scotland is a much smaller country, it was argued that it did not matter to whom its people voted and that England chose the winner. Therefore, much discussion has been generated on the political implications of the Scottish

electorate's feelings of disenfranchisement and being governed by a political party they did not elect (Dardanelli, 2005; Trench, 2007).

The same argument was made in Wales, which consistently voted for the Labour Party, but England elected the Conservative Party. Unlike Scotland, Wales claimed additional levels of disenfranchisement stemming from the post of Secretary of State for Wales being held by non-Welsh MPs from 1986 to 1997 (Ashworth et al., 2001). Mitchell (2006) rebutted the claims of disenfranchisement; it was not a democratic deficit but an issue of legitimacy that the centralised Westminster model of Government was not working and was driving a lack of political legitimacy (Mitchell, 2006). Mitchell (2006) argued that a lack of political legitimacy was felt across the UK but at different levels. The perception that England dominated elections due to its size, as it is still larger than all other parts of the UK and an earlier rejection of federalism in the Kilbrandon report fuelled the pressure for devolution as a solution (Mitchell, 2006).

In the 1980s-1990s, political debates focused on increasing discontent in Scotland, Wales, and some parts of England. However, Scotland's drive for more autonomy, or its breaking from the Westminster System, appears more evident. In 1988, the Scottish Constitutional Convention emerged as a cross-party campaign for MPs, civic leaders, and church members. They created Claims of Rights for Scotland. This document declared Scotland sovereign and stated that its people should have the right to select their Government (Kellas, 1992). This cross-party action and long-term discussion on what devolution could look like in Scotland never took hold in Wales to the same degree. This may go some way to explain why the Welsh seemed less visible and organised in demanding devolution.

2.4 Asymmetrical Devolution and Intergovernmental Relations

2.4.1 New Labour and the Devolution Process

The 1997 general election significantly impacted the debate over the UK's constitution and future. New Labour ran a campaign based on the promise of devolution in Scotland and Wales. The Conservatives ran a campaign against devolution, losing all their MPs in Scotland and Wales. When New Labour assumed power, it pledged to implement constitutional reforms, and unlike past attempts at devolution, the referendum was held before any Acts of Parliament were passed (Mitchell, 1998; Tierney, 2012). In September 1997, a referendum was held, which saw 74% of voters favouring Scottish devolution, with a slightly over 60% turnout. In Wales, the voter turnout was 50%, with a voting rate of 50.3%. Trench (2007) suggested that the vote

favouring devolution was successful because of the desire for more autonomy and the lingering apprehension of another government like Thatcher's (Trench, 2007). The literature suggests that New Labour's decision to pursue constitutional reform was motivated by two factors. Firstly, their support base had dwindled significantly during the 1980s, and the UK Labour Party became increasingly territorialised, with the remaining support predominantly in Scotland and Wales, which were able to exert influence and shape the 1997 manifesto to include devolution. New Labour had restructured its policy system to incorporate policy forums, encouraging regional party members in Scotland and Wales to contribute to party policy (Laffin & Shaw, 2007). The second was a defensive measure responding to growing demands for autonomy and increasing support for pro-independence parties. New Labour produced a manifesto that promised devolution, which they believed would increase their support (Burrows, 1999).

Many debates centre on New Labour's approach to devolution in Scotland and Wales and the lack of coherence and symmetry. Tierney (2009) claims that the UK government did not undertake devolution in a uniform format. The UK government formulated the powers for Wales and Scotland to reflect each part's distinctive institutions and history (Tierney, 2009). The White Paper, Scotland's Parliament, initially set out the new Parliament's powers but was altered to set out what powers Westminster would retain (Mitchell, 1998). The Scotland Act 1998 and The Government of Wales Act 1998 set out very different powers for each newly devolved administration.

The Scotland Act 1998 established a devolved parliament in Scotland that delivered a reserved power model of devolution. Schedule 5 established the specific areas of policy expressly reserved for Westminster, but all other competencies were devolved to Scotland (Anderson & Gallagher, 2018; Whitman, 2017). These primary legislative powers granted the Scottish Executive significant autonomy (Anderson & Gallagher, 2018; Whitman, 2017). This was a much more impactful settlement and offered more autonomy than the original devolution settlement through the Scotland Act 1978, which only provided limited powers over specific policy areas.

The Government of Wales Act 1998 established a Welsh devolution settlement based on the conferred power model. The powers conferred on this Assembly a limited list of specific areas devoted to the Welsh Administration and all other competencies reserved for Westminster (Shortridge, 2010). The Welsh Assembly was granted limited secondary legislative power. The

initial structure of the Assembly, as a corporate body responsible for executive and legislative functions, was challenging. The conferred powers model of devolution was criticised for causing confusion and a lack of clarity about what the Welsh administration could do. It has been viewed as problematic, placing restrictions on autonomy. Wales required more input from Westminster to make primary legislation on their behalf and ensure that the Assembly remained within its competencies (Hazell, 2004; Moon & Evans, 2017).

The new assemblies and parliaments installed by the New Labour government in 1999 applied to only three of the four countries that make up the UK (Tierney, 2009; Keating, 2010). This results in a disjointed system of devolution. As the largest and most populated territory, England did not receive a separate parliament; the government introduced only a fragmented form of devolution to some degree in London and some peripheral regions of England. Scotland was initially granted significantly more autonomy and legislative competence than Wales. This power has enabled the Scottish Parliament to control policy decisions and diverge policy areas from other parts of the UK (MacKinnon, Shaw & Dockerty, 2010). The Welsh Assembly was heavily constrained and limited in policy choices without Westminster's approval. The early Welsh Assembly could make some choices for Wales but did not have the same freedom as MSPs (Andrews & Martin, 2010).

2.5 Intergovernmental Relations

2.5.1 Formal Mechanisms

Further criticisms of the asymmetrical nature of the new devolution settlement arose because of the UK government's intergovernmental framework. An intergovernmental framework aims to enable central and devolved administrations to interact (Trench, 2006). With the introduction of devolution settlements in Scotland and Wales, institutional interaction was necessary to facilitate policy coordination, discussions, decision-making, and, if required, conflict resolution (Keating, 2005; Cairney, 2012). Academic literature agrees that some type of intergovernmental apparatus, which can be formal or informal, is necessary to regulate relations between the national, subnational, and local levels (Opeskin, 2002). The decentralisation of power includes executive, legislative, and judicial mechanisms. There are also usually intergovernmental agreements, ranging from formal, legally binding agreements to the weakest agreements with no legal enforceability (Opeskin, 2002). Trench (2007) states that the IGR is the government's system for coordinating policies, clarifying responsibilities, and avoiding conflict (Trench, 2007). Peters (2001) also agrees that IGR is necessary to facilitate

collaboration, policy coordination, and conflict resolution between the central government and DAs (Peters, 2001).

The formal IGR mechanisms between the Scottish and Welsh governments and the UK government take several forms to ensure the operation of government business. All four parts of the UK agreed to a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) and Concordats that set out terms for working together. However, this is not a legally binding agreement (Cairney, 2006; Horgan, 2004). The MOU was updated four times throughout devolution. Concordats ensure coordination between the UK and devolved governments (Jeffrey, 2007). Concordats can be multilateral or bilateral, and interdepartmental pacts can exist (Cairney, 2006; Horgan, 2004).

Another aspect of the IGR is the Joint Ministerial Committees (JMC), a committee of the devolved and UK governments (Cairney, 2012; Jeffrey, 2009). Several JMCs, such as the plenary meeting, enabled the UK and its devolved governments to discuss policies. There is a JMC on European affairs, and now there is a JMC on European Negotiations to address the UK's exit from the EU. JMC is the mechanism for coordinating policy initiatives and dealing with disagreements (Jeffrey, 2009; McEwen, 2017). The JMC provides an opportunity to discuss shared competence areas (McEwen, 2017). McEwen (2017) claimed that the purpose of the JMC (plenary) is to consider dispute resolution, but the format of these meetings is not substantial enough to deal with them (McEwen, 2017). "The JMC is a forum for dispute declarations if rarely dispute resolution" (Moore, 2016, p.133). They are not jointly owned meetings and are dominated by the UK government (Jeffrey, 2009).

No formal agreement exists on how often JMC (P) should occur. The JMC (Europe) took place more frequently and allowed devolved administrations to be involved at the EU level to some degree; however, devolved members were kept in place by the UK government (McEwen, 2017). A fundamental issue with JMCs is that they lack a neutral mediator; if they must resolve a dispute, the UK government has the final say (Keating, 2010). Moreover, because JMCs occur infrequently, more informal meetings tend to occur. Because JMC is multilateral, sometimes a policy area will be of more significance to one devolved administration, so they may prefer to seek bilateral meetings. The nature of devolution settlements may also impact how closely a devolved government needs to interact with UK officials. Until 2006 and 2017, the Welsh Assembly had limited legislative or executive power, so it collaborated with Whitehall in designing and delivering policies (Horgan, 2004). Wales requires intense bilateral IGR. With limited primary legislative and delegated powers, the Welsh Affairs Select Committee, the

National Assembly, the Welsh Office, and the Secretary of State for Wales all needed to provide input. The House of Lord's Scrutiny Committee (2002) review found frustration and tension due to the high institutional interaction required to pass primary legislation (Swenden & McEwen, 2014).

The other formal mechanism for devolved administrations is the legislative consent motion (LCM) or 'Sewel Convention.' The purpose of the LCM is to signify that the devolved administration and UK parliaments respect each other's roles. It is based on the convention that the UK parliament will not pass laws in areas of devolved competency without the approval of the devolved government (McHarg, 2016). However, as it is only a convention, the UK government can still pass legislation without consent from the devolved administrations (Anthony, 2018).

In the study of IGR, it is frequently the case that research will be conducted on a comparative basis with other countries. Most of this analysis focuses on the most similar or different systems' methods of comparison (Anderson & Gallagher, 2018). Most of this research compares unions and unitary states with federal systems. Typically, federations have designated jurisdictions at the national and sub-national levels with more explicit boundaries of competency or if a crossover of competencies exists (Keating, 2010; McEwen, 2020). A federal state usually has a constitution that clarifies the state's role and its sub-states and how the relationship between them should function in areas where crossover occurs, creating a balance of power (Keating & Laforest, 2018).

This situation is not the case in the UK, which has a primarily unwritten constitution and devolution established by the Act of Parliament (Keating, 2005; Cairney, 2012; McHarg, 2017). For several reasons, asymmetry exists across the UK, meaning a balance of power is unachievable. The devolution settlements established in 1999 in Scotland and Wales granted different levels of power and the population size of England, making it considerably larger than Scotland, Wales, and Northern Ireland combined. The lack of clarity and crossover of competencies, particularly in Wales, requires significant cooperation and coordination among governments (Keating, 2010; McEwen, 2017). Institutional interactions occur through both formal and informal processes and mechanisms. This lack of generality or common structures makes the IGR challenging when applying a theoretical framework (Trench, 2006; Keating, 2010; McEwen, 2017).

Another critical factor emerging from the literature on intergovernmental relations is the role of fragmented territorial governance. Limited power is decentralised through devolution in the UK, with each territory granted power by the Act of Parliament at Westminster. As set out earlier in this chapter, devolution settlements vary, with different competencies allocated to Northern Ireland, Scotland, Wales, and some smaller regions in England. Smaller regions cannot access the same formal intergovernmental framework as Scotland, Wales, or Northern Ireland (Hunt, 2010; Keating, 2017). Intergovernmental relations were established to enable these new institutions to interact, design, and deliver policies with established UK-wide institutions. Institutional interactions between the UK government, the DAs, Whitehall, and other government departments are inconsistent and often informal, lacking transparency (Trench, 2006; Keating, 2010; McEwen, 2017). This asymmetry has impacted how the Devolved Administrations engage with the IGR (MacKinnon, 2015).

2.5.2 Informal Relationships

The Labour Party was in power at the UK level and in coalition in Scotland and Wales, so party congruence was a significant factor in the IGR's periodisation between 1999-2007. Before devolution, the UK government used intragovernmental relations across departments and Scottish and Welsh offices. After devolution was established, bilateral interactions across departments continued. This arrangement may explain why formal IGRs were rarely used, and informal interactions were the norm (Swenden & McEwen, 2014).

Cairney (2012) points out that the formal mechanism of IGR was created after devolution, and some of the existing pre-devolution informal arrangements of intragovernmental relations were carried over and have continued to be used (Cairney, 2012). This decision has primarily been attributed to the fact that the Labour Party established devolution in Westminster, and initially, a Labour/Liberal Democrat coalition controlled the Scottish Executive and Welsh Assembly (Jones & Balsom, 2000; Cairney, 2012). However, Cairney (2006) noted that the Labour Party failed to develop intra-party or inter-ministerial structures to enhance the working relationship between the Party and coalition members in Westminster, Scotland, and Wales. There was also criticism of the JMCs as a continuation of cabinet subcommittees, and the Labour/Liberal Democrat coalition viewed them as early devolved governments. This decision may have contributed to minimal changes in IGR relationships, as it may have been business as usual (Peters, 2001). Some mechanisms are in place to coordinate policies and resolve disputes. Recommendations for change have been made but mostly avoided, and the system remains primarily informal (Mitchell, 2010). Horgan (2004) argues that the mechanisms put in place

are overwhelmingly inter-executive, but the inter-legislative links are weaker in comparison (Horgan, 2004). However, Cairney points out that later Scottish governments maintained this informal style even when led by different parties (Cairney, 2012).

2.6 Devolution in the UK

2.6.1 Scotland: Increasing Autonomy to Discourage Independence?

In 2007, the SNP formed a minority government in Holyrood. The relationship between the Labour Government at Westminster and Alex Salmond, the First Minister, began on a rocky footing, with Prime Minister Tony Blair not offering congratulations (Trench, 2008; Cairney, 2012). Academic debates have speculated on the likelihood of an incongruous relationship between the UK and the Scottish Executive. Despite the lack of political alignment between Westminster and Holyrood, an informal working relationship was established, and it has been suggested that it is not in the Scottish Government's best interest to push for a more formal IGR. However, the SNP ensured that the JMC was reactivated (Trench, 2007). The SNP acted cautiously and hesitated to confront the UK government. Cairney (2012) claims that the SNP attempts to portray itself as competent in public, as it stands to benefit more from discreet negotiations. They have limited constitutional authority to oppose the UK government, and the Sewel Convention is one of the few legislative powers in their favour (Cairney, 2012).

Subsequently, the SNP developed a paper titled *Choosing Scotland's Future: A National Conversation: Independence and Responsibility in the Modern World*. In response, the three other opposition parties, Labour, Conservatives, and Liberal Democrats, collaborated to oppose any discussion of independence and set in motion a review of devolution and intergovernmental relations. The review examined potential additional powers and ways to strengthen the IGR. The SNP opposed this review as it disregarded the case for independence, was commissioned by pro-Union parties, and was conducted by UK government departments (Cairney, 2009). The Calman Commission (2010) review asserted that devolution had succeeded and helped ensure Scotland's place in the UK. The review's recommendations resulted in the Scotland Act 2012, which granted new powers, mainly related to taxation. Initially hesitant to accept the new powers due to doubts about their efficacy, the SNP government in Scotland eventually gave the green light to the legislative consent motion, and the Act was implemented.

Furthermore, recommendations were made to enhance intergovernmental machinery, advising improvements to the Joint Ministerial Committee by expanding sub-committees and introducing changes to the civil service (Holden, 2010). Despite the increased power given to

the Scottish Government, the intergovernmental relationship with the UK government largely remained the same.

The literature examining devolution after introducing the Scotland Act 2012 points to increasing complexity in the devolution settlement, but an intergovernmental framework cannot manage the increasing interdependence. With increased autonomy in Scotland, there is a lack of mechanisms to manage shared rule with the UK government (McEwen & Petersohn, 2015). This situation intensified in 2011 when the SNP won a landslide majority (Electoral Commission, 2019). The electoral system in Scotland, an additional members' system, was designed by New Labour to prevent a majority government (Harvey, 2020). This endorsement by the Scottish electorate placed the SNP in a much stronger position to demand an independence referendum. The SNP sought legislative approval from the UK government to hold a referendum and began negotiations with the UK government's Conservative/Liberal Democratic Coalition (Mullen, 2014). These negotiations concluded with the Edinburgh Agreement (2012), which established arrangements to conduct an independence referendum. The Scottish Parliament passed the Scottish Independence Referendum Act 2013 and the Scottish Independence Referendum (Franchise) Act. The negotiation process appears to be straightforward. The agreement was created by Michael Moore, Liberal Democrat Secretary of State for Scotland (Moore, 2013). In September 2014, a referendum was held asking, 'Should Scotland be an independent country?' The votes won varied from 55.3% to 44% (Electoral Management Board for Scotland, 2014).

In the final days of the independence campaign, the leaders of the Unionist parties voted that if Scotland voted to stay in the UK, they would reform devolution. The Scottish Parliament was established by the Scotland Act 1998 as an Act of Parliament. However, amendments would enshrine its permanency unless a referendum was held to abolish it. The devolution settlement would be enhanced with extensive new powers, and the Barnett formula would remain. After the Scottish Independence referendum, The Smith Commission (2014) was formed to consider delivering these promises to Scotland. The Smith Commission recommendations contributed to the Scotland Act 2016. While it did set out some enhancements, it did not settle the constitutional question finally or provide more substantial intergovernmental machinery to manage the increasingly complex relationship between the Scottish and UK governments (Keating, 2015).

2.6.2 Wales: Resolving Confusion and Complexity

The literature has illuminated several issues related to the Welsh Assembly in 1999. Some problems resulted from political scandals and the minority Labour government's failure to function. This resulted in a coalition with the Liberal Democrats in October 2000, which led to a partnership agreement. According to Trench (2001), working in a coalition was a new experience for many in the Welsh Assembly, unlike in the Scottish Parliament, where many had national convention experience. Other issues stemmed from working relationships with officials transferred from the territorial Office to the new Assembly. First Minister Rhodri Morgan compared the civil service in the Scottish Office and different cultures because it had run autonomously for so long. The civil service deferred to Whitehall first, as if they were still working at the Welsh Office (Osmond, 2000).

The most significant issues with the Welsh Assembly were its structure and power. The Government of Wales Act 1998 created a corporate body without a distinction between the executive and legislative branches. In practice, the Cabinet created a separate executive. With a focused policy programme, the coalition instigated a more determined approach towards establishing a more parliamentary type of Government to make policy. Burrows (1999) referred to the Welsh Assembly as an anomaly, as it gained legitimacy through elections but lacked the power to pass legislation, reversing the situation of the Welsh Office before devolution. The presiding officers of the Assembly conducted an operational review that set out the 'common agenda' for the independent review, which called for 'enhanced methods for influencing primary legislation at Westminster,' yet no entirely crafted Welsh bill passed through Westminster in 2001-2002. The Welsh Assembly's operational review and the Intergovernmental Conference (IGC) of the EU pressured the central government to grant more legislative powers (Osmond, 2001).

In 2002, the Commission on the Powers and Electoral Arrangements of the National Assembly for Wales, more commonly referred to as The Richard Commission, was established to assess the powers and electoral arrangements of the National Assembly. The Commission comprised representatives from all major political parties (Wyn Jones & Scully, 2012). The Commission broached the issues of asymmetrical devolution and recommended more legislative powers and separation into separate legislative and executive assemblies (Johnson, 2008). The UK Labour government dismissed these recommendations but agreed to devolve more to Wales. The Richard Commission recommendations eventually became a White Paper, contributing to the Government of Wales Act 2006 (Wyn & Scully, 2012).

The Government of Wales Act 2006 restructured the Assembly from a corporate body to a separate legislature, the National Assembly for Wales and a new executive Welsh Assembly government. (Trench, 2007). With the transfer of some primary legislative powers or 'measures' (Johnson, 2008). The Richard Commission report resulted in a solid parliamentary structure that "is emerging much more rapidly than could have been imagined a decade ago" (Wyn & Scully, 2012). Wyn Jones and Scully (2012) argued that the Welsh Labour Party had initially presented the Assembly as having a structure like local government to appeal to those who were against devolution so that any National Assembly would be more palatable. They contended that the lack of resistance to the suggestion to eliminate those features and recommend limited primary legislative powers within the first five years of the Assembly's existence demonstrated the Assembly's success in garnering support in Wales (Wyn & Scully, 2012).

In a further review of devolution in Wales, the Silk Commission was established in 2012 and produced recommendations in 2014 to enhance devolution. The Commission delivered two documents, one for fiscal powers and the other for more legislative competence, in line with the Scottish reserved power model of devolution. The UK government enacted the Wales Act of 2014 in response to this review. This Act granted additional power, and the Assembly became a Welsh Government. These reforms and the recommendations by the Silk Commission would lead to The Welsh Act 2017, which gave primary legislative powers more in line with Scotland's devolution settlement (Trench, 2007; Moon & Evans, 2017).

2.7 Decentralising Power, Governance Structures and Parliamentary Sovereignty

2.7.1 What Kind of State?

Discussions about how the intergovernmental relationship was established and functioned in the UK typically contrast intergovernmental relations in a devolved state, such as the UK, with those of federal states or federations. According to the literature, devolution transfers power from the central government to the lower tier of government (Rawlings, 1998; Hazell & O'Leary, 1999). The implications and results of decentralising power can vary depending on the characteristics of the central government. McEwen states that "Intergovernmental relations are relations of power" (McEwen, 2020, p. 1). The transfer of power in a federal or unitary state can lead to different power dynamics and disparities in power-sharing. The interpretation of each term is contingent on the context, either federal or unitary, and the definition of each

term is unique. The federal and unitary systems in the United States of America (USA) contrast with those in the German Federation, as each has a distinct form.

Furthermore, the UK's devolution settlements and intergovernmental frameworks are distinct, implying various aspects of power, power-sharing, autonomy, and sovereignty (Hazell & O'Leary, 1999; Rawlings, 1998). Federal states or federations typically have codified constitutions, while central and devolved states have legally defined jurisdictions. This setup fosters horizontal and vertical power-sharing and conflict resolution because of its clear regional and central roles (Bolleyer, 2011; Benz & Broschek, 2013). However, the term "federalism" is disputed and can vary in definition. Elazar (1987) described federalism as a philosophical concept related to principles, while federation pertains to institutional relationships (Elazar, 1987). Burgess and Gagnon (2010) define "federalism" as a type of political organisation that includes various forms, such as federations and confederacies. For clarity, Watts (2008) proposed distinguishing between three terms: federalism, federal political systems, and federations.

The literature concentrates on the UK, which is not a federal state with distinct jurisdictions at the national and sub-national levels (Keating, 2010). This absence of well-defined competency limits explains the characteristics of IGR in the UK. Competencies overlap in a union state with devolved territories (Keating, 2010). This transition necessitates substantial government collaboration and coordination (Keating, 2010). Rhodes (1997) proposed that the UK be classed as a unitary state comprised of a multinational but centralised state with a sovereign parliament. Unlike many other unitary states, such as France, the UK has avoided becoming homogenous and retains a multicultural identity (Rhodes, 1997). The UK also permitted the continuation of institutions in Scotland before the Act of Union 1707 and enabled new ones, particularly in Scotland and Wales, such as Scottish and Welsh offices (Rhodes, 1997). It may be a union, but diversity continues (Rhodes, 1997).

Some would argue that the UK has features of a centralised state. One feature is the parliamentary system of government, and the Westminster Model's core feature is that the Parliament is sovereign and has a stable government, neutral civil service, opposition, and accountability to the electorate. Although its strong centralised leadership characterises the Westminster Model, there is still potential to delegate responsibilities to regions (Rhodes, 1997). However, Rhodes's (1997) argument was constructed before devolution. Devolution is now in place across Scotland, Wales, Northern Ireland, and some regions of England and has

impacted the structure of the UK (Keating, 2010). New Labour delivered devolution to solve political legitimacy issues and quash calls for Scottish independence (Keating, 2010). It was not done to reformulate the UK as a federal state, where there would be equality of sovereignty across UK regions. Keating (2010) argued that devolution has resulted in asymmetrical quasi-federalism. Devolution should not be considered the same as federalism; even when competencies are transferred to a devolved administration, Westminster remains sovereign and has no constitutional limitations (Keating, 2010). However, Kellas (2000) classifies devolution as "an uneasy space between federalism and unitary government" (Kellas, 2000, p. 28).

The idea of the UK as a unitary state has produced a long debate about what kind of state the UK is. The UK is a union of nations that have maintained a degree of diversity, and separate institutions indicate that they have not been fully absorbed into one centralised state (McLean & McMillan, 2005). Tijnstra (2009) added that devolution transfers power from the central state to a designated geographical region. This process indicates that power is dispersed across the UK and can no longer be considered centred only at Westminster (Tijnstra, 2009).

There is a distinction between a central authority and having the highest power of command, with the central authority governing the UK. The Act of Union and the retention of Scottish institutions exemplify this distinction. Critics argue that British lawyers often fail to differentiate between sovereignty and government. They contend that sovereignty is a theoretical concept that conveys the "illimitability, perpetuity, and indivisibility of the ruling authority of a state. Any limit on sovereignty eradicates it" (Loughlin & Tierney, 2018, p. 13). However, they stress that "sovereignty must not be confused with particular institutional forms of government" (Loughlin & Tierney, 2018, p.14). Understanding this distinction is crucial for analysing the shift from government to governance and how devolved administrations operate within this framework.

2.7.2 From Government to Governance

Establishing devolved governments has led to dispersed political power across specific territorial parts of the UK. Tijnstra (2009) suggests that because some competencies are devolved and some are reserved, it is essential to clarify how the central state and devolved territories play a role in delivering policy. Rhodes (1997) argues that the Westminster Model does not accurately explain how the UK state functions. The central state has gradually shifted from governing to governance. According to Rhodes (1997), governance describes the introduction of new agencies, organisations, and non-state actors' involvement in delivering

policy. It explains that policy is not necessarily delivered from the centre but in a system of networks (Rhodes, 1997). The unitary state has become fragmented and has a differentiated polity (Rhodes, 1997). However, Rhodes indicates that acknowledging the emergence of governance and networks does not mean that the central state has been stripped of its power. The Westminster parliament maintains sovereignty but operates interconnectedly with other institutions (Rhodes, 1997).

Likewise, Stoker (1998) put forward a similar argument to Rhodes (1997) by agreeing that there has been a shift from government to governance and that the traditional Westminster Model is no longer relevant. Economic policies have primarily driven this, as the government relinquishes responsibilities to non-state actors (Stoker, 1998). Bache and Flinders (2004) believe that the government's role is policy coordination rather than control (Bache & Flinders, 2004). Policy networks have filled the central state gap and enabled devolved administrations, local governments, and other organisations to deliver policies more efficiently. Rhodes (1997) argues that the centralised state was hollowed out. Goodwin (2012) claims devolution has 'filled in' this space. However, because of the asymmetrical nature of the devolution settlement across devolved administrations, it was unbalanced, leading to increased divergence across the UK (Goodwin, 2012).

Devolution has brought new institutions, and Jeffrey (2007) argues that before The Scotland Act 1998 and the Government of Wales Act 1998 granted devolution, the UK was a centralised unitary state (Jeffrey, 2007). However, Paterson (1994) argued that Scotland had maintained a degree of separateness through its distinctive institutions; this prevented assimilation into England even before devolution. Preserving these institutions creates an opportunity for divergence (Paterson, 1994).

The literature has focused on the Scottish Government increasingly following a path of policy divergence, either by doing things differently or by doing or not doing Westminster policy (Keating, 2010). Similarly, Goodwin (2012) contends that devolution has led to significant changes in government structure across the UK's devolved regions (Goodwin, 2012). It has enabled policy divergence from Westminster, not just constitutional reform that has had "profound implications for public services and consequences of differentiated policymaking" (Adams, 2006, p. 3). However, this argument lacks balance as there is limited literature on devolution in Wales that questions why it does not develop policy that diverges as much as

Scotland. It is unknown if there is limited divergence because they had limited primary legislative powers until 2017, constraining their options for policy divergence.

Michael Keating (2017) added that globalisation and membership in the EU have contributed to the trend towards decentralisation and shifted rigid national borders to a notion of multinational integration. At the same time, governments have shifted to governance and seen powers transferred to these regions. Keating terms this rescaling the movement “of economic, social, and political systems to new spatial levels above, below, and across the nation-state.”(Keating, 2021, p. 334). Rescaling challenges the nature of the traditional hierarchy as authority is arranged at different scales (Brenner, 2001).

Keating (2017) argues that the conventional nation-state model with fixed geographical boundaries is outmoded. Morphet (2013) agrees, noting that when policies are applied at different scales, there is potential for spillover across territories, necessitating cohesion and coordination. Although Keating highlights that the UK is not alone in undergoing rescaling, many European nations are experiencing a similar process. MacKinnon (2015) states, "Rescaling is not a zero-sum game that seeks to erode power from the nation-state." Instead, it can be in the state's interest to devolve powers to better address local and regional issues. This evolving governance landscape, characterised by the decentralisation of power and the emergence of multi-layered policymaking, sets the stage for a deeper exploration of multi-level governance (MLG) and its implications for intergovernmental relations in the UK.

2.7.3 Multi-level Governance

The United Kingdom's membership in the European Community resulted in the UK becoming a component of a supranational government, with the EU holding higher authority than the UK parliament. Establishing devolved governments within its territory has resulted in the UK government operating at multiple levels. Theorists have attempted to understand how the EU, as a sizeable supranational entity, can coordinate and deliver policy across many nation-states and subnational regions. One theory posits that the EU is more than its member states and that other non-government actors at the subnational administration level also play a role. This theory has been termed multi-level governance (MLG) (Bache, 1998; Hooghe & Marks, 2003).

Multi-level Governance (MLG) originated from the work of Marks in the early 1990s, who sought to explain the system of governance that had developed in the European Union (EU). Hooghe and Marks (2003) outline the EU as a supranational organisation that works at a multinational level; to do so requires cooperation, coordination, and negotiation at multiple

levels (Hooghe & Marks, 2003). Hooghe and Marks (2003) found that in MLG systems, power could be shared vertically and horizontally, and MLG recognises the importance of intergovernmental and non-state actors in policymaking (Bache, 1998). The literature argues that the DAs were established when the UK was part of the EU and operated within a system that encourages power-sharing across vertical and horizontal levels, which is not a zero-sum game (Dardanelli, 2005).

MLG advances the understanding of the complexity of policy delivery, the evolution of governance, and more multi-layered policymaking and implementation. MLG challenges the central state with the growth of policy networks that introduce a range of actors in policymaking and delivery (Piattoni, 2010). MLG may challenge the central state because of the increase in subnational and non-government actors that expand the numbers involved in policy delivery. The increase in subnational territories has had a transformative effect on the central state, changing the polity. Hooghe and Marks argued that the central state is no longer a gatekeeper; devolved territory can interact with the supranational state (Hooghe & Marks, 2001; Piattoni, 2009).

There are several differences in applying MLG theory to the UK and comparing it to the Westminster Model. Westminster centralises power and is a hierarchical system with clear accountability limits. Westminster parliament is sovereign within a unitary state, and a unified civil service carries out government business (Dunleavy, 2006). The argument against the Westminster Model is that it is too simplistic, has an organising perspective, and falls short of explaining the changing structures of governance (Bache & Flinders, 2004).

Bache and Flinders (2004) argue that linking Rhodes's (1997) differentiated polity to MLG provides a better organising perspective for understanding the UK than the Westminster Model. A differentiated polity represents a fragmented, not fully centralised state (Bevir & Rhodes, 2008). They argue that a multi-level polity exists and that the UK is a differentiated state with multiple lines of accountability. It is a quasi-federal state with a fragmented civil service and is not as centralised as expected in a unitary state (Bache & Flinders, 2004). Marsh (2011) disagrees with this organising perspective and dismisses differentiated polity as network governance and the hollowed-out state. Piattoni (2010) adds that the challenge for the centralised state is the growth in policy networks and the increase of non-state actors, and UK governance operates with "Overlapping competencies across multiple levels of government; it is not a two-level game; the networks are more complex than this" (Piattoni, 2010, p. 21).

Nevertheless, if the UK is still a unitary state, MLG can still be used to maintain the state's power in the face of complexity (Bache & Flinders, 2004). It can also be contended that MLG is simply an organising perspective with an additional differentiated polity approach. MLG emphasises the intricacy of governance across various levels (Bache & Flinders, 2004).

MLG is useful for exploring the international and domestic forces that impact governance. It is also helpful to understand the more complex nature of governance in the UK than in the Westminster Model system. There is a gap in understanding governance at different levels: MLG is a more dynamic concept (Bache & Flinders, 2004). MLG also acknowledges that power can be shared vertically and horizontally and requires constant negotiation and cooperation (Bache & Flinders, 2004; Piattoni, 2010; Hooghe & Marks, 2001). Devolved administrations have developed links across the EU that have bypassed Westminster. It is unclear how this relationship continued in the post-Brexit period. MLG indicates a change in dynamics and patterns in policymaking (Piattoni, 2010). Peters (2001) believes that the emergence of MLG is due to decentralisation and the hollowing out of the state from the increased autonomy of DAs.

Moran (2015) suggested that MLG can be advantageous in comprehending the intricacy of policymaking, the role of networks in this procedure, and the amount of coordination, negotiation, and compromise needed. Moran states that MLG poses authority, resources, and coordination issues. When power is distributed, it can be hard to determine who has authority, and competency duties can become complex, mainly when non-state actors are involved (Moran, 2015). Aligning policies across different territories and at various levels necessitates negotiation (Moran, 2015). Nevertheless, the success of these negotiations hinges on the effectiveness of intergovernmental relations between devolved administrations and the UK government. Certain modifications to informal IGR practices have been established due to the EU's impact on the UK. The progress of MLG has created the need for an IGR method that encourages coordination and cooperation across vertical and horizontal relationships.

2.8 Brexit: The Constitution, Devolution and Intergovernmental Relations

2.8.1 Brexit: Taking Back Control?

In 2016, the United Kingdom (UK) Government held a referendum to decide whether to remain a member of the European Union (EU). The UK is the first nation to choose to leave. Being part of the EU has had a significant influence on the transformation of British governance.

Much of the literature touches on how Brexit exacerbated territorial disputes. Scotland and Northern Ireland voted to remain in the EU but had to depart due to the UK-wide result. The UK Government's decision to pursue a "hard" Brexit, which involves exiting the EU customs union and internal market, has intensified territorial worries and encouraged nationalist calls for independence referendums in Scotland and a border poll for Irish reunification (McEwen & Murphy, 2022, p.375). Scotland's preference for a soft Brexit included a commitment to stay in the single market, keep freedom of movement, secure EU research funding, and protect the rights of EU citizens in Scotland (Whitman, 2017).

Many academic writers noted how the campaign to exit the EU and the period of negotiations for the withdrawal agreement was characterised by the slogan of 'taking back control', which rekindled the discussion of parliamentary supremacy and the constitution. Hunt (2017) questioned whether control would be restored with the emergence of devolved governments. Sandford and Gormley-Heenan (2020) refer to Schrodinger's devolution as the concept that devolution has brought about a basic constitutional transformation. However, there is also the claim that devolution has not modified the constitution, and Westminster still holds supremacy. Consequently, tension arises because either devolved administrations have authority or they do not. Baldini, Bressanelli, and Gianfreda (2020) argued that this had been a long-standing problem with the Westminster system of sovereignty. However, the devolved administrations had 'permissive authority' or uncontrolled divergence (Baldini, Bressanelli & Gianfreda, 2020). The UK's departure from the EU has caused these unresolved tensions to surface (Sandford & Gormley-Heenan, 2020). McEwen (2022) contended that the DAs gained autonomy through devolution in certain policy areas, but this did not result in constitutional alterations or a more balanced power distribution across the UK. By becoming a member of the EU, multi-level governance was enabled, thus allowing power to be shared among multiple institutions. Outside the EU, however, it is uncertain how power can be effectively shared or if policy areas will instead be implemented simultaneously.

Discussions about whether the UK is a unitary state with Westminster as the supreme Parliament have resurfaced. However, power is only delegated to the Scottish and Welsh Parliaments (Keating, 2022). There has been much discussion about how the politics of the UK might be entering a period of 'muscular unionism' that seeks to re-establish a unified state that never existed, and this is not the case now. Andrews (2021) comments on the shift from the 'devolve and forget' unionism of the early devolution settlement. There are indications that the UK Government is deliberately working to undermine devolution by employing 'muscular

unionism' to bypass the Scottish and Welsh governments, particularly with funding that once came from the EU (Andrews, 2021). Wincott, Murray, and Davis (2022) noted the return of the language of the unitary state. Keating (2022) commented on his surprise to find a White Paper by the UK Government describing the UK as a 'unitary state', adding that he believed it to be a fractional union. The formation of the UK was completed with the unification of one Parliament.

Nevertheless, the preservation of institutions in Scotland and the emergence of devolution, which established more regional institutions, made the UK far from a unitary state, and the logic of the unitary state is that power can be granted down but can be taken back (Keating, 2022). However, McHarg (2017) describes the UK being able to withdraw from the EU regardless of whether the devolved administrations gave legislative consent as a *de facto* victory for the central state in asserting its power (McHarg, 2017). Furthermore, as the UK left the EU in 2020, new legislation was introduced through the House of Commons that could impact devolved power. The UK Internal Market Act 2020 (UKIMA) could constrain the devolved ability to make regulatory choices and impact devolved autonomy (Dougan *et al.*, 2020).

2.8.2 Constitutional and Devolution Issues - Common Frameworks

As the debate persists regarding where power will and should lie in the UK when it is no longer part of the EU, attention turns to how the UK government would replace EU policy frameworks. This is an emerging subject with a limited body of literature. The literature available focuses on what the frameworks will entail and how they will be constructed.

At a Joint Ministerial Committee EU Negotiations (JMC EN), the UK government and the devolved governments issued a communique outlining the primary principles of the new common frameworks (NCF) that would replace the EU policy frameworks. The communique outlines the NCF as an intergovernmental agreement between the UK Government and DAs. These new frameworks are designed to safeguard the UK's internal market while still allowing some degree of divergence, enable the UK to enter trade agreements without obstruction, ensure compliance with international obligations, and ensure the security of the UK. The UK and devolved administrations agreed that the NCF would be developed cooperatively and collaboratively (Cabinet Office, 2017).

The UK government issued documents stating that frameworks would establish a common UK approach and how it will be regulated. "Frameworks may be implemented by legislation, by

executive action, by memorandums of understanding, or by other means depending on the context in which the framework is intended to operate." (Cabinet Office, 2017:2). The UK government argues that there is a need for a common approach, and a new common framework will have to be agreed upon to ensure cohesion but allow for divergence where it is appropriate while harmonising standards or breaking agreed standards. However, due to the different geographic, cultural, political, and economic landscapes across the UK, each of the four nations has differing needs (Ojo *et al.*, 2020). The process could have significant implications for the constitution and the future of the Union, with the potential for policy differentiation across the UK. The sidelining of the DAs during EU negotiations was unhelpful for relations. The JMC (EN) is important for conducting discussions (Hazell & Renwick, 2016).

The UK government had introduced legislation to begin the process of leaving the EU. However, this legislation, the European Union (Withdrawal Agreement) Act 2018, in its original form, threatened to restrict the return of devolved competencies. This led to significant political tensions and the refusal of the devolved governments to agree to a legislative consent motion (Anthony, 2018). The lack of coordinated guidelines led the UK government to decide that shared competencies might only be transferred to the Scottish and Welsh administrations when new common frameworks (NCF) are established to replace the existing EU frameworks (Institute for Government, 2017; Paun, 2018).

2.8.3 The Next Step for Intergovernmental Relations

The development of common frameworks in the post-Brexit era has raised significant questions about the future of intergovernmental relations (IGR) in the UK. Concerns about how effectively IGR can function to ensure sustained cooperation and coordination among the UK government and the devolved administrations have been widely discussed (Hunt, 2017). The need for robust mechanisms to negotiate joint competencies and resolve disputes is paramount to redefining and stabilising the constitutional relationship within the UK. Existing literature offers a range of proposals, from establishing new structures to moderate enhancements of current practices. However, many of these recommendations have not yet been implemented (Sandford & Gormley-Heenan, 2020). This section explores these issues and potential pathways for improving IGR to manage the evolving landscape of UK governance.

Sandford and Gormley-Heenan (2020) propose that establishing new structures enabling the UK government and devolved administrations to negotiate joint competencies and more effective dispute resolution mechanisms could redefine the constitutional relationship.

However, they also point out existing literature suggesting more moderate changes to current structures, such as more frequent JMC meetings (Tierney, 2009), the formation of additional sub-committees and parliamentary oversight (Trench, 2014), and increased transparency and review of IGR procedures (McEwen, 2015). Despite these recommendations, none have been implemented (Sandford & Gormley-Heenan, 2020).

The literature turns to the issues of intergovernmental machinery. Sometime before the discussion about Brexit, Tierney (2009) noted the lack of UK-wide institutions coordinating policy and limited mechanisms to manage disagreements. Paun and Munro (2015) question if the discussions could be developed through the Joint Ministerial Committee (JMC). The evidence indicates that JMCs are usually dominated by the UK government and are not seen as meetings of four partners (Paun & Munro, 2015). Hunt (2017) raises concerns about the unresolved issues of dispute resolution. If a suitable dispute resolution system is not established, friction may arise and be difficult to resolve (Hunt, 2017).

Furthermore, Hunt (2017) notes the limited scope for DAs to engage in a law-making process due to a lack of experience in 'shared' rulemaking. The Miller case has highlighted that the UK government no longer needs consent, as it is only a convention that is not legally enforceable. The Welsh Government produced details on a plan to move towards a more federal style of governance, but the UK ignored this (Hunt, 2017).

Also, Keating (2010) argues that IGR mechanisms are designed to coordinate policy, but if excessive policy divergence arises, the existing mechanisms may not function adequately. So, if the UK government overreacts in response to divergence they disagree with, it could lead to a re-centralisation of power and weaken the devolution agreement. The Act of Parliament created devolved administrations that rely on the benevolence of this Parliament and have limited authority to safeguard the areas they have jurisdiction over if the UK decides to supersede them (Tierney, 2009).

The DAs have been highly critical of the lack of consultation from the UK government on Brexit, which does not bode well for post-Brexit relations (McEwen, 2017). Administering policy in a devolved post-Brexit UK suggests that several issues could cause friction between the UK and devolved governments, as the structure of these connections has not been completely established. There is no way to force the UK government to consult with devolved administrations and involve devolved governments (Cairney, 2012). How the UK resolves conflict concerning competencies, establishes new structures for shared competencies, and

upholds the devolution settlement within a unitary state with Westminster as the supreme Parliament will shape the future of the UK and its ties with devolved administrations.

Following the Brexit vote, the UK government has ordered an additional review of IGR to determine how the UK government and the devolved administrations can collaborate once the UK leaves the EU. The Dunlop Review (2021), headed by Lord Dunlop, identified significant issues like those identified in prior reviews. Suggestions were put forward to modify and formalise certain aspects of IGR and build upon existing institutions (Cabinet Office, 2021). Given that cooperation and coordination are necessary when crafting new common frameworks to replace EU frameworks, it is concerning that issues of the devolution settlement and constitutional matters have already been flagged by the DAs, the House of Lords Select Committee, and the UK government (Hunt, 2017). Addressing these concerns will be crucial for maintaining effective governance and harmonious intergovernmental relations in the post-Brexit era.

2.9 Conclusion

The literature presents a consensus that the UK has evolved into a unique state with an uncodified constitution (Cairney, 2006; Dunleavy, 2006; Keating *et al.*, 2003). This evolution is marked by the different experiences of devolution across the UK, shaped by different constitutional, institutional, historical, and political arrangements. These differences highlight the complexity of asymmetrical devolution and underscore the unresolved constitutional issues, suggesting that the devolution settlement remains unfinished, further complicated by questions about the repatriation of competencies post-Brexit.

Since joining the EU, the UK's political structure has undergone significant changes. EU membership introduced multi-level governance and required the UK to create directives and regulations (Bache, 2004; Jessop, 2004; Hooghe & Marks, 2001). This places the literature review within broader conceptual discussions on power and political authority, regional autonomy, decentralisation of power, and the dynamics between autonomy and shared decision-making. Formulating UK-wide policy frameworks in the post-Brexit context presents several challenges for the UK government and its relationship with the devolved administrations. Any attempts of the UK government to reverse aspects of the devolution settlement could reignite issues of legitimacy (Dardanelli, 2005; Trench, 2007).

The literature explored how devolution has compelled the UK to establish intergovernmental relations, enabling ministers and officials to engage with new subnational institutions. These

intergovernmental relationships will be crucial in managing tensions over devolved policy areas in the post-Brexit period and will be crucial for the UK's future. While the vote to withdraw from the EU has generated a burgeoning field of literature on the impact of Brexit on devolution, the constitution, and devolution, there is still a lack of empirical studies on intergovernmental relations; existing literature suggests that formal intergovernmental frameworks are inadequate and overly reliant on informal connections. Although proposals to strengthen these structures have seen limited implementation, there is a notable gap in the literature on how intergovernmental relations operate in developing common frameworks, such as agricultural support. This lack of empirical data on the UK intergovernmental relationship and the design of common frameworks post-Brexit presents a significant gap in understanding how these dynamics will evolve.

The following chapter will discuss how a theoretical framework of historical institutionalism will be applied to the empirical chapters to generate new literature and contribute to the burgeoning field. This approach addresses the existing gaps and provides a deeper understanding of the evolving intergovernmental relations in the post-Brexit UK.

Chapter 3: Theoretical Framework: Historical Institutionalism, Path Dependency, and the Power to Maintain the Status Quo or Change Institutions

3.1 Introduction

The literature review in the preceding chapter demonstrated that devolution and governance in the UK have evolved. Despite the limited number of empirical studies on intergovernmental relations (IGR), the existing academic literature suggests that the formal structures of the intergovernmental framework are inadequate and overly reliant on informal relations. This study examines how the UK government and the devolved administrations of Scotland and Wales will collaborate to develop a new policy framework for agricultural support.

In this study, the unit of analysis is the intergovernmental framework between the UK government and the devolved administrations of Scotland and Wales. This framework encompasses the formal and informal structures, processes, and interactions that govern these governmental bodies' relationships and collaborative efforts. The intergovernmental framework refers to the systematic and structured arrangements that facilitate intergovernmental relations in the UK. This includes formal mechanisms such as joint committees, regular meetings, and informal interactions and negotiations within the broader context of UK governance. Examining how the IGR framework has operated across the devolution settlement could provide insights into its performance during the development of common frameworks. Consequently, this research will span from 1999, with the introduction of devolution and the intergovernmental framework, to 2022, when the new common framework is implemented.

This study employs historical institutionalism and path dependence as a theoretical framework and examines how historical developments and institutional legacies have shaped the current intergovernmental framework. Historical institutionalism allows us to understand the enduring impact of past institutional arrangements, while path dependence highlights how critical junctures and historical trajectories influence present-day intergovernmental relations. The analysis will focus on key aspects of the intergovernmental framework, including the evolution of formal structures, the nature of intergovernmental processes, and the impact of historical events on current practices. By examining these elements, we aim to uncover the mechanisms through which historical institutionalism and path dependence manifest in the UK's intergovernmental relations.

Studying the intergovernmental framework is essential for understanding the complexities of UK governance in a devolved context. This analysis provides insights into how institutional arrangements evolve, and historical decisions shape contemporary governance practices. By addressing this unit of analysis, the study contributes to broader debates on devolution, intergovernmental relations, and institutional theory.

This chapter explains why historical institutionalism is applied as a theoretical framework. It explores the key concepts derived from historical institutionalism, including path dependency, critical junctures, and power distribution. This chapter explains how these concepts help institutions maintain stability or adapt to change, particularly under pressure. It will then show how identifying the mechanisms of reproduction and the modes of stability and change can be operationalised for empirical analysis.

3.2 The Significance of Institutions

Intergovernmental relations (IGR) and their political systems provide a framework and mechanisms for regional or territorial institutions to communicate and interact (Trench, 2006). In the study of IGR, it is frequently the case that research will be conducted on a comparative basis with other countries. Most of this analysis focuses on the most similar or different system methods for comparison (Anderson & Gallagher, 2018). Academic research often focuses on comparisons between unions and unitary states with federal systems or federations (Laforest & Keating, 2018). Usually, the federal state sets out designated jurisdictions at the national and sub-national levels with more explicit boundaries of competency or if a crossover of competencies exists (Keating, 2010; McEwan, 2020). A federal state usually has a constitution that clarifies its role and that of its sub-states and how the relationship between them should function in areas where crossover occurs (Keating & Laforest, 2018).

This situation is not the case in the UK, which has a primarily unwritten constitution and devolution established by an Act of Parliament (Keating, 2005; Cairney, 2012; McHarg, 2017). This lack of clarity and crossover in the UK requires significant cooperation and coordination between governments (Keating, 2010; McEwan, 2017). Institutional interactions occur through formal and informal processes and mechanisms. This lack of generality or common structures makes the operationalisation of studies and analysis of IGR challenging when applying a theoretical framework (Trench, 2006; Keating, 2010; McEwan, 2017).

Another key factor emerging from the literature is the role of territorial governance. Limited power is decentralised through devolution in the UK, with each territory granted power by

Westminster's Act of Parliament. As set out in the previous chapter, devolution settlements vary, with different competencies allocated to Northern Ireland, Scotland, Wales, and smaller regions in England. In 1999, Scotland immediately attained executive and legislative powers over policy areas unless specifically reserved for Westminster (Keating, Cairney, & Hepburn, 2009). The Welsh Assembly was not granted similar legislative or executive powers until the Government of Wales Act 2006 restructured the Assembly from a corporate body to a separate legislature, the National Assembly for Wales and a new executive Welsh Assembly government. (Trench, 2007). The Welsh Act 2017 gave primary legislative powers more in line with Scotland's devolution settlement (Trench, 2007; Moon & Evans, 2017).

Smaller pockets of devolution in England cannot access the same IGR as Scotland, Wales, or Northern Ireland (Hunt, 2010; Keating, 2017). Intergovernmental relations were established to enable the new institutions in Scotland and Wales to interact, design, and deliver policies with the established UK-wide institutions. Institutional interactions between the UK government, DAs, Whitehall, and other government departments are inconsistent and often informal, lacking transparency (Trench, 2006; Keating, 2010; McEwan, 2017). This asymmetry has impacted how the devolved administrations engage with IGR (MacKinnon, 2015). Pierson and Skocpol (2002) note how territories respond to similar events differently and explain that this is due to the varying forms of institutions within each territory that influence decisions. The devolved administrations in Scotland and Wales have had access to the exact intergovernmental mechanisms but were granted different legislative and executive powers, which may have impacted how those mechanisms were employed (Keating, 2017).

Employing territorial or regional theories and focusing on devolution alone would only go so far as to explain that asymmetry exists and adds complexity to how these institutions interact (Hunt, 2010; Keating, 2017). However, this does not fully explain the existence of asymmetrical elements. The historical context is missing from these theories, which explain how territorial governance and power across UK administrations are unbalanced because they are built from a pre-existing structure that places Westminster and Whitehall as the central power (Trench, 2006; Keating, 2010).

3.3 The Institutional Approach

The institutional approach was devised to analyse formal organisations and their structures (Rhodes, 1995; Goodin & Klingemann, 1996). Since the 1980s, this approach has developed and expanded beyond the scope of assessing the formal institutional structure of rules and laws

to consider the informal aspects of institutions (March & Olsen, 1984; North, 1990). New Institutionalism, a term coined by March and Olsen, builds upon institutionalism but considers the importance of institutions in shaping behaviours and influencing political life (Lowndes & Lempriere, 2018). It also considers how temporal phenomena might impact existing institutions or influence the creation of new ones (Goodin & Klingemann, 1996; Fioretos, Falleti, & Sheingate, 2016). New Institutionalism (NI) has three branches: rational choice, sociological, and historical institutionalism. It is generally agreed that there is some overlap between the three branches of NI, as each shares a common belief that institutions are central to political behaviour. However, each holds different ontological and epistemological perspectives (Steinmo, 2001).

Rational choice theory (RCT) aims to understand political behaviour and action. Institutions are entities created by efficiency-maximising individuals with clear intentions (Mahoney & Thelen, 2010). Rational choice theory is based on the premise that institutions are actor-centred and focus on decisions made by individuals within institutions (Weingast, 1996; Lowndes & Robert, 2013). This supports the position that institutional change can be explained by actors having agency and the power to make choices and that they do so logically and strategically (North, 1984; Weingast, 1996).

Sociological institutionalism centres on how institutions form and reflect accepted norms and behaviour. This idea influences a broader perception of what can or cannot be done and acknowledges the broader cultural aspects that affect institutions; therefore, the sociological perspective focuses on structure rather than agency (Meyer & Rowan, 1991). Historical Institutionalism (HI) bridges rational choice theory and the sociological perspective on how institutions are created and how stability and change can occur (Hall & Taylor, 1998; Thelen, 1999; Steinmo & Thelen, 2001).

3.4 Historical Institutionalism

3.4.1 History Matters

Although no universally agreed definition of historical institutionalism (HI) exists, several established features differentiate it from the rational choice and sociological interpretations of institutionalism. Similar to sociological institutionalism, it has roots in structural functionalism, as there is an emphasis on the structural aspects of institutions and how they interact and less focus on the actions of individuals (Hall & Taylor, 1996). Sociological institutionalism offers an organisational perspective on how institutions are created and reflects society's culture and

social norms (Pierson & Skocpol, 2002). Historical institutionalism is a theoretical approach that emphasises the role of institutions in shaping political and social outcomes. It focuses on understanding how institutions, understood as formal and informal rules and procedures, shape behaviour, political processes, and social change over time (Blyth, 2002; Blyth, 2016). Historical institutionalism strongly emphasises institutions' historical context and path-dependent nature (Pierson, 2015). Thelen (1999) defines historical institutionalism as an approach that seeks to "understand and explain how institutions change or persist over time" (Thelen, 1999, p.383). She argues that historical institutionalism views institutions as both constraining and enabling actors' behaviour and shapes the outcomes of political and social processes (Hall, 1996; Blyth, 2002). Hall (1996) emphasises that historical institutionalism seeks to explain how institutions are created, maintained, and changed and how they influence actors' choices and behaviour. Historical institutionalism highlights the importance of historical contingencies and the idea that the development of institutions is path-dependent, meaning that previous decisions and institutional arrangements shape future possibilities. It recognises that institutions are not fixed or immutable but can evolve, adapt, or be transformed in response to changing circumstances or external shocks.

One of the most significant factors that separate HI from the rational choice or sociological perspective is the importance of history and timing. Institutions are historical products created in a time and place and exist as a structure that constrains choice, differing from the rational choice theory of individual agency, which uses institutions as an instrument (Pierson & Skocpol, 1979; Hay & Wincott, 1998; Pierson, 2000; Marsh, 2004). Historical institutional theorists argue that researchers must consider temporal events to understand fully why an institution is created, its impact, and its evolution (Thelen, 2002; Pierson & Skocpol, 2002). These institutions should be studied following the sequence of events taken when established by tracing how formal rules and procedures, informal practices, and functions are established and developed. This approach has enabled researchers to understand why some countries develop national healthcare and comprehensive welfare systems or favour private insurance systems (Steinmo, 2008). Through the application of historical institutionalism through process tracing, a context can be built that shows when and how the institution is shaped, its power dynamics, and how that power has evolved and who it benefits (Pierson & Skocpol, 2002; Mahoney, 2004; Fioretos, Falleti, & Sheingate, 2016). This sequence of events can expose subtle power imbalances, explain why some decisions were made, and explain how the legacy of those choices influenced or restricted future actors (Thelen, 2002).

History matters in gaining empirical knowledge about institutions and how they remain stable or transform (Thelen, 1999). Pierson and Skocpol (2016) expand on the importance of research over a selected period; widening the analysis timeframe extends the range of experience available for examination. This aspect simultaneously makes more data available and produces more significant outcome variation. Historically informed research also signals the temporal circumstances of causal relationships (Rueschemeyer & Stephens, 1997; Mahoney, 2006). Therefore, systematic process tracing can support or challenge claims on causation (Hall, 1998; Mahoney, 2006; Rueschemeyer & Stephens, 1997).

"Sophisticated process-tracing thus often involves a substantial historical component. Without attentiveness to a temporally specified process, a distinctive hallmark of historical institutionalist scholarship, important outcomes may go unobserved, causal relationships may be misunderstood, and valuable hypotheses may never be considered." (Pierson and Skocpol, 2016, p.6)

Historical institutionalism is a theoretical framework that can be applied to contemporary issues and is better understood by widening the study's timeframe. Patterns may become evident, and causal relationships can be traced and identified, providing a deeper and richer understanding of a phenomenon (Thelen, 2000; Mahoney, 2006; Pierson & Skocpol, 2016). This research project addresses a unique event. No other state has left the EU; therefore, there is a lack of knowledge of how a member state negotiates with its devolved administrations to replace the EU policy framework. This can be accomplished by applying the historical institutional framework.

3.4.2 Path Dependency

Historical institutionalists claim that a significant tool for understanding institutional change is exploring how institutions follow 'path dependency.' Path dependency has evolved from economics and technology literature to explain why some systems exist and prevail, even when they may not be the most efficient (Arthur, 1989). Pierson focuses on how historical events and initial institutional choices can create enduring behaviour patterns and shape the trajectory of political and social processes. According to Pierson, path dependence refers to a situation where the outcome of a process or the development of an institution is heavily influenced by its initial conditions or choices. In other words, the choices made in the past can set a particular path or trajectory that becomes difficult to change in the future. Pierson argued that path dependence is driven by two key mechanisms: Increasing Returns that create Positive Feedback loops and institutional lock-in.

Pierson (2015) states that 'increasing returns' explain how choices or events can create self-reinforcing dynamics, in which initial advantages or disadvantages are amplified over time. This means that once a particular option gains an advantage or dominance, alternative options become increasingly challenging to gain traction. The increasing returns generate 'positive-feedback loops.' Positive feedback occurs when the benefits or advantages of a particular path accumulate and create a reinforcing cycle. As the benefits of a chosen path increase, it attracts more resources, support, and adherence, further entrenching its dominance.

Institutions, once created, tend to persist, a phenomenon often attributed to the initial financial investment in their establishment. This concept is linked to the economic theory of 'increasing returns,' which leads to an institution becoming 'locked in' (Pierson, 2015). Pierson (2015) emphasises the concept of lock-in, referring to the entrenchment of a particular path due to the high costs associated with changing it. Lock-in occurs when switching to an alternative path becomes prohibitively expensive, making it difficult for actors to deviate from the existing trajectory. Even if they recognise its limitations or inefficiency, it is argued that change becomes difficult to imagine once an investment has been made and an institution has become ingrained due to the time and money spent on its establishment and maintenance (Pierson, 2004; Bennett & Elman, 2006). Path dependence underscores the notion that institutions and policy choices do not necessarily result from rational decision-making processes or optimal outcomes. Instead, historical events and initial conditions can create "pathways" that shape subsequent political and social developments, often with unintended consequences.

This theory contrasts with the economic concept of 'diminishing returns,' in which returns diminish once equilibrium is reached. However, for institutions, a reduction in returns does not imply that a change will occur, as institutions and policies can become embedded in the norms of a society in which change seems unimaginable. Additionally, those with vested interests in continuity strive to maintain the status quo. Ironically, economic reforms have proven to resist change, with regressive tax systems remarkably resilient (Conran & Thelen, 2016). This situation results in 'institutional stickiness' and helps explain why institutions, particularly political ones, cleave to outdated or antiquated modes of operation or are slow to change (Campbell, 2010; Pierson, 2015).

Historical Institutionalism and path dependency reveal that institutions maintain the status quo and resist change; any change or shift tends to be incremental or subtle (Mahoney & Thelen, 2010; Van der Heijden & Kuhlmann, 2017). However, some path dependency theorists argue

that change can be sudden and extreme, resulting in a critical juncture (Krausener, 2018). According to historical institutionalism, critical junctures are pivotal moments when significant institutional changes occur, leading to long-lasting effects on subsequent political and social development trajectories. Thelen (2004) argues that these critical junctures are characterised by a breakdown of existing institutional arrangements and the emergence of new ones resulting from a combination of exogenous shocks. Hall (1993) describes critical junctures as "moments of fundamental transformation in which existing institutions are challenged, new institutions are created, and path-dependent processes are disrupted" (Hall, 1993, p. 282). Hall emphasises that critical junctures often arise from external shocks, such as economic crises or geopolitical shifts, creating opportunities for actors to reshape institutional arrangements. This can lead to rapid institutional transformation and reshape an institution's trajectory and development (Fioretos, Falletti, & Sheingate, 2016).

The UK's withdrawal from the EU was a unique and unprecedented event that could have caused significant disruption and change. A member state withdrawing from the EU is an exceptional occurrence, and there are no prior examples of how a state reorders itself or removes a higher level of power. Additionally, the UK does not have the same governance structures as before joining the EU. By applying Historical Institutionalism, research can retrospectively address this issue and determine whether such an event is dramatic enough to constitute a critical juncture that sets the institution on a new path. Without process tracing, it is challenging to identify when these junctures occur and their impact on institutional functions (Capoccia & Kelemen, 2007; Capoccia, 2016).

Nevertheless, not all HI theorists agree that critical junctures appropriately describe how institutional change occurs. Often, a perceived sudden change is less impactful than expected and can be classified as a punctuated evolution or equilibrium, resulting in little change (Hall, 2001; North, 1994; Capoccia & Kelemen, 2007). Not all changes can be attributed to exogenous shocks. In some circumstances, endogenous events can amplify existing or increasing pressure, creating a cumulative effect and pushing existing institutions to their limits. When institutions are stable, they are in a state of equilibrium; once equilibrium has peaked or forced by excessive endogenous pressure increases and positive feedback has been exhausted, changes might occur (Thelen, 2006).

Table 3.1 External and internal drivers for changes.

Exogenous Shocks	Endogenous Pressures
War	Policy Change
Recession	Policy Reform
Regime Change	Change in Social Norms
Global Pandemic	Political Change

(Collier & Collier, 1991; Pierson, 2010; Campbell, 2010; Conran & Thelen, 2016).

Exogenous events may be more straightforward to identify, and any disruption may be so significant that a critical juncture or punctuated equilibrium is readily observed (Mahoney, 2000; Pierson, 2015). These incidents include major external events, such as wars, global recessions, or pandemics. Institutions may have to be created, or existing institutions may be reset on a new course and repurposed to manage these issues (Campbell, 2010; Conran & Thelen, 2016). Recognising changes caused by endogenous pressures may be more challenging to ascertain because they may not arrive as suddenly as exogenous pressures might. These pressures might initially appear minor or subtle and usually occur when a government change brings different political and policy agendas and attempts to amend or transform existing institutions or policies (Pierson, 2010). Thus, by considering path dependency and performing process tracing to analyse a particular period, it may be possible to recognise the events that lead to a build-up of pressure that pushes an institution to its limits, resulting in changes that may occur more gradually or subtly. Identifying the source of the change may be more difficult in such cases because it occurs more slowly (Collier & Collier, 1991). However, many theorists have argued that even if institutions are path-dependent, they typically follow incremental but continuous evolution: institutions maintain the status quo but are not inert (Pierson, 2010; Campbell, 2010; Conran & Thelen, 2016).

3.5 Measuring Institutional Stability and Change

3.5.1 The Mechanisms and Modes

The challenge for all branches of institutional analysis is identifying and measuring institutional stability or change and discovering the power dynamics that maintain the status quo or drive institutional change. This section clarifies how historical institutionalism, using path dependency, can uncover and explain institutional stability and change. Early literature

surrounding historical institutionalism and path dependency has been criticised for focusing on continuity until sudden or radical shifts occur. Recent work in this field has been directed towards understanding the influence of endogenous pressures (Mahoney & Thelen, 2010).

Developments in the literature have focused on identifying the mechanisms that indicate institutional stability to discover whether incremental change has occurred and how it can be measured. Identifying these mechanisms plays a key role in this study. Streeck and Thelen (2005) argue that historical institutionalism and path dependency can be operationalised to analyse a sequence of events. If frequently noted patterns are found, causal propositions that identify sources of institutional change can be developed. Pierson (2016) emphasised the need to identify Increasing Returns, Positive Feedback loops, and Institutional Lock-In as factors important to understanding the features that enable actors to take actions that lead to change and the features within an institution that make it vulnerable to change. Mahoney and Thelen (2010) broadened this concept and further suggested that other elements that should be studied are how certain institutions are more prone to institutional lock-in than others and that it is essential to recognise the characteristics of an institution that will influence its transformation.

3.5.2 Institutional Reproduction

Several key theorists have proposed ways to recognise the self-reinforcing mechanisms that sustain institutional stability, which they refer to as mechanisms of reproduction. These institutional mechanisms of reproduction (IMR) can also be referred to as positive or negative feedback loops (Pierson, 2004). Institutional reproductive mechanisms are the persistent features of an institutional interaction pattern that cause overall stability. Increasing returns and positive feedback loops allow institutions to reach an equilibrium. The key to understanding how institutions remain stable or 'locked in' is to identify the mechanism of reproduction; if stability is maintained, what creates vulnerability can be identified, as stability and change are 'two sides of the same coin' (Thelen, 2006; Conran & Thelen, 2016). The three branches of new institutionalism and their mechanisms of reproduction are listed in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2. Mechanism of Reproduction

Rational Choice Utilitarian-Functionalism	Sociological Sociological-Cultural	Historical Institutionalism Power-Distribution
Start-up cost	Legitimacy	Power Asymmetry
Educational Investment	Expectations	Hierarchy
Complementary systems/domino effect	Behaviour	Multiplicity/Institutional Interdependence
Policy lock-in	Cultural	Actor/Power Coalition

(North, 1990; Pierson, 2004; Mahoney, 2004; Thelen, 2006; Duit, 2007)

The Rational Choice branch of new institutionalism is based on functionalist-utilitarian theories of institutional stability. This concept emphasises efficiency and its link to increasing returns. Institutions resist change due to investments in existing structures, entrenched frameworks that impede change, and a more rigid policy-making or decision-making process (Campbell, 2010; Streeck & Thelen, 2005; Thelen, 2004). In contrast, the sociological branch of new institutionalism falls under the legitimacy-sociological-cultural category. Here, institutional principles become part of the culture and are widely accepted without much opposition. Examples include human rights and international organisations like the UN (Campbell, 2004; Thelen, 2004; Boas, 2010).

The third category comprises historical institutional theories, which focus on power imbalances. Patterns of power distribution emerge when disagreements over authority, uncertainties about hierarchy, multiple actors, and a dominant coalition exert excessive power (Thelen, 2004; Mahoney & Thelen, 2009). However, the mechanisms of reproduction in rational choice and sociological institutionalism do not consider historical perspectives. These perspectives could reveal when and why institutions begin to develop increasing returns, how culture and norms shift, and the power dynamics driving these changes (Pierson, 2004; Mahoney, 2016; Thelen, 2016).

Rational choice theory, sociological institutionalism, and historical institutionalism identify different elements explaining how institutions possess self-reinforcing characteristics that ensure stability. Historical institutionalism, however, views institutions as instruments of power distribution that perpetuate the benefits of power (Skocpol et al., 2010). In contrast, rational

choice and sociological institutionalism acknowledge that power underpins cultural and normative practices. Historical institutionalism contends that institutions are legacies of past political conflicts (Hall, 1996; Mahoney, 2009). Understanding power distribution is crucial to understanding who maintains the status quo and what drives institutional change. According to this perspective, change occurs when "problems around rule interpretation and enforcement open up space for actors to implement existing rules in new ways" (Mahoney & Thelen, 2010, p. 2).

Historical institutionalism is a power-political perspective that emphasises the power-distributional nature of institutions, which could explain why institutions remain in place due to increasing returns to power. HI argues that institutions are vulnerable to internal forces that cause transformation because they are "distributional instruments laden with power implications" (Pierson, 2016). Conflicts arise within and between institutions because of competition for power and resources. Nonetheless, the tension is not always intentional but can result from the unintended consequences of conflict and compromise, meaning that institutional arrangements are not always self-sustaining or automatic. Compromise makes organisations susceptible to changes, and those who favour stability must ensure ongoing political backing or take advantage of ambiguities if they work to their benefit. When resources are accumulated, systems are implemented to ensure that those in power continue to benefit from the distribution. Institutions also vary, and resource allocation may affect conflicts in other institutions. Consequently, those disadvantaged by institutions can use their power to compete for change (Mahoney & Thelen, 2010).

This research project seeks to critically examine how the UK government and devolved administrations developed a new common framework for agricultural support, making the mechanisms of reproduction associated with historical institutionalism particularly pertinent to this enquiry. The UK government and its devolved administrations agreed to cooperate in a cooperative and collaborative working relationship. Existing literature suggests a lack of mechanisms to enable joint decision-making or manage disputes within the intergovernmental framework. Investigating the power imbalances within the intergovernmental relationship should reveal whether a status-quo bias enables UK institutions to constrain devolved institutions and enforce a common framework that the UK government prefers or if the devolved administrations could drive change and shape new frameworks and institutions.

3.5.3 Modes of Change

Historical institutionalism helps us comprehend how institutional transformation is achievable, how it can be recognised, and where the impetus to alter or transform institutions is derived. Streeck and Thelen (2005) identified five modes that can be used to detect incremental changes: displacement, layering, drift, conversion, or exhaustion. After further investigation, they concluded that exhaustion and drift were too similar to be considered distinct modes and thus narrowed the list down to four (Streeck & Thelen, 2005). When implementing power shifts, it is also essential to assume the role of 'intercurrence'. One mode can create space and bring in other modes, implying that gradual changes can be dynamic (Koreh et al., 2019).

Displacement may occur when a power shift to another political party intentionally destroys existing policies or institutions. This change often requires significant veto powers in the hands of those capable of defeating strong or numerous interest groups that may resist change (Thelen, 2009; Hacker et al., 2015). Some institutions are so normalised within a society that they are taken for granted. This is often the case in countries with an established welfare system. It may be possible to make minor or radical adaptations to policy depending on the ideology or aims of the incumbent government. However, there is a fundamental assumption that some form of the welfare state would persist. Even when there is a good reason to remove an institution, such as a change in government, ideology, or culture, they are so ingrained in cultural norms that they persist.

Mahoney and Thelen (2010) use the example of the House of Lords as an institution filled with unelected, hereditary elites who held opposing ideological ideals to incoming Labour governments. Before winning the election, the Labour Party promised to dismantle the House of Lords. They did not radically reform or dismantle the second chamber, but reducing their hereditary peers and curtailing their power enabled them to survive. Even those in power find that they must make political compromises and may seek change by capitalising on existing weaknesses instead of dismantling existing institutions and avoiding displacement (Koreh et al., 2019).

If extensive institutional or policy changes are not possible, layering may change institutions. Often, decisions are made to layer over existing rules; however, doing so may lead to unanticipated changes in the existing rules and structures. Changes believed to be small or minor revisions have resulted in significant changes in existing institutions (Conran & Thelen, 2018; Van Der Heijden, 2011). Layering is required because of the existence of gaps. Pierson

(2004) outlines the reasons for this gap as the limits of initial institutional design. Layering the gap between intentions and outcomes may involve additions or revisions to rules, policy processes, or actors (Mahoney & Thelen, 2010). A layering process occurs when changes are incremental as further rules or structures are added to the existing ones. In addition, increasing the number of additional layers may result in minor changes; however, this process can transform the institution's fundamental nature. Newer institutions built around existing ones grow faster and dominate resources away from pre-existing ones (Boas, 2007; Mahoney & Thelen, 2010; Thelen, 2004). This idea of layering over existing structures may explain the form that devolution takes in the UK. In Scotland, more powers are devolved, which may reflect pre-existing administrative capacity. In Wales, limited powers were granted in 1999, possibly because most of the existing administrative and institutional capacity for policy delivery was still held by Westminster and Whitehall.

Another mode of change can be attributed to drift, which occurs when a policy or institution is no longer appropriate or outmoded, and decisions are avoided to correct this; therefore, institutions and policies are deliberately neglected (Streeck & Thelen, 2005; Mahoney & Thelen, 2010). Hacker et al. (2015) argue that drift is a deliberate resistance to introducing new rules that ensure the institution is no longer relevant. They argued that this was a covert political manoeuvre, as drift implies the gradual demise of an institution through neglect to avoid conflict with influential stakeholders (Thelen, 2009; Hacker & Pierson, 2010; Thelen, 2013). Examples of drift often relate to welfare policies, where it may be publicly unpopular to end or restrict the welfare state, but the government avoids adapting to meet or keep pace with current needs. These policies then become ineffective, allowing them to justify significant changes.

Conversion is an institutional redirection by actors who wish an institution to perform differently without changing rules. This process is attributed to the fact that actors in power may have very different ideologies or motivations from those who created the institution. The institution's shifting towards a new function is a deliberate course of action by the government or policymakers so that it has a different purpose from the one it conceived for. However, Institutions that have undergone conversion may be at risk of unanticipated and unintended consequences (Hacker et al., 2015; Thelen, 2009).

It has been argued that these modes of change are more likely to be achieved in opaque institutions because actors with specific strategies or agendas can use drift or conversion to reshape or end an institution, with little threat of this becoming apparent due to a lack of

scrutiny or transparency (Thelen, 2009; Hacker et al., 2015). It is also more likely if the rules of the institution lack 'precision', leaving an institution vulnerable to conversion as the actors within can take advantage of the ambiguity (Thelen, 2009; Hacker et al., 2015).

These modes may indicate that change is often a gradual process, and those with vested interests in continuity strive to maintain status quo bias. In addition, 'institutional stickiness' may constrain the changes that can be made (Campbell, 2010; Pierson, 2010; Conran & Thelen, 2016). Nevertheless, actors with power and strategy or agenda may be motivated to attempt and achieve change. Outside a sudden critical juncture, institutions tend towards incremental change and remain relatively stable. This stability is attributed to self-enforcement and increasing power returns (Thelen, 2009; Hacker et al., 2015). Hacker et al. (2015) believe that layering, conversion, and drift are required for stability. Institutional reproduction requires actions to ensure institutions function through layering or conversion; otherwise, drift will occur.

3.5.4 Modes of Stability

Historical institutionalism and path dependency propose that once an institution is set on a course, the capacity for change onto a new path becomes constrained by a lack of choices, so the institution becomes 'locked in' (Pierson & Skocpol, 2002; Mahoney, 2004). Institutions tend to remain stable; if a change occurs, it may be sudden and dramatic. Much of the early research on institutional change has focused on critical or punctuated equilibrium. However, Pierson (2016) acknowledged this problem and how incremental changes are often overlooked. He claimed that institutional change could be better understood if closer attention is paid to periods of stability.

Galik and Chelbi (2021) systematically reviewed environmental policy literature. They found that the demand for policy change is often rapid but developing in an area that involves institutions that may be slower to adjust or interact effectively due to a lack of institutional capacity. Galik and Chelbi (2021) identified the key elements of institutional change as being who held power and their ability to maintain the status quo, thus ensuring institutional stability. Established institutions tend to be heavily biased towards the status quo. Unless an external event creates a pivotal moment, institutions will likely resist internal pressure to bring about change. Only when more influential veto players surface can they bring about some form of transformation and destabilise existing institutions (Thelen, 2009; Hacker et al., 2015; Galik & Chelbi, 2021).

Table 3.3. Modes of stability

	<i>Non-purposeful</i>	<i>Purposeful</i>
<i>Institution reinforced</i>	Passive Stability	Active Stability
<i>Change avoided</i>	Intended Inaction	Failed Action

(Duit, 2010; Capoccia, 2016; Veenendaal, 2017; Galik and Chelbi, 2021)

First, stability can be maintained through 'passive stability' when there is adherence to established norms. If standards and practices have been established, agents within an institution will be aware of how interactions across institutions are conducted. Once these norms are set, the agents cannot change how the interactions are performed. In addition, established culture and ingrained patterns can create barriers that impede different institutions from collaborating (Sedgwick & Jensen, 2021). Second, active stability occurs when agents are motivated to retain their advantageous arrangement. Agents within institutions actively pursue the status quo and reproduce legitimacy (Duit, 2010; Veenendaal, 2017; Galik & Chelbi, 2021).

Change can also be avoided through 'intended inaction,' when influential veto players intentionally avoid actions threatening the status quo bias. However, 'failed action' may also maintain stability even if some veto players attempt to change as other veto players work against them to resist change. This resistance to change usually occurs in institutions with power asymmetries (Capoccia, 2016; Galik & Chelbi, 2021). Determining who becomes a powerful veto player and how an institution can become dominated by one group over others is crucial for understanding the historical context of institutions. By considering who designed the institution, it may be possible to identify that the structure of the institution was intentionally designed to favour one group over another. Institutions dominated by influential veto players have the power to resist change and to impede or facilitate policies (Thelen, 2009; Hacker et al., 2015; Galik & Chelbi, 2021).

3.5.5 Agents of Change

When seeking to understand the institutional status quo or change through the lens of historical institutionalism, it should be noted that this theoretical approach views institutions as the

political outcomes of past conflicts, with a power-political element to institutions emphasising the distributional aspect. This explains their endurance due to increasing returns to power. Owing to ambiguity and the lack of rule enforcement, some actors can introduce change through displacement, layering, conversion, or drift by reinterpreting the rules.

Compliance with rule interpretation and enforcement is another critical variable for analysing the institutional status quo and change. Ambiguity over either of these aspects makes institutions vulnerable to change (Mahoney & Thelen, 2010). In addition, power or resource distribution changes can create events across a series of institutions. This disruption may not necessarily be dramatic or evident but can lead to incremental changes. As power coalitions shift and divisions develop, institutions can become vulnerable, enabling some to take advantage of rule ambiguity or lack of rule enforcement. Stability requires actors to accept, follow, and enforce rules. Actors with conflicting beliefs or interests may take advantage of this and take divergent actions, leading to a shift in institutions. In countries with devolved administrations governed by opposing political parties to the central government, this might become a feature that enables DAs to pursue their agendas or push towards a culture change, leading to behaviour that becomes a new norm (Mahoney & Thelen, 2010).

However, institutions are complex, and it is impossible to create a set of rules so precise that ambiguity is wholly avoided. In addition, events may require an institution to adapt and necessitate a lack of compliance to fulfil these needs. This lack of compliance is not deliberate game-playing but an adaptation to real-world events. A second factor is how rules are followed and enforced and by whom, which requires a level of compliance to rule enforcement. Will all rules be enforced, or will some rules be more likely to be implemented over others? Changes occur in rules, interpretations, and enforcement gaps. Those who can take advantage of this are veto players; however, it would be more accurate to describe these actors as having veto possibilities (Tsebelis, 2002).

Veto possibilities might better explain that while some individual actors may have significant power, others with strong veto possibilities may have considerable powers to resist change; however, that power may only be over particular departments of institutions (Mahoney & Thelen, 2010). The modes of change pursued by those who wish to push for change depend on two variables. Firstly, the strength of those veto possibilities matters. Secondly, the amount of discretion they hold to reinterpret or avoid enforcing rules.

Table 3.4 Veto Possibilities Political Context vs Targeted Institutions

Veto Possibilities	Discretion	Mode of Change
Strong veto possibilities	low-level discretion	Layering
Strong veto possibilities	high-level discretion	Drift
Weak veto possibilities	low levels discretion	Displacement
Weak veto possibilities	high-level discretion	Conversion

(Hacker & Pierson, 2010; Mahoney and Thelen, 2010)

Earlier historical institutionalism and path dependency literature define institutional stability and incremental change as distinct phenomena. However, recent studies have attempted to establish how the modes of change identified by Streck and Thelen (2005)—layering, conversion, and drift— can be used by those in power to maintain the status quo (Capano, 2018). These modes can be used to avoid institutional transformation. However, some may be more successful than others, depending on the extent of the veto power available to those who wish to limit change. In addition, the success of these agents depends on the ambiguity of the existing rules of the institutions and the lack of transparency or accountability that offers opportunities for reinterpretation (Capano, 2018).

Layering is identified as leading to incremental change. Capano (2018) argues that layering may 'lock in' or 'stabilise' an institution, drive institutional stickiness, or act as a countermeasure to deter or stall change pushed by other forces. Capano (2018) further argues that layering is misunderstood and underspecified. This should be identified as a mode of institutional design, not a change because it is an essential element of state reproduction through incremental adaptation. Changing how layering is perceived makes it a better analytical tool for understanding how legacy, vested interest, and maintaining equilibrium may direct new policies or institutional designs to layer upon existing ones (Capano, 2018).

Conversion can be identified as a mode of change when the government or policymaker applies new rules to an existing institution to alter existing goals. However, it can be used to maintain the status quo by making minor adaptations to existing regulations to maintain institutional relevance and avoid making costly changes or unpredictable outcomes (Koreh et al., 2019).

Drift usually means that a deliberate decision has been made to freeze an institution or policy, resulting in the demise or irrelevance of institutions. This action may involve abandoning welfare policies or healthcare to enter the private market. However, damaging the function of an institution may upset the equilibrium to the extent that stakeholder support can be driven to correct the drift with layering. Drift as a mode of change can backfire on those in power; change does not necessarily mean that the change will be driven towards the changes the agents want.

Modes of change such as layering, conversion, and drift can be employed to change or maintain the status quo. However, if opacity or ambiguity surrounds the functions of an institution, it becomes difficult to determine who will benefit from it. Applying historical institutionalism as a theoretical framework and employing process tracing can identify the modes used to reinforce the status quo or change institutions and, more importantly, detect power structures. Understanding the existence of power asymmetries should indicate whether a status quo bias exists, favouring one group to dominate and hinder inter-institutional relationships to function in a truly cooperative and collaborative manner (Hacker & Pierson, 2010; Thelen, 2009; Sedgwick & Jensen, 2021).

3.6 Conclusion

This chapter has explored the theoretical frameworks of historical institutionalism and path dependency to understand the dynamics of institutional stability and change. It has provided an in-depth examination of the mechanisms and modes through which institutions maintain their stability or undergo transformation. Historical institutionalism offers a robust framework for analysing how past decisions and conflicts shape current institutional structures, highlighting the importance of temporal factors and historical context. Path dependency underscores the significance of initial choices and the self-reinforcing mechanisms that make institutions resistant to change.

The chapter detailed the various mechanisms of institutional reproduction, such as increasing returns and positive feedback loops, that contribute to institutional stability. It also discussed the modes of change identified by Streck and Thelen (2005)—displacement, layering, drift, and conversion—illustrating how these processes can lead to incremental changes within institutions. Examining these modes, we can understand how institutions adapt and evolve, even without exogenic shocks.

Moreover, this chapter has highlighted the role of power dynamics in shaping institutional outcomes. The distribution of power within institutions and among actors plays a crucial role

in determining whether institutions remain stable or undergo change. The concepts of veto players and veto possibilities have been introduced to explain how veto power can be transient and how those actors with significant veto power can influence the trajectory of institutional development.

The discussion has also emphasised the importance of compliance with rule interpretation and enforcement. Ambiguity in these areas makes institutions vulnerable to change, as actors can exploit these ambiguities to introduce new interpretations or avoid enforcement. This aspect is particularly relevant in the context of the UK's intergovernmental relations, where devolved administrations may seek to pursue their agendas within the constraints of the existing institutional framework.

In conclusion, historical institutionalism and path dependency provide valuable insights into institutional stability and change complexities. They offer a comprehensive framework for analysing how institutions evolve, the mechanisms that sustain them, and the conditions under which change occurs. By applying these theoretical perspectives to the study of the UK's intergovernmental relations, we can better understand the dynamics at play and the potential for future developments in the context of devolution and governance.

This theoretical framework will be instrumental in analysing the empirical data and understanding the specific case of the UK's intergovernmental framework for agricultural support. The following chapter discusses the methodological approach and research design applied to generate and analyse empirical data. Subsequent chapters will apply these concepts to the empirical analysis, exploring how historical developments and institutional legacies have shaped intergovernmental relations in the UK.

Chapter 4: Methodology and Research Design

4.1 Introduction

The previous chapters have situated this study within the existing literature and defined the theoretical approaches of historical institutionalism used in this study. This section outlines and justifies the research design and methodological approach for the operationalisation of this thesis. The opening section of this chapter addresses the overall methodological approach of critical realism, explaining how this approach fits within broader debates about ontological and epistemological issues. The second section of this chapter examines the thesis research design as a comparative case study and how process tracing is applied. The concluding section outlines how the data from documentary evidence, parliamentary debates, and committee meetings were collected and analysed through a critical realist approach to thematic analysis. The chapter ends with a discussion of ethical considerations.

4.2 Methodology Approach

The research project methodology should be consistent with the study's focus, research design, and theoretical framework. Furlong and Marsh (2010) stress that ontological and epistemological positions "are like a skin, not a sweater: they cannot be put on and taken off," and thus the researcher's stance must be articulated, as it serves as a guide for the research (Furlong & Marsh, 2010, p. 177). Therefore, the methodological assumptions in this thesis are grounded in a critical realist framework. A fundamental tenet of critical realism is that ontology, or what is real, cannot be reduced to epistemology or our understanding of reality. This perspective is an alternative to a positivist or interpretive stance; critical realism acknowledges the role of actors' subjective understanding and the presence of structures that limit their options for action (Wynn & Williams, 2012).

Roy Bhaskar, a key proponent of critical realism, developed an ontological framework that asserted that reproductive forces work in a social environment that produces social phenomena. Scientific enquiry usually reveals these processes, which are not visible to the naked eye. Critical realism stresses the significance of uncovering the hidden mechanisms that shape social reality. Bhaskar (1975) positioned critical realism within the context of institutions, perceiving them as composed of individuals and resources. He contended that understanding the interactions between institutions and the power dynamics of other entities reveals how change is generated, with entities constrained only by other, more influential entities. Critical realism explicitly outlines causality by clarifying the methods or processes through which

structures and actions create events and contextual conditions in a particular setting (Williams, 2012; Fletcher, 2017; Maxwell, 2012). According to critical realism, researchers determine a causal explanation for a phenomenon by recognising how structural entities and contextual conditions interact to produce events (Wynn & Williams, 2012). This approach offers a more comprehensive explanation of causality, considering actors' interpretations of events and the structures and mechanisms that lead to a particular result (Wynn & Williams, 2012).

This study uses historical institutionalism as a theoretical framework to explore the complex relationships among multiple institutions with various power dynamics. Easton (2010) recommends critical realism as an inventive way of comprehending intricate organisational occurrences. Marsh (2004) argues that based on critical realist assumptions, historical institutionalism and path dependency circumvent the issue found in rational choice theory, which mainly concentrates on agency, and sociological institutionalism, which focuses on structure.

"We need an approach that sees the relationship between structure and agency as dialectical, interactive, and iterative. This approach is axiomatic within critical realism" (Marsh et al., 2004, p. 11).

According to Marsh (2004), the relationship between structure and agency should be understood as the dynamic process in which structures and individual actions continuously influence and shape each other over time. This perspective is fundamental within critical realism, reinforcing the importance of structural constraints and human agency in social analysis. Historical institutionalism, an epistemology based on critical realism, can produce qualitative analyses (Marsh et al., 2004). Critical realism, used to direct comparative case studies, provides an in-depth examination of how similar organisations with similar processes function in various contexts over time (Cruickshank, 2003; Vincent & O'Mahoney, 2018). Both critical realism and historical institutionalism emphasise the significance of context in comprehending social phenomena. They acknowledge that institutions and social processes are formed by distinct historical, cultural, and political contexts and that these contexts are essential for understanding the evolution of institutional change. Critical realist ontology and historical institutionalism have much in common, as both approaches take a critical and nuanced view of social phenomena, emphasise the importance of structures and mechanisms, and recognise the impact of historical processes and contexts on the formation of institutions (Fawcett & Marsh, 2015).

4.3 Research Design

4.3.1 Comparative Case Study

A comparative case study was the most appropriate approach to address the research questions. Bennett and Checkel (2012) suggest that all research methods have benefits and limitations, and researchers must consider which method offers (Bennett & Checkel, 2012). A comparative case study can uncover undiscovered elements, identify causal mechanisms, build a context and explanation for historical events, and identify relationships that indicate path dependency (Bennett & Checkel, 2012).

A case study offers a greater possibility of enabling the researcher to gain deeper and more nuanced insights into how and why an outcome occurs (Goodwin & Horowitz, 2002). Adding a comparative aspect instead of focusing on one case can also enhance the possibility of generating important data from multiple sources, which other methods may not achieve (Merriam & Tisdell, 2015; Creswell et al., 2007; Hancock & Algozzine, 2017). This comparative method is useful when context is at the core of understanding an issue. Finding similarities and differences adds to finding patterns for process tracing that contribute to identifying causal mechanisms (Goodwin & Horowitz, 2002). In addition, research exploring path dependency benefits from this method as it offers a holistic analysis of events. This makes it possible to identify the variables underlying a contingent event that may be missed if not looked for. However, this method has limitations, as it may provide insightful data on this specific phenomenon and may be difficult to generalise and apply to other areas (Hodkinson & Hodkinson, 2001). Nevertheless, this criticism can be overcome by incorporating multiple sources of evidence from transcripts, policy documents, and reports, ensuring that triangulation of evidence provides a more convincing result and avoids studies that lack validity (Stake, 1995; Yin, 2003).

4.3.2 Comparative Case Study Selection – Scotland and Wales

A comparative case study between the devolved administrations of Scotland and Wales and their institutional and intergovernmental relationships with the UK government offers an intensive cross-case analysis (Collier & Collier, 1991; Mahoney, 2004).

Firstly, the devolution settlements of Scotland and Wales differ significantly, providing a rich ground for comparative analysis. Scotland immediately attained executive and legislative powers in 1999 over policy areas unless specifically reserved for Westminster (Keating et al., 2009). In contrast, the National Assembly for Wales was initially granted more limited powers,

functioning primarily as a corporate body until the Government of Wales Act 2006 restructured it into a separate legislature and established the Welsh Assembly government. (Trench, 2007). The Wales Act 2017 provided primary legislative powers that were more in line with Scotland's devolution settlement (Trench, 2007; Moon & Evans, 2017). This variation in devolution timelines and scope allows for a nuanced examination of how different levels and timings of devolved powers impact governance and policy implementation.

Frequently, when comparative research is conducted, institutional change is explored at the national level but overlooked at the subnational level (Snyder, 2001). Employing a Subnational comparative method enables researchers to consider the significance of a scale when measuring institutional changes. Assumptions about regional or subnational levels disregard uniformity; therefore, when institutional or policy change occurs at the national level, there is a lack of knowledge of the impact at the subnational level, which may work differently in each unit (Harbers & Ingram, 2019). This issue is relevant to Scotland and Wales; each territory's devolution settlement differs and has been enhanced across devolved administrations (DAs) at different times and degrees. This project seeks to determine whether changes made at the national level have similar or different effects at the subnational level. Moreover, it explores the mechanisms that influence stability and change within the devolved administrations of Scotland and Wales and how the dynamics of power relationships, other events, or more subtle processes may present themselves differently, creating a similar or different outcome.

Considering the position of devolved administrations in this research project offers the opportunity to discover whether causal relationships operate differently at the subnational level (Harbers & Ingram, 2019). Evidence to find out how these relationships might operate differently can be collected in two ways: from a bottom-up approach to discovering whether there are subnational variables that create national outcomes. Alternatively, a top-down approach can be employed to discover the variable that operates at the national level but causes subnational outcomes within a nation-case study (Harbers & Ingram, 2019; Soifer, 2019). Bottom-up theories utilise subnational factors to strengthen the explanations of national outcomes. Top-down theories value the experience of each subnational unit as worth discovering regardless of the outcome at the national level (Giraudy, 2019). This project will critically examine the intergovernmental framework employed by the central government with a devolved administration. The top-down approach enables the research to look for more than just similarities or differences between Scotland and Wales; it also allows researchers to

discover how their specific relationship with the UK government influences the institutional status quo.

However, this approach has limitations when operationalising a study when the unit of analysis is the UK intergovernmental architecture. Researchers must anticipate data availability at the subnational level when conducting subnational comparisons. This study faced several issues in this regard. First, authorities frequently aggregated Welsh data with English data. Second, the devolution settlement in Wales granted limited power, leading ministers and officials to conduct most interactions through informal discussions, which are not in the public domain. Third, during the early days of devolution in Scotland, party congruence across the UK led to intra-party and informal interactions, resulting in limited tangible data.

Furthermore, examining new common frameworks, particularly in the context of post-Brexit UK, is crucial in understanding the evolving intergovernmental relationships between the UK government and the devolved administrations of Scotland and Wales. With the UK's withdrawal from the EU, policy areas previously governed by EU regulations, such as the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), now require UK-wide frameworks to ensure consistency and coherence across the UK. The CAP, which provided substantial autonomy to subnational administrations in its implementation, is a significant case study for assessing these new intergovernmental dynamics. As Scotland and Wales transition from managing EU-driven policies to designing a UK-wide framework, this shift offers a unique opportunity to analyse how these devolved administrations navigate and negotiate their policy-making autonomy within the new structures. This analysis will shed light on the implications of these frameworks for governance and policy implementation and their broader impact on the stability and change within the institutional arrangements of the devolved administrations. It underscores the importance of understanding how the specific relationship between the UK government and its devolved counterparts influences the operationalisation and effectiveness of such frameworks, thus providing deeper insights into the intergovernmental landscape in the post-Brexit era.

Also, while three devolved administrations exist in the UK, this project focuses exclusively on the Scottish and Welsh administrations and excludes Northern Ireland (NI). The situation in NI during this period was complex, making the research project unmanageable if included. The Brexit settlement in NI differs significantly from that in Scotland and Wales, and the NI Executive was also closed during essential parts of this thesis's timeframe. These delimitations

are necessary to maintain feasibility and focus, ensuring a thorough and manageable analysis of the selected case studies.

4.4 Process Tracing

This chapter has so far explained the selection of a comparative case study between the devolved administrations of Scotland and Wales. The research applies a theoretical framework of Historical Institutionalism (HI) and path dependency (PD) to the research question. Several key historical institutional theorists, including Thelen (1999) and Pierson & Skocpol (2002), contend that researchers pursuing this approach should apply process tracing. This method searches for causal mechanisms through the historical trajectories of an institution's informal rules, procedures, functions, or networks. By doing so, researchers can build a context that shows when and how the institution was shaped, what power dynamics exist, how that power evolved and who it benefits (Pierson & Skocpol, 2002; Mahoney, 2004; Fioretos, Falleti, & Sheingate, 2016).

Process tracing originated in cognitive psychology but was adopted by Alexander George (1979) for political science case studies and used as a method to produce inferences to explain historical events (Bennett & Checkel, 2005). George (1979) applied process tracing to political psychology to analyse individual decision-making. However, he believed it could be applied to structural or macro-level matters. George found that this method contradicted Rational Choice theory, which assumed that political actors made the best decision based on their knowledge. Process tracing can be used to track the causal chain and mechanism of the decision-making process, and he discovered that this was a helpful method of understanding bias and other factors, such as preferences, values, and goals, that influenced the decisions of actors (Bennett & Checkel, 2005; Vennesson, 2008).

The process tracing method takes three forms: theory testing, theory building, and case-oriented. The first two methods rely on hypothesis testing, and several theorists have created a prescriptive formula for operationalising these types of studies. Hypothesis testing may be helpful in some instances; however, theory testing or theory building was inappropriate for this study. The forms of process tracing that engage in hypothesis testing can restrict the perspective and scope of the study and the researcher, especially in unknown or under-researched areas. This study focuses on the relationship between the UK government and devolved administrations (DAs) outside the EU. As the EU withdrawal is a recent event, there is little research in this field. In addition, before the EU withdrawal, intergovernmental relations

between the UK government and DAs attracted limited interest, except for a few key authors. A significant gap in the literature indicates that a case-oriented study would be a useful approach.

The purpose of the case-oriented method is not to test or build a theory but to find a sufficient theoretical explanation of a particular outcome. It is a valuable narrative creation method that discovers inferences and causal mechanisms with substantively and theoretically interesting outcomes (Bengtsson & Ruonavaara, 2017). It is also helpful in cases lacking generalisability to a broader population. Setting out without a hypothesis enables the researcher to discover and examine both systemic and non-systemic mechanisms. Przeworski and Teune (1970) illustrated the difference between theory- and case-centric research. A theory-centric study might consider revolutions, but a case-centric model would better understand the French Revolution. Therefore, the study of a specific event benefits from a case-centric, in-depth approach that seeks to determine the link or absence of a link in a causal chain of mechanisms.

4.4.1 Comparative Process Tracing

Critics argue that the case-centric model of process tracing lacks external validity due to its limited generalisability. Researchers can overcome this problem by cross-case comparing similar cases (Beach & Pedersen, 2019). Comparative process tracing (CPT) effectively links theory, comparison, and chronology (Bengtsson & Ruonavaara, 2017). Path dependence forms the core components of CPT; Bengtsson and Ruonavaara (2017) stress the importance of “identifying critical junctures, political focal points, social mechanisms, contexts, periodisation, and counterfactual analysis” (Bengtsson & Ruonavaara, 2017, p.45). Comparative process tracing follows a two-step approach. In the first step, researchers systematically analyse cases selected for comparison from A (initial conditions) to B (outcome) to identify and examine social mechanisms. In this study, A started in 1999 and B in 2022. In the second step, researchers compare these processes using the mechanisms identified during a specific period in the literature review.

4.4.2 Step One - Social Mechanisms

Comparative process tracing (CPT) explores how and why outcomes occur instead of counterfactual outcomes. It uses cross-case comparison to uncover systemic and non-systemic interpretations, recognising that understanding the events leading to an outcome is sometimes necessary. Process tracing examines how actors' actions, relationships, and other contextual factors produce various social and political outcomes. Researchers achieve this by focusing on

tracing processes. This method helps understand institutional change and stability through path dependence (Bengtsson & Ruonavaara, 2017).

Researchers achieve this by conducting within-case studies focusing initially on Scotland and Wales separately. This approach addresses the primary research questions by identifying critical junctures, political focal points, and social mechanisms contributing to institutions' path dependency. According to Bengtsson and Ruonavaara (2017), the first step of comparative process tracing involves identifying indicators of these elements. Beginning by addressing what Bengtsson and Ruonavaara (2017) identified as social mechanisms, they described them as regular patterns of actions and interactions that are causally productive by producing outcomes. (Bengtsson & Ruonavaara, 2017, p.53). Their description of social mechanisms fits with the historical institutionalist concept of the mechanism of reproduction set out in the theoretical framework chapter. These institutional mechanisms of reproduction (IMR) may also be referred to as positive or negative feedback loops (Pierson, 2004).

Increasing returns and positive feedback allow institutions to reach an equilibrium. The key to understanding how institutions remain stable is identifying the mechanisms of reproduction. If what maintains stability is understood, what creates vulnerability can be identified, as stability and change are 'two sides of the same coin' (Thelen, 2006; Conran & Thelen, 2016). The chapter on the theoretical framework clarifies that this study focuses on power-distributional mechanisms. It seeks to understand the decision-making process, the veto possibilities held by some individual actors or coalitions, and their power to create change or maintain the status quo. Power distribution mechanisms are identified when there are issues over authority, confusion over hierarchy, multiplicity, and a dominant coalition overexerting power (Thelen, 2004; Mahoney & Thelen, 2009).

Path dependency focuses on identifying self-reinforcing sequences and mechanisms of reproduction. Mahoney (2000) argues that understanding not just that history matters but how it matters involves identifying elements that explain how institutional continuity is maintained. Mahoney further asserts that institutions often originate from critical junctures, sudden, exogenous events that exert sufficient pressure to instigate significant change. At these critical junctures, alternative structures and frameworks become possible. Once a choice is made and a new pathway established, reverting to discarded options becomes nearly impossible, leading the institution to develop "deterministic causal patterns" (Mahoney, 2000, p. 511). This type of

path dependency is known as strong path dependency (PD). However, this form of PD does not account for gradual change or the influence of endogenous pressures on institutions.

Bengtsson and Ruonavaara (2017) propose a weak form of path dependency that considers PD a “historical pattern where the outcome can be traced back to a particular set of events that indicate endogenous pressures that led to change” (Bengtsson & Ruonavaara, 2017, p.50). This method shows that change does not always occur because of a critical juncture; however, finding a significant political focal point might suggest the possibility of gradual institutional change. Bengtsson and Ruonavaara (2017) described political focal points as periods when there is a political decision to make policy or institutional change, but institutional limitations restrict changes. This method identifies decisions that may seem insubstantial and incremental, such as the modes of change in the theoretical framework (displacement, layering, drift, or conversion). This path dependency may explain the differing devolution settlements across the UK. In Scotland, more power was delivered, reflecting pre-existing administrative capacity. In Wales, limited powers were granted in 1999, indicating a lack of administrative and institutional capacity before devolution compared to Scotland.

4.4.3 Step Two - Context and Periodisation

The next step is context-dependent; therefore, social mechanisms must have an element of generalisability to be portable for comparison, which means that to make a comparison relevant, the context of the units chosen for comparison should be similar. In this case, Scotland and Wales were selected as there are enough similarities to make a comparison possible but enough differences to make an evaluation. Other contextual factors include the social, political, and cultural settings within which actors and social mechanisms function to understand how a situation originates from points A to B. What elements influence actors' preferences, social norms, and beliefs within institutions and their access to resources that enable or reduce their ability to act? (Bengtsson & Ruonavaara, 2017).

Path dependency and periodisation require the study to be conducted in temporal situations and phases. This does not mean that a rigid timeframe is universally applied when comparing because countries rarely simultaneously undergo stages when a specific process occurs. However, a particular timeframe (1999-2022) was used in this study to set permits for gathering data. This study identified key political focal points that could distinguish specific periods when events occurred, which may have created enough pressure to cause change. The literature review revealed emerging themes and focal points ranging from devolution to

intergovernmental relations (IGR), how UK governance has changed, the influence of European Union (EU) institutions, and institutional interactions across the United Kingdom (UK). The data were broken down into key dates to identify political focal points and examined in three empirical chapters:

- **Chapter 5 (1999-2016):** This period marks the introduction of devolution, including the SNP election in Scotland and increased powers granted to Wales. During this period, significant developments occurred, including further devolution of powers, the Scottish independence referendum, and the Brexit referendum.
- **Chapter 6 (1999-2016):** This section covers when the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) became a devolved competence for the Scottish and Welsh administrations. Scottish, Welsh and English agricultural support policies diverged significantly, leading each nation to implement its own version of the CAP.
- **Chapter 7 (2016-2022):** This chapter discusses key events such as the UK's withdrawal from the EU, the consultation and publication process of the new intergovernmental framework, and the establishment of a new common framework for agricultural support.

4.5 Data Collection Methods

This section outlines the data collection methods used in this research and is divided into two parts. The first part details the documentary data sources and their justification, while the second part explains the rationale for and sources of committee meeting transcripts and parliamentary debates.

4.5.1 Document Data

Document study, also known as the analysis of written sources, is critical to this research. This study predominantly employs documents produced by governments and stakeholders, incorporating a mix of primary, secondary, and tertiary sources (Bryman, 2004). The sourced documents were published between 1999 and 2022, and this comparative case study draws on documents from various institutions. The selected documents address complex issues across multiple fields, including intergovernmental relations, devolution, new common frameworks, and agricultural policy. Identifying and collecting documents for this research was methodical and comprehensive. Extensive searches were conducted across relevant government and stakeholder websites, including government archives and institutional repositories, using

targeted keywords related to intergovernmental relations, devolution, common frameworks, and agricultural policies.

The selection criteria for their ability to provide significant insights into intergovernmental relations, devolution, common frameworks, or agricultural policies between 1999-2022. This relevance criterion ensured that only documents directly pertinent to the core areas of investigation were included (Bryman, 2004). Selected documents, including UK government documents such as Acts of Parliament, memoranda of understanding, and Joint Ministerial Committee Communiqués from 2017, set out principles agreed upon by the UK government and devolved administrations for designing new common frameworks. This sample includes reports on the progress of these frameworks, documents from UK government-commissioned reviews of intergovernmental frameworks, and DEFRA documents outlining the future of agriculture. These documents were crucial for understanding the UK government's perspective and actions. Samples from the Scottish Government, Parliament, and Directorates documents, including letters between Scottish parliamentary committees and cabinet secretaries, were reviewed to understand concerns about common frameworks, the IGF, or progress made. Documents from Welsh institutions included reports and proposals for future Welsh agriculture, although fewer documents and letters were available compared to Scotland.

Additional sources included documents from House of Lords Scrutiny Committees, particularly the House of Lords Select Committee Common Frameworks Scrutiny Committee, established in 2020. This committee gathered substantial evidence from relevant administrations, ministerial departments, and stakeholders. Two key reports published in 2021 and 2022 provided critical evidence on the common frameworks.

Documents from agricultural and environmental stakeholders, such as the National Farmers Union in Scotland (NFUS) and Wales (NFUSW), and other Scottish and Welsh farming, agricultural, and environmental groups, were also included. These documents discussed agricultural policy and their engagement with the UK or devolved administrations, offering perspectives that might not be found in government documents.

These documents were selected to understand the phenomena being studied comprehensively. They offer a timeline of events, track changes, and help identify institutional mechanisms of reproduction (Bowen, 2009). The following table provides a detailed overview of the documents used, justifying their inclusion and indicating the chapters in which they are analysed.

Table 4.1: Document Sources and Justification

Document Source	Justification	Chapter of Thesis
Provisional Common Framework for Agricultural Support	Essential for understanding the new common frameworks and their development process	7
Intergovernmental Review (2022).	Provides insights into the latest review of intergovernmental relations	7
Memorandum of Understanding and Concordats (MoU)	Key documents outlining the agreed principles of working arrangements since the establishment of devolution	5, 7
UK Government Commissioned Reviews: The Richard Commission, 2004; Calman Commission, 2009; The Smith Commission, 2014; Silk Commission, 2014; Dunlop Review, 2021	These reviews provide evidence of the evolution of devolution and intergovernmental relations. It provides statements from Officials and Ministers who engaged in IGR and explained their experiences. These reviews systematically document the recommendations for changes and are used to assess whether these recommendations were implemented in subsequent reviews.	5, 7
House of Lords Constitutional Committee Scrutiny Reports: Devolution: Inter-institutional Relations in the United Kingdom (2002) The Union and devolution (2016)	This committee collected statements from Officials and Ministers who engaged in IGR and explained their experiences. This report offers critical scrutiny of constitutional and intergovernmental matters.	5, 7
House of Lords Common Frameworks Scrutiny Committee Reports: First report, Common Frameworks: Building a Cooperative Union, (2021) Second report, Common Framework: An Unfulfilled Opportunity? (2022)	These reports provide detailed analysis and recommendations on the common frameworks (House of Lords, 2021, 2022).	7
Relevant policy documents from the UK government and devolved administrations	Provide context and specifics on policy changes and proposals, including agricultural support policy	5, 6, 7
Joint Ministerial Committee Communiqués (Plenary and EU negotiations)	Document the principles and discussions related to the design of new common frameworks (JMC, 2017).	5, 7
Inter-Ministerial Group for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (IMG EFRA) Communiqués	Provide insights into coordinating agricultural policy and dispute resolution mechanisms (DEFRA, 2022).	7
Government reviews of Foot & Mouth Response	Insights into UK-wide and Scotland and Wales specific action of crisis management	6

Government Reviews of BSE Response		
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This refined selection process ensured that the documents included in this study were highly relevant, authoritative, and comprehensive, providing a robust foundation for analysing the evolution of intergovernmental relations, devolution, and agricultural policies in the UK

4.5.2 Transcripts

Initially, the research plan included interviewing ministers and officials from Scottish, Welsh, and UK administrations. These interviews aimed to gain in-depth insights from those involved in the consultation, design, implementation, and management of new common frameworks. However, conducting these interviews proved unfeasible due to several factors, including the prolonged timeline caused by Brexit negotiations, general elections, and the COVID-19 pandemic. Consequently, the study relied on an alternative data source: committee meeting transcripts and parliamentary debates.

4.5.2.1 Committee Meeting Transcripts

The House of Lords Select Committee Common Frameworks Scrutiny Committee extensively examined the common framework process. From November 2020 to April 2022, they conducted twenty-two in-depth meetings to gather oral evidence. At these meetings, eleven lords invited key individuals, such as Members of the Scottish Parliament, Members of the Senedd, Members of Parliament, the Minister for the Constitution and Devolution at the Cabinet Office, and other senior officials from the Cabinet Office, including the second permanent secretary and the Deputy Director for Common Frameworks. Other officials came from the Department for Levelling Up, Housing and Communities, the Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs, the Scottish Government, the Welsh Government, the Scotland Office, the Wales Office, and the Northern Ireland Office. Furthermore, other key stakeholders from agriculture and experts in the constitution and devolution were invited, including Lord Dunlop, who had just concluded the latest review of intergovernmental relations.

During these meetings, extensive questions were asked about the process and progress of the new common frameworks. The committee was also concerned with understanding how the intergovernmental relationship functioned during this process. These meetings generated twenty-two transcripts that voiced ministers' and officials' experience designing the new common framework. However, it should be noted that Michael Gove, who was the Chancellor

of the Duchy of Lancaster responsible for the Union and then became Secretary of State for Levelling Up, Housing, and Communities with the additional title of Minister for Intergovernmental Relations until his resignation in 2022, only interacted with the committee in writing.

Therefore, the House of Lords Select Committee Common Frameworks Scrutiny Committee transcripts are an excellent data source that offers in-depth insights into critical areas of interest to address research questions. They cover the common framework design and interview every key individual participating in the process, providing a comprehensive overview from inception to completion. Access to such detailed information and key individuals would be challenging for a post-graduate researcher, making these transcripts an exceptional data source.

4.5.2.2 Parliamentary Transcripts

Incorporating parliamentary debates into this study provided another valuable data source. Parliaments are arenas of discussion, compromise, accountability, and scrutiny (Ilie, 2022). The debates offer insights into the political climate, queries posed to ministers, and their responses, thereby contributing to constructing context and information on events.

These transcripts were sourced from parliamentary websites such as the Scottish Parliament (MSPs), members of the Assembly (MAs) and Senedd (MSs), and members of the House of Commons (MPs). Generating data from each parliament involved a thorough search from 1999 to 2022 using keywords related to devolution, intergovernmental relations, common agricultural policies, agricultural support, and common frameworks. The process was laborious, requiring meticulous searching of each meeting's records. This effort generated a substantial number of transcripts, which were then systematically coded. To ensure manageability, these transcripts were further distilled into several excerpts to exemplify key findings uncovered during the coding process and are presented in the findings chapters to illustrate the study's insights effectively.

Table 4.2: Transcript Sources

Parliamentary Debates & Committee Meeting Transcript Source	Excerpts Referenced Within Thesis	Chapter of Thesis
House of Commons Parliamentary Debates & Committee Meetings	7	5, 6
House of Lords Committee Meetings	17	5, 7
Scottish Parliament Debates & Committee Meetings	18	5, 6, 7
Welsh Assembly/Senedd Parliamentary Debates & Committee Meetings	15	5, 6, 7

These transcripts were crucial for understanding the political discourse and the intergovernmental relationships between the UK government and the devolved administrations, thereby providing a well-rounded perspective for the research (Ilie, 2022).

4.6 Data Analysis Methods

4.6.1 Introduction

This study aims to discover whether the Scottish and Welsh administrations' experiences engaging with the intergovernmental framework to design a new common framework for agricultural support differ and to understand the reasons behind these differences. This case-oriented study uses data analysis to provide evidence for both descriptive and causal inference (Collier, 2011).

As the key proponents of process tracing agree, the finding of causal inference leads to identifying causal mechanisms that are key to understanding a particular outcome. However, there is no clear definition of a causal mechanism, and it could be an ambiguous term open to interpretation (Gerring, 2010). Guala (2010) advises that when conducting comparative process tracing and trying to identify causal mechanisms, they should be classed as "regularly operating causal relationships that generate one or more regularities between events" (Guala, 2010, p.1072). Gläser and Laudel (2019) describe causal mechanisms as a "sequence of causally linked events that repeatedly occur in reality if certain conditions are given and which link specified initial conditions to a specific outcome" (Gläser & Laudel, 2019, p.3). They further

argue that their summation of a causal mechanism is consistent with the definitions put forward by Mayntz (2004), Boudon (1979), and Elster (2015). However, Gläser and Laudel (2019) argued that qualitative research lacks a strategy for extracting causal mechanisms from empirical materials. They recommended applying thematic analysis to answer this research question.

4.6.2 Establish reliability and Trustworthiness

While thematic analysis is a versatile approach to qualitative research methods, discrepancies may arise when creating codes (Holloway & Todres, 2003). Nowell *et al.* (2017) proposed that these issues can be minimised by ensuring an explicit ontological and epistemological stance (Nowell *et al.*, 2017). Critical realism, which emphasises identifying and understanding causal mechanisms behind observable events and patterns, provides such a stance. By applying thematic analysis from a critical realist perspective, researchers can move beyond merely describing patterns to explain why these patterns emerge. This approach allows for a deeper exploration of the mechanisms generating the themes in the data, offering a richer and more explanatory account of the social phenomena under investigation. Ensuring the reliability of thematic analysis is crucial for establishing research validity. Tobin and Begley (2004) suggest addressing this challenge through data collection triangulation.

4.6.3 The Critical Realist Approach to Thematic Analysis

Combining critical realism with thematic analysis provides a nuanced and insightful understanding of social phenomena. Critical realism posits that reality exists independently of our perceptions, but our knowledge of this reality is mediated through our experiences and perceptions. This ontological stance allows researchers to explore the underlying structures and mechanisms that shape social phenomena. Thematic analysis within a critical realist framework can help uncover the deeper, often hidden, structures and mechanisms that influence the themes observed in the data. It encourages researchers to move beyond surface-level descriptions to understand the underlying causal processes (Bhaskar, 1978; Kowalczyk Sayer & New, 2000).

Critical realism highlights the significance of context in shaping social reality. Thematic analysis within this framework encourages researchers to consider the broader social, cultural, and historical contexts that influence the emergence of themes in the data. This approach contextualises the themes, providing a more holistic understanding of the social phenomena (Archer, 1995). It enables researchers to explore how context interacts with mechanisms to produce outcomes. It may also encourage reflexivity, acknowledging the researcher's role in

the research process. Thematic analysis within this perspective prompts researchers to reflect on their assumptions and biases that may shape the interpretation of themes. By being reflexive, researchers can enhance the epistemic virtue of their analysis, ensuring a more rigorous and self-aware approach to understanding and representing social reality (Danermark, Ekström, & Karlsson, 2019).

Critical realism offers a versatile and robust framework for thematic analysis, acknowledging the complex interplay between social structures and human agency. It recognises that data are based on participants' interpretations of reality, influenced by their social and cultural contexts (Wiltshire & Ronkainen, 2021; Fryer, 2022). This approach aims to provide an engaging interpretation of participants' perspectives while acknowledging that social structures influence their views of events. Critical realism posits that reality consists of three layers: the empirical, which involves experiences and perceptions; the actual, referring to events that take place; and the real, encompassing the underlying structures and mechanisms that cause events.

By applying critical realism to thematic analysis, this study seeks to uncover not only what is experienced (the empirical) and what happens (the actual) but also to understand the deeper causal mechanisms (the real) that underpin these phenomena. Integrating critical realism with thematic analysis allows this study to describe observed patterns and explain why they occur, offering a comprehensive understanding of the social phenomena under investigation (Wiltshire & Ronkainen, 2021; Fryer, 2022).

4.6.4 Thematic Analysis Coding Framework

This study employs Fryer's (2022) method of thematic analysis. This version adapts Braun and Clarke's (2021) thematic analysis framework to a critical realist perspective (Fryer, 2022). Table 4.3 sets out Fryer's five-step approach.

Table 4.3: Summary of the five-step critical realist approach to TA

Step 1: Develop your research questions	Identify the experiences or events of interest and develop one or more causal research questions.
Step 2: Familiarise yourself with the data	Skim read a large proportion of the data. Make notes on initial thoughts and questions.
Step 3: Apply, develop and review codes	Apply descriptive codes to the data using a data-led approach. Develop these codes by standardising processes (using the same wording for similar codes) and consolidating (using theoretical terms to unite different codes). Review codes by assessing their validity.
Step 4: Develop and review themes	Develop themes (causal explanations of experiences/events). Review themes by assessing their validity.
Step 5: Generate conclusions and reports	Reflect on the overall analysis and review the validity of conclusions. Consider how to communicate the conclusions best.

(Fryer, 2022)

Step One: Research Questions

Following Fryer's (2022) five-step approach, the first step is identifying the phenomena under study and formulating research questions that seek causal explanations. The primary research question and supplementary questions are as follows:

Primary Research Question: To what extent does the intergovernmental relationship enable Scottish and Welsh administrations to participate in designing a new common framework for agricultural support?

Supplementary Questions

- What are the fundamental principles and structures underpinning the UK's intergovernmental frameworks?

- To what extent have they developed since the introduction of devolution?
- To what extent has previous engagement with the UK government in developing agricultural support policy shaped the current intergovernmental relationship?
- To what extent is the experience different for Scottish and Welsh administrations?

Fryer (2022) suggests considering experiences, events, and causal mechanisms when developing research questions. In this context, experiences relate to the perceptions of ministers and officials who interact with the intergovernmental relationship, events refer to their actual interactions and outcomes, and causal mechanisms involve the factors driving these interactions and outcomes.

Step Two: Familiarisation with the Data

The initial stage involved data immersion to gain a deeper understanding. Relevant documents were uploaded to the qualitative data analysis software NVivo to assist in identifying phrases and sentences pertinent to the research questions using keyword searches related to devolution, intergovernmental relations, common agricultural policies, agricultural support, and common frameworks.

Step three: Apply, develop and review codes.

In this stage, a comprehensive coding process was implemented using inductive, deductive, and abductive approaches. This combined approach aims to understand the empirical data and the underlying causal mechanisms, allowing for a dynamic and iterative method.

Inductive Coding was initially employed to let themes emerge naturally from the data without imposing pre-existing categories. This bottom-up, data-driven approach generates unbiased analysis and produces themes rooted in empirical evidence (Braun & Clarke, 2013). By closely examining the data, patterns and themes surfaced organically, ensuring the analysis was grounded in the data rather than influenced by external frameworks or theories. This approach was instrumental in identifying new and unexpected themes related to the evolution of the UK's intergovernmental frameworks.

Following this, Deductive Coding was employed to bring a structured methodology to the analysis. Deductive coding employs predefined concepts or categories from the theoretical framework to guide the analysis. According to Fereday and Muir-Cochrane (2006), this top-down, theory-driven approach provides a structured methodology for examining the data. By

applying established theories to the data, deductive coding helps affirm or refine these theoretical constructs within the study context, providing a clear linkage between theory and empirical findings.

Next, Abductive Coding was introduced to add depth and richness to the analysis. This iterative process moves continuously between the data and the theoretical framework to identify and interpret patterns that were not immediately apparent. Abductive coding facilitated the development of new understandings or modifications to existing theories, uncovering deeper insights and enhancing the overall analysis (Timmermans & Tavory, 2012).

After applying initial coding, a standardisation process was developed so that similar codes used consistent wording and consolidated different codes using theoretical terms to ensure clarity and coherence. The codes were reviewed to assess whether they accurately represented the data and aligned with the theoretical framework, resulting in valid and reliable codes.

For instance, Chapter 5 used this coding approach to examine the principles and structures underpinning the UK's intergovernmental frameworks and their evolution since devolution. The initial codes that emerged through this iterative process were associated with the transfer of powers from the Scottish/Welsh Office, asymmetrical power distribution, continuation and continuity, devolution nested within existing structures, lack of devolved parliamentary engagement, UK-designed IGR architecture, and the legacy of previous arrangements before devolution. Inductive coding highlighted new themes, deductive coding aligned them with the theoretical framework, and abductive coding refined these insights, ensuring a robust and nuanced analysis (See **Appendix A** for a more detailed example of Chapter 5 coding).

The analysis comprehensively understood the findings using inductive, deductive, and abductive coding methods. Each approach contributed uniquely, ensuring a thorough examination of the data that integrated empirical evidence with theoretical perspectives for a robust and nuanced analysis.

Step 4: Develop and review and Analyse Themes

This step required identifying patterns among the codes to generate initial themes. The process involved developing and critically reviewing themes to ensure validity and coherence. The development of themes began with a detailed examination of the codes to identify recurring patterns. For example, codes related to the transfer of powers and lack of engagement were

grouped into subthemes such as "Devolution structure" and "Devolved engagement in the process." These subthemes formed into a broader theme: "UK Government Sets the Parameters for the Relationship." This thematic grouping provided a structured framework for understanding the overarching dynamics of the data.

The next phase involved a thorough review of the identified themes. This review aimed to uncover the underlying mechanisms and encompassed several steps. Firstly, an examination to critically analyse the data and codes to reveal how and why certain patterns emerged to understand causal mechanisms. Then, as Fryer (2022) advised, codes were combined into coherent themes. This synthesis was essential for creating themes that accurately represented the complex interactions within the data. Through this iterative process of developing and reviewing themes, the analysis ensured that the themes were valid and coherent. This provided a robust framework for understanding the intricate dynamics of devolution and intergovernmental relations in the UK.

Deeper Analysis and Causal Explanation

A deeper analysis aimed to understand the causes of different experiences identified in the data. Firstly, by exploring and determining how causal mechanisms produced observed experiences. Then, in explaining themes, the themes are analysed to reveal underlying power dynamics and institutional constraints. For example, codes related to UK legislation and perceived powerlessness among devolved administrations were synthesised to highlight institutional reproduction and the status quo. Following these steps in developing, critically reviewing, and analysing the themes ensured they accurately represented the causal explanations of the experiences and events identified in the data. This comprehensive approach provided a nuanced understanding of the UK's complex dynamics of devolution and intergovernmental relations.

Step five: Generate Conclusions and Reports

The final step involved reflecting on the overall analysis to ensure the conclusions' validity and determining the best way to communicate these findings. This critical step was essential in shaping the findings chapters of my thesis, where I synthesised the thematic analysis to present coherent and impactful conclusions.

First, I reflected on the overall analysis by reviewing the comprehensive analysis to confirm the validity and reliability of the conclusions drawn by cross-checking the findings against the original data to ensure consistency and accuracy. Next, I reviewed the validity of the findings

to ensure they accurately reflected the data and thematic analysis performed. This step was crucial in verifying that the conclusions were grounded in the evidence and supported by the identified themes and causal mechanisms. Finally, I considered the most effective ways to communicate the findings, ensuring clarity. This involved structuring the findings chapters to present the key themes and causal explanations. This process produced three chapters of the findings, each covering a specific period and influenced by process tracing.

Chapter 5, 1999 to 2016, addresses the UK's general approach to intergovernmental relations (IGR). It draws on UK government-commissioned reviews to reveal patterns of power transfer, engagement levels, and the evolving structure of devolution and changes to intergovernmental mechanisms.

Chapter 6 shifts focus to agricultural policy from 1999 to 2016, critically examining how the intergovernmental framework functions within this specific policy domain, guided by theoretical frameworks from historical institutionalism and path dependency literature.

Chapter 7 begins with the 2016 UK referendum vote to withdraw from the EU, detailing how the UK, Welsh, and Scottish governments agreed on the purpose and principles of new common frameworks for Agricultural Support (2022) and the latest intergovernmental review (2022). This chapter details the experiences of those who participated in the design process, including ministers and officials from the Scottish, Welsh and UK governments.

By systematically reflecting on the overall analysis, reviewing the validity of the conclusions, and carefully considering how to communicate the findings, I ensured that each chapter presented a clear, coherent, and evidence-based narrative. This approach effectively conveyed the complexities and nuances of the intergovernmental framework and its evolution over time. The five-step approach generated themes and causal explanations that enabled me to find relevant excerpts within the data to address the research questions comprehensively in each findings chapter.

4.7 Ethical Considerations

While this study did not involve direct interaction with human subjects, ethical considerations were still paramount. The primary concern was the approach to sourcing qualitative data from parliamentary debates, committee meetings, and letters. Guidance on the ethical treatment of transcripts primarily addresses issues of confidentiality, which was not relevant here, as all data were publicly available (Jenkins, Monaghan, & Smith, 2023). The main ethical focus was ensuring that quotes extracted from transcripts were not misrepresented or manipulated,

accurately reflecting what was said. This was crucial to avoid damaging quoted individuals' reputations and maintain the data's reliability and validity.

4.8 Conclusion

This chapter has justified this study's methodological approach and research design, which are grounded in critical realism and aim to uncover the underlying mechanisms driving observable phenomena. The comparative case study method, focusing on a new common framework for agricultural support, was chosen to explore intergovernmental relationships and institutional changes post-Brexit. The comparative analysis between Scotland and Wales was specifically selected to delve into the sub-national dimensions of governance, allowing for an examination of how different devolution settlements impact institutional and policy changes.

A comparative process tracing method informed by path dependency was used to identify and analyse causal mechanisms. This method highlighted context-specific issues through pattern recognition in process tracing (Pierson & Skocpol, 2002). The data collection strategy was detailed, emphasising the sourcing of documents from the Scottish, Welsh, and UK administrations. As Bowen (2009) argued, document analysis offers a deeper understanding of institutional mechanisms of reproduction. Given the impracticality of conducting planned elite interviews—due to prolonged Brexit negotiations, political instability, and the COVID-19 pandemic—the study leveraged the House of Lords Scrutiny Select Committee transcripts as a significant data source that provided invaluable insights.

The data analysis process employed critical realist thematic analysis to identify causal mechanisms. An example of the coding process is provided. Ethical considerations related to the research are also outlined, ensuring the integrity and credibility of the study.

The following three chapters will present the empirical evidence generated through the methods described in this chapter, aiming to answer the research questions comprehensively. These chapters will build on the methodological foundation, integrating the theoretical framework with empirical findings to provide a detailed analysis of the intergovernmental relationships and the development of the new common framework for agricultural support.

Chapter 5: 1999-2016: Intergovernmental Relations

5.1 Introduction

This chapter aims to describe, examine, and explain the empirical findings that will contribute to building the context required to address the primary research question: **To what extent does the intergovernmental relationship enable Scottish and Welsh administrations to participate in designing a new common framework for agricultural support?** The focus of this chapter is on the supplementary research questions:

What are the fundamental principles and structures underpinning the UK's intergovernmental frameworks?

To what extent have they developed since the introduction of devolution?

To what extent is the experience different for Scottish and Welsh administrations?

This chapter examines the formal structure of the intergovernmental framework and informal arrangements and how they have developed alongside the changing nature of asymmetrical devolution from 1999 to 2016.

Chapter 6 focuses on agricultural policy from 1999-2016 and critically examines how the intergovernmental framework functions in a specific policy area. This chapter engages with numerous UK government-commissioned reviews. These reviews played a significant role in appraising the devolution settlements and the IGF and, in many cases, contributed to the new Acts of Parliament that introduced further powers for Scotland and Wales. This chapter is guided by the theoretical frameworks outlined in Chapter 3, which draws from the historical institutionalism and path dependency literature.

The methodology set out in Chapter 4 describes how this comparative case study was operationalised by using case-oriented comparative process tracing to extract qualitative data. This method is a two-step process: Step one focuses on finding Political Focal Points. Step two requires the application of periodisation to the data (Bengtsson & Ruonavaara, 2017). Step one was conducted by employing the literature review in Chapter 2 to capture the political focal points between 1999-2016. Bengtsson and Ruonavaara (2017) described political focal points as periods when political events or policymaking decisions occur. These decisions may seem insubstantial at the time but may lead to future institutional changes.

Step two required the application of context and periodisation. Falletti and Lynch (2001) described periodisation as slicing a period into phases. Each phase can then be examined to discover the context of an institution: how it was formed and developed and how it has changed over time. Chapter 2 reveals examples of emerging political focal points caused by shifts in political power across the UK, changing governance structures, European Union institutions and policy influence, and increased institutional interactions across the United Kingdom. Therefore, this chapter is structured by the periodisation of the most significant focal points. The chapter begins in 1999 with the founding of newly devolved parliaments in Scotland and Wales. The chapter concludes with a referendum to withdraw from the European Union, which will be the focus of Chapter 7 and the primary research question. Furthermore, this chapter is divided into 1999-2006 and 2007-2016.

The first section, 1999-2006, will encompass the introduction of devolution in 1999 and the early intergovernmental framework. As the UK government transferred power to devolved administrations, an intergovernmental framework was introduced to guide how the devolved and UK institutions should work together. This section shows how they were designed, who played a role in the decision-making process, how they would be structured, and their anticipated functioning. Then, the conclusions of the first review of intergovernmental relationships are explored. This chapter explains how early formal and informal intergovernmental frameworks shaped the relationship between devolved administrations (DAs) and the UK government and departments in Whitehall.

The second section focuses on the period 2007–2016. During this period, there were changes in power across the UK. In Scotland, the pro-independence SNP, and in Wales, the coalition of the Labour Party and pro-independence party Plaid Cymru. This instigated many UK government-commissioned reviews of the devolution settlement and intergovernmental framework. Many recommendations for improvement have been made, which will be discussed later in this chapter. In addition, the differences in experience between the Scottish and Welsh administrations and the drivers behind these disparities are explored. These questions will delve deeper into how the intergovernmental framework facilitates a cooperative working relationship across the UK when different political parties are in power.

5.2 1999-2006: The Devolved Institutional Structure

Institutional structures play an important role in understanding the balance of power in the UK. The referendum vote in 1997 in favour of devolution ushered in new Scottish and Welsh

institutions. The Scotland Act 1998 created a reserved power model of devolution with a Scottish executive who could create primary and secondary legislation. With areas of policy such as defence, international treaties, trade deals, some welfare powers, and employment law expressly reserved for Westminster, all other competencies were devoted to Scotland (Anderson & Gallagher, 2018). The Government of Wales Act 1998 established the Welsh devolution settlement based on a conferred power model. It provided a limited list of specific policy areas devoted to the Welsh Government, with all other competencies reserved for Westminster, allowing only secondary legislative powers (Shortridge, 2010). The decentralisation of power from Westminster introduced a new dynamic to the UK constitution, forming a multi-level political system within the UK and the EU.

The path dependency literature suggests that this transfer of powers and establishment of new institutions created a significant change in the UK constitution, indicating a critical juncture leading to a new pathway for British governance (Capoccia & Kelemen, 2007; Capoccia, 2016). This perspective implies that devolution was a transformative event that triggered a sudden institutional change in the UK, setting it on a new trajectory that would constrain future decision-making. However, Coran and Thelen (2018) argue that introducing new institutions and structures does not always drive significant institutional change, especially if these new structures are layered over existing ones (Mahoney & Thelen, 2010).

This concept of layering over existing structures may explain the form of devolution in the UK. The powers held by the Secretary of State for Scotland and Wales were transferred to new parliaments. Scotland received more substantial powers, reflecting the pre-existing administrative capacity of the Scotland Office (Tierney, 2009). In Wales, limited powers were granted because most of the administrative and institutional capacity for policy delivery remained with Westminster and Whitehall. This represents a continuation of the existing institutional structure and reflects Westminster's political culture rather than the promised new politics of doing things differently, as advocated by New Labour (Mitchell, 2009).

By examining these developments through the lens of path dependency and historical institutionalism, it becomes evident that the introduction of devolution in 1999, while significant, did not wholly disrupt the existing power dynamics. Instead, it added layers to the pre-existing structures, allowing for continuity and gradual adaptation rather than radical transformation. This period, therefore, highlights the complexity of institutional change and the interplay between new and old structures in shaping the UK's political landscape.

5.2.1 The New Institutions and the Intergovernmental Framework

Before devolution, the UK government appointed a Secretary of State for Scotland or Wales to oversee policy delivery (Keating, 1976). This interaction between Whitehall's territorial and central offices did not require formalised structures to enable communication. However, the advent of devolution and new executives necessitated a framework of intergovernmental relations (IGR) to facilitate interaction between the UK government and the newly developed institutions. As the new administrations opened in Edinburgh and Cardiff on 12th May 1999, the intergovernmental framework that would direct how these new administrations would interact with the UK government was still to be finalised.

In 1999, the Secretaries of State and the Scottish and Welsh offices were under the control of the Labour Party, which was in power in Westminster and Wales and in coalition with the Liberal Democrats (LD) in Scotland. Once the Scotland Act 1998 and the Government of Wales Act 1998 were passed, the UK government, including the Secretaries of State in Scotland and Wales, designed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) and overarching concordats that would set out the principles of how the new administrations would work and interact with the UK government and Whitehall departments. Soon after the Scottish Parliament and Welsh Assembly officially opened, the existing Scottish and Welsh Secretaries of State, Donald Dewar and Alun Michael, were elected as the First Ministers of their respective parliaments (Hazell, 2000).

On 1st October 1999, the Memorandum of Understanding was sent to the Scottish Parliament and Welsh Assembly. Many concordats that set out the guidance for specific policy areas were still not completed. However, Whitehall would work with the devolved executives over the following year to design ten multilateral intergovernmental concordats and over twenty bilateral concordats. The Memorandum of Understanding established principles for the relationship between the UK government and the three administrations in Scotland, Wales, and Northern Ireland by explicitly stating the importance of effective communication and consultation, especially regarding shared competencies (Cabinet Office, 2001, p. 3).

Table 5.1 Intergovernmental Relations 1999

Core Principles	IGR Machinery
Communication	Memorandum of Understanding (MOU)
Consultation	Joint Ministerial Committees
Cooperation	The Sewel Convention
Confidentiality	

(Cabinet Office, 2013)

The MoU states that a policy that is not devolved is the responsibility of the UK government. The Secretary of State is responsible for representing the interests of the UK government in non-devolved matters, and all other UK ministers would represent the interests of the UK government. However, in certain circumstances, actions may be required for shared competencies. This action may be necessary because some public bodies or policies operate at the UK level and require cooperation and sharing of information and data. Another formal mechanism of the IGR is the legislative consent motion (LCM) or 'Sewel Convention.' The MoU outlines the LCM as a mechanism that enables the Scottish Executive to consent to the UK government's passing legislation on policy areas within Scotland's competency. There was no need for this mechanism to be used by the Welsh Assembly, as the UK government retained responsibility for the most part for primary legislation until 2006. Lord Sewel, a UK government minister after whom the motion was named, set out the policy terms in the House of Lords during the passage of the Scotland Bill 1997-98. Lord Sewel stated that the devolution settlement did not prevent Westminster from passing legislation on devolved matters.

"We envisage that there could be instances where it would be more convenient for legislation on devolved matters to be passed by the United Kingdom Parliament. However, we would expect a convention to be established that Westminster would not normally legislate with regard to devolved matters in Scotland without the consent of the Scottish Parliament" (Sewel, HoL, July 1998, p. 1).

By incorporating this clause into the Scotland Act 1998, the UK government asserted its right to vote on devolved matters and implicitly clarified the UK government's sovereign power. However, the standard convention was to ensure consent before proceeding with legislation.

"The thinking behind the Convention is that the UK Parliament, as a sovereign body, retains full legal power to legislate on devolved matters, yet the spirit of devolution

implies that political power rests with the Scottish Parliament" (Bowers, 2005, SN/PC/2084).

The legislative consent motion is based on the convention that the UK parliament will not pass legislation on devolved competence without consent. No mechanisms are available to devolved administrations to prevent legislation from being passed without their consent. An imbalance of power is ingrained in the relationship between the UK and DAs. The presence of an institution that can control inter-institutional relationships raises doubts about how a relationship can be genuinely cooperative and collaborative in both directions (Hacker & Pierson, 2010; Thelen, 2009). The MoU further sets out the importance of all four administrations cooperating and working together and outlines guidance to avoid issues arising, for example, by exchanging information and data to make timely decisions on areas that might impact other administrations. The final principle is confidentiality in sharing data and how information must be treated with discretion.

The MoU also established guidelines for formal meetings and how they should be held between senior ministers and officials. Formal interaction mechanisms would occur during the Joint Ministerial Committee (JMC). These meetings would enable the Prime Minister and First Ministers from the four administrations to meet and discuss matters that may impinge on the devolved administrations or devolved matters that impact other parts of the UK and, if necessary, resolve disagreements. The JMC Plenary was the main forum for the Prime Minister and First Ministers to meet. JMC Europe was the forum for the UK, Scottish, and Welsh ministers to meet and discuss policies relating to the EU, such as agricultural policy. These meetings would usually occur quarterly before the EU Council of Ministers. This document also directs most contacts between departments to be conducted informally on a bilateral or multilateral basis. However, the document does not specify the frequency of meetings, and there is no mechanism to ensure that the Prime Minister and the First Ministers meet regularly. This has led to criticism of the ad hoc nature of intergovernmental meetings and the lack of opportunities for ministers to discuss policies formally (McEwen, 2020).

5.2.2 The UK Government Sets the Parameters for the Relationship

On October 7, 1999, Donald Dewar, the First Minister of Scotland, and Welsh Business Secretary Andrew Davies introduced the Memorandum of Understanding and Concordats (MoU) to their respective Parliaments. Members were encouraged to endorse these documents, but there was notable resistance. Several members of each Parliament voiced concerns about how the new intergovernmental framework had been presented as a 'fait accompli,' with

members excluded from the design process. For instance, MSP Alex Neil (SNP) expressed his displeasure at the lack of information and consultation from the UK government regarding the framework's contents. He criticised the lack of parliamentary scrutiny and transparency, stating:

"My first concern is how the Scottish Executive has treated—or, to be more accurate, maltreated—the Parliament in the way in which the concordats have been drawn up. There is no doubt that the concordats have been drafted in London and in secrecy. At no time has the Parliament been given the opportunity to input its ideas on the agreements, nor have we been consulted on their content" (Neil, 1999, p.1113).

Annabel Goldie (Con) also criticised the process, highlighting the lack of opportunity for consideration and discussion:

"There is a spirit of cooperation in this chamber on this subject and a desire—at least among the parties that believe in the United Kingdom—for the concordats to work. Given that, it is ironic that an opportunity for consideration, discussion or even disclosure of some of what was proposed in the document was denied to us" (Goldie, 1999, p.1118)

Margaret Ewing (SNP) further condemned the lack of consultation, expressing her anger at the perceived imposition:

"When I first read the document, I was incandescent with rage. I went back to the dictionary: concordat is supposed to mean a pact or an agreement reached in harmony" (Ewing., 1999, p.1126)

The debates in both the Scottish Parliament and the Welsh Assembly reflected substantial disappointment over the lack of involvement in creating the intergovernmental agreements. Critics argued that the UK government had unilaterally decided the framework's parameters, reflecting the asymmetrical devolution introduced by New Labour. This approach established a power dynamic favouring the UK government (McEwen, 2020). Concerns were also raised about the scope of intergovernmental relationships. Michael German, a Welsh Liberal Democrat, proposed an amendment to establish communication procedures across all parliamentary members in the four administrations. However, this amendment failed, and the Welsh Business Secretary argued that "it would be inappropriate for the UK and Scottish Governments to make agreements with the Assembly" (Davies, 1999, p.22).

Further issues arose regarding the legal status of the formal agreements. The MoU stated:

"This is a statement of political intent and should not be interpreted as a binding agreement. It does not create legal obligations between the parties" (MoU, 2001, p.4).

Concordats were similarly described as non-legally binding working documents. First Minister Donald Dewar explained the lack of legal enforceability, emphasising their role as administrative guidelines:

"I stress again that the document should be viewed as a set of administrative ground rules. The concordats are essentially working documents which will contribute to the smooth running of relationships under devolution. Some unkind souls have called them road maps for bureaucrats." (Dewar, 1999, p.1099).

MSPs Alex Neil, Annabel Goldie, and John Swinney sought clarification on the binding nature of these documents, citing comments from UK government ministers in the House of Commons. Swinney referred to an exchange where it was suggested that the concordats "will be justiciable to an extent" and could result in legal action if not followed (Swinney, 1999, p.1102).

In response to these concerns, Dewar emphasised that the intergovernmental framework aimed to enable collaborative working relationships between the UK and devolved administrations, including on EU policy areas such as agriculture. He explained:

"The relevant concordat explains how to deal with the exchange of information, mechanisms for agreeing to a UK line, attendance at EU meetings, and less formal contact with EU institutions...The European Union concordat allows Scottish Executive ministers and officials to have complete and continuing involvement in policy formulation, negotiation, and implementation. That message is reinforced in paragraph B3.13, which makes it clear that the UK ministers 'will take into account that the devolved administrations should have a role to play in meetings of the Council of Ministers at which substantive discussion is expected of matters likely to have a significant impact on their devolved responsibilities'" (Dewar, 1999, p.1105).

In the Welsh Assembly, Davies reiterated to Parliament that the Welsh Assembly agreed that a legally binding document was unnecessary. He stated that executives in Wales and their counterparts across the UK were committed to the fundamental principles of cooperation and mutual respect of responsibilities, and resorting to legal enforcement would not reflect this. Davies also echoed Donald Dewar by stating that the concordats enabled the Welsh minister's access to European Union policy negotiations, particularly concerning changes to the Common Agricultural Policy and EU funding that affected Wales:

"We are aware of the importance of European policy for Wales. We have recently had graphic illustrations regarding the common agricultural policy, the structural funding regime and Objective 1. It is vital that our role in setting European policy is clearly and fully set out, and that is the purpose of the overarching concordat on Europe. In the past, Welsh Office Ministers rarely, if ever, played a direct part in European negotiations. The concordat changes that, providing for us to be fully involved at all stages of agreeing the UK line and in negotiating for it in Brussels. It allows Cabinet members, by agreement, to form part of the UK delegation to the Council of Ministers and to speak to the UK line. This will ensure that Wales's needs are taken into account on each occasion" (Davies, 1999, pp. 21-26).

The Welsh Assembly welcomed increasing involvement in negotiating future EU policies. However, some concerns were raised about the UK government's reluctance to increase responsibility for the Parliament. Michael German (LD) voiced concerns over Secretary of State for the Environment, Transport, and the Regions John Prescott's reluctance to transfer powers to implement directives within devolved competencies. This was linked to the Welsh Assembly's lack of primary legislative powers and mechanisms to transfer all devolved competencies from the UK government and departments. German questioned how the new intergovernmental relationship would operate differently from Scotland, which had primary legislative powers and was not reliant on Westminster passing legislation first:

"The key area of our relationship is the shaping of primary legislation, which is of primary concern to us. Unlike Scotland, which can create its bills, all our legislative powers derive from primary legislation that has either been passed in the past or will be passed in the future in Westminster. How the primary legislation is shaped and written down and how subordinate legislation will flow from that is crucially important to us" (German, 1999, p.31).

He argued that this lack of power meant that UK MPs did the "framing, shaping, and developing" of primary legislation and then implemented it by the Secretary of State when the Welsh Assembly should have done it. The only way to influence this process was through a Joint Ministerial Committee. There was no other formal mechanism to ensure that Welsh ministers would fully engage in initial decision-making or influence how the policy designed at Westminster but implemented in Wales could be shaped. German argued that "Wales needs a more powerful relationship with Westminster, Whitehall and Scotland because of our more limited powers" and that the JMC "was not what we would expect to see in an ongoing relationship on a day-by-day basis where planning could take place for the shaping of that legislation" (German, 1999, pp. 31-33). Finding a resolution to this issue instigated the appointment in 2002 of the Commission on the Powers and Electoral Arrangements of the National Assembly for Wales (Richard Commission, 2004). However, the Committee did not

complete its report until 2004, and the recommendation to separate Executive and legislative power functions did not take effect until the Government of Wales Act 2006.

Nevertheless, the devolved administrations and the UK government endorsed the Memorandum of Understanding and Overarching Concordats. They were officially published in 2001, with minimal amendments, retaining core communication, consultation, and cooperation principles. The documents also remained in a non-legally binding agreement.

5.2.3 Preliminary Scrutiny: Too Much Ambiguity and Informality

The first review of the new devolution settlement and Intergovernmental Framework (IGF) was conducted by the House of Lords Select Committee on the Constitution report *Devolution: Inter-institutional Relations in the United Kingdom* (2002). This review raised several concerns about the new intergovernmental framework. One major issue was the framework's lack of legal enforceability and formal mechanisms, leading to ambiguity and a lack of accountability and transparency. The Secretary of State for Scotland, Rt Hon. H. Liddell MP, noted the benefits of the "easy, informal relationship" (Liddell, 10 April 2002, p. 157) between officials, facilitated by their shared party membership, which helped maintain smooth communications). However, this reliance on informality was seen as problematic. The Committee acknowledged the benefits of goodwill in current intergovernmental relations but expressed concerns over the heavy dependence on it. They pointed out that such reliance might not be sustained if there were changes in the party in power in any of the administrations. The Committee observed, "We are concerned with the sheer extent of reliance on goodwill as the basis for intergovernmental relations within the United Kingdom" (HoL, 2002, p. 25).

The Committee suggested that formal mechanisms, like the Joint Ministerial Committee (JMC), should be regularly engaged. By 2002, only two plenary meetings had taken place, and three by 2007, contrasting with the quarterly JMC Europe meetings. Additionally, the lack of transparency in reporting JMC outcomes was problematic, prompting the Committee to recommend that meeting details and outcomes be documented and communicated. They advised, "Statements should be agreed by the parties and contain as much information as possible"(HoL, 2002, p. 37). They recommended that the UK Prime Minister report to the House of Commons after each annual plenary meeting.

The Committee also questioned the appropriateness of the term 'devolution' to describe the decentralisation of power in the UK, noting that it obscured the lack of uniformity in the process and failed to describe the dispersal of powers. Despite identifying these significant issues, the

UK government did not adopt the Committee's recommendations to formalise the intergovernmental framework or improve transparency. Some literature suggests this inaction was due to the same party being in power across the UK, facilitating informal cross-departmental cooperation (Peters, 2001). Critics argue that intergovernmental relations were not a priority and that the UK government's framework design reinforced a hierarchical power dynamic, even post-decentralization (Pierson, 2000). Further examining how intergovernmental relations functioned with different parties in power could provide additional insights into this issue.

5.3 2007- 2016: Political Change

The following section analyses the extent to which the fundamental principles and structures underpinning the UK's intergovernmental framework were developed between 2007 and 2016. During this period, several events changed political dynamics across the UK. These include general elections, devolved elections, and two referendums. The first event occurred in the 2007 Holyrood election, with the election of a pro-independence party in Scotland. At the same time, in the Welsh election, the Labour Party formed a coalition with the pro-independence party, Plaid Cymru. In 2010, the UK general election of the UK Conservative/Liberal Democratic coalition government resulted in different parties in power across the UK. In 2011, the SNP was elected with an overall majority in the Scottish Parliament, leading to Scotland's independence referendum in 2014. By 2015, the SNP had won 56 seats in the House of Commons, and the Conservatives were in power at Westminster, promising to hold an EU referendum in 2016.

Several UK and devolved government institutions systematically reviewed the Devolution settlement and intergovernmental framework during this period. These reviews collected extensive written and oral evidence to understand the history of the devolution settlement and intergovernmental framework before setting out the issues they uncovered and proposing recommendations to resolve them. This resulted in the UK government instigating more enhanced powers in devolved administrations. The evidence produced by these commissions will be utilised in this section to address how the principles and structures of the intergovernmental framework have developed over devolution.

5.3.1 Reinforcing Scotland's Place in the Union

In 2007, the Scottish Parliament election resulted in an SNP minority government. This shift in power from the Labour Party, which was still in power at Westminster and in Wales, triggered

a series of reviews of devolution settlements and the intergovernmental framework. The election of the first pro-independence party, the SNP, saw a rebranding from the Scottish Executive to the Scottish Government. In the hope of starting a national discussion on independence, this new Government published a paper, *Choosing Scotland's Future: A National Conversation: Independence and Responsibility in the Modern World*. In response, the three other opposition parties, Labour, Conservatives, and Liberal Democrats, collaborated to oppose any discussion of independence and sought to enhance the devolution settlement by creating a conversation about the future of Scotland. This response led to the establishment of the Calman Commission in 2008. Its purpose was to review the provisions of the Scotland Act 1998 and recommend changes to improve the Scottish Parliament's service to the people, financial accountability, and Scotland's position within the UK (Holden, 2010).

This first review of devolution in Scotland and its relationship with the Union aimed to improve it. However, the party in power in Scotland opposed the fundamental principles of this review. The SNP disagreed with the Commission's parameters, which excluded independence or federalism as options. Professor Sir Kenneth Calman wrote to the First Minister, Alex Salmond, requesting "assistance and cooperation of the Scottish Government," but the First Minister refused. The Commission's 2008 report, *The Future of Scottish Devolution within the Union: A First Report*, outlined how four key elements were to be examined for the final report in 2009, stating, "We look at the functions of the Scottish Parliament, how it is financed and is accountable to the Scottish people, and how the new Scottish political institutions relate to the rest of the UK" (Holden, 2010, p.14). The final report, *Serving Scotland Better: Scotland and the United Kingdom in the 21st Century*, published in 2009, stated that devolution was lopsided, the Scotland Act 1998 lacked fiscal power, and mutual respect between Parliament and governments was key to strengthening cooperation (Calman, 2010, p.16). The final report made 63 recommendations in four key areas: strengthening devolution, cooperation, the Scottish Parliament, and financial accountability. Responses in the Scottish Parliament debate mainly focused on resolving issues. The UK and the Scottish Government welcomed recommendations for additional powers and measures to enhance their relationship; however, there were serious concerns about the UK government's intentions. Concerns were raised that the UK government went ahead with a review without the full consent of the Scottish Parliament. Stephen noted that Labour MPs had briefed in early 2008 that the Commission was "as much about considering the return of powers to Westminster as it was about considering new powers for Scotland" (Stephen, 2009, p. 18864).

Despite concerns about the UK government's motivations, there was hope for significant change. Iain McWhirter's comments on the recommendations suggested that the report was as important as the 1988 Claim of Right and the 1997 Devolution white paper. He believed it made a strong intellectual case for fiscal autonomy and set Scotland on a new course that could lead to a federal United Kingdom within ten years (Stephen, 2009, p. 18865). The UK government formally responded in a report, *Scotland's Future in the United Kingdom Building, on ten years of Scottish devolution* (2009). This response stated that the UK government had taken the recommendations on board, and discussions on improving intergovernmental cooperation had already begun in the Joint Ministerial Committee. They highlighted how the Calman Commission commended the collaboration between institutions, noting that the Government and the Devolved Administrations "can and do work together" (Scotland Office, 2009, p.5). The response also emphasised that the UK government had shown respect for the Scottish Parliament by considering the Sewel Convention and waiting for the Scottish Executive's agreement on new powers before passing the Scotland Act 2012. "Since devolution has taken place, the UK Parliament has not legislated on devolved matters without the consent of the Scottish Parliament" (Scotland Office, 2009, p.5).

Further recommendations by the Calman review focused on strengthening the Joint Ministerial Committee to improve cooperation by expanding it to include a JMC for officials, greater transparency, and more regular contact with all four administrations. The Secretary of State for Scotland's statement on June 15, 2009, emphasised the importance of effective collaboration between the UK and Scotland's institutions to serve Scotland's people better and secure Scotland's position within the UK (Murphy, 2009). The recommendations from this review were not radical approaches to improving the IGR. Instead, they focused on adjusting existing intergovernmental machinery to increase frequency and transparency. Capano (2018) suggests that this kind of action can help 'stabilise' an institution by layering over existing structures and avoiding radical changes (Capano, 2018).

5.3.2 Welsh Reforms: Addressing Confusion and Complexity

The first review of the Welsh devolution settlement and its engagement with the intergovernmental framework was conducted by the Commission on Powers and Electoral Arrangements of the National Assembly for Wales in 2002, commonly known as the Richard Commission. By 2004, the Richard Commission recommended that the corporate body of the National Assembly be separated to perform both legislative and executive functions. It noted that intergovernmental relations between the UK government and devolved administrations

relied too much on informal relationships and lacked regular JMC meetings. An official providing evidence to the First Minister observed that the JMC lacked decision-making powers, describing it as a situation where "good chaps sit round the table and come to a decision, a consensus", but ultimately, "the power would lie where it lay" (Pomeroy, 2002). The Richard Commission highlighted the complexity of intergovernmental relations, involving numerous contacts between civil servants across Cardiff, Whitehall, Brussels, and other government offices. Due to the Assembly's structure as a corporate body, it noted that "the Wales model of executive devolution seems to be the most complex set of arrangements" (Richard Commission, 2004, p. 142).

In response, the UK Government's Better Governance for Wales White Paper (2005) proposed enhancing the devolution and legislative system in the Welsh Assembly. It agreed with the recommendation to separate legislative and executive functions for better transparency and accountability: "Often, decisions are made in the name of the Assembly which are quite properly the responsibility of one Minister or official, making it hard to know who should be accountable to the public for them" (Office for the Secretary of State for Wales, 2005, p.3). The White Paper acknowledged that the Government of Wales Act 1998 and the Assembly's structure constrained devolved legislative powers. The Assembly relied on primary legislation from Westminster, causing delays in addressing urgent legislative needs. Rhodri Glyn Thomas, speaking at the Welsh Assembly debate on the Richard Commission, pointed out that the Government of Wales Act 1998 was the result of internal Labour Party discussions, which led to frustrations due to its unclear delineation of devolved powers (Thomas, 2004, pp. 51-52). The UK Government's white paper agreed with many Richard Commission recommendations but opted for gradual reforms: "We are therefore proposing to give the Assembly, gradually over a number of years, enhanced legislative powers in defined policy areas where it already has executive functions" (Office for the Secretary of State for Wales, 2005, p.3). The Richard Commission and the UK Government's Better Governance for Wales White Paper culminated in the Government of Wales Act 2006, transforming the Assembly into a devolved legislature with the authority to pass some primary legislation and Assembly Measures. These changes aimed to clarify legislative powers, though the Assembly retained a conferred powers model, relying heavily on Whitehall for policy decisions.

Furthermore, criticism of the JMC had not been addressed. The UK government was willing to modify the power granted to the DAs but remained resistant to reforming the IGR or introducing more binding commitments to the central government. The argument that

devolution had transformed the UK into a quasi-federal state would suggest the central Government would work towards a more clearly defined IGR, especially in light of the increasing decentralisation of power (Keating, 2010). Nevertheless, the UK government appears reluctant to make significant or binding changes. The unitary state system is based on the idea that power can be delegated and reclaimed (Keating, 2022). Pierson (2015) argued that once an institution has been established and has achieved a dominant position, there is no benefit to changing direction and weakening the institution's power. The UK Government's implementation of more formal structures could limit its authority and may explain its reluctance to reform IGR machinery.

5.3.3 House of Commons Committee Reviews

Shortly after the Calman reports were published, two further reviews were conducted. The first was by the House of Commons Justice Committee in 2009, resulting in the report *Devolution: A Decade On*, and the second by the House of Commons Scottish Affairs Committee in 2010, titled *Scotland and the UK: Cooperation and Communication Between Governments*. These reviews focused on how devolution and the intergovernmental framework impacted UK interests and UK foreign policy. Both collected evidence from MPs, officials, and academics.

These reports identified several issues hindering intergovernmental relationships. The Justice Committee noted that intergovernmental arrangements "were no longer necessarily fit for purpose given the current political and economic climate within the United Kingdom" (House of Commons Justice Committee, 2009, p.32). This was partly due to the political incongruence created by the SNP in power in Scotland and the Labour Party at Westminster (McAllister, 2015). Both reviews emphasised updating the Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) and concordats. Rt Hon Paul Murphy MP highlighted the need for constant review, stating that the "machinery constantly needs looking at" because the landscape was "changing all the time" (House of Commons Justice Committee, 2009, p.32). Witnesses described the concordats as largely obsolete. Sir John Elvidge remarked:

"They worked in that almost no one refers to them as documents. They set a climate of expectation. They have worked in the sense that they have set the right expectations about the standards that the relationship should reach. They do not stop things going wrong" (House of Commons Justice Committee, 2009, p.162).

Alan Trench added that concordats were "a useful exercise between 1998 and 2000 for making Whitehall departments think about how devolution would work and what it would mean for them." However, since then, "they have largely gathered dust" (House of Commons Justice Committee, 2009, p.164).

The evidence suggested that there had been limited disputes between the UK Government and devolved administrations, described as "remarkably harmonious since 1999." Trench noted that there had been no intergovernmental litigation before the Judicial Committee of the Privy Council, no disputes referred to the Joint Ministerial Committee, and "relatively few spats" behind the scenes (House of Commons Justice Committee, 2009, p.160). However, he cautioned that this harmony might not last, as regular disagreements are typical in multi-level countries, often manifesting in political disputes, intergovernmental conferences, and litigation (House of Commons Justice Committee, 2009, p.169). Professor Charlie Jeffery explained that the UK's arrangements, inherited from the pre-devolution era and suited for coordination within a single central government, appeared unfit for purpose in the current context of governments led by different political parties (House of Commons Justice Committee, 2009, p.171). Lord Steel of Aikwood reflected on the potential for future disputes, noting, "We always said the test of devolution would come when there were political differences between the Government at Westminster and the Government in Scotland, and that, of course, has now happened" (Justice Committee, 2009, p.173).

The Justice Committee echoed the interim report of the Calman Commission, stating, "We do not think that the lack of use of formal mechanisms for discussion and dispute resolution is sustainable over the years ahead as new challenges emerge" (Calman Commission, 2008, p.34). The conclusion was that what worked pre-devolution does not necessarily work post-devolution, especially with the likelihood of political cohabitation (Jeffrey, 2009). The intergovernmental relations (IGR) framework did not reflect the complex nature of governance that had developed in the UK (Cairney, 2012).

5.3.4 More Powers to Secure the Union?

The election of the SNP pro-independence party in Scotland prompted the creation of the Calman Commission. The majority SNP government in 2011 led to an independence referendum in 2014, resulting in the "Better Together" campaign promising a new package of powers in the event of a no-vote. The Smith Commission was established to determine how to deliver these powers. It became clear that enhancing devolved powers would necessitate an assessment of the intergovernmental framework to cope with the change in power dynamics between the UK and Scottish Governments. The Commission emphasised that the issue of weak intergovernmental work needed to be addressed, stating, "Both governments must work together to create a more productive, robust, visible and transparent relationship" (Lord Smith of Kelvin, 2014, p.5). While collecting evidence, the Smith Commission assessed the

effectiveness of the intergovernmental machinery between the Scottish and UK Governments, including the Joint Ministerial Committee (JMC) structures. It recommended urgent reform and significant scaling up to reflect the agreement's scope, suggesting that the JMC be enhanced with new sub-committees covering policy areas such as home affairs, rural policy, agriculture and fisheries, and social security/welfare (Smith Commission, 2014, p.15).

To perform effectively, the Commission proposed that governments should work towards "transparent parliamentary scrutiny," including the proactive reporting of Joint Ministerial Committee conclusions and other bilateral meetings to their respective Parliaments. Additionally, it recommended the creation of effective and workable mechanisms to resolve inter-administration disputes in a timely and constructive manner (Smith Commission, 2014, pp.14-15). The review highlighted the importance of the Sewel Convention for balancing the relationship between the UK government and devolved administrations. It recommended that "the UK Parliament should strengthen the Sewel Convention by entrenching it in the standing orders of each House" to show respect for the legislative competence of the Scottish Parliament. Furthermore, it proposed legislating the Scottish Parliament and Scottish Government as permanent institutions within the UK (Smith Commission, 2015, p.21).

However, the Secretary of State for Scotland responded by asserting that "Stating that the Scottish Parliament and Government are permanent institutions in UK legislation does not necessarily make it so" due to the principle of parliamentary sovereignty, which implies that the UK Parliament cannot legally diminish its authority (SPICe, 2015, p.9). This response illustrates that, despite commissioning several reviews of devolution and the intergovernmental framework, the UK government is under no binding obligation to accept and enact the recommendations. This aligns with Pierson's (2010) argument that institutions tend to 'stick' because they create self-reinforcing dynamics that maintain the status quo.

In a debate on the proposed Scotland Act 2016 in the Scottish Parliament, John Swinney, the Deputy First Minister and Cabinet Secretary for Finance, Constitution and Economy, acknowledged the publication of the UK Government's command paper and draft bill. He noted, "The Scottish Government welcomes the publication... but the Smith proposals do not go nearly far enough. The draft clauses are an important step in providing the Parliament with further levers to improve the lives of the people of Scotland" (Swinney, 2014, p.12). The debate continued with Iain Gray reflecting on the history of the Parliament's powers, stating,

"Our Parliament was created with a high degree of legislative competence... but it was clear that we had little fiscal or financial power. The Smith Agreement and the Scotland Bill will write the next chapter in the story of devolution" (Gray, Scottish Parliament, 2016, p.6).

Fabiani expressed concerns about the UK's behaviour during the process, highlighting the Treasury's initial attempts to reduce Scotland's budget and emphasising the need for "parity of esteem and equal partnership" in future negotiations (Fabiani, 2016, p.6).

The *Scotland Act 2016* delivered more power to the Scottish Parliament based on many of the recommendations of the Smith Commission in 2014. These included new financial, tax, and social security powers requiring more collaboration with the Whitehall departments. A witness at the House of Lords Constitution Committee stated,

"The new settlement ... increases the extent to which both parliaments will be working in concurrent jurisdictions, especially in tax and welfare, necessitating cooperation, coordination and joint decision-making" (McEwen, 2015,p.5).

However, even with these enhanced powers and the need for more joint decision-making between the UK government and the DAs, no further IGR mechanisms were introduced to manage this process.

5.3.5 Enhancing Powers in Wales

The UK government established the Commission on Devolution in Wales, commonly known as the Silk Commission, to review devolved powers and recommend modifications. Chaired by Paul Silk, the Commission produced two reports. The first, *Empowerment and Responsibility: Legislative Powers to Strengthen Wales*, examined how more financial and tax powers could be devolved to Wales to serve its people better (The Commission on Devolution in Wales, 2012, p.4). An interesting aspect of this review was the recommendation of a mechanism for amending and expanding devolution on an evolving basis without needing further independent commissions (The Commission on Devolution in Wales, 2012, p.51).

The second report, *Empowerment and Responsibility: Legislative Powers to Strengthen Wales*, published in 2014, reviewed the powers of the National Assembly for Wales and recommended changes to constitutional arrangements to "serve the people of Wales better." The report indicated that the conferred model of devolution was widely criticised for being confusing and lacking clarity, thereby complicating legislative processes. The Commission preferred the reserved powers model, providing clear guidelines on what the Parliament could legislate on and establishing a more "adult footing" between Wales and the UK (The Commission on

Devolution in Wales, 2014, p.31). Carwyn Jones expressed frustration with the conferred power model, stating:

"Despite this rapid evolution, we are still constrained by a set of outdated governance arrangements that hark back to the days of executive devolution. Moving to a reserved powers model, which the Commission recommends, would not be just a technical change but would create a more coherent constitution for Wales within the UK, putting all of the devolved administrations on the same footing. It would also reduce the uncertainty and complexity" (Jones, 2014, 14.58).

The Silk Commission also considered intergovernmental mechanisms for engagement, agreeing with the MoU principles of good communication, consultation, and cooperation. However, it is recommended that mutual respect and equality of esteem be added to these principles. The review found instances where the UK government showed a lack of consideration for the Welsh Government in legislation or policy formation. It also revealed Whitehall's unfamiliarity with the MoU or the Devolution Guidance Notes (DGN), which are collaborative agreements between the DAs and the British government outlining core principles for administering the devolution agreement (Commission on Devolution in Wales, 2014).

The Silk Commission identified a lack of institutional involvement as problematic. Although the Wales Office advised UK government departments to collaborate with the Welsh Government, neither the Wales Office nor the UK government departments took action to consult with the Welsh Government on areas of inadequate engagement (The Commission on Devolution in Wales, 2014). Additional issues were found in formal procedures for resolving disputes. The Commission suggested establishing a tier between the informal resolution process and the JMC process (Commission on Devolution in Wales, 2014, p.53). The report noted:

"The evidence we have received has highlighted that, while the number of formal disputes since devolution has been small, there is a need to improve mechanisms for the resolution of disagreements between the Welsh Government and the UK Government. We have heard...that intergovernmental negotiations are often reliant on good personal relationships between officials and Ministers" (The Commission on Devolution in Wales, 2014, p.53).

The Silk Commission's recommendations contributed to the Government of Wales Act 2017, which replaced the conferred powers model with the reserved powers model, similar to that in

Scotland. However, recommendations for improving intergovernmental relationships did not emerge.

5.3.6 The Final Pre-Brexit Review

The Constitution Committee, which conducted the first review of intergovernmental relations in the UK in 2002, reconvened in 2015 and produced another review of intergovernmental relationships. The Committee reflected on how much the political landscape had changed and increased in complexity. How many changes have been made to the devolution settlement and the introduction of the Scotland Act 2012, 2016, Government of Wales Act 2014, and Wales Act 2017? This review contributed to the broader consultation process of changing the IGR to meet the increased powers in the DAs. However, these recommendations have echoed the recommendations made in other reviews. There is a need to improve formal structures through reforms to the JMC or by creating a forum like the British-Irish Council. The need for more forums for policy coordination is made possible through subcommittees. More structures manage dispute resolution either through a mechanism that provides arbitration or mediation. It is also suggested that the principles of the MoU have a statutory basis. IGR should be based on mutual respect. However, as most IGRs are conducted informally between ministers and officials, more focus should be placed on civil service and departmental interaction. This Committee concluded their report with a comment on the forthcoming need for

"An overarching vision for the future shape of the United Kingdom should be a stabilising force in its own right and would also allow for intergovernmental arrangements to be organised on a more stable basis" HoL Constitution Committee, 2015, p.211).

They also added a comment specifically about Scotland and the future of the UK. The Committee also commented on Scotland's future within the UK, highlighting the need for a comprehensive, pan-UK strategy. This strategy should reinforce the Union's central position in the UK's constitutional architecture while recognising the benefits of devolution. It should also provide a coherent basis for discussions on further devolution and enhance the constitutional stability of the United Kingdom.

5.4 Discussion of Findings on Intergovernmental Relations between the UK and the Scottish and Welsh Administrations (1999-2016)

5.4.1 Introduction

This chapter presents findings covering the period from the introduction of devolution in 1999 until 2016. It delves into key aspects highlighted in parliamentary debates, UK government-

commissioned reviews, and findings from the House of Commons and House of Lords scrutiny committees. By examining both formal structures and informal arrangements, this discussion contextualises the analysis within the theoretical frameworks of historical institutionalism and path dependency.

5.4.2 The Challenges and Dynamics of Asymmetrical Devolution in the UK: Early Institutional Design and Intergovernmental Relations (1999-2006)

Early debates in the Scottish Parliament and Welsh Assembly revealed disappointment and anger over the lack of consultation in designing the new intergovernmental framework. The assemblies were not offered a role in its design and could only agree to the final format, leading to criticism of the UK government. The initial approach did not reflect the principles of communication, consultation, cooperation, and confidentiality, which underpin the UK's intergovernmental frameworks. From the beginning, the UK government set the parameters of how the IGR would work.

Some of the academic literature has claimed that the introduction of devolution in 1999 brought significant constitutional change to the UK (Bogdanor, 2001; Hazell, 2000; Trench, 2004; Mitchell, 2009). However, Keating (2005) argues that the new devolved institutions were a transfer and extension of the pre-1999 administrations at the Scottish and Welsh Offices controlled directly by the UK government. Tierney (2009) argues that the UK government tailored devolution to fit the unique requirements of each part, transferring powers from the Secretaries of State to the new administrations, resulting in institutions layered over pre-existing structures (Streeck & Thelen, 2005). This aligns with Pierson's (2000) concept of path dependency, where the outcome of a process or the development of an institution is heavily influenced by its initial conditions or choices.

This institutional layering indicates political expedience on the part of the UK government to get devolution done and reflects a 'devolve and forget' culture within Whitehall (Greer, 2008). Academic debates have critiqued New Labour's approach for its lack of coherence and symmetry (Trench, 2004; Keating, 2005; Jeffrey, 2006). Asymmetrical devolution illustrates how the central government designed a framework that devolved some responsibilities while retaining significant power. The different levels of power granted to Scotland and Wales highlight pre-existing administrative capacities and the central government's strategic use of power distribution, further reinforcing the significance of path dependency (Pierson, 2010). Historical context and initial conditions heavily influenced the current devolution settlements, resulting in a system where past decisions shape contemporary governance structures.

Much of the government-commissioned reviews examined in this chapter focused on how the devolution settlements functioned. The House of Lords Scrutiny Committee (2002) noted that devolution masked the lack of uniformity and the 'disparate and discrete nature of what has occurred' (HoL, 2002, p. 191). Devolution was asymmetrical, with the powers initially granted to Wales being significantly limited compared to Scotland, reflecting the powers of the Secretary of State and Administration before devolution. Furthermore, the UK government set the parameters of intergovernmental relations by ensuring they were not legally bound by the intergovernmental machinery (House of Lords, 2016). This chapter highlights the significant interplay between formal structures and informal arrangements in the UK's intergovernmental framework. These principles are operationalised through formal mechanisms such as the Memorandum of Understanding (MOU), Joint Ministerial Committees (JMCs), and the Sewel Convention. Despite these formal structures, the frameworks heavily rely on informal arrangements to facilitate flexibility and responsiveness. However, the House of Lords (2016) noted that this often leads to a lack of transparency and accountability. The MOU, for example, is a 'guidance' document rather than a legally binding agreement, reflecting the UK's preference for non-statutory arrangements to retain flexibility (McEwen *et al.*, 2020). The academic literature emphasises the importance of robust frameworks for effective governance. Hooghe, Marks, and Schakel (2016) argue that effective regional authority involves self-rule and shared rule, necessitating structured mechanisms for central and sub-national governments to collaborate. Without these structures, the sub-national administrations may struggle to exercise their authority fully and influence decisions that impact their autonomy (Hooghe & Marks, 2001; Schakel, 2015). The balance between self-rule and shared rule is crucial for maintaining the integrity of devolved administrations and ensuring their active participation in the UK's broader governance framework.

5.4.3 Evolving Intergovernmental Relations and Devolution Reforms in the UK (2007-2016)

From 2007 to 2016, political changes in Scotland and Wales prompted numerous UK government commission reviews that identified the need for reforms of the intergovernmental framework. The rise of the pro-independence SNP in Scotland and the Labour-Plaid Cymru coalition in Wales highlighted dependency on intra-party interactions and the need for more robust and transparent intergovernmental mechanisms. The first House of Lords Scrutiny Committee review (2016) identified similar issues, such as the lack of formalised procedures and the dominance of informal arrangements, which hindered effective intergovernmental

relations. The experience of devolution has varied significantly between Scotland and Wales, shaped by differing political landscapes and priorities.

5.4.3.1 Strengthening Scotland's Place in the Union

Each UK government-commissioned review of the Scottish devolution settlement or intergovernmental relationship between 2007 and 2016 consistently referred to strengthening Scotland's place within the Union. This emphasis responded to the election of an SNP, pro-independence government, which created a more contentious relationship with the UK government, characterised by frequent disputes over competencies and resources. A more formalised and structured approach to intergovernmental relations was necessary to manage these tensions. The Calman Commission (2010) and statements by political figures underscored the objective of "strengthening devolution while continuing to secure the position of Scotland within the United Kingdom" (Browne, 2007, p.8). This sentiment was echoed in responses to the commission, highlighting a consistent focus on resisting demands for independence, which would be achieved by gradually increasing the responsibilities of the Scottish parliament and executive.

Incremental change has been a key feature in the evolving nature of the devolution settlements. The layering concept described by Streeck and Thelen (2005) involves adding new responsibilities and structures over existing ones, leading to gradual adaptation rather than significant transformation. This approach allows for integrating new elements while preserving the core structures and principles of the existing frameworks, thus protecting the status quo. The persistence of informal and ad hoc arrangements reflects passive stability and intended inaction (Cairney, 2011). The willingness of the UK government to increase responsibility by enhancing Scotland's devolution settlement to counteract political pressures from the SNP yet avoiding increased formalisation of the intergovernmental relationships illustrates active stability, where changes are made strategically to maintain the broader status quo (Duit, 2010; Galik & Chelbi, 2021).

5.4.3.2 Welsh Reforms: Addressing Confusion and Complexity

In contrast with Scotland, Wales experienced a more collaborative but complex interaction with the UK government. The Labour-Plaid Cymru coalition sought to address the confusion and complexity of the Welsh devolution settlement through various reforms to clarify the Welsh government's roles and responsibilities. These efforts were reflected in the incremental enhancements to the Welsh devolution settlement, although challenges remained in achieving a fully coherent and effective intergovernmental framework. The recommendations of the

Richard Commission (2004) brought incremental changes in Wales, evolving from a corporate body and conferred power model to a reserved power model, mirroring the concept of layering, where new policies and structures are added over time, leading to gradual adaptation (Streeck & Thelen, 2005). Wales's evolution from initial challenges and confusion represents the concept of conversion, where existing structures are incrementally adapted to improve functionality while maintaining overall institutional continuity (Capano, 2018). In Wales, the drive to enhance devolution and improve intergovernmental relations aimed to overcome the challenges posed by the original corporate body and conferred power model. The early Welsh Assembly's reliance on the UK government to pass primary legislation resulted in significant issues, including shaping legislation, competing with Whitehall for legislative time, and negotiating with Westminster and Whitehall officials (Trench, 2014). The transition to a reserved power model of devolution has been a gradual process in Wales.

5.4.3.3 Power Dynamics and Veto Possibilities

Understanding the power dynamics between the UK government and the devolved administrations is critical to understanding the IGR frameworks. The UK government retains significant control through non-binding agreements and informal practices, effectively acting as a veto player to resist more formalised and legally binding mechanisms (McEwen *et al.*, 2020). The House of Lords Scrutiny Committee (2016) highlighted that the non-binding nature of the Memorandum of Understanding and the ad hoc nature of most intergovernmental interactions underscore how the UK government retained significant control, ensuring it can influence or block changes that do not align with its interests maintaining the status quo.

The Joint Ministerial Committee lacked statutory conditions to ensure regular meetings, making most intergovernmental interactions ad hoc or informal (McEwen *et al.*, 2012). Additionally, while the legislative consent motion allowed the devolved administrations to agree or disagree with the UK passing legislation on devolved matters, they could not enforce their preferences (House of Lords, 2016). The informal and irregular nature of IGR underscores the asymmetrical power dynamics within the UK's IGR frameworks.

Criticisms from early parliamentary debates and UK government-commissioned reviews raise questions about the capacity for shared decision-making and self-rule (Wolff & Weller, 2007). The central government's resistance to reforming the IGR framework underscores a reluctance to grant more substantial decision-making power to the devolved administrations. The House of Lords Constitution Committee (2016) stressed that the Scottish Independence Referendum (2014) indicated how much the political landscape had changed since devolution's introduction,

necessitating IGR reforms to meet new challenges. Joint policy decisions require new formal dispute resolution structures, potentially through arbitration or mediation, and the MoU's principles should have a statutory basis. IGR should be based on mutual respect, and a new IGR framework is necessary for effective operation. The committee stated, "An overarching strategy should reinforce the central position of the Union in our country's constitutional architecture while recognising the benefits that devolution can bring" (HoL, Constitution Committee, 2015, p.212).

However, the UK government did not implement significant IGR changes before the Brexit referendum (2016). Consequently, the potential for genuinely collaborative governance remains constrained, hindering the development of a balanced and effective system of shared rule. Despite the gradual evolution of the devolution settlements in Scotland and Wales, the lack of adequate formal mechanisms and regular inter-institutional interactions impedes genuine shared decision-making (Hooghe & Marks, 2001; Schakel, 2015). The literature on regional authority emphasises the importance of structured IGR mechanisms in facilitating cooperation between different government levels. Hooghe, Marks, and Schakel (2016) argue that effective regional authority involves self-rule and shared rule, requiring robust frameworks for regional and central governments to collaborate effectively. Without these structures, regions may struggle to exercise their authority fully and influence decisions impacting their autonomy (Hooghe & Marks, 2001; Schakel, 2015). This balance is crucial for maintaining the integrity of the devolved administrations and ensuring their active participation in the UK's broader governance framework.

The persistent issues highlighted in UK government-commissioned reviews emphasise the need for a more structured approach to IGR that supports self-rule while fostering cooperative decision-making processes. Ultimately, the interplay between the devolution settlement and IGR shapes how devolved administrations can exercise political autonomy and engage in meaningful shared governance. Addressing these structural deficiencies is crucial for advancing self-determination and effective joint decision-making within the UK. Yet, between 1999 and 2016, the UK government resisted recommendations for substantial intergovernmental reform.

5.4.4 Conclusion

The development of the UK's intergovernmental frameworks from 1999 to 2016 reflects a complex interplay of formal structures and informal arrangements shaped by political changes

and the differing experiences of the Scottish and Welsh administrations. While informal practices have facilitated flexibility, they have also led to inconsistencies and power imbalances. The core principles underpinning the UK's IGR, communication, consultation, cooperation, and confidentiality, have often fallen short in practice, leading to significant challenges.

Despite multiple UK government-commissioned reviews and enhancements to the devolution settlements in Scotland and Wales, recurring issues persist due to inadequate formal mechanisms and regular inter-institutional interactions for joint decision-making (Peters, 2018). The potential for substantial conflict and the breakdown of cooperative relationships remains high, especially as more competencies are shared rather than specifically reserved or devolved. Additionally, most reviews stress the lack of appropriate forums for dispute resolution (House of Lords, 2002; House of Lords, 2016). Despite these findings, the UK government has resisted reforming the existing IGR framework or creating a new one to address the concerns raised.

Theoretical insights from historical institutionalism and path dependency highlight the power asymmetry between the UK and devolved administrations. The UK government retains significant veto powers over how the intergovernmental relationship functions and can use these powers to resist changes that would create a more balanced forum for shared decision-making and dispute resolution. As a result, the status quo is preserved, allowing the UK government to retain power despite some gradual evolution of the devolution settlements in Scotland and Wales.

The subsequent chapter will build on this analysis by examining how these intergovernmental relationships developed and implemented the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), further illustrating the dynamics of devolution and intergovernmental relations in the UK.

Chapter 6: 1999-2016: The Inception, Implementation, and Application of the Common Agricultural Policy in the UK, Scotland, and Wales

6.1 Introduction

The previous chapter analysed the intergovernmental relationship by examining the outcomes of government commission reviews. This chapter describes, examines, and discusses the empirical findings that will contribute to building the context required to address the primary research question: **To what extent does the intergovernmental relationship enable Scottish and Welsh administrations to participate in designing a new common framework for agricultural support?**

This chapter focuses on supplementary research questions.

Supplementary Questions

- To what extent has previous engagement with the UK government in developing agricultural support policy shaped the current intergovernmental relationship?
- To what extent is the experience different for Scottish and Welsh administrations?

This chapter will explore and assess how the Scottish and Welsh governments executed agricultural support policy within the EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) framework from 1999 to 2016. It examines how the intergovernmental framework enabled each devolved administration to set and achieve its agricultural support policy objectives within the UK, how they interacted with the UK government to negotiate future EU policy reforms, and how this has impacted the current intergovernmental relationship. Nevertheless, this chapter does not focus on how effectively devolved administrations can implement this policy. This chapter is divided into 1999–2006 and 2007–2016.

The first section, 1999-2006, coincides with the passing of the Scotland Act 1998 and the Government of Wales Act 1998. Before devolution, the Secretaries of State and the Scottish and Welsh offices were responsible for overseeing the administration of agricultural support policy on behalf of the UK government. The devolution settlement granted the devolved administrations responsibility for delivering this policy. Consequently, the initial section will examine how the Scottish and Welsh administrations assumed responsibility for executing the CAP and establishing an intergovernmental relationship with UK Government Ministers and

Whitehall departments of the Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (MAFF), which was replaced in 2001 by the Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (DEFRA).

Managing and supporting farmers through crises are important aspects of agricultural support. The first section of this chapter will also explore how the Scottish and Welsh administrations and the UK government oversaw several critical events in the UK farming sector. The BSE crisis began before devolution but became increasingly concerning in the early 2000s. The Foot and Mouth outbreak in 2001 devastated farming in the UK. These events required the EU and all the UK administrations to coordinate their actions. The devolved administrations in Scotland and Wales jointly managed the crisis with the UK and the EU. This chapter section describes how events unfolded and examines how the different devolution settlements impacted how each administration responded and how well the formal and informal intergovernmental relationships functioned as the UK and devolved administrations worked to resolve this crisis.

The second section focuses on the period from 2007 to 2016. In 2007, a new block of CAP reforms granted member states more flexibility to deliver financial support and policy goals. In addition, as part of the 2003 negotiations, it was agreed that a CAP health check should be conducted. This check began in 2008 and allowed each region to assess how previous funding impacted the agricultural sector and the delivery of future funding. This section explores how the Scottish and Welsh governments used new reforms to design tailored policies and achieve this within the UK.

Finally, this section covers the period preceding the 2014-2016 reforms. All parts of the UK began to put forward proposals for the future of agriculture in their areas in anticipation of a new block. Negotiations for the next block started in 2013. However, in 2013, the Conservative Government agreed to hold a referendum to decide whether the UK should withdraw from the EU. In 2016, the UK voted to leave but did not leave until 2020. This section will examine the period up to 2016, and Chapter 7 will continue to 2016-2022.

6.2 The Purpose of Agricultural Support

The European Economic Community (EEC) introduced the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) under Article 33 of the Treaty of Rome in 1962. The UK joined the EEC in January 1973 and was required to implement the CAP. The purpose of the CAP was to act as a protectionist measure in agriculture, ensure a fair standard of living for farmers, and produce affordable food for consumers (Seidel, 2019). By 2005, it had become the largest area of

spending for the EU, accounting for 45% of the total EU budget (European Parliament, 2023). The CAP objectives and budget are set in seven-year blocks and undergo renegotiation every two to three years before each new agreement. The EU has enhanced the CAP by introducing policies that strive to improve the environment, encourage sustainability, and increase rural development. However, it has maintained its core principle of providing financial support for farming through three main courses of action: various direct payments of income support; taking market measures to deal with sudden drops in demand, price drops, and oversupply; and introducing national and regional programmes to manage crises and meet the challenges faced by rural communities.

In 1999, agricultural policy was devolved to the Scottish Parliament and the Welsh Assembly. The Scotland Act 1998 granted primary legislative powers over agriculture, fisheries, animal welfare, forestry, and the environment. The Government of Wales Act 1998 transferred power over agricultural policy previously held by the Secretary of State for Wales and the Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, and Food. However, the Welsh Assembly held only secondary legislative powers. Each devolved nation oversees the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) but has varying powers in designing and delivering CAP directives and financial support.

As the UK was the member state responsible for negotiating with the EU on agricultural support policy, the devolved administrations still had to interact with their respective Secretaries of State, UK Ministers for Agriculture and the Environment, and UK government departments, such as the Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (MAFF), until it was abolished and replaced in 2001 by the Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (DEFRA). Formal meetings at the UK and EU levels were conducted as outlined in the Memorandum of Understanding and bilateral concordats between the Scottish and Welsh administrations, MAFF, and later DEFRA. The devolved administrations also negotiated with the UK government on priorities for each new negotiation period with the EU or any other immediate agricultural issues requiring UK coordination. These negotiations could take place through the JMC (EU) sub-committee, informally through DEFRA officials, or the United Kingdom Permanent Representation to the European Union officials (UKREP). The devolved administrations also had informal access to officials who dealt with EU policy, as the UK maintained a substantial permanent representation of officials in Brussels, with approximately 100 policy experts seconded by Whitehall, often on loan from DEFRA. The UKREP organised the visits of ministers and senior officials from the UK and the devolved administrations to the EU institutions, monitored the position and interests of British officials in those institutions,

and oversaw the three representative offices of the devolved executives in Scotland, Wales, and Northern Ireland.

6.2.1 Devolving the Common Agricultural Policy to Scotland

In 1999, the Scottish Executive took control of agricultural policy from the Scottish Office. This is a significant policy area for Scotland as 98% of the land mass is classed as rural, and 75% of the land is classed as 'predominantly rural' compared to 13% of the United Kingdom, placing it in the top ten of OECD countries with the highest share of rural territory (OECD, 2004, p.5). In the early 2000s, 80% of the land was farmed (6.2 million hectares). Of that area, 84% was classified as a Less Favoured Area (LFA), which is difficult to farm owing to climate and soil conditions. England has a land mass of 130,279 km² compared to Scotland's 78,352 km², but in England, only 12% of agricultural land is classified as LFA (LUPG, 2003). In 1975, the EEC introduced Directive 75/268 Less Favoured Area (LFA) to support farming in these areas (Scottish Government, 2021). It forms part of the rural development component. It is crucial for the CAP to channel financial support to regions across the EU where the natural environment makes farming difficult, particularly Scotland.

The EU gradually moved from a post-war approach of supporting agricultural production to developing increased support for rural communities, local land management, and advancing environmental protection (Jordan & Halpin, 2006). In 1999, the EU introduced its most ambitious reforms to the CAP (Office of the European Union 2001). The Agenda 2000: For a Stronger and Wider Union aimed to create a single policy framework to establish a new financial budget for 2000-2006, incorporating Regional Policy to regulate extensive and potentially costly farming sectors arising from EU expansion. It also had to meet new environmental obligations agreed in The Maastricht Treaty (1992) and comply with international obligations set out in the 1999 World Trade Negotiations.

The rural development component of the new Common Agricultural Policy necessitated a unified rural policy structure for Scotland. This led to the dissolution of numerous long-standing agricultural boards that regulated the Scottish Office's policy (Jordan & Halpin, 2006). The Scottish Executive's strategy for agriculture was to create a new department, the Scottish Executive Environment and Rural Affairs Department (SEERAD). This department amalgamated agricultural policies and rural affairs. Historical Institutionalism defines a critical juncture as a pivotal moment when a substantial transformation sets an institution on a new course (Mahoney & Thelen, 2010). Introducing an elected parliament and significant

agricultural support policy reforms eliminated many agricultural policy networks. The new Executive created new governance structures around agricultural policy and shifted policy objectives from purely agricultural to expanding and including rural affairs. These changes in 1999 substantially changed Scotland's agricultural support policy, and a new pathway was opened.

SEERAD shared a Concordat with the Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, and Food (MAFF) to establish domestic and EU policy working arrangements, agreement processes, and meeting frequencies between officials and ministers. Officials would meet monthly, and ministers would meet bi-monthly, with decisions to be agreed upon during these meetings. If an agreement could not be reached, "The Secretary of State for Scotland, whose functions include the promotion of good relations between the UK Government and SE, should be consulted in any significant case of disagreement" (MAFF, 2000, p.56). The Secretary of State becomes important in smoothing relations behind the scenes, but there is an issue if they have a poor relationship with the Scottish or Welsh Government (Trench, 2007). Theoretically, the Secretary of State should work as an honest broker between the governments. However, the Secretary of State is a member of the UK government, not an impartial intermediary. A political crisis could arise if the Secretary of State intervenes inappropriately (Wright, 2000).

In the first debate on agricultural policy in the Scottish Parliament, the primary concern was better representing Scotland's unique agricultural issues within the EU. The Scottish Parliament, the new Rural Affairs Department, and the Scottish Rural Affairs Committee would be responsible for making decisions on the Agricultural Support Policy. However, they would be limited by EU directives and regulations they had no part in designing. Minister for Rural Affairs Ross Finnie and MSP Alasdair Morgan (SNP) anticipated regular access to UK ministers and officials, as the Concordat set out, allowing Scottish ministers to present their case during negotiations in 2003 to ensure important elements of Scottish agricultural policy were considered. When the UK joined the EEC and had to comply with the CAP, some policies negatively impacted Scottish agriculture and created financial hardship because the EU did not understand the issues in Scotland. Winnie Ewing (SNP) queried why the Scottish Office and Secretary of State had not effectively advocated for Scottish agriculture before resolving these issues before devolution. Ewing also stated that several CAP issues unique to Scotland needed immediate resolution by the EU to avoid further hardship for farmers.

"I recently visited Shetland, and the head of the crofting association there expressed to me a serious view that the Shetland crofters were beginning to develop. They felt that

there was a plot to do away with Crofting and the privileges attached to it under the legislation that was introduced so long ago by the Liberals. That is a real fear. Very often, European legislation is enforced with no attempt at reasonableness" (Ewing,1999, p. 323).

Referring to an EU policy enforcing sheep farmers to provide headcounts of their flocks, MSP Ewing explained how it was unworkable in Scotland and the EU had not been made aware by the UK government representatives or Secretary of State. This law was enacted for sheep securely enclosed in a field with a fence. However, the lawmakers did not account for sheep that grazed on communal grazing areas and hillsides, a common feature of Scottish farming. Attempts to relocate them down slippery slopes for counting, a legislative requirement and frequently conducted on short notice, risked their lives as some of them might not survive the journey, "I might not have the required number of sheep left by the time I reach the base to qualify" (Ewing, 1999, p. 323). These agricultural policies imposed impossible obligations on farmers and crofters; Ewing argued that crofting and hill farming in Scotland were unique, and the EU did not make exceptions because the UK government had not advocated for them, even though the Secretary of State had the power to do so. If the EU were unaware of the situation, it could lead to further problems. "In the context of Agenda 2000 and working closely with the UK Government, the Executive's measures are the right steps to take. They will help us to meet present and future challenges to the agriculture sector in the context of rural development policy as a whole". (McDonald, Scottish Parliament 1999, p.296).

The newly devolved Executive produced its first vision for Agricultural policy in Scotland. On 26th June 2001, the Rural Development Committee produced A Forward Strategy for Scottish Agriculture. The executive brought together stakeholders from various organisations with personal stakes in agriculture, ranging from landowner organisations to enterprise companies, banks, and environmental groups. The document presented a holistic strategy, combining plans for agriculture and the environment, improving economic benefits, and food production under a package for rural development. This document revealed a new, multifunctional approach to Scotland's future agricultural policy development.

6.2.2 CAP Reforms 2003: An Opportunity for Scotland?

The EU's plans for reforming agricultural policies were even more ambitious than those in Agenda 2000. The most significant reform introduced in 2000 was 'decoupling,' which removed the direct link between subsidies and production levels; subsequent reforms allowed each member state to choose a historic, acreage-based, or hybrid model for subsidy payments

(Edwards, 2007). This change gave member states unprecedented flexibility in implementing the Single Farm Payment Scheme (SFPS) (Edwards, 2007), which replaced multiple payment systems. England opted for a 'dynamic hybrid' model with a decreasing historical component, while Wales and Scotland adopted a 'Historic' model, calculating payments based on 2000-2002 (Pack Inquiry, 2011). The UK uniquely allowed regional variations in implementing the scheme, recognising the differing needs of Scottish agriculture compared to England. This regional flexibility was essential for developing a more appropriate support framework for Scotland despite criticism of the Scottish Executive's divergence from the UK (Keating, 2010).

On November 6, 2003, the Scottish Parliament debated the CAP reforms agreed upon on June 26. There was a broad consensus that the Scottish Executive could influence the UK government to shape new CAP reforms to suit Scotland's agricultural and rural needs better. Ross Finnie, the Minister for Environment and Rural Development, highlighted the autonomy these reforms provided:

"The agreement provides, for the first time in more than a generation, genuine and real autonomy in the decisions that we can make on the main subsidy arrangements that shape Scottish agriculture. The changes have the potential to be a turning point for Scottish agriculture and for rural areas more generally" (Finnie, 2003, p.3041).

The reform simplified subsidies by introducing the Single Farm Payment Scheme, which decoupled payments from production levels. Finnie emphasised that cross-compliance provisions would improve environmental outcomes:

"The key policy in the agreement is the change to decoupling to remove subsidy payments linked to production. Significantly, the decoupled payments will depend on producers meeting cross-compliance conditions, including the need for land to adhere to good agricultural and environmental conditions" (Finnie, 2003, p.3041).

Roseanna Cunningham (SNP) expressed concerns that decoupling was supported by the UK government and the English National Farmers Union (NFU). She questioned whether Scotland could pursue a different path:

"I had presumed that the Minister was aware of comments made by both Margaret Beckett and Ben Gill of the National Farmers Union in England that retaining the link—by which I mean partial recoupling—would not necessarily be the best way forward... Indeed, I have some details about the extent to which Margaret Beckett has implied that there should be a uniform approach across the UK on the question of decoupling or partial recoupling. Will the Minister assure us that, notwithstanding the fact that the UK is the member state, Scotland will be able to take a different course, or will we be forced

willy-nilly down the road of UK uniformity regardless of what is best for Scotland?" (Cunningham, 2003, p.3048).

Finnie reassured Cunningham, asserting that the Scottish Executive would make decisions on CAP reform for Scotland:

"We fought very hard in Luxembourg to ensure that all the flexibilities in the agreement could be delivered at a regional level. As a result, I give the member an absolute assurance that, whether or not Scotland takes up some of the flexibility to address some of the problems that she has raised, decisions on how Scotland will apply CAP reform will be taken in Scotland by the Scottish Executive" (Finnie, 2003, p.3048).

In the House of Commons, Margaret Beckett confirmed this regional autonomy when questioned by Theresa May about creating a uniform system for decoupling:

"Wales and Scotland are able to adopt a different system—it is their free choice; they are responsible for agriculture under the devolution settlement—precisely because I negotiated that freedom for them. It would be ridiculous for me, having sought to obtain that freedom, to attack them for exercising it. It is for them to make the decisions that they believe to be right in their own context" (Beckett, 2004, p.41).

Despite the flexibility offered by decoupling, basing subsidies on historical payments from 2000-2002 raised concerns about increased farm income inequality, a point highlighted by Liberal Democrat MSP George Lyon. The McSharry reforms of 1992 had previously caused market distortions and supply issues, impacting Scotland's base rate calculation under Agenda 2000 (Allanson, 2004): "There is a fundamental problem with rural development regulations in that, historically, our base rate calculation under agenda 2000 was the lowest in Europe due to the failure of the Conservative Government to implement any of the accompanying measures under McSharry. The CAP deal that has been negotiated by Ross Finnie, working with his DEFRA colleagues, has delivered a good deal for Scottish farmers, consumers, the environment and Scotland" (Lyon, 2003, p.3058).

Shona Baird (Greens) MSP expressed scepticism about whether the new reforms would address agricultural inequality:

"Historically, the common agricultural policy has not been a good deal for Scotland. Currently, the 250 largest farm businesses in Scotland receive £50 million from CAP, while 8,600 small farms take their share of just £13 million. A Forward Strategy for Scottish Agriculture rightly states that agriculture should play a significant role in sustainable rural development. After all, agricultural land covers more than 70 percent of Scotland's land area, and the industry currently receives more than £600 million in subsidies from Europe" (Baird, 2003, p.3060).

George Lyon argued that CAP had protected Scottish agriculture from cost-cutting measures introduced by successive UK Treasuries: "The view of the farming industry is that the common agricultural policy has protected it from some of the more cost-cutting measures that successive UK Treasuries have introduced. There is tremendous support from agricultural producers for remaining in the CAP" (Lyon, 2003, p.3066).

Allan Wilson, the Deputy Minister for Environment and Rural Development, noted the importance of the flexibility introduced by the latest CAP reforms, allowing the Scottish Executive to tailor policies to meet Scotland's needs (Wilson, 2004, p.5853).

The Scottish Crofting Foundation (SCF) and the National Farmers Union for Scotland (NFUS) emphasised the need for targeted support in less favoured areas:

"It is likely that agriculture in hill, upland, peripheral and fragile areas will decline under a decoupled support system ... unless there is significant direction of support from other measures put in place" (Shaw, 2004, p.844).

"We definitely want to shape that debate in Scotland. Through the CAP reform agreement in Luxembourg last year, we have already got regionalisation, which allows the Executive to identify specific areas within Scotland. What is important for Scotland is what is delivered for Scottish farming, crofters and the Scottish public" (Kinnaird, 2004, p.849).

Due to Scotland's topography and climate, supporting hillside farming in less favoured areas was vital for rural affairs. The Scottish Crofting Foundation and NFUS encouraged the Scottish Executive to communicate Scotland's needs directly to the UK government and the EU. The UK Government supported the Scottish Executive's autonomy in determining agricultural support policy, with no indication of attempts to limit this autonomy or any significant disagreements. As outlined in the Concordat, consistent meetings between Scottish and UK officials and ministers ensured cooperation (Cairney, 2006). The Scottish Executive's primary focus continued to be strengthening its position in the EU for upcoming budget reforms.

6.2.3 Devolving the Common Agricultural Policy to Wales

In 1999, the Welsh Assembly assumed the powers previously held by the Welsh Office. These powers included control over agricultural policy within the directives and regulations of the EU Common Agricultural Policy. However, unlike Scotland, the National Assembly was limited to secondary legislation-making powers. Wales represents 8.35% of the UK with a land mass of 20,782 km², making it significantly smaller than Scotland and England. However, 88%

of the land is used for agriculture, and 78% is classified as Less Favoured Areas (LFA) (PUPG, 2003).

Wales did not immediately establish a coherent policy framework centring on rural affairs, unlike Scotland, where all the previous agricultural boards were replaced with a Department of Rural Affairs that presumed future agricultural policy and rural affairs should be intertwined. In Wales, the new institution was the Department of Agriculture and Rural Affairs. This distinction reflected Wales's much more powerful farming lobby groups. Hillside farming is an integral part of Wales's culture and identity, and the Unions used the strong connection between farming and a rural identity (Woods, 2005). Agriculture was the most debated topic in the first year of the Welsh Assembly (Woods, 2005).

These influential farming unions were able to dictate the new Assembly's agenda. These entrenched practices made it challenging to transition to a new institutional structure that would provide an integrated rural policy framework (Woods, 2005). This demonstrates the degree of path dependence and the expectations of the farming community on the Assembly, thus limiting the amount of divergence that would be permissible. This restricts the policies Wales can negotiate with the UK for future policy (Pierson, 2010).

As part of the Agenda 2000 CAP reform, a Proposed Area-Based Compensation Scheme for Less Favoured Areas (LFA) would introduce changes to those receiving direct payments. The proposed discretionary funding would use new payment rates based on per hectare of land under the reformed Hill Livestock Compensation Allowance (HLCA) scheme. Each member state had to submit to the EU a Rural Development Plan (RDP) to set a model for delivering payments under the new HLCA scheme. However, at that time, the UK was unique. The four administrations across the UK developed their RDPs to reflect their responsibility for delivering the policy and the different landscapes and climates that resulted in four distinctive agricultural sectors. It became apparent that the new scheme could result in different payment rates per hectare. Due to the higher levels of upland farming and Less Favoured Areas (LFA) in Scotland (84%) and Wales (78%), they shared similar concerns about this scheme.

"These payments are relevant to 80 per cent of Wales's topography and they touch upon a substantial number of farms and farmers and their livelihoods. This issue is of the greatest importance to Wales. It is not as important to England, as we are talking about 18 per cent of England's topography and 80 per cent of Wales's topography" (Thomas, 2000, p. 25).

The National Assembly for Wales Agriculture Department (NAWAD), with the help of the Scottish Executive, worked together to produce a draft proposal for a new area-based compensation scheme that would be much fairer for farmers in LFA. They submitted the Tir Mynydd scheme proposal to the European Commission in December 1999. The Tir Mynydd scheme would support sheep or suckler cow producers and be based on three elements: the first was an area-based payment dependent on herd numbers; the second was an area payment per hectare of forage land, and the third element was an environmental top-up payment for those who farmed in particularly defined and sustainable ways (Gwyther, 2000). The Welsh Assembly was only able to pass secondary legislation, and it was expected that in developing a policy strategy specifically for Wales, the Executive had to consult with UK agriculture departments to ensure that they had the powers necessary to design such a policy and to ensure that they remained within the EU regulations. However, this new scheme was used as a test to see if the EU would approve the scheme.

"The Assembly is the negotiating body for Wales. Therefore, we do not go through the UK Ministers for Tir Mynydd and other aspects of the rural development plan. We do the negotiating ourselves. The rest of the UK is waiting for us to succeed in getting this safety net imposed. It is not only important for Wales. It is also important for Scotland, as it is made up of nearly 85 per cent less favoured areas. Scotland is watching our progress with interest and trepidation, because if it does not work for us it will not work for it either" (Gwyther, 2000, p.25).

The Commission disagreed with the first element of the Assembly's proposal for an area-based payment derived from stocking levels, as this contradicted the decoupling policy instrument. However, the second component, a payment based on an area per hectare of forage land, and the third component, an environmental top-up payment for those whose farms are sustainably managed, were accepted (NA, 2000).

As the Welsh Assembly assessed the powers it held and the direction of Agricultural policy they wished to pursue, a common theme that arose in the Assembly debates and the Agriculture & Rural Development Committee was how Wales could become more involved in developing policy with the UK and be better represented at the EU level.

"We need effective Welsh representation in as many EU institutions as possible. I communicated those views on behalf of the Committee on European Affairs after a meeting earlier this year. I have spoken to Keith Byers about it and written to the big UK departments to try to ensure that the Welsh view is not forgotten when they decide upon the UK view. We realise that we have not been represented at Council of Ministers

meetings, apart from when Christine Gwyther attended on one occasion" (Michael, 2000, p.50).

It was repeatedly noted how frequently the Scottish Executive would be represented at Council of Ministers meetings and often led the UK delegation in areas such as Fishing. There were concerns that members of the Assembly would fail to develop expertise in the workings of the Council, which would impede their ability to present their policy needs successfully. This would be a hindrance when the next block of negotiations began.

6.2.4 CAP Reforms 2003: An Opportunity for Wales?

The EU CAP reforms proposed in 2003 introduced enhancements to the policy instruments, giving the Welsh Assembly more flexibility in how direct payments should be made to farmers and encouraging more integrated rural development policies. The single farm payment was introduced because decoupling the link between production and subsidy represented a significant change in the CAP support system. Payments could be based on a historic model, land acreage, or a hybrid model. The Welsh administration chose the historic model. It was thought that applying equal payments across all farmed land would redistribute funding in a way that would disadvantage smaller farms and those in LFAs.

"The historic option is the way forward for Wales. This will meet our commitment in 'Farming for the Future', is consistent with the stance that we, as part of the UK team, adopted throughout the detailed negotiations at a European level, and is supported by our farming unions. The historic model will allow farming to continue to contribute to the economic, social, environmental, and cultural cohesion of rural Wales" (Jones, 2004, p.27).

Many Assembly members were pleased with the flexibility introduced by the CAP reforms and the possibility of regions within member states having more power in decision-making.

"The 2003 CAP reform package empowers the Assembly Government to shape reform to the needs of Wales and Welsh farming. Decisions on how we implement reform in Wales will have a long-lasting effect and will dictate the face of Welsh farming over the next ten years. It is a matter of public record that decisions on the CAP reform package will be informed by extensive consultation with our external partners in Wales" (Jones, 2004, pp. 28-30).

Additionally, Welsh ministers were allowed to participate in developing the constitutional treaty of Rome with the UK and the EU. The First Minister, Rhodri Morgan, spoke in the National Assembly for Wales about the modifications made to the treaty and expressed the administration's role in the process in conjunction with Peter Hain, the Secretary of State for Wales.

"Although I do not wish to exaggerate Wales's contribution, we did make a difference. The reference to the regional tier of Government that is found in the final text is there because of the joint paper submitted by Peter Hain, on behalf of the Foreign and Commonwealth Office when he was the Minister for Europe, and a great deal of the work was done by the Assembly Government and our officials. It was a joint paper by the Scottish Executive, the Welsh Assembly Government and the Foreign and Commonwealth Office, produced in February 2003" (Morgan, 2004, p.36).

This demonstrates goodwill and good working relationships between Welsh and UK ministers, the key ethos of the IGR. Furthermore, the experience delivered a positive example to the EU of how a member state could cooperate with its devolved administrations to reach agreements and illustrates multi-level governance (Hooghe & Marks, 2003).

"It led to a considerable revision among other European countries of their attitude towards the UK and an acceptance of the new devolved format that we have. Before that, they—and perhaps many Members in the Chamber—did not think that we would ever see such an international conference as that on the constitution treaty, in which there was a paper that had been authored jointly by the Foreign and Commonwealth Office, the Welsh Assembly Government and the Scottish Executive, with the Welsh Assembly Government playing a major role. The role of the Committee of the Regions is strengthened in the new treaty" (Morgan, 2004, p.36).

The First Minister also expressed how the Assembly Government Ministers had succeeded in ensuring they were present at the European Union's Council of Ministers meetings. The First Minister also had the opportunity to represent the United Kingdom as part of the delegation in the Council of Ministers. Furthermore, he expressed to the Assembly how he

"was allowed to lead the meetings on regional policy in Halkidiki in Greece in April 2003, in the informal meeting on the role or importance of the devolved regions in Rome in October 2003, and also with Andrew Davies, the Minister for Economic Development and Transport, at the forum on 'cohésion' in May this year" (Morgan, 2004, p.37).

These early interactions with the UK government and the EU demonstrate a strong cooperative and collaborative relationship even though the four parts of the UK have different agricultural needs due to differences in geography and farming traditions. The devolved administrations were encouraged by the flexibility the CAP reforms brought in designing policies supporting farming and rural communities. When the Scottish Parliament and Welsh Assembly opened, many concerns were raised about the lack of consultation and understanding of these different needs by previous UK governments. Each administration had taken the opportunity to engage with UK and EU-level officials and participate in key meetings.

6.3 Agricultural Crisis Management Policy Across the UK

An important aspect of agricultural support is managing and providing financial assistance for crisis events. The UK experienced two significant crises: the increase in Bovine Spongiform Encephalopathy (BSE) cases and the Foot and Mouth outbreak in 2001, which demanded emergency action across all parts of the UK. These events required all four administrations to work closely with the EU to manage and resolve each crisis, providing a test of the intergovernmental relationship. These events also offer an opportunity to see how the Scottish and Welsh administrations engaged in multi-level governance with "overlapping competencies across multiple levels of government" (Piattoni, 2010, p. 21).

The EU set out guidelines on how each crisis should be managed and introduced legislation to control the movement or export of animals and animal products from the UK. Bovine Spongiform Encephalopathy (BSE), mad cow disease, is an incurable neurodegenerative disease detected in British cattle in the 1980s. By 1996, the link between BSE and Creutzfeldt-Jakob Disease (CJD), a fatal human disease, forced the EU to impose a worldwide ban on all British beef exports. This outbreak had a devastating economic impact on farmers. The Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (MAFF) and the Intervention Board were responsible for arranging the slaughter and disposal of 2.6 million animals and spent £1.5 billion supporting the beef industry (National Audit Office, 1998, p.17).

In 2001, the UK agricultural industry faced another crisis. The Foot & Mouth epidemic resulted in the destruction of over 6 million cattle and sheep, with the public sector incurring costs of around £3 billion and the private sector incurring costs of around £5 billion (National Audit Office, 2002, p.1). The UK Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (MAFF) initially handled the crisis, which was later taken over by the Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (DEFRA) in June 2001. These departments implemented plans to handle the outbreak as outlined by the European Commission.

In 1999, agricultural policy and animal health matters were devolved to the Scottish Parliament under the Scotland Act 1998. Scottish ministers took responsibility for managing the crisis and could adapt MAFF and DEFRA guidance to make it more appropriate for Scottish agriculture. Wales's National Assembly (NA) did not have the same powers as Scotland, so they could only make secondary legislation with the Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs. The National Assembly was limited to regulating meat exports and public footpath access, was initially excluded from the Downing Street task force, and was not consulted on recovery plans.

At a National Assembly for Wales debate in May 2001, the First Minister, Rhodri Morgan (LAB), questioned how well the relationship between the Assembly and UK government departments was operating during the crisis. The First Minister stated that the joint effort of the UK government agencies and Assembly officials had worked together seamlessly. It had been a valuable experience in cooperation and coordination for the different administrations.

"If you visit the operations room in Cathays Park, you will see British Government Agencies and Assembly officials working together as a team to provide the coordinated response you refer to. In one corner of the room is the army, the Ministry of Defence representing the British Government, and in another corner is the Environment Agency in England and Wales, which is devolved in Scotland. They were all working together as a team, which responded magnificently. Anyone who wanted to see an operations room at work would get a classic example of how to coordinate different agencies" (Morgan, NAW, 2001, p.12).

However, David Davis (CON) questioned if the picture of cooperation and coordination presented by the First Minister accurately portrayed the working relationship. Davis asked why there was so much inconsistency in the speed of information shared in Wales and the confusion by the Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food about the role of the National Assembly in managing the crisis (Davis, 2001, p.13). The First Minister faced further questioning on the reality of coordinating so many agencies and who held overall responsibility in Wales. Rod Richards asked if the First Minister was misleading the Assembly on the reality of different administrations trying to manage the crisis.

"I got the impression that you had all these agencies and Government departments working together like happy families, whereas the rest of us on the outside thought that Captain Chaos was in charge. Who is in charge of this so-called idyllic teamwork? Does the responsibility change according to what issue is coming up, or is one department continuously in charge? If that is not the case, when is your department ever in charge of a particular issue, and what may those issues have been over these last eight weeks?" (Richards, NAW, 2001, p.17).

The First Minister explained to the Assembly that, unlike Scotland, where animal welfare was a devolved matter, they had the authority to make decisions that the Welsh Assembly did not have the power to make. The Prime Minister was in control in Wales as it was not devolved. Carwyn Jones, the Welsh Minister for Agriculture, and Gareth Jones, a senior administrator, were responsible for the day-to-day control (Morgan, 2001, p.37).

A government review of the crisis found inconsistent levels across the administrations. The Foot and Mouth Disease 2001: Lessons to be Learned Inquiry Report found that the

management and control of the outbreak in Scotland and Wales began to raise concerns about the asymmetrical devolution settlements across the UK. The inquiry report noted that

"the outbreak was better managed in Scotland with a different management structure and closer relationships between the central Government, local Government, and the farming industry. Contingency planning had been more systematic, and the disease did not spread so far. Key problems were identified early and dealt with quickly" (House of Commons, 2002).

In contrast, in Wales, "the lack of devolved powers for animal disease control was a source of tension and confused communication, responsibility, and accountability between the National Assembly for Wales and MAFF, now DEFRA" (House of Commons, 2002).

"The National Assembly for Wales and DEFRA should develop a comprehensive agreement for coordinating the management of outbreaks of infectious animal diseases in Wales. This should cover all aspects of a disease outbreak, delegating responsibility locally, where appropriate, and providing clear lines of communication and accountability" (House of Commons, 2002, p.84).

During the crisis, Carwyn Jones, the then Minister of Rural Affairs in Wales, highlighted the tension caused by his perceived political responsibility for crisis management despite lacking constitutional authority. He noted several occasions when significant policy decisions or developments were communicated to the Welsh Assembly at the last moment, leading to delays in preparation and briefing. Jones stated, "I was seen as politically responsible for the management of the crisis in Wales even though, constitutionally, I was not" (House of Commons, 2002, pp.83-85).

Despite these issues, the review found that the National Assembly's efficient situation management altered its perception from merely a "talking shop." Other measures for disease control were implemented through assumed powers from Whitehall and carried out on behalf of MAFF. Nevertheless, the National Assembly adopted a distinct culling approach from England. It was deemed more successful, given its ability to act more swiftly due to the smaller area it had to manage. Overall, the management of the crisis across the UK tested the ability of all the administrations and their agencies to cooperate and coordinate agricultural policy under pressure. However, the outcome differed in Scotland and Wales because of the different devolution settlements. In Scotland, due to the reserved model of devolution, Scotland had a Ministry for Agriculture, and animal health was a devolved matter; the administration had a clearer understanding of its responsibilities and could make decisions in a timely and effective manner. Mahoney and Thelen (2010) argue that ambiguity in the rules and roles of an institution

can lead to its instability. The devolution model in Scotland and the mutual understanding between the UK and Scottish Executives of their respective areas of authority established a cooperative and productive working relationship.

The Welsh administration was working under a conferred powers model of devolution and had to work more closely with Whitehall departments and other agencies. The Ministry for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food operated in England and Wales and animal health was not devolved. However, the Welsh Assembly could only make secondary legislation with the Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs. The National Assembly was limited in the measures they could take without consultation with the UK government or Whitehall departments. They were also hindered by the lack of information sharing and communication on the course of action taken by the UK government and DEFRA and reliance on information being passed by officials. The limited powers in Wales led to delays in action, and the model of devolution led to confusion and ambiguity over who held decision-making power (Keating, 2010).

6.4 2007-2016

6.4.1 Introduction to the CAP Health Check

This section of the chapter will examine the period from 2007 to 2016. Up until 2007, it had become expected that negotiations for the next block of CAP reforms would begin at least two years before their introduction. A new block came into effect in 2007 and would end in 2014, so negotiations were anticipated to begin in 2012. However, the reality was much more complex. From 2008 to 2014, the CAP underwent a period of assessment and further recommendations for reform linked to CAP reforms introduced in 2000. The EU introduced these changes to reduce the CAP budget and improve rural communities and environmental outcomes. This led the EU to assess the reforms' performance and allow changes before introducing a new block. This assessment resulted in some changes to CAP delivery across the UK between 2008-2012 while negotiations for the 2014-2020 block were underway.

The debate and consultation for the Health Check occurred between November 2007 and March 2008. The main element considered by the 'health check' was to understand how the changes to funding from multiple programmes to a Single Farm Payment Scheme had performed. There was also an examination of how Cross-Compliance functioned. This required farmers to achieve good agricultural, environmental, animal, and public health standards in exchange for funding. A further aspect of the health check was the introduction of modulation.

The CAP budget was agreed to until 2013, so a redistribution mechanism was introduced to increase funding for Pillar 2, rural policy objectives. This would transfer funding from Pillar 1 to Pillar 2, and two options for achieving this were possible. Through compulsory modulation, at a flat rate of 5%, the EU redistributes 80% of the money back to the member state. Alternatively, voluntary modulation allows the member state to avoid transferring money back to the EU and could increase the amount to more than the flat rate. Only the UK and Portugal applied voluntary modulation. As a net contributor to the CAP, the UK would receive less funding through compulsory modulation. Therefore, the UK preferred voluntary modulation to ensure enough funding was available from rural development plans paid for through Pillar 2. The rates of funding from voluntary modulation across the UK in 2008 and the projected funding up to 2013 were as follows:

Table 6.1 Voluntary Modulation Contributions by %

	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012
Wales	0.0	2.5	4.2	5.8	6.5	6.5
England	12.0	13.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	14.0
Scotland	5.0	18.0	9.0	9.0	9.0	9.0

Source: Welsh Assembly Government, Scottish Government, DEFRA

The UK Government had already produced its 'Vision for the Common Agricultural Policy' (2005) before the Council meetings began for the 2007-13 budget. The document features a 'vision' of the CAP: that the EU's expenditure on agriculture is directed to the Second Pillar, Rural Development. The UK Government's assessment was provided in a House of Commons EU Scrutiny Committee report, which stated that Lord Rooker, the Minister for Sustainable Food and Farming and Animal Welfare at the Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs, said:

"The Government welcomes the Health Check and the Community budget review scheduled for 2008–09 as opportunities to pursue further reforms of the CAP and that it will respond in due course. He also says that the UK will want to ensure that the Health Check will cut further the trade-distorting nature of the CAP, reduce regulatory burdens, give farmers more significant control over their business decisions, and direct more public spending towards the delivery of targeted public benefits" (Rooker, 2007, p.117).

The Minister also stated that the UK government favoured greater decoupling of financial support for production and improved and simplified cross-compliance. It also supported increasing funds from Pillar 1 (market support) of the CAP to Pillar 2 (rural development) through modulation and wished to increase the rate to 20%. Additionally, the UK would pursue increasing rural development funding, especially as the Commission pushed for more environmental measures.

6.4.2 The Health Check in Scotland

When the SNP won the election in Scotland in 2007, Richard Lochhead was appointed the Cabinet Secretary for Rural Affairs and the Environment. Speaking at the Oxford Farming Conference in January 2009, he emphasised the difference in Scotland's attitude to agricultural policy compared to the rest of the UK. He highlighted that Scotland has 85% less favoured land compared to 20% in England, requiring a different approach as many farmers would not survive without support. Removing or reducing support would lead to farmers quitting their businesses (Lochhead, 2009).

"There is a need for continuing support, given that 85 per cent of land in Scotland has less favoured area status, whereas the opposite is the case in the rest of the UK. It is clear to me, having visited many Council of Ministers meetings in Brussels and Luxembourg, that the UK is not speaking for Scotland" (Lochhead, 2008, p. 10925).

In 2004, SEERAD introduced the Less Favoured Area Support Scheme (LFASS), which is similar to the LFA payment scheme but with an element that increases funding for areas classed as fragile. These fragile areas were based on location and grazing quality, including those on the islands or mainland in remote locations (Scottish Government, 2005). These schemes had effectively supported farming in less favoured areas, covering 85% of all farming in Scotland. In 2005, the Scottish Executive Environment and Rural Affairs Department (SEERAD) introduced the Scottish Beef Calf Scheme to support farming in less favoured areas (LFA). The funding came by deducting 10.13% from Pillar 1, Single Farm Payments.

There was unease in the Scottish Parliament regarding the EU's focus on justifying the amount of EU funding used for subsidies, fearing that the subsequent CAP reforms would significantly reduce Pillar 1 support. This concern was echoed during discussions about the modulation process, where John Scott (Con) highlighted the unique position of the UK and Portugal as the only EU countries to have adopted voluntary modulation. He stated:

" Madame Fischer Boel rightly believes that there should be a level playing field throughout Europe and intends to increase compulsory modulation from its current level of 5 per cent to 13 per cent by 2012" (Scott, 2007, p.9111).

Richard Lochhead acknowledged this potential problem for Scotland, emphasising the importance of outcome-based approaches. He agreed with the conservative amendment, stressing the need to carefully consider the changes and their impact on Scotland. (Lochhead, 2007, p.9105). During a debate on the Common Agricultural Policy, Lochhead invited Commissioner Fischer Boel to visit Scotland to engage directly with the EU and express Scotland's agricultural priorities. Lochhead stressed the importance of EU awareness of Scotland's unique farming conditions: "Scotland has almost 20 per cent of the UK's cattle herd and more than 20 per cent of the UK's sheep flock... We also have more than our fair share of challenges, with 85 per cent of the Scottish agricultural area officially being classed as less favoured areas" (Lochhead, 2008, p.9105). During a debate on the CAP Health Check, Lochhead invited Commissioner Fischer Boel to visit Scotland to engage directly with the EU and express Scotland's agricultural priorities. He highlighted Scotland's unique farming conditions: "Scotland has almost 20 per cent of the UK's cattle herd and more than 20 per cent of the UK's sheep flock... We also have more than our fair share of challenges, with 85 per cent of the Scottish agricultural area officially being classed as less favoured areas" (Lochhead, 2008, p.9105). Lochhead highlighted the Scottish Government's commitment to ongoing direct support for farming, contrasting this with the UK Government's approach:

"We want a vision that involves ongoing direct support for farming. The Scottish Government simply does not buy into the United Kingdom policy of removing direct CAP support for farming and food production in Scotland. Removing direct support would halt farming in many parts of Scotland" (Lochhead, 2009, p.14180).

There had been increasing concern that after the Health Check was conducted, the UK government would approach negotiations for the next CAP block with a plan to remove subsidies and adopt more liberal, market-driven policies. In Scotland, the situation was different. Lochhead expressed Scotland's opposition to this vision: "The vision of the Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs seems a long way from the multifunctional type of agriculture that is described in the European model for agriculture... Scotland can be proud to count itself in with the majority view rather than the minority UK view" (Lochhead, 2009, p.14180).

The Scottish Government was keen to ensure the EU maintained a multifunctional approach, as this would ensure the continuation of funding and policies that would protect less favoured and fragile areas. However, there were growing concerns that due to the need to reduce the CAP budget, the EU might be drawn to more liberalisation of agricultural policy and move entirely away from subsidies. Scottish farming has unique land, climate, and population density, including some fragile and remote areas, but they were necessary for contributing towards the UK's food security and environmental protection.

6.4.3 The CAP Health Check in Wales

In the Welsh Assembly, the Labour Party was in coalition with Plaid Cymru. Even though the UK government was in power at Westminster, the Assembly's discussion mirrored those in Scotland. In January 2008, the Welsh administration conducted its CAP 'Health Check' and launched a consultation with stakeholders. The consultation would shape the Welsh Assembly's position on future CAP negotiations. When the CAP introduced decoupling and moved from providing subsidies for production in 2003, Wales adopted the Single Payment Scheme (SPS) and accepted payments based on the historic model of payments from 2000-2002. This led to a disparity in payments across Wales, favouring areas with better land quality, climate, and size. Considering the need to assess the payment model, the Welsh Assembly moved to an area-based model with a flat rate per hectare based on land areas. However, some key stakeholders who contributed to the consultation were unhappy with this change. The National Farmers Union for Wales stated their misgivings:

"NFU Cymru sees the Health Check as an opportunity to adjust the 2003 reforms, not to make radical changes. The Union does not believe that moving to a flatter rate SFP system would benefit Wales; it would merely redistribute monies without objective benefits" (House of Commons EU Scrutiny Committee, 2008, 7.1.6).

The Welsh Health Check also developed concerns over changes to modulation and its impact on funding for Pillar 1 payments to hillside farming. The Welsh Assembly had developed Tir Mynydd, its scheme to support sheep and cattle farming. The Welsh Assembly Government's consultation document suggested that any changes to Voluntary Modulation rates to accommodate increases in Compulsory Modulation could put Wales and its Rural Development programmes at a disadvantage compared to the rest of the EU, as less money would be available for Pillar 2 activities. Unless the formula for redistributing Compulsory Modulation funds were altered, Wales would only receive 80% of the funds back from the EU and would not receive

full reimbursement for its contributions to compulsory modulation (Senedd, 2008). This implies that sustaining the expenditure level in Rural Development would be challenging:

"Members will be aware that the current schemes were drawn up over 10 years ago when people considered that the main purpose of agri-environment schemes was to improve and maintain biodiversity. Since then, new issues have arisen, and this change is reflected in the new challenges that have been brought forward by the recent health check of the common agricultural policy." (Jones, 2009, p. 64).

The Scottish and Welsh governments were concerned about how funding would be distributed in the next CAP block and its impact on hillside farming. The UK government made policy and funding decisions for England, where hillside farming was not a priority. The difference in priority meant that the UK government and the devolved administrations would begin the negotiation process with different needs.

The divergence in attitude between the UK government, the Scottish government, and the Welsh administration towards agricultural subsidies became more pronounced during the CAP health check, as each government presented their future policy proposals for agricultural support. Due to the amount of farming on LFAs compared to England, the differing farming needs in Scotland and Wales became a significant concern for Scottish and Welsh agriculture. The devolved governments had no intergovernmental mechanism to oblige the UK government to consider their needs. As an EU member state, the UK had full authority to determine its policy objectives for agricultural policy negotiations. The asymmetrical nature of devolution means that Westminster remains sovereign and has no constitutional limitations (Keating, 2010).

6.4.4 The Negotiations for 2014-2022

The negotiations for the 2014-2020 CAP reforms began in July 2010, with legislative proposals published in 2011 and the budget agreed in 2013. The EU Council of Ministers, European Parliament, and Commission finalised the CAP reforms in December 2013. These reforms addressed economic, environmental, and territorial challenges while ensuring viable food production, sustainable resource management, and balanced territorial development.

The Commission set out the purpose of the reforms, the challenges facing the EU, and the changes required to meet these challenges. In previous discussions about reform, there was concern that some elements of the CAP would be abolished or reduced due to the size of the EU budget allocated to the CAP and whether this was a justifiable expense. The Commission recommended that future policy be based on sound economic and sustainable policies to ensure

the CAP's long-term future. After extensive discussion with the public and the European Parliament, a strategy was devised to reflect the main concerns for future policy. It was strongly recommended that the two pillars be retained. Agricultural policy should support improved food security, and farmers should be supported to provide quality, value, and a diversity of food. Support for rural communities was also emphasised, as was creating local employment, aligning with market-oriented agricultural policy, and promoting greener policies to address environmental and climate change concerns (European Commission, 2010).

The European Commission described the new CAP as building on past reforms to meet new challenges and objectives. The new challenges were economic, environmental, and territorial. The policy objectives included viable food production, sustainable management of natural resources and climate action, and balanced territorial development (European Commission, 2013). The new reforms included a new Basic Payment Scheme with 70% of funding going to direct payments for farmers and 30% allocated to 'greening payments' for environmental improvement.

The UK traditionally receives a low proportion of CAP funds, divided among the four UK countries. The allocation is based on objective criteria and past performance, potentially altering how payments are distributed within the UK (Gething, 2011, p.5). Kaley Hart from the Institute for European Environmental Policy highlighted concerns about funding for Less Favoured Areas (LFA) under the new CAP, noting that the move to 'Specific Natural Constraints' could mean future funding would be applied regionally and possibly even more locally, though this needs clarification (Hart, 2011, p.8).

The impact of 'greening' under Pillar 1 raised concerns, especially regarding the Glastir policy in Wales, an agri-environmental scheme introduced in 2012. Hart noted that if the proposals remain, the basic elements of Glastir would need to be part of the greening elements of Pillar 1, impacting payments and other aspects (Hart, 2011, p.14).

Welsh Deputy Minister Alun Davies attended a meeting in London in 2011 with DEFRA and ministers from devolved administrations to discuss their positions on CAP reform. Davies noted a general agreement among the UK administrations:

"There is a fair degree of commonality across the four administrations, though some disagreements exist. We believe there is potential to do far more, and we are working together" (Davies, 2011, p.21).

Davies emphasised the importance of Wales's participation in EU meetings, which had increased significantly under his tenure:

"By Christmas, I will have attended more Council of Ministers meetings than my predecessor did in four years. This ensures that Wales's voice is heard as part of the UK delegation" (Davies, 2011, p.6).

In the Scottish Parliament discussions about the UK's position on CAP reforms refer to the Environment Secretary Owen Paterson's comments at the Oxford Farming Conference suggested ending Pillar 1 support, favouring market-driven food production, which could have devastating consequences for Scottish agriculture (Graeme, 2013, p.16138). During a debate on crofting, further concerns were voiced about DEFRA's market approach, which was seen as potentially disastrous for Scottish agriculture, especially for crofting areas. Minister for Environment and Climate Change Paul Wheelhouse added that the sustainability of crofting is at risk due to the UK Government's position on CAP reform, noting that crofters depend on €11.6 million of single farm payments annually, and expressing disappointment that the UK Government did not argue for additional Pillar 2 funding (Wheelhouse, 2013, p.17635).

These negotiations highlighted the differing priorities between the UK government and devolved administrations, emphasising the need for tailored agricultural policies that address regional needs and challenges. The UK government did not strongly advocate for Scottish farming needs during the 2014-2020 CAP reform negotiations. As the UK government is not bound by agreements reached during UK-based negotiations, the devolved governments could not hold it to account. Both the Labour and Conservative parties had long opposed the size of the CAP budget (Gravey, 2022). Since 2005, the UK government has moved towards a more liberal position on the CAP, emphasising that farmers should be:

"rewarded by the market for their outputs, not least safe and good quality food, and by the taxpayer only for producing societal benefits that the market cannot deliver," aiming to reduce EU agricultural spending (Gravey, 2022: Defra and HM Treasury, 2005, p. 4).

Richard Lochhead, Cabinet Secretary for Rural Affairs and the Environment, attended multiple meetings at UK and EU levels to express Scottish farming needs. He stated, "I have stressed how important it is that Scotland gets a fairer share of the UK's CAP budget. There is yet no sign of the UK Government being sympathetic to Scotland's needs" (Lochhead, 2013, p.17662). Tavish Scott (LD) agreed that CAP reform should address Scottish agriculture's needs, acknowledging the UK's broader market context. "In effect, there are four CAPs across the UK," he said, emphasising the need for compromise and consensus-building (Scott, 2013,

p.17694). He urged the Scottish Government to use its "enormous discretionary powers" to plan for the future of farming (Scott, 2013, p.17693). These discretionary powers refer to 'soft power diplomacy,' often used by smaller states or sub-national administrations lacking constitutional power. They build support through policy communities or cross-party alliances to increase veto possibilities, though this does not guarantee they will achieve their goals (McEwen, 2020; Tsebelis, 2002).

The CAP reforms for 2014-2020, agreed upon in December 2013, included greening measures, equal support distribution, and better-targeted income support for those most in need. The funding structure remained, with Pillar 1 delivering income support and market management measures and Pillar 2 providing funding for rural development (European Council, 2013). The greening reform introduced payments to farmers who practised 'environmentally sound farming' (European Council, 2013). This could be achieved through changes to a range of policy instruments within both Pillars of the CAP. The new agreement linked greening requirements to receiving Pillar 1 funding and introduced higher environmental standards for agri-environmental schemes to receive Pillar 2 funding. Under the new deal, 30% of direct payments from each country's CAP allocation (known as the national envelope) would be linked to three "environmentally-friendly" farming practices: Crop diversification, Maintaining permanent grassland, and Maintaining an "ecological focus area" (Matthews, 2013, p.4).

The funding allocated to the UK between 2014 and 2022 is shown in the table below. A reduction in payments received from 2007 to 2013 allocated €26.4 billion for Pillar 1. However, Pillar 2 funding increased from the €1.9 billion allocated in 2001 to 2013.

Table 6.2 UK CAP Allocation 2014-2020

	Pillar 1 / € million % share		Pillar 2 / € million % share	
England	16,421	65.5	1,520	58.9
Scotland	4,096	16.3	478	18.5
Wales	2,245	8.96	355	13.7
Northern Ireland	2,299	9.2	227	8.8
Total UK allocation	25.1 billion		2.6 billion	

Source: (DEFRA, 2013), House of Commons Library (2014)

The response to the CAP reforms across the UK was mixed. Owen Paterson, the UK Government Secretary of State for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs, who directly participated in the negotiations, expressed a lukewarm acceptance:

"Overall it is an acceptable outcome for the UK, even though it is not the genuine reform we had hoped for. We have fought to secure a CAP package that is much better than is much better than the original proposals. It is thanks to the UK working with its allies that we have stopped a whole raft of regressive proposals being adopted that would harm UK farmers" (Paterson, 2013).

The UK Government had strongly advocated for flexibility in implementing greening requirements, recognising the diverse farming practices and environmental challenges across the EU and the UK. Paterson emphasised this point, stating, "I am determined that we use the freedom we secured to design our greening implementation system to make sure that it is as simple as possible" (Paterson, 2013).

The Scottish Government summarised the agreement as one that "rewards activity, supports production, and encourages greener choices" and that "should see new entrants benefit while slipper farmers lose out" (European Commission, 2013). The Scottish Government campaigned to remove what was referred to as slipper farmers, usually landowners of large areas or sporting estates. The Scottish Government wanted much more stringent checks placed on land and estate owners to prove they actively participated in farming. However, the UK government lobbied against a more complex system requiring farmers to prove their 'active' status. Defra Minister Owen Paterson has said that the UK successfully lobbied to "reduce dramatically" the complexity of the original "horrendously complicated" proposals, which would have required detailed information on each farm's income to prove that agriculture was the main source of profit. The UK Government feels that the short list of business types that will now be submitted to this test is far more proportionate (Paterson, 2013, p.49). Nevertheless, reflecting on the change to funding from Pillar 1, the overall assessment of the Scottish Government's reaction to the agreed reforms was one of concern.

In Wales, Minister Alun Davies stated that he was 'deeply unhappy' that the overall CAP budget had been cut. However, he welcomed the agreement on key issues such as area-based payments, greening, and the ability of devolved administrations to develop and operate their schemes (Davies, 2013). The response from Welsh farming unions was also negative regarding how the UK government had conducted their negotiations and what they had agreed. The Farmers Union of Wales were disappointed and accused the UK government of giving away more of its

Pillar 2 allocation than any other Member State, despite the UK being entitled to a significant increase in its allocation. Like the NFU, they were concerned about the UK implementation flexibility within the deal (FUW 2013).

The National Farmers Union for Scotland President Nigel Miller was more pragmatic about the reforms and how the UK and Scottish Governments had performed during the negotiations. He said:

"This was always going to be a tough package for Scottish agriculture. Without pushing rules to the limit, the thin budget would leave real gaps when compared to the existing support system" (Miller, 2013).

He also stated:

"Credit is due to the Scottish Government for securing additional tools and devices from Europe to try and make our budget achieve as much as possible. Working with the Commission and the UK Government, it won flexibilities that go beyond the base CAP agreement, and Richard Lochhead has taken these up to the benefit of Scottish agriculture" (Miller, 2013).

This block of reforms had only been in place for two years when the UK voted to withdraw from the European Union. The UK would no longer be obligated to follow the CAP and must devise its policy and agricultural support framework. The UK government's attitude to the latest CAP reforms indicated their wish to move away from subsidies and towards a liberalising agenda. The devolved administrations still support subsidies, adding tensions.

6.5 Discussion of Findings on The Inception, Implementation, and Application of the Common Agricultural Policy in the UK, Scotland, and Wales (1999-2016)

6.5.1 Introduction

This chapter examined the period from 1999 to 2016, focusing on how the devolved administrations could design and deliver their agricultural support policy and objectives, manage policy crises, and interact with the UK government to influence the negotiation of future EU policy reforms. This analysis investigates how the intergovernmental relationships functioned to enable each devolved administration. These dynamics are explored through historical institutionalism and path dependency theoretical frameworks, considering the asymmetrical nature of devolution, decentralisation of power, autonomy, and shared rule.

6.5.2 The Impact of Asymmetrical Devolution on Agricultural Policy and Intergovernmental Relations in the UK (1999-2006)

The first part of this chapter focused on the early years of devolution, from 1999 to 2006. During this period, the devolved administrations in Scotland and Wales took over the responsibility for executing the CAP from the Secretaries of State and their respective offices. Establishing an intergovernmental relationship with UK Government Ministers and Whitehall departments, particularly the Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (MAFF) and later the Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (DEFRA), was a primary focus.

The implementation of CAP in Scotland and Wales highlighted the importance of intergovernmental relations, characterised by communication, consultation, cooperation, and confidentiality. These principles were embodied in formal mechanisms such as the Memorandum of Understanding (MOU), Joint Ministerial Committees, and the Sewel Convention. The asymmetrical nature of devolution is evident in the different powers and legislative capabilities granted by the Scotland Act 1998 and the Government of Wales Act 1998. Scotland, with primary legislative powers over agriculture, fisheries, animal welfare, forestry, and the environment, had greater autonomy than Wales, which initially had secondary legislative powers.

This disparity is highlighted in the findings, where the influence of Welsh ministers and officials and their ability to respond to crises and implement CAP effectively is discussed. UK government-commissioned inquiries found that during the Foot and Mouth outbreak, Scotland's devolved powers allowed for more tailored and effective crisis management than Wales, which relied more heavily on UK government directives. The Foot and Mouth Disease 2001: Lessons to be Learned Inquiry Report raised concerns about the asymmetrical devolution settlements across the UK, noting that in Wales, the lack of devolved powers for animal disease control led to confusion over communication, responsibility, and accountability between the National Assembly for Wales and MAFF, now DEFRA (House of Commons, 2002). In contrast, Scotland's clear delineation of responsibilities and mutual respect between the UK and Scottish administration established a cooperative and productive working relationship. This clarity and respect contrast sharply with the ambiguity in Wales, illustrating Mahoney and Thelen's (2010) argument that ambiguity in institutional rules can make institutions vulnerable to change and impact how institutions function effectively (Mahoney & Thelen, 2010).

6.5.2.1 Power Dynamics and Policy Implementation in Asymmetrical Devolution

Historical institutionalism and path dependency provide a framework for understanding how initial conditions and institutional choices influence policy trajectories. The devolution settlements created distinct institutional paths for Scotland and Wales, leading to different policy outcomes and intergovernmental dynamics (Pierson, 2015). The findings in this chapter indicate that Scotland's ability to implement tailored agricultural policies and engage directly with the EU reflects its higher degree of institutional autonomy and power distribution. Political autonomy, the degree of self-governance or independence a political entity enjoys, varies within different political frameworks, from full sovereignty to partial autonomy (Hooghe & Marks, 2016; McEwen & Schakel, 2016). In delivering the CAP, the Scottish government demonstrated significant autonomy in designing and delivering bespoke agricultural support policies and distributing Pillar funding from the EU.

The historical institutionalism literature stresses that institutions remain stable through modes of stability such as active and passive stability, intended inaction, or failed action, illustrating how they maintain stability or pursue change. Scotland's proactive approach in CAP negotiations and policy implementation reflects active stability. At the same time, Wales's reliance on UK government instructions during crises indicates failed action, where ambiguity in policy or institutional control leads to inaction or ineffective responses. This situation arises when those who wish to take control lack the necessary powers, leading to dependence on those who hold established control (Capoccia, 2016). Such struggles over control typically occur in institutions with power asymmetries (Capoccia, 2016; Galik & Chelbi, 2021). In the case of Wales, the lack of devolved powers meant that Welsh officials must often rely on directives from the UK government, leading to less effective crisis management and policy implementation. This dynamic highlights how institutions with greater power can dominate policy and decision-making processes, often against the desires of less empowered entities, thereby perpetuating existing power imbalances.

The differing devolution settlements, particularly in Wales, highlight asymmetrical power dynamics. This asymmetry aligns with the concept of veto players, where certain actors, such as the UK government and Whitehall departments, significantly influence the decision-making. The necessity for the Scottish and Welsh governments to negotiate with the UK government and use UK officials to access EU representatives underscores the complexity of power distribution and the need for cooperation among veto players. These interactions illustrate how power dynamics shape policy implementation and devolved administrations (Tsebelis, 2002).

However, describing power dynamics in terms of veto possibilities may be more appropriate within a devolved polity. This concept suggests that while some individual actors may have significant power, others with strong veto possibilities may have considerable powers to resist change, albeit potentially only within specific departments of institutions (Mahoney & Thelen, 2010). The methods pursued by those wishing to push for change depend on the strength of veto possibilities and the discretion they hold to reinterpret or avoid enforcing rules. The Scottish administration's strong veto possibilities and high discretion allowed for layering and drift, enabling them to have the power to change existing policies (Capano, 2018). Capano argues that layering can 'lock in' or 'stabilise' an institution, drive institutional stickiness, or counteract forces pushing for change. This means that the Scottish administration, with its greater legislative powers and autonomy, could adjust its agricultural policies to better align with its priorities and respond to any emerging crisis.

In contrast, with weaker veto possibilities and lower discretion, the Welsh Administration was more vulnerable to policy changes through displacement and conversion. Conversion occurs when new rules are applied to an existing institution to alter its goals, often to maintain the status quo by making minor adaptations to avoid costly changes or unpredictable outcomes (Koreh et al., 2019). Drift refers to the deliberate decision to freeze an institution or policy, leading to its eventual irrelevance (Streeck & Thelen, 2005). Due to its more limited powers, Wales had less flexibility in shaping agricultural policies independently and had to follow instructions from the UK government more closely.

This difference in veto possibilities and discretion directly impacts the control over agricultural policy under devolution. Scotland's greater legislative autonomy allowed it to tailor the common Agricultural Policy (CAP) to its specific needs, reflecting its unique agricultural landscape. In contrast, Wales faced challenges due to its weaker veto possibilities and reliance on UK government decisions, particularly during crises such as the Foot and Mouth outbreak. This difference underscores the asymmetrical power dynamics in the devolution settlements, highlighting how greater autonomy in Scotland led to more effective and context-specific policy evolution. Wales's weaker position resulted in more abrupt and less tailored policy changes, reflecting the broader power imbalances.

6.5.3 Incremental Change and Adaptation in Agricultural Policy (2007-2016)

The second part of this chapter focused on 2007 to 2016. The CAP Reforms 2007 and the CAP Health Check 2008 granted member states increasing flexibility and allowed regions to assess

the impact of previous funding and plan future allocations. During this time, Scotland and Wales designed tailored agricultural support policies and negotiated these within the UK context. Debates on future funding subsidies, particularly for hillside farming, in Scotland and Wales, in contrast with the UK government's move towards liberalisation, illustrate the growing differences between their policy objectives.

In delivering agricultural policy, the Scottish and Welsh administrations developed an expectation of having 'parity of esteem.' While the UK government was the EU member state and responsible for negotiations, the devolved administrations developed an expectation of influence in discussions and access to UK and EU officials. Scotland and Wales's ability to use UK government officials to access EU representatives demonstrates how actors exploit ambiguities to achieve policy goals, aligning with theoretical discussions on institutional vulnerability.

Mahoney and Thelen (2010) argue that ambiguity in institutional rules can lead to vulnerability, allowing incremental changes. As power coalitions shift, certain actors can exploit these vulnerabilities. This idea links to the duality of self-rule and shared rule, which are central to regional governance. Self-rule allows subnational entities to govern independently, while shared rule requires cooperation with higher levels of government (Hooghe & Marks, 2001). Balancing these aspects is crucial for effective governance. The findings of this chapter illustrate the complex relationship between self-rule and shared rule in the UK's CAP implementation from 1999 to 2016. The distinct challenges faced by Scotland and Wales and the UK government's agricultural support to England resulted in 'four CAPs' within one EU member state. These challenges underscore the need for appropriate forums for discussion, decision-making, and dispute resolution.

The findings highlight that while there is strong self-rule in agricultural policy, shared rule in the UK is generally weak. Scotland and Wales engaged directly with UK and EU officials and made policy decisions to tailor their agricultural support policies to regional needs. Scotland, with primary legislative powers and control over animal welfare from the outset of devolution, exemplified a higher level of self-rule. In contrast, Wales initially relied more on UK government directives and had to negotiate with Whitehall departments, gaining primary legislative powers only in 2012 (McEwen & Schakel, 2016).

These dynamics reflect the political, constitutional, and institutional factors that shape regional governance (Hooghe & Marks, 2016). The need for effective forums for discussion, decision-

making, and dispute resolution becomes evident when considering the power asymmetries among the UK's devolved administrations. Regions with higher levels of self-rule and shared rule are better equipped to manage policy implementation and crises, exemplified by Scotland's efficient handling of the Foot and Mouth Disease outbreak compared to Wales's challenges due to its limited initial powers.

The degree of self-rule significantly impacts Scotland and Wales's ability to deliver agricultural policy and respond to crises. However, the challenges of shared rule, necessitating cooperation and coordination with the UK government, highlight the need for robust intergovernmental mechanisms. These insights underscore the importance of establishing effective forums for discussion, decision-making, and dispute resolution that accommodate different regions' diverse needs and capacities within a multi-level governance system.

6.5.4 Conclusion

This chapter's findings highlight the significant impact of asymmetrical devolution on agricultural policy implementation and intergovernmental relations in the UK. The differing levels of autonomy and legislative powers between Scotland and Wales resulted in distinct approaches to CAP negotiations, crisis management, and policy implementation. Historical institutionalism and path dependency frameworks provide valuable insights into how initial conditions and institutional choices shape policy trajectories and intergovernmental dynamics.

As the UK prepared to leave the EU, the expectation of 'parity of esteem' underscores the importance of mutual respect in intergovernmental relations. However, this expectation might become problematic due to the absence of enforcement mechanisms. The lack of a formal framework to ensure this parity could lead to tensions and challenges in future intergovernmental relations.

The continued evolution of these relationships will be critical in addressing future challenges and ensuring effective governance within the UK's devolved framework. In the concluding discussion, these findings will be linked to the broader academic literature on the asymmetrical nature of devolution, decentralisation of power, autonomy, and shared rule, as well as the theoretical frameworks of historical institutionalism and path dependency. This will provide a comprehensive understanding of the interplay between institutional structures, policy outcomes, and intergovernmental relations in the UK's agricultural policy context.

Chapter 7 will focus on how formal and informal intergovernmental relations enabled the Scottish and Welsh governments to participate in designing a new common framework for agricultural policy.

Chapter 7: 2016-2022: Examining Intergovernmental Relations through the Designing of a New Common Framework for Agricultural Support

7.1 Introduction

This chapter describes, examines, and explains the empirical findings to address the primary research question: *To what extent does the intergovernmental relationship enable Scottish and Welsh administrations to participate in designing a new common framework for agricultural support?* In doing so, this chapter will begin in 2016, when the UK voted to withdraw from the European Union (EU) and finish in 2022, when the Provisional Common Framework for Agricultural Support was published.

The preceding chapters established the intergovernmental relationship between the UK government and the devolved administrations (DAs) in Scotland and Wales from 1999 to 2016. They explored both formal mechanisms and informal relations, concluding that the different models of devolution—with reserved powers in Scotland and conferred powers in Wales—contributed to the asymmetries of power between the UK government and the Scottish and Welsh administrations. The evolving nature of devolution saw enhanced powers granted to the Scottish and Welsh administrations. However, the intergovernmental framework was criticised for its ad hoc formal interactions and lack of a forum for decision-making and dispute resolution (Moore, 2016). There was also an over-reliance on informal relationships, impacting transparency and depending heavily on good personal relationships (Cairney, 2012). The intergovernmental framework saw little change despite the increasing need for joint policy work and decentralising more power to the devolved administrations.

The previous chapter specifically examined agricultural support, an area of devolved responsibility, and the relationship between the UK government and the devolved administrations in implementing the Common Agricultural Policy. It concluded that, since 1999, Scotland and Wales had pursued different agricultural support frameworks than England, primarily due to their unique topographies and reliance on direct subsidy support. The EU's recognition of nine different bio-regions facilitated policy divergence across the UK. These chapters collectively provide a historical context for developing the intergovernmental relationship since 1999.

This chapter begins in 2016, following the UK referendum vote to withdraw from the EU, which necessitated the UK government replacing EU policy frameworks. It was agreed that the

UK government would 'cooperate and collaborate' with the DAs to design the replacement framework (Cabinet Office, 2017). In 2017, at a Joint Ministerial Committee Meeting for European Negotiations (JMC EN), the UK government and the devolved administrations of Scotland and Wales agreed on the purpose and principles of these new common frameworks (NCF).

The introductory chapter of this thesis outlined the political tensions that overshadowed the intergovernmental relationship during the development of the new common frameworks. These factors included the possibility of a no-deal Brexit, three Prime Ministers, outcomes of several Supreme Court cases, and the Covid-19 pandemic. Tensions were further exacerbated by legislation such as The European Union (Withdrawal) Act 2018, the Agricultural Act 2020, the UK Internal Market Act 2020, and the Subsidy Control Act 2022. This chapter examines how the new common framework for agricultural support was designed and assesses how well the intergovernmental framework facilitated the participation of the devolved administrations.

The first section of this chapter outlines how the UK, Welsh, and Scottish governments agreed on the common framework's purpose and underlying principles. During the NCF design, a concurrent review of the intergovernmental relationship was conducted, introducing significant reforms and new dispute management structures within the common framework.

The following section examines the Common Framework for Agricultural Support published in 2022 and assesses the experiences of cooperation and collaboration among the Scottish and Welsh governments and the UK government. Evidence is drawn from transcripts of Cabinet Secretaries responsible for agricultural support in Scotland, Wales, and England, as well as from Committees overseeing the framework in Scotland and Wales. Additionally, transcripts of oral evidence from the House of Lords Common Frameworks Scrutiny Committee (HoL CFSC) are analysed, which conducted twenty-two interviews with Ministers, Senior Officials, Academics, and stakeholders over two years. The chapter concludes with a reflection on the findings from the House of Lords Common Frameworks Scrutiny Committee, which conducted extensive scrutiny and published two reports on the process.

7.2 Tracing the Process for Agreement on Principles for a New Common Framework for Agricultural Support

In February 2017, the UK government published a white paper, "The United Kingdom's Exit in a New Partnership with the European Union." This document set out how the UK would establish a new relationship with the EU and strengthen the UK union. It stated that the UK

government was committed to working with the devolved administrations (DAs), and at a plenary Joint Ministerial Committee (JMC) in 2016, all four members agreed that a new sub-committee, the Joint Ministerial Committee on European Negotiations (JMC EN), would be established "so ministers from each of the devolved administrations can contribute to the process of planning for our departure from the EU" (UK Government, 2017, p.3).

The JMC (EN) commenced in November 2016 to discuss how the UK government and DAs would replace EU policy frameworks. An agreement was reached in October 2017, and the JMC (EN) communiqué established how EU frameworks could be replaced with new common frameworks (NCF). The communiqué outlines the NCF as an agreement between the UK government and the DAs and how they will work together to establish common approaches in areas previously regulated by the EU but within the competence of the DAs. The new common frameworks in the communiqué include the definition of NCF and its underlying principles. The NCF is described as a necessary framework that will protect the UK internal market but still allow some degree of divergence, enable the UK to enter trade deals without impediment, ensure that international obligations are met, and protect the security of the UK (Cabinet Office, 2017). In addition, the framework established a common UK approach and how it should be regulated.

“Frameworks may be implemented by legislation, by executive action, by memorandums of understanding, or by other means depending on the context in which the framework is intended to operate” (Cabinet Office, 2017, p.2).

The communiqué also set out agreed principles that claim to respect the devolution settlement and abide by four key values: stick to current conventions and accept legislative consent motions, ensure policy divergence is possible, increase decision-making powers, adhere to the Belfast Agreement, and respect the EU land border between Northern Ireland and Ireland. This study excludes Northern Ireland, so it will only discuss the three principles that affect the Scottish and Welsh governments. Table 7.1 outlines the purpose and principles agreed upon as fundamental to common frameworks.

Table 7.1 The NCF Principles Agreed at JMC (EN) October 2017

Common frameworks will be established where they are necessary in order to:

- Enable the functioning of the UK internal market while acknowledging policy divergence

- Ensure compliance with international obligations.
- Ensure the UK's ability to negotiate, enter into and implement new trade agreements and international treaties.
- Enable the management of common resources.
- Administer and provide access to justice in cases with a cross-border element.
- Safeguard the security of the UK.

Frameworks will respect the devolution settlements and the democratic accountability of the devolved legislatures and will, therefore:

- Be based on established conventions and practices, including the fact that the competence of the devolved institutions will not normally be adjusted without their consent.
- Maintain, as a minimum, equivalent flexibility for tailoring policies to the specific needs of each territory as is afforded by current EU rules.
- Lead to a significant increase in decision-making powers for the devolved administrations.
- Frameworks will ensure recognition of the economic and social linkages between Northern Ireland and Ireland and that Northern Ireland will be the only part of the UK that shares a land frontier with the EU. They will also adhere to the Belfast Agreement. (Cabinet Office, 2017).

The first principle set out in Table 7.1 indicates that the common framework is based on established conventions and practices, including the fact that the competence of devolved institutions will not normally be adjusted without their consent. This raises concerns over two issues: the effectiveness of the legislative consent motion (Sewel Convention) and the introduction of further legislation, such as the UK Internal Market Act 2020 (UK IMA) and the Subsidy Control Act 2022 (SCA).

The second principle implies that the common framework will maintain, as a minimum, equivalent flexibility for tailoring policies to the specific needs of each territory, as afforded by current EU rules. This principle is supposed to offer devolved governments the opportunity to design bespoke agricultural policies and support programmes. However, the Agricultural Act

2020, UK IMA 2020, and Subsidy Control Act 2022 (SCA) could undermine this framework and curtail the possibility of divergence. This is a particular issue for agricultural support in Scotland and Wales because of the substantial amount of farmland classed as less favoured areas (LFA), so dependent on subsidies, as outlined in Chapter 6.

The third principle states that NCF leads to increased decision-making power; however, it is unclear how this would be possible. There was no further discussion or agreement on how this principle could be achieved during the JMC (EN).

The Cabinet Office, responsible for common frameworks, created a five-phase process for development and delivery initially planned for 2020. The circumstances that delayed the process will be discussed further in this chapter. The Cabinet Office mapped out the devolved competencies that required a new framework and then assigned each policy area to the relevant government department for further development. It is unclear how the mapping process was achieved, and it is beyond the scope of this study. However, Sandford and Gormley-Heenan (2020) suggest that the selected areas do not meet the criteria set out in the MoU (2018) and that path dependency and UK government political priorities influenced the decisions (Sandford & Gormley-Heenan, 2020).

DEFRA assumed responsibility for the common framework for agricultural support, collaborating closely with the Scottish and Welsh administrations. The development of this framework was structured into five distinct phases, as outlined in Table 7.2. The initial phase focused on policy development, where foundational guidelines and objectives were established. This phase was crucial as it set the direction for subsequent actions and ensured the framework would be robust and aligned with overarching goals. Following the initial policy development, the process moved into the consultation phase. During this period, key stakeholders, including representatives from the agricultural sectors of Scotland and Wales and other relevant parties, were engaged to provide input and feedback. This phase was integral to ensuring the framework was comprehensive and addressed the unique needs and circumstances of the territories involved.

Further policy development succeeded in the consultation phase. This iterative phase allowed for the framework refinement based on the feedback received. Adjustments and improvements were made to ensure the policy was practical and effective in addressing each region's specific agricultural support needs. The fourth phase, endorsement, involved obtaining formal approval from the necessary authorities. This step was critical in moving the framework from a draft

stage to a provisional status. It required agreement and support from various governmental bodies and stakeholders, ensuring the framework had the necessary backing for implementation. When the Provisional Common Framework for Agricultural Support was published in 2022, it had reached Phase 4, the endorsement stage. The final phase of the process was parliamentary scrutiny. This phase would involve a thorough review and assessment by parliament to ensure the framework was legally sound, practical, and aligned with national and regional policies; however, this phase had not been reached in time for the publication of the Provisional Common Framework in 2022.

Table 7.2 Common Framework 5-Phase Stage of Development

Phase 1	Phase 2	Phase 3	Phase 4	Phase 5
Initial Framework programme development	Detailed Framework policy development	Initial engagement with relevant Scottish Parliament committee(s) and summary of Framework submitted Relevant committee(s) decides extent of scrutiny required Discussion between Scottish Government officials and Clerks about planned scrutiny and timescales JMC(EN) ministers agree provisional Framework	Preparation and implementation of final Framework proposals Provisional Framework submitted to relevant committee(s) with any accompanying information Committee(s) conducts scrutiny Committee(s) provides written views on provisional Framework to portfolio minister UK Government and devolved administrations consider views received from all four legislatures Portfolio ministers agree response to respective legislatures Final Framework endorsed by JMC(EN) ministers	Implementation (and post-implementation review)

(Cabinet Office, 2019)

7.3 Another Intergovernmental Review: Encouraging Cooperation and Effective Dispute Resolution

7.3.1 Introduction

At a Joint Ministerial Committee (Plenary) meeting in January 2018, Prime Minister Theresa May, First Minister of Scotland Nicola Sturgeon, and First Minister of Wales Carwyn Jones agreed that officials should review and report on the intergovernmental framework to ensure it was 'fit for purpose' for future discussions over EU withdrawal and beyond (Cabinet Office, 2017). The Review of Intergovernmental Relations was published in January 2022, just before the new provisional Common Framework for Agricultural Support, which included new structures for managing dispute resolution recommended by this review. One reason for the delay in publishing the Common Framework for Agricultural Support was to ensure the new structures set out below were incorporated into the document.

7.3.2 The Review of Intergovernmental Relations

The Review of Intergovernmental Relations document outlines five key principles accompanying the Memorandum of Understanding (MoU). These principles foster positive relations based on mutual respect, build and sustain trust through communication and confidentiality, promote understanding and accountability for intergovernmental activities, and resolve disputes transparently (Cabinet Office, 2022). These principles reflect a markedly different approach from previous agreements. The language in the document positions the devolved administrations as equals to the UK government. Unlike the MoU, which lacked references to collaboration or regular engagement, this document emphasises these aspects. It establishes principles for positive relationships and equal opportunities that are absent in the MoU.

Furthermore, the review introduces a more nuanced approach to managing shared competencies between the UK and its devolved governments. It acknowledges that UK governance operates with "overlapping competencies across multiple levels of government. It is not a two-level game; the networks are more complex than this" (Piattoni, 2010, p.21).

The review also recommends regular official-level engagement with ministerial oversight and decision-making through consensus at all levels. It introduces (Table 7.3) a new three-tier structure to guide joint work, decision-making, and dispute resolution, replacing the Joint Ministerial Committee, which previous reviews criticised for its ineffectiveness in managing disagreements (McEwan, 2017). The first tier of the new structure encompasses newly formed

inter-ministerial groups (IMGs). These groups are similar to the sub-committees recommended by the Smith Commission, though it is unclear where officials drew inspiration for their inclusion in this intergovernmental review.

The Environment, Food, and Rural Affairs (IMG-EFRA) became responsible for agricultural policy matters and met for the first time in February 2019. This group aims to ensure monthly portfolio engagement between officials and ministers in the UK. Ministerial interactions were conducted sporadically at the JMC Plenary or the JMC European Union when negotiations for Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) reforms were conducted. Even during the Brexit negotiations, the UK government was criticised by devolved administrations for sporadically conducting JMC (EN) meetings. This group also discussed and managed disputes as soon as possible. The Inter-Ministerial Group for the Environment, Food, and Rural Affairs (IMG-EFRA) developed and oversaw the implementation of a Common Framework for Agricultural Support.

The middle-tier structure oversees cross-cutting matters that have not yet been addressed at the portfolio level. The middle-tier also included Inter-ministerial Committees (IMCs) with limited timeframes to deal with situations requiring ministers' attention. The IGR Secretariat, provided by the Cabinet Office, offers administrative support and manages disputes. This standing secretariat comprises government officials who report to the council annually. A fundamental issue with the JMCs is that the plenary meetings occurred infrequently and lacked a neutral mediator: "If they must resolve a dispute, the UK government has the final say" (Keating, 2010).

The top-tier includes the Prime Minister, First Ministers, and heads of the devolved government council. The portfolio and middle-tier lead this forum, chaired by the Prime Minister.

Table 7.3 Three-Tier Intergovernmental Structure

Top Tier	<p><u>The Council</u></p> <p>Prime Minister, First Minister of Scotland, First Minister of Wales, First Minister of Northern Ireland</p>
Middle Tier	<p><u>Standing Committees</u> <u>IGR Secretariat</u></p> <p>Inter-ministerial Standing Committee (IMSC)</p> <p>Inter-ministerial Standing Committee (F: ISC)</p> <p>Additional inter-ministerial Committees</p>
Lowest Tier	<p><u>Inter-Ministerial Groups (IMG)</u></p> <p>Policy area-specific groups:</p> <p>Inter-ministerial Group for the Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (IMG-EFRA)</p>

(Cabinet Office, 2022)

This review outlines the management and resolution of disputes at the portfolio level, introducing a three-step process with guidance on dealing with disputes at the lowest possible level, replacing the previous forum for dispute resolution in the JMC. It also introduced a new secretariat that could arbitrate disputes. The earlier structures included a secretariat, but their only function was to deliver administrative support. This new structure replaced the JMC, which was described as “a hierarchical structure dominated by the UK government, which chairs the meetings and largely controls the agenda” (Trench, 2004).

These new structures have just been introduced (see Table 7.4), so there is limited empirical analysis of how these IGR changes function. However, McEwen (2021) has suggested that the changes offer a more developed structure for managing disputes, acknowledging that the increase in policy crossover and institutional interdependence has become more evident after Brexit and that replacing frameworks must be cooperative and coordinated (McEwen, 2021).

Table 7.4 Intergovernmental Relations 2022

Principles Of IGR
Maintaining positive and constructive relations based on mutual respect for the responsibilities of the governments and their shared role in the governance of the UK.
Building and maintaining trust based on effective communication
Sharing information and respecting confidentiality
Promoting understanding of and accountability for their intergovernmental activity
resolving disputes according to a clear and agreed process
IGR Structure
Standing IGR Secretariat
The new IGR structure comprises three tiers:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Top tier: The Prime Minister and Heads of Devolved Governments Council (“The Council”).
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Middle tier: The Inter-ministerial Standing Committee (IMSC), the Finance Inter-ministerial Standing Committee (F: ISC) and additional time-limited inter-ministerial committees formed as necessary
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lowest tier: a number of inter-ministerial groups (IMG) formed to discuss specific policy areas
Dispute resolution process
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stage 1: consideration of dispute by IGR Secretariat
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stage 2: consideration by IMSC or F: ISC
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stage 3: consideration by the Council

The principles indicate a willingness for cooperation and collaboration, with mutual respect for shared and distinct responsibilities. There is increased transparency for officials and ministers participating in intergovernmental relationships and more explicit guidelines on conflict resolution. The new principles extend the previous ones in the Memorandum of Understanding, aiming to foster positive relationships and improve the intergovernmental framework.

Despite these advancements, the devolved governments are described as equal. However, no significant changes exist to give them a legally binding ‘equal footing’ or to empower the DAs to stop the UK government from introducing laws in devolved areas. The new structures are

essentially additional layers over the pre-existing structure and culture, reflecting incremental change rather than a radical overhaul (Mahoney & Thelen, 2010).

7.4 The Provisional Common Framework for Agricultural Support

The provisional Agricultural Support Common Framework was published in February 2022. Initially, this document was intended to be available upon the UK's exit from the European Union on 31 January 2020 but was unofficially in operation before phase 4 was completed. It states that the Ministers of the UK government, the Scottish and Welsh Governments, and the Department of Agriculture, Environment, and Rural Affairs (DAERA) for Northern Ireland created this non-legislative structure based on the principles of collaboration, coordination, and cooperation in agricultural support (DEFRA, 2022, p.1). This intergovernmental agreement includes a Framework Outline Agreement (FOA) and a concordat.

The first section of the document, the Framework Outline Agreement (FOA), is very similar in structure to the Memorandum of Understanding (MoU), which is unsurprising, as both documents are intergovernmental agreements. The FOA begins by providing a breakdown of the policy areas within the scope of the document. The summary of policy areas the framework includes relates to areas of agricultural support, such as:

- Agricultural spending, associated regulations, and enforcement.
- Marketing standards.
- Crisis measures, Public Intervention (PI) and Private Storage Aid (PSA).
- Cross-border holdings (United Kingdom).
- Data collection and sharing.

The document's scope includes retained EU laws, the World Trade Organization (WTO) Agreement on Agriculture, and protocols for Ireland and Northern Ireland. This document framework replaces the EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) legislation (Appendix A). Under the terms of the European Union (Withdrawal) Act 2018, some legislation that intersects devolved competencies was retained. The CAP covers four areas governed by EU regulations called 'basic acts'. These basic acts also contain subordinate legislation and are now retained in domestic law (DEFRA, 2022, p.2). The departments of each government were responsible for administering this legislation, as they were when part of the EU and within the CAP. These departments oversee providing advice, monitoring compliance with agricultural policies, and

financial support. In England, this will be the Department for the Environment, Food, and Rural Affairs (DEFRA), which is the Agriculture and Rural Economy Directorate; in Wales, it will be the Climate Change and Rural Affairs Group; and in Northern Ireland, it will be the Department of Agriculture, Environment, and Rural Affairs (DAERA). Ministers from each department form the Inter-Ministerial Group for Environment, Food, and Rural Affairs (IMG EFRA).

The principles of the framework agreed upon at the JMC (EN) are to enable the functioning of the UK internal market while acknowledging policy divergence; ensure compliance with international obligations; ensure that the UK can negotiate, enter, and implement new trade agreements and international treaties; enable the management of common resources; administer and provide access to justice in cases with a cross-border element; and safeguard the security of the UK (Senedd, 2022). The operational aspects of this document set out the working arrangements of all four governments.

7.4.1 Levels of Governance in the Provisional Common Framework

The framework introduced a new three-level formal structure (Table 7.5) derived from the new systems outlined in an intergovernmental review published in January 2022.

Table 7.5 3-level IGR Structure

Level Three	IMG-EFRA – Intergovernmental Arrangements covering Environment, Food and Rural Affairs
Level Two	Senor Officials Program Board (SOPB) from DEFRA and Devolved Administrations
Level One	Agriculture Policy Collaboration Group (PCG) UK Agriculture Market Monitoring Group (MMG).

(DEFRA, 2022)

Level One: This level comprises officials in the newly established Agriculture Policy Collaboration Group (PCG) (Appendix B) and the UK Agriculture Market Monitoring Group (MMG) (Appendix C). The concordat describes the Agriculture Policy Collaboration Group (PCG) as officials who aim to unite the parties involved in agricultural support and ensure the JMC (EN) principles are upheld. This group will meet ten times yearly unless more is required. A standing DEFRA secretariat and a rotating chair from each government support it.

Level Two: The Senior Officials Program Board (SOPB) for the Environment, Food, and Rural Affairs oversees the PCG and MMG. The SOPB is comprised of senior officials from DEFRA and devolved governments. They are responsible for providing coordination and oversight of the work program of the Inter-Ministerial Group (IMG-EFRA) and meet before each IMG-EFRA meeting to discuss issues that require ministerial decisions. This document contains significant details about officials and senior officials, clarifying their roles for the first time. Previously, access to more information on how officials interacted and their remits were not publicly available. Informal intergovernmental interactions across the UK have often been criticised as informal and lacking transparency (Mitchell, 2010). This document provides extensive details on working groups, their responsibilities, and a hierarchy for decision-making.

Level Three: The ministerial level and Inter-Ministerial Group (IMG-EFRA) (Appendix D). This group comprises ministers from DEFRA and devolved governments, substituting the JMC (EU), where most discussions and negotiations are conducted. This group meets ten times a year to monitor progress and discuss primary and secondary legislation and any other issues regarding agricultural support that impact all nations in the UK. It also reports to the top tier of the newly formed Council of the Prime Minister and First Ministers of Scotland, Wales, and Northern Ireland. A criticism of the JMC was the lack of regular meetings (Tierney, 2009) due to their ad hoc nature (McEwen, 2020). However, DEFRA and the devolved Ministers for Agriculture have an established history of regular contact, so this is not a significant change to the joint-working relationship (Cairney, 2006).

7.4.2 Policy Divergence and Dispute Resolution

An essential function of this common framework is to guide policy divergence and resolve disputes. One of the principles of the Joint Ministerial Committee on European Negotiations (JMC EN) is that it enables the internal market to function while acknowledging policy divergence. Therefore, divergence is acceptable within specific parameters. The document outlines determining whether policy divergence fits within these parameters and is permissible. The process begins with assessments of new policies managed at Level One, which are discussed by the Provisional Common Framework Group (PCG) to evaluate if they cause divergence. Suppose the level of divergence is deemed acceptable. In that case, the policy is then referred to Level Two, where Senior Officials review it and make recommendations to portfolio ministers, indicating that the divergence is acceptable. These recommendations are passed to Level Three and discussed in the Inter-Ministerial Group for Environment, Food, and

Rural Affairs (IMG-EFRA). If this group agrees, the policy is approved. However, if Level One cannot decide, the issue is escalated to the Level Two Senior Officials Program Board (SOPB). If there is still no agreement at this level, the problem is transferred to the dispute resolution mechanism for further deliberation and resolution.

The Common Framework outlines settling disagreements concerning policy divergence or other matters through the dispute resolution procedure outlined in the Memorandum of Understanding on Devolution, which was still under review when the Common Framework for Agricultural Support document was released. The Review of Intergovernmental Relations (UK Government, 2022) outlines the guidelines for dispute resolution, which states that, at the portfolio level, all three levels must address disagreements. If these levels cannot resolve conflicts, the issue must be escalated to the inter-ministerial standing committee (IMSC) supported by the standing IGR Secretariat or the highest level at the Prime Minister and Heads of the Devolved Government Council. If a disagreement reaches the Prime Minister and Heads of the Devolved Government Council and cannot be settled, each government will state its respective parliament, outlining the reasons for the breakdown.

The published document, The Provisional Common Framework for Agricultural Support, clarifies what is classed as agricultural support, the legal obligations and legislation connected to agricultural support, and details the roles and responsibilities of officials. It also establishes a clear working structure for officials and ministers to manage disputes and dispute management. Nevertheless, this document was expected to contain some details on agricultural support policy. This document sets out a process for managing agricultural support across the UK. However, it does not set out a common policy approach. The reasons for this and the contents of the final document are explored in the following sections.

7.4.3 Navigating Intergovernmental Agreements: Designing a Common Framework for Agricultural Support

The UK and its devolved governments agreed on the needs and principles of the NCF and then began mapping out potential policies for common frameworks. A total of 153 policy areas were identified, of which 24 required primary legislation, 82 required non-legislative frameworks, and 49 required no further action. Further work was agreed upon to define the scope and structure of these frameworks. The Welsh Parliament Climate Change, Environment, and Infrastructure Committee (CCERAC) suggested that new common frameworks be structured like the EU's. There was disagreement, as some argued that the UK's exit from the EU provided an opportunity to create a bespoke framework. However, most agreed that using existing EU

frameworks was the best option because of the complexity of the work and limited delivery time (CCERAC, 2018).

The Department of Environment, Food, and Rural Affairs (DEFRA) oversaw the design process and publication of the Provisional Common Framework for Agricultural Support in February 2022. The Secretary of State for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs, George Eustice MP, and Deputy Director Danny Jeyasingam from the Devolution Team in DEFRA participated in the framework's design on behalf of England and oversaw the process for the UK government. Members of the devolved governments involved in the process were from Wales, with the Cabinet Secretary Lesley Griffiths (Member of Senedd (MS) Minister for Environment and Rural Affairs and officials. From the Scotland Cabinet Secretary for Rural Economy, Fergus Ewing (MSP) until 2021, then Mairi Gougeon, MSP Cabinet Secretary for Rural Affairs and the Islands. However, discussions were overseen by the Joint Ministerial Committee (EU), Cabinet Office, Department for Levelling Up, Housing and Communities, Scotland Office, Wales Office, Scottish Government, and Welsh Government, which also participated in developing or overseeing the progress of the common framework for agricultural support. The following section explores the experiences of those who participated in developing a common framework.

7.5 DEFRA: Building Consensus and Respecting Divergence

The process of designing a common framework for agricultural support began in August 2018 with official meetings in multilateral workshops. The Deputy Director of the Devolution Team in the Department for Environment, Food, and Rural Affairs (DEFRA), Danny Jeyasingam, a senior official overseeing the common framework, described the approach to the initial framework design:

"There are 14 common frameworks in the DEFRA portfolio, all sharing common themes. They build on long-standing arrangements between UK administrations, aiming for consensus to avoid unnecessary regulatory fragmentation while recognising devolved competence and existing divergence. They propose governance, decision-making, and dispute resolution arrangements to facilitate joint decision-making where commonality is necessary" (Jeyasingam, 2022, p. 2).

In the initial stages, DEFRA decided to develop all common frameworks in a similar format. Given the complexity and time constraints of creating bespoke documents for each policy area, DEFRA aimed for consistency to avoid unnecessary regulatory fragmentation. This approach also highlighted the importance of coordination and alignment between UK administrations. Each framework published by DEFRA included a Framework Outline Agreement (FOA) and

a concordat. Danny Jeyasingam, Deputy Director of the Devolution Team in DEFRA, reflected on the development of the agricultural support framework:

"We went through a lot of detail when we developed the agricultural support framework. Starting in the summer of 2017, we aimed to manage subsidies in a common way while recognizing the differences in farmers and farmlands across the UK and the devolved nature of agricultural policy. Economists and other experts contributed to discussions, ensuring that different funding regimes or schemes would not necessarily lead to distortions in divergence. The framework was designed to address these issues" (Jeyasingam, 2022, p. 11).

From the initial stages of development, DEFRA officials were mindful of devolved competencies and respected diverging agricultural support policies. This recognition was essential for adhering to the principles set out in the Joint Ministerial Committee on European Negotiations (JMC EN), which mandated that frameworks respect devolution and accommodate the different policy priorities of the devolved regions. This early consideration aimed to ensure that the new framework could accommodate divergence to meet the varying agricultural needs across the UK, demonstrating an awareness of the sector's complexity and diversity. Danny Jeyasingam, Deputy Director of the Devolution Team in DEFRA, reflected on the development of the agricultural support framework, the roles of officials and the expertise required:

"Each framework is made up of various sub-groups: technical-level, official-level, and senior steering groups at the deputy director level. These groups meet and can escalate disputes to a senior official's programme board at the director level. While there's no standing senior-level committee, senior officials can be convened as needed" (Jeyasingam, 2021, p.17).

This statement provides insight into the hierarchical structure within the groups working on the development stage. The new structures recommended by the Intergovernmental Relations (IGR) review have already been incorporated into DEFRA's working arrangements. This clear structure allows for effective coordination and escalation of issues, ensuring appropriate levels of expertise and authority participate in decision-making. Jeyasingam also emphasised the importance of the four-nation agreement in the framework development:

"At every stage of the framework development, we prioritised the four-nation agreement, and it was only towards the end of last year that we got ministerial agreement between the Cabinet Office Ministers and their devolved Administration counterparts on cross-cutting issues. It took time to ensure the policy fit the specifics of each framework" (Jeyasingam, 2022, p.7).

This account suggests that officials overseeing the framework development tried to consistently maintain collaboration and consensus-building among the different administrations. This was

achieved by prioritising reaching an agreement to ensure that the framework reflected the needs and perspectives of all involved parties. The Senior Official acknowledged that agreeing on cross-cutting issues with the relevant ministers and counterparts took time. Although the exact reasons for these delays are not specified, it is common for complex policy frameworks involving multiple stakeholders to require extensive negotiation and consultation (Nelson, 2009). It is crucial to invest sufficient time to ensure that all perspectives are considered and that the resulting framework is robust, fair, and endorsed by devolved governments. However, the number of Ministers and Senior Officials involved in this process also stressed the impact of the response to COVID-19 on the framework's progress. The policy team's efforts to ensure that the framework worked for the circumstances and complexities indicated an intention to adapt it to accommodate each administration's specific needs, challenges, and nuances. Such tailoring is essential to ensure that the framework is relevant, effective, and capable of addressing the unique circumstances of each nation's agricultural sector.

George Eustice MP, Secretary of State for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs, affirmed that DEFRA ensured the new framework adhered to the JMC principles of respecting devolution and fostering a cooperative and collaborative relationship with the devolved governments. He stated:

"We have been clear from the start that there is nothing in these frameworks that changes the fundamental parameters of our devolution settlement. Those things that are devolved remain devolved, and those things that are reserved remain reserved. It is an agreed code of conduct about how each of us exercises those respective powers where they could intersect" (Eustice, 2021, p. 14).

Eustice emphasised that the framework does not alter the core principles of the devolution settlement but provides guidance on operating these powers when there is potential overlap. The document's main function is to manage divergence and resolve disputes through new intergovernmental structures. Agricultural support policy has been devolved, raising concerns from the Scottish Parliament about whether the common framework might constrain Scotland's ability to create future agricultural support systems that differ from England's (SPICe, 2022). The framework contained ambiguities regarding divergence and the extent to which it would be permitted. The UK government plans to phase out direct support payments in England by 2027, while Scotland will likely continue providing farmers with direct income support. SPICe noted:

"It is not clear to what degree divergence will be considered acceptable for each of the four nations. Specific details of agricultural support schemes are not discussed as part

of the framework. Direct payments are only mentioned in relation to cross-border holdings" (SPICe, 2022, p. 34).

The Welsh government indicated it intends to broadly align its support framework with England's policy, while Scotland will maintain the same framework under the CAP until 2025. Therefore, the effectiveness of the new structures for managing divergence remains unclear until they are tested.

7.6 Exploring the Scottish Government's Collaborative Experience of Designing a Common Framework for Agricultural Support

7.6.1 Exploring the Scope for Collaboration for an Intergovernmental Agreement

The JMC Communique stated that the UK government and the devolved administrations "agree to work together to establish common approaches in some areas currently governed by EU law" (Cabinet Office, 2017). In 2021, the UK government reiterated its commitment to working collaboratively and constructively with the devolved administrations of Scotland, Wales, and Northern Ireland to progress Common Frameworks (UK Government, 2021). This section of the chapter will examine the experience of the Scottish Government in designing a Common Framework for Agricultural Support and whether the process was cooperative and collaborative.

The House of Lords Common Frameworks Scrutiny Committee (HoL CFSC) was commissioned to investigate the development of Common Frameworks. They began taking oral evidence in November 2020. The first question was addressed by Michael Russell (SNP), MSP, the Cabinet Secretary for the Constitution, Europe, and External Affairs from the Scottish Government. He was asked to report on the common framework process, benefits, and challenges. Russell was the only minister to attend all 28 Joint Ministerial Committees (EN). He was also part of the government that oversaw the development of frameworks in Scotland.

"The biggest advantage of the common frameworks is that they are mutually agreed and voluntary. Their biggest disadvantage for me is that I find it very difficult to see how they can operate effectively if the internal market Bill is to be passed, particularly in its present form" (Russell, 2020, p.1).

One function of this framework is to protect the integrity of the UK's internal market. However, the UK government introduced an internal market bill. Russell questions how committed the UK government is to the principles of the common framework and the extent to which it was willing to work collaboratively with devolved governments if it imposed legislation on top of the frameworks that should be jointly owned.

Lord Murphy of Torfaen questioned Michael Russell further about the working relationship between the Scottish, Welsh, and UK governments during discussions of common frameworks. Michael Russell responded by stating how productive the relationship had been between officials but criticised the lack of understanding of devolution in Westminster, particularly within the current UK government, highlighting a recent incident where a senior UK government source seemingly asserted the hierarchy of the UK government over the devolved governments and the Prime Minister's superiority over the First Minister of Scotland.

"There is a problem with devolution. That is a lack of understanding of what devolution is, not in Scotland but in Westminster, and particularly in this current Government. It is in the headlines again today in Scotland, with a senior UK government source—there appear to be many of them who are quoted regularly—pointing out that the Prime Minister has, in the words of that source, more pips on his collar than the First Minister and therefore that he outranks her" (Russell, 2020, p.4).

Russell suggested that this promotion of hierarchy by the UK government is based on a misunderstanding of devolution, contributing to tensions during ministerial-level discussions on frameworks.

"Devolution is not about a hierarchy of Governments; it is about a hierarchy of Parliaments. The Westminster Parliament regards itself as sovereign and the other Parliaments as not sovereign, so they can be overruled. But the Governments have specific responsibilities, and those are clear. In the case of Scotland, in Schedule 5 of the Scotland Act, it is very clear. Essentially, only those things named are reserved; everything else is devolved" (Russell, 2020, pp.4-5).

This misunderstanding has led to challenges in fostering a cooperative and respectful intergovernmental relationship, which is crucial for effectively implementing common frameworks. Russell argued that this highlights the importance of recognising the devolved parliaments' separate legislative powers and autonomy. Statements by MPs that assert that Westminster is sovereign and holds the ultimate decision-making authority added to political tensions. This perspective may reflect the UK's constitution; however, members of the UK government who encourage opinions such as this damage the claim that the government wishes to cooperate and collaborate with devolved governments. The JMC (EN) communique agreement stated that the frameworks would "respect devolution and the democratic accountability of the devolved legislators" (Cabinet Office, 2017). Michael Russell stressed the importance of the JMC (EN) communique, as it provides a clear basis for ensuring the purpose and principles of common frameworks worked effectively for the devolved administrations.

Referencing this document, he indicated that the agreed principles should have guided the establishment of the common frameworks.

"It is important to point to the communique of the Joint Ministerial Committee in October 2017. They say, 'Common frameworks will be established where they are necessary' to 'enable the functioning of the UK internal market, while acknowledging policy divergence'. That is the first principle and that is what we have been seeking to establish. That is why the internal market bill is such a disruption, because it seeks to do the same thing, but by imposition, not by negotiation and agreement" (Russell, 2020, p.2).

However, Russell's comment suggests that the UK government did not adhere to the principles set out in the JMC (EN). He expressed frustration with the UK government for introducing the Internal Market Bill, which he believed was unnecessary since the common frameworks were sufficient to protect the internal market. He argued that if legislation was necessary, the UK approached this through coercion instead of negotiation and consensus as they had promised to do in the JMC (EN). Michael Russell proposed that the scope of the Internal Market Bill goes beyond just regulating the internal market; instead, it grants the UK government additional spending powers in devolved areas.

"Our vision for that, the common frameworks, starts from the premise that power is distributed in these areas across the UK and the best means of building that robust internal market is to do it by agreement" (Russell, 2020, p.7).

Russell insisted there was no need for UKIMA, arguing that the common frameworks would protect the internal market and align with the agreement to act cooperatively for decision-making and shared responsibility among devolved administrations and the UK government.

Gillian Martin, MSP, Convener of the Environment, Climate Change and Land Reform Committee, expressed concerns about the UK government's handling of the Internal Market Bill while developing the common framework intended to manage the UK internal market. She noted that issues arose during Joint Ministerial Committee (JMC) negotiations, stressing that respecting and treating devolved nations as equal partners is crucial. Martin warned that the approach taken with the Internal Market Bill—imposing rather than negotiating—could undermine the unity of the four nations. She stated:

"There is nothing to be feared from giving the devolved nations that respect and parity. There are only things to be gained. If the common frameworks were to be brought through in the same way as the internal market Bill was, we are in big trouble" (Martin, 2021, p.13).

This comment suggests a perceived lack of respect or unequal treatment in the relationship between the UK government and devolved administrations. Treating devolved nations as equal partners in decision-making processes is essential for maintaining a cooperative relationship and could otherwise weaken the UK's unity. This highlights the importance of consultation and shared decision-making when developing and implementing policies that affect devolved nations.

7.6.2 Asymmetrical Relationships: Promoting Mutual Respect and Parity of Esteem

When addressing the Cabinet Secretary for Rural Affairs and Islands about the progress of the common framework for agricultural support, Mairi Gougeon (SNP) MSP expressed her dissatisfaction with the UK government. She accused the UK government of introducing laws that seemed to limit the intergovernmental agreement and harm the cooperative relationship established by the agricultural support common framework. Gougeon argued that these laws would weaken devolution and that the UK government had not followed the guidelines set out in the JMC (EN). She emphasised that the frameworks were designed as "a model for progress by agreement and collaboration between equals." However, she noted significant threats from the United Kingdom Internal Market Act 2020 and the Subsidy Control Bill, describing them as "an assault on devolution" (Gougeon, 2022, p.27).

Gougeon further compared the UK government's approach unfavourably with the Scottish government's experience implementing agricultural policy within the EU. She stated that as an EU member, Scotland could develop and tailor policies to its needs through the principle of subsidiarity. Gougeon expressed frustration that the new legislation represents a "backwards step that undermines our power to set our policies based on what best meets the needs of the people of Scotland," explaining that the common frameworks process was meant to enable the devolved administrations to work together on an equal basis while respecting each government's roles (Gougeon, 2022, p.30).

This statement highlights concerns about the risks to the common framework process. Gougeon suggests that the common framework is a model for progress through agreement and collaboration between equal parties, implying that devolved administrations have acted in good faith to manage policy divergence while respecting each government's roles. The Cabinet Secretary's frustration with the new legislation reflects a perceived restriction on Scotland's ability to create policies tailored to its needs, contrasting with its previous autonomy under EU principles.

Mairi Gougeon and Michael Russell emphasised the need for the UK government to treat devolved administrations with 'parity of esteem'. This principle is crucial for improving intergovernmental relationships and ensuring collaboration on common frameworks (McAllister, 2015; McEwen & Murphy, 2022). Russell has argued that all four governments should be treated equally, recognising their different roles and responsibilities. He criticised the UK government for not fully acknowledging this principle, which hinders progress. Russell stated:

"Transparency is an important issue here, but the really important issue in the intergovernmental review is finding a way in which it reflects devolution at its best... not in a subsidiary way but as equals" (Russell, 2020, p.17).

The new intergovernmental structures aim to treat the four governments equally, introducing more transparency and better dispute management. However, substantial constitutional reform may be necessary to protect each government's interests and perspectives legally. Before the common framework for agricultural support was published, it was unclear how disputes would be resolved. Russell acknowledged the complexity of creating formal mechanisms for each framework. He suggested a flexible approach, emphasising the need for a system that includes arbitration and public involvement, with Parliaments having a say (Russell, 2020, p.18). Russell advocated for context-specific solutions, aligning dispute resolution mechanisms with the nature of each issue. He hoped the new intergovernmental structure would correct the power imbalance between the UK government and the devolved administrations. Previously, the UK government held final decision-making powers, effectively vetoing the other three governments. Russell emphasised the importance of avoiding veto powers and ensuring public accountability, aligning with cooperative governance principles (Mahoney & Thelen, 2010). Michael Gove, Cabinet Office minister, acknowledged the poor relationship between the UK and devolved administrations, stating that it needed to be reset. When asked how this could be achieved, Russell replied:

"We can do the right thing together by agreement, but we cannot be dragooned into doing it, still less legislated into doing it" (Russell, 2020, p.19).

Despite progress at the official level, political tensions between the Scottish and UK governments have interfered with their ability to work cooperatively. These tensions arise partly from their different political goals and attitudes towards Brexit. The Scottish government's frustration is rooted in the UK's introduction of legislation that undermines the

common frameworks' ethos and purpose. This highlights the limited capacity of the devolved governments to prevent the UK from passing legislation they disagree with (McHarg, 2017). Without adopting a structure or legal underpinning found in federations, the new intergovernmental structures seem unlikely to resolve this power imbalance (Keating, 2010; McEwen, 2020).

7.6.3 Lack of Parliamentary Scrutiny: An Indicator of Inadequate Transparency in Intergovernmental Agreements

The Common Framework for Agricultural Support, initially expected in December 2020, was delayed and not published until February 2022. It had already been in operation for a year before its publication. It had only reached phase 4 of the common framework development program shortly after its publication, during which parliamentary scrutiny was conducted. Gillian Martin, MSP, Convener of the Environment, Climate Change and Land Reform Committee, expressed concerns about the lack of scrutiny due to insufficient detail from DEFRA.

"Our committee has not been able to extract the detail on the common frameworks. That has been the biggest issue. We do not really have the detail on a lot of the common frameworks. That has not been published and has not been put before us" (Martin, 2021, p. 2).

Martin also questioned the extent of parliamentary scrutiny that could be applied to an intergovernmental agreement such as the common framework:

"The very fact that that is in a devolved area of policy but is not under the full control of Scottish Ministers gives us two problems. It gives a problem for the Government. From the Parliament's and the committee's point of view, we do not have the opportunity to scrutinise those decisions... because the power does not lie with the Scottish Government; it lies with the UK Minister. We have no power to say to UK Ministers, 'You must come and tell us what is going on'... The other issue is transparency in decision-making" (Martin, 2021, p. 2).

This raises concerns about the lack of oversight and transparency in devolved policy areas. These issues have significant implications for democratic accountability and the Scottish Parliament's ability to advocate for its constituents effectively. Lack of transparency has consistently been criticised in inter-institutional operations (Trench, 2006; Keating, 2010; McEwan, 2017). To address these concerns and uphold transparency and responsibility in devolved governance, a reliable system is required to guarantee the meaningful participation of Scottish ministers, parliamentary committees, and public oversight. Martin further emphasised the need for thorough scrutiny:

"We hold the Scottish Government to account, but these negotiations are happening in an intergovernmental way... if decisions on common frameworks are made in an intergovernmental way, and just presented to a committee to rubber-stamp, we are missing a big part of scrutiny" (Martin, 2021, p. 13).

Achieving a balance between direct engagement and cross-parliamentary cooperation is crucial to ensure that the concerns and recommendations of devolved administrations are respected and addressed effectively in intergovernmental negotiations. The Cabinet Secretary for Rural Economy, Fergus Ewing, responsible for developing a common framework for agricultural support in Scotland, was critical of the UK government's lack of transparency and engagement. He argued that there had been insufficient discussion about the Agricultural Act 2020 and its impact on agricultural policy development in Scotland.

"I also spoke with the Secretary of State, Mr Gove, last week to discuss the UK Agriculture Bill. I have repeatedly asked for discussion of the Bill at the regular ministerial meetings... but there has been zero discussion of the content and merely discussion about the timetable... we did not see the full version of the Bill until the very end of August. This could result in serious constraints on Scotland's future choice of policies and schemes" (Ewing, 2018, pp.11-12).

Ewing expressed disappointment that the focus remained on the timeline despite repeated requests for meaningful dialogue about the bill's content. This implies a reluctance from DEFRA to engage in extensive discussions with devolved administrations. The late release of the full version of the bill limited the time available for thorough examination and understanding of its provisions, raising concerns about the quality of parliamentary discussions and the efficacy of the legislation. Ewing's statement suggests that the bill exacerbates concerns about a power grab by the UK government rather than alleviating them. He emphasised that DEFRA's assertion that certain areas of law are reserved contradicts the Scottish government's stance, implying that the bill could restrict Scotland's ability to choose its policies and programmes, threatening its devolved powers. This aligns with broader criticisms regarding the transparency and effectiveness of intergovernmental relations and the necessity for a system that ensures meaningful participation and oversight by devolved administrations (Trench, 2006; Keating, 2010; McEwen, 2017).

The Scottish Parliament's response to the Provisional Common Framework for Agricultural Support was published in the SPICe Briefing Agricultural Support Framework (2022). One major issue highlighted was the lack of parliamentary oversight of the frameworks, given that they were intergovernmental agreements. The parliament recommended increasing

parliamentary oversight of interdepartmental operations at the official level to ensure the framework's impact on policy is thoroughly examined. Another concern was the UK government's agricultural policy objectives. The framework lacked detailed policy content, leaving unanswered questions about how new legislation would intersect with the devolved administrations' policy decisions. The Scottish Parliament was concerned that this indicated the UK government's intention to circumvent the common framework and establish a "high level of regulatory coherence," contrary to the Scottish government's approach to "permit legitimate policy choices" (SPICe, 2022).

The Scottish Parliament was mainly concerned with the Agriculture Act 2020 and its implications for Scotland, which has been implementing an agricultural support policy within the CAP since 1999. The CAP framework allowed the four UK countries to devise individual plans. The Subsidy Control Act 2022, which would oversee subsidies, including agricultural support subsidies, raised concerns. Scotland and Wales withheld legislative consent for this bill. The Scottish government continued the CAP payment system until 2025 with some amendments to simplify the system. However, there are concerns about how direct payments for agricultural support will continue if the UK phases them out in England by 2027 and only offers support for environmental schemes. The framework outlines how divergence will be managed, but it does not clarify the acceptable level of divergence for other UK nations. This could be problematic if direct support in Scotland were seen as an unfair advantage over other nations. The Scottish Parliament's response underscored a need for greater parliamentary oversight and transparency in intergovernmental agreements and clearer guidelines on managing policy divergence to ensure fair and effective agricultural support across the UK.

7.7 Exploring the Welsh Government's Collaborative Experience of Designing a Common Framework for Agricultural Support

7.7.1 Limited Information and Delays: Unveiling the Structure of the Common Framework

Officials at DEFRA initiated the first phase of developing a common framework for agricultural support by engaging in multilateral workshops with officials in Wales. Welsh ministers participated in discussions and decision-making with the UK government as the process progressed to develop the framework further. However, due to a lack of information being passed on to the Welsh parliament, there was uncertainty about the scope and policy details of the frameworks. During a discussion in the External Affairs and Additional Legislation Committee, Simon Brindle, Director of the COVID-19 Restart and Recovery for

the Welsh Government, suggested that the new structure was likely non-legislative and akin to a memorandum of understanding emphasising the portfolio-to-portfolio relationships required for joint working (Brindle, 2019, p. 104). The lack of information on the framework's structure and contents was due to slow progress, with the framework being stuck in the first two phases of development until mid-2021. This delay was partly caused by political matters, including the EU exit delay, two general elections, and the COVID-19 outbreak. Tim Render, Lead Director for the Environment and Rural Affairs of the Welsh Government, addressed these postponement issues. He explained that many officials had been reassigned to handle the pandemic, but teams were now at full capacity and making considerable progress. Render stated that the delay was a problem with DEFRA's progress, saying:

"We're almost held up by the UK Government and their ability to engage, rather than our side. So, I think we're pretty much ready to go on most of the key ones from our side" (Render, 2020, p.173).

This indicates that while the Welsh Government was prepared to advance, the overall progress of the common framework was hindered by DEFRA's slower pace of engagement and decision-making.

Lord Deben, the Climate Change Committee Chair, attributed delays in advancing and implementing the frameworks to a lack of ideas and clarity within DEFRA. He expressed concern over DEFRA's failure to produce documents for parliamentary scrutiny, suggesting that the delay was due to indecision and lack of a clear plan for replacing common agricultural policy payments (Lord Deben, 2021, p.17). The uncertainty regarding the progress and content of the frameworks was exacerbated by government officials conducting most framework developments with ministerial oversight. The House of Lords Common Frameworks Scrutiny Committee (HoL CFSC) also expressed concerns about the lack of detailed information provided by DEFRA. Moreover, some delays were attributed to an intergovernmental review introducing new structures. It was decided to incorporate these structures into the common framework, which was eventually published in February 2022. This incorporation ensured that the frameworks were comprehensive and aligned with the latest intergovernmental agreements despite the initial slow progress.

7.7.2 Fostering Goodwill and Strengthening the IGR

The common framework was developed concurrently with the intergovernmental review, so the HoL CFSC also assessed this with work on common frameworks. The House of Lords Constitution, Foreign Affairs and Defence Committee asked Jeremy Miles MS, the Counsel-

General and Minister for European Transition for the Welsh Government, how the working relationship between the UK government and the Welsh Government was performing.

"In many ways, the experience of intergovernmental relations in the context of leaving the European Union and the transition period has been turbulent. One thing we have been able to demonstrate is that the capacity of governments to work together in a collaborative and productive way has been the common framework work stream. This has been consistently an area where we could say, 'Look, if we managed to adopt the principles and the common frameworks across the board, it would lead to much better collaboration between the governments'" (Miles, 2020, p.3).

These comments suggest that developing common frameworks is a positive example of a collaborative experience between governments despite difficult circumstances. The Brexit period increased tensions, and the Welsh Government's experience in interactions with the UK government over Brexit produced unsatisfactory outcomes (McEwen, 2019). Developing common frameworks offers an opportunity to discuss policy development and aid decision-making. Establishing and implementing common frameworks requires agreement and consensus among governments, which can be complex and time-consuming. Differences in policy priorities, political ideologies, and power dynamics often impede progress and hinder collaborations. The Welsh Government has adopted a pragmatic approach to ensure better future interactions.

Lord Murphy of Torfaen of the HoL CFSC asked about the working relationship between the Welsh Government and the United Kingdom Government over the past months concerning common frameworks,

"The common thread throughout the unsatisfactory relationship between the UK Government and the Devolved Governments is the absence of institutional resilience. You cannot have a robust constitutional settlement capable of bearing the weight of things such as Covid and EU exit that is so heavily dependent on that dynamic" (Miles, 2020, p.6).

This comment implies that the UK and its devolved governments' working relationships rely on goodwill and cooperation. The Smith Commission (2014) criticised this reliance on personal dynamics, which is yet to be addressed. The institutional structure is necessary for stable and dependable relationships. Institutional resilience is essential for the UK government and the devolved administration's constitutional agreements. Resilient institutions guarantee consistency, stability, and effective decision-making. Formalised and robust institutional mechanisms could bolster the relationship between the UK and the devolved governments. This reduces reliance on individual goodwill and creates more stable and predictable

intergovernmental relations. This could include reviewing constitutional arrangements and power distribution and making the decision-making processes transparent and inclusive. Enhancing institutional resilience necessitates a commitment to creating and maintaining effective collaborative decision-making mechanisms. It also balances centralisation and devolution for effective governance, accountability, and national/regional representation. UK constitutional arrangements limit the central government's legal enforceability (Opeskin, 2001). Thus, the devolved government must negotiate intergovernmental cooperation.

Miles acknowledged the advancements in intergovernmental reviews, especially in dispute prevention and resolution, but also recognised the need for further research:

"Progress on the intergovernmental review has perhaps been more positive than we might have thought, subject to the long shadow the Bill casts over it. In a sense, it is complementary to a common framework program. It provides a mechanism for escalating the sorts of disputes that may arise between Governments in the common frameworks programme. It escalates them above a portfolio level into a structure that, we would hope, is much more robust and resilient than the ones we currently work to" (Miles, 2020, p.6).

Evaluating the progress of tangible outcomes and the effectiveness of the proposed mechanisms to tackle intergovernmental issues is crucial. The internal market bills affect intergovernmental cooperation, so assessing the bill's impact on the UK government's relationship with devolved governments is essential. Common frameworks can enhance engagement and resilience in intergovernmental relationships. Miles further explained the new structure for dispute resolution:

"If you had said to us a year ago, 'Do you feel you would be making progress on dispute resolution?', it felt like an area where progress was least likely to be productive, in a sense. But the truth is that the conversations have been pretty creative. It's been led by the Northern Ireland Executive, and they obviously have particular experience in this area. But as well as there is a mechanism within the framework for disputes to be resolved, one of the themes of the broader intergovernmental review, which obviously extends beyond Brexit, is also how we can move forward with our dispute resolution mechanisms" (Miles, 2019, p.96).

The review of intergovernmental relations was commissioned at a JMC (Plenary) on behalf of the UK, Scottish, and Welsh governments and was conducted by officials. Previous IGR reviews have recommended improving dispute mechanisms, but the UK government has disregarded them. However, the UK government approved the most recent review, which led to the most significant reforms in the intergovernmental framework. Jeremy Miles discussed the new intergovernmental mechanisms and how they might be applied.

"In the context of the IGR, there is a more umbrella set of mechanisms because they apply on a cross-portfolio basis. We have been pressing for there to be a role for an independent secretariat, which would provide comfort to the four Governments that there was an independent element in how disputes are managed and a role for independent advice in that process, again to give reassurance that there is some objective measure against which those things have been considered" (Miles, 2020, p.18).

This statement raises questions about whether a uniform or structured dispute resolution process is better for shared frameworks. A formal process may bring uniformity and clarity, while a formal process may bring legal certainty and enforcement. This statement stresses the need to assess how the dispute resolution process in common frameworks interacts with internal market bills. Evaluating the compatibility and consistency between the proposed dispute resolution mechanisms and internal market bills is essential. This assessment should consider whether the dispute resolution process adequately meets the interests and objectives of all parties and is in line with the principles and regulations of internal market legislation.

The HoL CFSC questioned Jeremy Miles about cooperation with the UK Government to ensure the efficacy of common frameworks. Responding to Michael Gove's suggestion of resetting the intergovernmental relationship, Miles described it as "Kafkaesque" to talk about resetting relationships while pursuing the internal market Bill in its current form, acknowledging inadequate relations due to UK legislation undermining collaborative framework negotiations (Miles, 2020, p.20). Miles argued that the Bill aims "to not have to bother with the common frameworks and simply be able to impose the provisions of internal trade agreements." He emphasised that common frameworks could enable the four UK governments to seek agreed positions in international negotiations on devolved matters, advocating for robust intergovernmental structures as outlined in the Welsh Government's Reforming our Union document (Miles, 2020, p.21). This approach suggests a missed opportunity to fully engage with devolved governments, similar to European negotiations, raising questions about inclusivity in decision-making. Miles further clarified that "common frameworks are not about finding a common policy. They are about a common approach to manage divergence effectively," highlighting their ability to adapt to evolving circumstances and regional needs, thereby addressing policy challenges effectively (Miles, 2020, p.23).

7.7.3 The Impact of UK Legislation on Common Frameworks

The common framework is a non-legally binding intergovernmental agreement designed to protect the UK internal market. However, the UK government passed the UK Internal Market Act 2020 (UKIMA), creating great concern for Wales. When asked about the impact of the Bill

when it was introduced into the House of Commons, Jeremy Miles responded negatively about the potential damage this Bill would do to the cooperative, co-owned aspects of the common frameworks.

"The introduction into that landscape of the internal market Bill has really threatened that in the way Mike (Russell) was describing. I fear that the very, very heavy-handed legislative mechanism that the Bill contains removes any incentive for the UK Government to continue engaging in a constructive way in the common frameworks" (Miles, 2020, p.3).

Strong legislative measures of the internal market bill may reduce the UK government's motivation to collaborate in common frameworks. If the Bill focuses on centralising power, it could weaken the spirit of cooperation that the frameworks aim to promote. The internal market bill seeks to maintain the UK's internal market after Brexit. The Bill must balance centralisation and meet the diverse needs of devolved administrations to maintain regulatory consistency across the UK. If it fails to do so, it can damage common collaborative frameworks. Intergovernmental collaboration depends on trust and positive relationships between the UK government and the devolved administration. If an internal market bill weakens cooperation, it can damage trust and impede future collaborations. This could affect the UK's internal market and intergovernmental relations (IGRs). The UK government should communicate and negotiate with devolved administrations to ensure a successful common framework.

The Counsel General and Minister for the Constitution for the Welsh Government, Mick Antoniw (MS), also expressed his concerns about the UKIMA's impact on common frameworks.

"The collective position I think is this: as far as possible, we want agreements to be reached collaboratively, with a mechanism to resolve disputes. The internal market Act came as a sort of juggernaut through the process, which had been based on a series of principles and agreements and on a collaborative way of working. There has always been the belief, which I think is now being proved to be the case, that agreement in most of these areas would be reached—there was so much common interest—but the internal market Act actually shifted the balance of power within that process in a very unilateral way" (Antoniw, 2021, p.3).

This statement stresses collaborative agreement-making and dispute resolution. This raises questions about how collaborative decision-making has been respected and the effect of power shifts. This implies that the internal market unilaterally shifted the power balance. The Act's impact on prior principles and agreements and its implications for intergovernmental relations are uncertain. The Internal Market Act fails to meet the principles set out in JMC (EN), which

states that devolved administrations would gain more decision-making powers. This Act would restrict current power-making decisions, so it could not increase under these circumstances. It also impedes DAs' democratic accountability by enabling UK ministers to curtail the devolved legislation that is part of a manifesto promise.

"Perhaps at some levels of the UK government there is quite a high degree of cooperation and progress, but it is at the higher echelons of Government that we end up with a number of things that seem to be quite provocative, whether it be the internal market Act, the overriding of financial resource—former EU resources—coming to the Welsh Government, and so on. Those areas have been extremely provocative, and the complete bypassing of the Welsh Government in the replacement funding for European Union social funding has been very damaging" (Antoniw, 2021, p.13).

This statement suggests that there may be a lack of cooperation and progress in the higher echelons of the UK government. This raises questions about the nature and extent of cooperation, the reasons for the lack of collaboration, and the potential impact on intergovernmental relations and policy outcomes. This statement highlights the Internal Market Act and the handling of financial resources as examples of provocative actions with implications for the Welsh Government. This raises questions about the motivations behind these actions, their legal and constitutional implications, and their effects on devolved powers and decision-making. The statement mentions the bypassing of the Welsh Government in the replacement funding for EU social funding, which is seen as damaging.

The introduction of the Subsidy Control Bill in 2021 raised further concerns, and the Welsh Government attempted to engage with the UK government to ensure that the bill did not harm the devolution or interfere with agricultural policy decisions. Huw Irranca-Davies MS (LAB) explained that their report expressed hope that the UK Government would not refuse to cooperate constructively on legislation potentially undermining the devolution settlement. He found the UK Government's refusal to fully engage with the Welsh Government puzzling, given the potential benefits of working together to find a fair and workable approach within the existing constitutional framework (Irranca-Davies, 2022, p.377).

The Welsh Government believed that this legislation had the potential to undermine the devolution settlement and the Welsh Government's policy delivery in devolved areas. Concern is expressed about the implications of such an approach for understanding devolution and the existing settlement. The refusal of the UK Government to cooperate and engage fully with the Welsh Government raises important questions. First, it highlights the significance of cooperation and constructive engagement between different levels of government, particularly

in devolved systems. Collaboration is crucial for maintaining effective governance, ensuring policy coherence, and respecting the autonomy of devolved administration (Peters, 2018).

The UK government was willing to engage in this way when designing non-legislative intergovernmental agreements, but it was less cooperative with legislation that would pass through Westminster. Pursuing legislation undermining the devolution settlement could have serious repercussions and contradict their attempts to improve the intergovernmental framework to strengthen the Union. Collaborative work between governments can lead to better outcomes, improved policy implementation, and enhanced public trust in the devolution settlement. Introducing legislation undermining this cooperation raises the need to explore why the UK government refuses to cooperate. It highlights the complexities and challenges of balancing devolved powers with national-level legislation and decision-making (Hooghe & Marks, 2016).

7.8 Common Frameworks: An Unfulfilled Opportunity?

The House of Lords Common Frameworks Scrutiny Committee (HoL CFSC) was appointed to scrutinise all matters related to common frameworks. Starting in late 2020, the Committee published its first report, *Common Frameworks: Building a Cooperative Union*, in March 2021. This report highlighted the potential for common frameworks and new structures introduced by the intergovernmental review to strengthen the working relationship between the UK government and devolved administrations, fostering a more cooperative union. However, the Committee's second report, *Common Framework: An Unfulfilled Opportunity?* Published in July 2022, it suggested that the common frameworks did not achieve the hoped-for outcomes. The Committee identified three major issues: lack of transparency in the development process, political tensions between the UK and devolved governments, and UK legislation that exacerbated these tensions. These factors have impeded intergovernmental relations across the UK.

The initial HoL CFSC report raised concerns about the lack of transparency in intergovernmental agreements during the common framework design process. The JMC (EN) principles declared that the democratic accountability of devolved legislatures must be respected (Cabinet Office, 2017). The HoL CFSC found many cases in which this principle was disregarded. Concerns were raised about the initial design process, conducted "behind closed doors" (HoL CFSC, 2021, p.3). Delays in publishing documents resulted in incomplete frameworks being implemented without endorsement or scrutiny, limiting stakeholder

engagement and hindering parliamentary oversight. Gillian Martin, MSP, Convener of the Environment, Climate Change and Land Reform Committee, provided evidence to the Committee, highlighting the limited engagement from UK Government Ministers compared to the House of Lords:

"We have had more engagement with the House of Lords than we have with UK Government Ministers. How do we ensure that our views and recommendations are respected in negotiations between governments? [...] I have had several conversations with committee Chairs in the House of Lords, who just picked up the phone to me and said, 'What's the score here? What's happening?' That back-channel information and knowledge sharing is really helpful in scrutiny. It is not really the way it should be done, but we all know that it is better to have conversations" (Martin, 2021, pp.17-18).

This statement suggests that cross-parliamentary work and cooperation can help ensure that devolved administrations' views and recommendations are respected during government negotiations. Limited engagement may lead to decisions that do not adequately reflect the interests of devolved administrations. Enhanced cooperation and joint work between parliaments can address challenges associated with common frameworks, providing valuable insights, fostering knowledge sharing, and contributing to more robust scrutiny. This approach aligns with the JMC (EN) principles by ensuring the 'democratic accountability of the devolved legislatures.' Martin's statement also highlights the discrete role of the HoL CFSC as intermediaries between the UK government and devolved administrations, an aspect not emphasised in previous reviews of intergovernmental relations.

The Committee described the common frameworks as essential for coordinating the internal market, setting minimum standards, ensuring that the UK adheres to international treaties, and encouraging collaboration and cooperation across all four nations. Although they:

"appear to be technical in content and purpose, they are highly political in context and impact. Common frameworks should be the product of consultation and policy development between the four administrations. They offer a unique and novel opportunity for the security and development of the Union of the UK. As such, they require close attention and political goodwill to fulfil that potential" (HoL CFSC, 2022, p.3).

The Committee raised concerns about the lack of political goodwill and the ineffective intergovernmental mechanisms for managing political tensions and disputes. Reflecting on evidence provided by Lord Dunlop, who was commissioned by Prime Minister Theresa May to report on the UK government's Union capability, it was noted that:

"intergovernmental relations were handled on a more informal basis when the administrations across the UK were drawn from the same political party" (Lord Dunlop, 2021, p. 31).

This suggests that intergovernmental relations have not been sufficiently adapted to address the challenges posed by political differences.

Academic experts provided evidence to the Committee, emphasising the importance of collaborative processes. McEwen highlighted that "probably the most important aspect of the frameworks programme has been the process of bringing the different Administrations around the table and of recognising the complexities that devolution and multi-level Government present to the way the UK is governed" (McEwen, 2020, p. 2). This process has demonstrated the potential for joint working, even among parties with different ideological and constitutional outlooks. However, McEwen cautioned that the success of this collaborative approach is not guaranteed and would require a change in ministerial-level decision-making culture to permit ongoing cooperative work.

The framework programme could provide a route for enhanced collaboration in the future, emphasising the possibility of joint work based on increased cooperation. Developing a culture of collaboration among ministers could lead to improved results and better governance. Nevertheless, the success of the framework programme and the potential for sustained collaboration depends on altering the ministerial decision-making culture to encourage continuous collaborative efforts. This underscores the necessity of adapting intergovernmental relations to foster a more cooperative and effective governance model capable of addressing the complexities of devolution and multi-level government.

The HoL CFSC stated that the common frameworks had the potential to develop "UK-wide policy by collaboration and consensus" (HoL CFSC, 2022, p.3). It was also stated that the newly introduced intergovernmental structures have the potential to enable joint decision-making and resolve disputes in a more appropriate manner than the JMC offered. However, legislation introduced by the UK government during the development of common frameworks, such as the Internal Market Act 2020 and the Subsidy Control Act 2022, has intensified the strain between the UK and DAs. Angus Robertson, MSP, Cabinet Secretary for the Constitution, External Affairs and Culture in the Scottish Government, spoke to the Committee.

"The United Kingdom Internal Market Act is, unfortunately, far more representative of this Government's approach to intergovernmental relations and devolution. Let us not forget that the current Prime Minister has described devolution as a "disaster"; that is

the default position. It is quite difficult to make things work without a willingness to try and make them work." (HoL, 2022, p.19).

The main issue surrounding the Internal Market Act was its interaction with the common frameworks. Robertson cited the example of the Scottish Government's request for an exclusion for single-use plastics legislation. The Scottish Parliament passed regulations in November 2021 to ban certain single-use plastic items, set to be enforced on June 1, 2022. However, it was not until June 9, 2022, that the Secretary of State for the Environment, Food, and Rural Affairs laid a statutory instrument allowing single-use plastics to be exempted from the UK Internal Market Act. An exclusion had already been agreed upon through the Resources and Waste frameworks. However, UK ministers ignored this agreement and conducted a "wholesale re-examination of the issues over several months," ultimately deciding unilaterally to narrow the scope of the exclusion (Robertson, 2022, p. 25).

Tom Cartlidge, Head of the UK Frameworks Division in the Cabinet Office, responded by noting that the demand for an exclusion regarding single-use plastics preceded the agreement on the exclusions process and emerged "as something of a test case." He stated that the government was "going through a lessons-learned exercise... with BEIS, Defra and other departments to ensure that we are able to reach decisions more quickly in future" (HoL CFSC, 2022).

Robertson summed up the intergovernmental relationship in Scotland with the other devolved administrations by emphasising its cooperative and collaborative nature:

"Our relationship, both on an official level and on a ministerial level, with other devolved Administrations is first class. We speak very regularly. Our official colleagues talk with one another weekly... and share best practice and insight... It is a sign of the fact that we are working so well with one another that we literally speak with one voice on these issues, regardless of the party-political differences" (Robertson, 2022, p.21).

This statement illustrates a strong, collaborative relationship that regularly exchanges information to improve policy. However, Robertson contends that the UK government is not part of this positive dynamic. The House of Lords Scrutiny Committee found similar sentiments across devolved administrations, noting that the common framework was a missed opportunity to construct a genuinely cooperative union.

7.9 Concluding Discussion: Examining Intergovernmental Relations through the Designing of a New Common Framework for Agricultural Support (2016-2022)

7.9.1 Introduction

This chapter focused on 2016-2022 and examined how intergovernmental relationships facilitated the Scottish and Welsh governments' participation in designing a new common framework for agricultural support.

7.9.2 Challenges and Dynamics in Developing the New Common Framework for Agricultural Support: Insights from Scotland and Wales

Initially expected to provide an overarching policy framework, the Common Framework for Agricultural Support (2022) was a two-part document consisting of technical instructions and legal acts transferred from EU legislation. Several of those interviewed by the House of Lords Common Framework Committee expressed disappointment in the final document being about process rather than policy (McEwen, 2020; Keating, 2021). Due to time pressures related to delays in withdrawing from the EU and the redeployment of officials due to COVID-19, the resulting document shared a generic format with all new common frameworks designed by DEFRA.

While the common framework lacks an overarching policy framework that replaces the CAP, it does introduce new, more transparent intergovernmental features, such as setting out the role of officials. New subgroups of officials will offer technical support and advice to ministers across the UK, who regularly engage in the Inter-Ministerial Group for the Environment, Food, and Rural Affairs (IMG-EFRA) to oversee its implementation. A new three-level structure for managing policy divergence and dispute resolution is also outlined. However, there is no clarity on the parameters and limits of divergence.

The chapter also examined the most recent UK government-commissioned review of Intergovernmental Relations (IGR), published in 2022, which resulted in this new three-level structure. These mechanisms aim to manage divergence and resolve disputes, promoting stability through structured, predictable processes and preventing escalation to higher levels of political contention (Mahoney & Thelen, 2010). However, these reforms remain untested, and their effectiveness in defusing disputes is yet to be determined. While the UK government engaged in producing this review and created a more detailed system, it still lacks legally binding guidelines on responsibilities, highlighting the UK government's power to avoid significant constitutional change (Streck & Thelen, 2005).

The UK government's decision to maintain the existing intergovernmental framework while enhancing structures and methods for addressing divergence and dispute resolution at the official level first demonstrates a commitment to historical practices rather than a departure from them. In their first report, the House of Lords Common Framework Scrutiny Committee suggested that common frameworks could be an opportunity to build a cooperative union. However, their second report questions whether this opportunity has been unfulfilled. The new structures set out in the common framework and the IGR review add layers to the existing framework, illustrating the resilience and continuity of the intergovernmental system without fundamentally altering it. This approach maintains a power imbalance favouring the central state, thus limiting cooperation across the UK (Pierson & Skocpol, 2002; Mahoney, 2004).

These new intergovernmental structures set out in the common framework and the IGR review reflect path dependency, expanding upon pre-existing ones rather than replacing them. This illustrates the theory that institutions evolve incrementally based on historical trajectories (Pierson, 2000; Mahoney, 2000; Mahoney & Thelen, 2010). This continuity aligns with path dependency and layering, where new elements are added to existing structures to adapt to new demands without fundamentally altering the core framework, demonstrating the resilience of the intergovernmental system (Thelen, 2003).

This chapter provides further insight into the continuing power asymmetries between the UK government and the devolved administrations, observable in previous chapters' findings. While designing the new common framework, ministers from Scotland and Wales expressed concerns about the UK government passing legislation before the new framework was completed, which they believed would undermine it. Examples include the Internal Market Act 2020 and the Subsidy Control Act 2022, which Scottish and Welsh ministers believe undermines devolution (Keating, 2010; McEwen, 2017). This reflects that the asymmetrical power dynamics persist so that the UK government retains significant control over devolved matters, shaping the institutional landscape to maintain the status quo or direct changes in alignment with its interests (Keating, 2010; McEwen, 2017).

However, the House of Lords Common Framework Scrutiny Committee found evidence of productive engagement at the official level, increasing institutional stability through collaboration between administrations (Capano, 2018). This productive engagement is crucial for achieving a balance between self-rule and shared rule and for effective regional and national governance. The agreement between the UK and devolved governments to cooperate and

collaborate, as well as the effective working arrangements of officials, indicated that power imbalances might be less pronounced between different levels of government (Peters, 2018).

The empirical findings from this chapter illustrate the experiences of Scottish and Welsh ministers in engaging with the common framework development process and highlight the interplay between power distribution and strategic actions within the intergovernmental framework. Concerns over recent UK legislation and the productive yet delayed engagement process at the official level underscore the ongoing challenges for institutional interaction within the UK's multi-level governance system (McEwen, 2017).

7.9.3 Intergovernmental Dynamics and Policy Autonomy: The Impact of the New Common Framework for Agricultural Support on Scotland and Wales

The findings in this chapter build on those in Chapter 6, examining how Scotland and Wales have historically approached the delivery of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). This policy allowed them to develop strategies tailored to their specific farming needs, such as hillside farming and less favoured areas, which are more prevalent in these regions than in England. Scottish and Welsh farming rely on subsidies, and both governments have been vocal about continuing policies designed to meet these unique needs. This background of policy control has influenced their approach to designing the new common framework for agricultural support.

The Joint Ministerial Communiqué, agreed upon by the Scottish, Welsh, and UK governments, established that cooperation, coordination, and respect for devolution principles would underpin the process (Cabinet Office, 2017). There was an expectation of 'parity of esteem' in working jointly to design the common framework and its capacity for flexibility once implemented. However, the final common framework document does not establish an overarching framework akin to the CAP, which sets standards but permits sufficient flexibility for regional adaptation (Edwards, 2007).

Scottish and Welsh ministers emphasised the need for a co-designed, jointly owned collaborative process that respects devolution, enables policy flexibility, and provides more decision-making powers for devolved administrations. However, concerns were consistently raised about the potential harm to intergovernmental relationships and the circumvention of common frameworks by the UK government. The passage of the Agricultural Act 2020, the UK Internal Market Act 2020, and the Subsidy Control Act 2022 during the framework's design

raised significant concerns for the devolved governments. Ministers questioned the necessity of such legislation, as the Common Frameworks were expected to manage these issues.

The UK's departure from the EU has brought unresolved tensions to the surface (Sandford & Gormley-Heenan, 2020). McEwen (2022) contended that while devolution granted autonomy in certain policy areas, it did not result in a more balanced power distribution across the UK. EU membership allowed for multi-level governance, sharing power among multiple institutions. However, how power can be effectively shared outside the EU remains uncertain. Devolved governments are concerned about the impact of recent legislation on their autonomy and policy development.

The empirical findings from this chapter illustrate the experiences of Scottish and Welsh ministers in engaging with the common framework development process. They highlight the interplay between power distribution and strategic actions within the intergovernmental framework. Concerns over recent UK legislation and the productive yet delayed engagement process at the official level underscore the ongoing challenges for institutional interaction within the UK's multi-level governance system (McEwen & Schakel, 2016).

7.9.5 Conclusion

In conclusion, the intergovernmental relationship has enabled Scottish and Welsh administrations to participate in designing the new Common Framework for Agricultural Support to a certain extent. Introducing new intergovernmental structures and regular ministerial engagement reflects an effort to incorporate devolved input. However, the actual influence of devolved administrations has been limited by the nature of the final framework documents, which focus on technical and legal processes rather than substantive policy innovation. Additionally, recent UK legislation, such as the Agricultural Act 2020 and the UK Internal Market Act 2020, has raised significant concerns that they will constrain the devolved administrations' policy-making powers and undermine devolution. Therefore, while the JMC Communique stated that ensuring cooperation and collaboration was a primary objective in designing the new common frameworks, significant barriers remain. These barriers limit the full realisation of a genuinely collaborative and shared approach to decision-making in the design of the agricultural support common framework, especially if it can be undermined by UK legislation. The following chapter will delve deeper into the insights and themes that emerged from the three preceding findings chapters, providing a comprehensive synthesis and analysis of the overall study.

Chapter 8 Concluding Discussion

8.1 Introduction

The three preceding chapters have presented empirical findings on how the intergovernmental relationship has performed from 1999 to 2022. The evidence in Chapter 5 provides a comprehensive assessment of UK government commissions reviewing intergovernmental relations (IGR) from 1999 to 2016. Chapter 6 examines how the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) was implemented across the devolved UK from 1999 to 2016. Chapter 7 focuses on 2016 to 2022 and examines the common framework for agricultural support, new intergovernmental structures, and participants' experiences.

This concluding discussion synthesises the insights and themes that emerged from these findings. It discusses broader themes, such as the impact of initial institutional design on intergovernmental relations, the power asymmetry in the devolution settlements, and the practice of layering new structures over existing intergovernmental frameworks. Additionally, this chapter will explore how agricultural policy has diverged across the devolved administrations, particularly in Scotland and Wales, and the scope for further divergence. The discussion will also address the development and principles underpinning common frameworks, the concept of 'muscular unionism,' and how these factors influence the UK's intergovernmental relations. Through this analysis, the chapter aims to provide a holistic understanding of the evolving intergovernmental landscape and its implications for future policy and governance.

8.1.2 Initial Institutional Design

The path-dependency literature suggests that the outcome of a process or the development of an institution is influenced by its initial conditions (Mahoney & Thelen). In other words, past choices can set a particular path or trajectory that is difficult to change in the future (Pierson, 2016). The first empirical chapter examined the origins of the intergovernmental relationship (IGR), how it was designed and introduced, and how it functioned. The intergovernmental framework enables the UK and its devolved Government to interact. It was established in 1999 because of the devolution settlement. It became apparent that the UK government set the parameters for intergovernmental relationships. The UK government introduced intergovernmental machinery that would not bind them legally, and the working relationship was established through an intergovernmental agreement they had designed.

The literature suggests that this was possible because the decentralisation of power from Westminster was layered upon a pre-existing administrative structure. Coran and Thelen (2018) suggested that introducing new institutions and structures by layering over existing structures enables the central government to maintain the status quo as it does not create significant institutional changes. This also explains why Scotland received more substantial power, as it reflected the pre-existing administrative capacity of the Scotland Office (Tierney, 2009). In Wales, limited powers were granted because Westminster and Whitehall still held most of their administrative and institutional capacity for policy delivery. The devolution settlement did not immediately reform the UK constitution, and the powers granted through the Scotland Act 1998 and the Government of Wales Act 1998 were transferred from the Secretary of States for Scotland and Wales. This enabled the central Government to address demands for home rule and resolve claims of democratic deficits without being drawn into making substantial constitutional changes (Dardanelli, 2005; Trench, 2007).

The contention is that there are continuities between asymmetrical devolution and post-1999 forms of devolution, both legislative and executive. The literature suggests that layering over preexisting structures is a method for the dominant power to maintain the status quo and avoid significant change or threats to its authority. The UK government can distribute some powers to the DAs through layering while asserting a hierarchy and retaining parliamentary sovereignty (Pierson, 2004). This approach reflects historical continuities in the asymmetrical devolution of power, with existing administrative capacities significantly influencing the extent of devolution.

8.1.3 Power Asymmetry and Institutional Reproduction in UK Devolution

The literature of historical institutions identifies power asymmetry as an indicator of a mechanism of reproduction. These institutional mechanisms of reproduction (IMR) can also be referred to as positive or negative feedback loops (Pierson, 2004). Institutional reproductive mechanisms are the persistent features of an institutional interaction pattern that causes overall stability and maintains the status quo. Increasing returns and positive feedback loops allow institutions to reach an equilibrium. Identifying power asymmetry makes it possible to determine how the UK government maintains its power and institutional stability or is 'locked in' (Thelen, 2006; Conran & Thelen, 2016).

Pierson (2015) states that 'increasing returns' explain how choices or events can create self-reinforcing dynamics, in which initial advantages or disadvantages are amplified over time.

This means that once a particular option gains an advantage or dominance, alternative options become increasingly challenging to gain traction. The increasing returns generate 'positive-feedback loops.' Positive feedback occurs when the benefits or advantages of a particular path accumulate and create a reinforcing cycle. As the benefits of a chosen path increase, it attracts more resources, support, and adherence, further entrenching its dominance (Pierson, 2015).

The UK government was responsible for devolution's institutional design and intergovernmental relationships. Much of the literature focuses on the asymmetrical nature of devolution and the disparity in powers of the devolution settlement between Scotland and Wales and between the UK. The UK government built asymmetry into the devolution settlement. The Scottish and Welsh administrations do not have equal status with Westminster, and resolving this would require the UK government to give away power, so balance is unachievable (Keating, 2010).

Despite the inherent asymmetry, the UK government demonstrated a willingness to increase some of the power held by the devolved administrations. A comprehensive examination in Chapter 5 of UK-commissioned reviews of devolution and intergovernmental relations revealed that each review recommended enhancements to the devolution settlements by increasing the powers of the Scottish and Welsh administrations and improving the intergovernmental machinery. However, the evidence suggests that these reviews were commissioned in Scotland and Wales for different reasons, not necessarily to address power imbalances. The findings in Chapter 5 underscore that while the reviews proposed strengthening the devolution settlements, their primary motivations varied, reflecting distinct political and administrative contexts in each country. This nuanced understanding highlights that the UK government's willingness to enhance devolved powers was influenced by specific circumstances in Scotland and Wales rather than a uniform approach to rectifying power imbalances.

The first UK commission reviewed in Scotland, the Calman Review, was instigated as a response to the SNP winning the Scottish Parliamentary election in 2007, forming a minority government. The increasing support for independence dominated the discourse surrounding this review and how it could be discouraged. Scottish Labour, Conservatives, and Liberal Democrats collaborated to set in motion a review of devolution and intergovernmental relations (Cairney, 2009). The first report, titled "The Future of Scottish Devolution within the Union", and the final report, "Serving Scotland Better: Scotland and the United Kingdom in the 21st

Century.” Where guided by an ethos and discourse of ensuring Scotland stayed within the UK. These reports recommended the introduction of enhanced powers through the Scotland Act of 2012. However, recommendations to strengthen intergovernmental relations were limited, and building on existing structures was advised. Ultimately, these recommendations were disregarded.

The Smith Commission was commissioned in response to the Scottish Independence Referendum 2014. This review also provides recommendations for enhanced power and improvement of intergovernmental machinery. The enhanced powers came under the Scotland Act of 2016. Both reviews acknowledged issues with the IGR, but neither suggested substantial reforms, and their suggestions were limited. Both reviews were conducted in response to Scotland's increasing demand for independence. The UK government was willing to expand the responsibilities of the Scottish Government but resisted implementing IGR reforms other than including the Sewel Convention in the Scotland Act 2016. The UK government is willing to increase some of its responsibility to reduce the demand for independence but does not address the issues of IGR.

In 2004, the Richard Commission recommended that the National Assembly for Wales be restructured and granted increased power and legislative capacity. This led to the Government of Wales Act 2006, which restructured the Assembly from a corporate body to a separate legislature, the National Assembly for Wales, and a new executive Welsh Assembly government. (Trench, 2007). The Silk Commission conducted a substantial review of Welsh powers, and its recommendations were implemented through the Government of Wales Act 2014 and the Wales Act 2017. These revisions were introduced to resolve the complexity of the original conferred model, which created confusion among those with decision-making powers.

Devolutions in Scotland have been enhanced to stave off increasing demands for autonomy and independence. Devolution has been enhanced in Wales to resolve the complexity of delivering legislation and policy through a limited model of devolution. There have been many criticisms of IGR and the lack of space to hold formal discussions for joint-decision making and resolving disputes. However, the UK government was unconvinced about making significant changes to the intergovernmental machinery.

8.1.4 Resistance to Change and the Evolution of Intergovernmental Structures in the UK

The argument that devolution had transformed the UK into a quasi-federal state would suggest that the central Government would work towards a more clearly defined IGR, especially considering the increasing decentralisation of power (Keating, 2010). However, the UK government seems to be highly resistant to change. The logic of the unitary state is that power can be granted down but can be taken back (Keating, 2022). The UK government's introduction of more formal structures could have impeded its power.

This aligns with Pierson's (2016) argument that institutions tend to 'stick' because those who establish an institution can build in self-reinforcing dynamics that provide them with an advantage that can increase over time as it becomes difficult for an alternative option to gain traction. Those who create an institution with a power imbalance in their favour can maintain the status quo, even if that institution is inefficient (Pierson, 2016).

The intergovernmental framework was criticised because formal interactions were held 'ad hoc' and lacked a forum for decision-making and dispute resolution. However, the most recent intergovernmental review sought to improve the intergovernmental machinery. The document published in 2022 introduced new structures. Comparing the new structures with the previous intergovernmental framework suggests some development (see Tables 8.1 and 8.2).

Table 8.1 Intergovernmental Relations 1999

Principles of the IGR
Communication
Consultation
Co-operation
Confidentiality
IGR Structure
Intergovernmental agreements MoU and Concordats
Sewel conventions (Scotland Only)
Joint Ministerial Committee (Plenary) (European Union)

(Cabinet Office, 2013).

Table 8.2 Intergovernmental Relations 2022

Principles Of IGR	IGR Structure
Maintaining positive and constructive relations based on mutual respect	Standing IGR Secretariat
Building and maintaining trust based on effective communication	The new IGR structure comprises three tiers:
Sharing information and respecting confidentiality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Top tier: The Prime Minister and Heads of Devolved Governments Council ("The Council").
Promoting understanding of and accountability for their intergovernmental activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Middle tier: The Inter-ministerial Standing Committee (IMSC), the Finance Inter-ministerial Standing Committee (F: ISC) and additional time-limited inter-ministerial committees formed as necessary
Resolving disputes according to a clear and agreed process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lowest tier: a number of inter-ministerial groups (IMG) formed to discuss specific policy areas
	Dispute resolution process
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stage 1: Consideration of dispute by IGR Secretariat
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stage 2: Consideration by IMSC or F: ISC
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stage 3: Consideration by the Council

(House of Commons Library, 2022).

The principles indicate a willingness for cooperation, collaboration, and mutual respect for shared and distinct responsibilities. The new common framework and this new intergovernmental framework clarify the role of officials and Ministers, introducing a new level of transparency. The introduction of a multi-tiered dispute resolution process, as outlined in the 2022 framework, adds clarity and predictability to how conflicts will be managed. This structured approach helps prevent disputes from escalating and ensures a clear path to resolution; nevertheless, these new structures maintain the status quo (Pierson, 2010). The new principles are an extension of the previous ones in the Memorandum of Understanding. The devolved governments are described as equal, but there are no significant changes to give the devolved governments a legally binding ‘equal footing’ or to empower the DAs to stop the UK government from introducing laws in devolved areas. The new structures are new layers over the pre-existing structure and culture (Mahoney & Thelen, 2010). According to Galik and Chelbi (2021), established institutions tend to be heavily biased towards the status quo and can prevent institutional change by engaging in ‘active stability’. This occurs when agents are

motivated to retain their advantageous arrangement to employ a mode of change such as layering (Galik & Chelbi, 2021).

This raises questions about the effectiveness of the new structures and how they will prevent the same criticisms of intergovernmental relations from arising. Furthermore, the Miller case has indicated that the UK government no longer needs consent, as it is only a convention that is not legally enforceable (McHarg, 2017). There was no attempt to resolve this issue and ensure the UK government would seek consent from the devolved governments when introducing legislation on devolved matters.

8.2 The Evolution of Agricultural Policy in the UK

8.2.1 Scope for Divergence

Since 1973, the UK government has been responsible for policy development and implementing the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). The establishment of devolved administrations in 1999 who took responsibility for agricultural policy introduced a multi-level dynamic to this process. The purpose of the CAP was to act as a protectionist in agriculture, ensure a fair standard of living for farmers, and produce affordable food for consumers (Seidel, 2019). It encompassed nine different bio-regions across the EU (Office of the European Union 2001). The CAP was developed with inherent flexibility and choice to ensure it could be applied across diverse landscapes.

The challenging topographies of Scotland and Wales compared to England led to significantly more difficult land to farm, resulting in a higher reliance on direct subsidy support and necessitating tailored agricultural support frameworks. This flexibility within the CAP enabled policy divergence across the UK, allowing the devolved governments to design and control their agricultural support policies. As a result, there were essentially 'four CAPs' within one member state, each adapted to the unique agricultural needs of its region (Scott, 2013).

Additionally, the UK was the member state responsible for negotiating reforms with the EU every seven years. Unlike the general criticism of the intergovernmental relationship, which highlighted a lack of forums for discussion, the devolved agricultural departments were in regular contact with DEFRA. This element of trust and good working relations allowed the devolved administrations to engage directly with the EU, attend EU meetings, and, in some cases, be represented at the Council of Ministers meetings. It was repeatedly noted how frequently the Scottish Executive would be represented and often led the UK delegation in

areas such as fishing. Alun Davies (LAB) also stated he had many opportunities to attend EU meetings, although he could only make proposals and had no decision-making powers.

8.2.2 Agriculture Policy Wales

When the National Assembly for Wales assumed responsibility for agricultural support in 1999, it did not immediately establish a coherent policy framework centring on rural affairs. In Wales, Hillside farming is deeply intertwined with Welsh culture and identity. Powerful farming lobby groups and unions leveraged this strong connection between farming and rural identity to influence policy (Woods, 2005). Agriculture was the most debated topic in the first year of the National Assembly for Wales (Woods, 2005). These influential farming groups were able to dictate the new Assembly's agenda. These entrenched practices made it challenging to transition to a new institutional structure that would provide an integrated rural policy framework (Woods, 2005). This situation illustrates the degree of path dependence and the expectations of the farming community on the National Assembly for Wales, thus limiting the amount of divergence that would be permissible.

Despite these initial challenges, the Welsh administration made significant strides in managing agricultural policy, particularly evident during the Foot and Mouth crisis in 2001. This crisis required Welsh ministers and officials from an agricultural department to engage with multiple UK government departments and organisations, showcasing the Executive's ability to engage in multi-level governance effectively. The response to this crisis transformed the image of the National Assembly for Wales from merely a "talking shop" to an institution capable of delivering important functions even with its limited powers.

Further illustrating the complexities of Welsh agricultural policy, the Welsh government has historically focused on supporting its unique agricultural landscape. This includes schemes tailored to the specific needs of Welsh farmers, such as the Tir Gofal agri-environment scheme, which aimed to promote sustainable farming practices. However, the implementation of such schemes was often hampered by the overarching UK frameworks and the need to align with broader EU policies under the CAP.

In developing its agricultural policies, the Welsh administration faced the challenge of balancing traditional farming practices with the need for modernisation and sustainability. For example, the Glastir scheme, introduced in 2012, sought to integrate environmental management with agricultural productivity. This scheme replaced several initiatives to simplify the support framework and improve environmental outcomes. However, its implementation

was met with mixed reactions, as some farmers felt that the new requirements were too stringent and did not adequately reflect the practical realities of farming in Wales.

The Welsh government's approach to agricultural policy has also been shaped by its interactions with the UK government and other devolved administrations. While there has been a degree of collaboration, tensions have occasionally arisen due to differing priorities and the need to compete for limited resources. For instance, during negotiations for CAP reforms, the Welsh government had to advocate strongly for policies that recognised the unique challenges faced by Welsh farmers, such as the high proportion of less-favoured areas (LFAs).

Post-Brexit, the Welsh government has continued to push for policies that support sustainable and resilient agricultural practices (Gravey, 2019). The introduction of the Agriculture (Wales) Bill in 2020 marked a significant step towards developing a bespoke agricultural policy tailored to Welsh needs. This bill emphasised sustainable land management, biodiversity, and climate resilience, reflecting the Welsh government's commitment to addressing environmental challenges while supporting the agricultural sector.

However, the ability of the Welsh government to fully realise its policy ambitions remains constrained by the broader UK legislative framework. The introduction of the UK Internal Market Act 2020 and the Subsidy Control Act 2022 has raised concerns about the potential for these laws to undermine devolved powers and restrict policy divergence. The Welsh government has expressed fears that these acts could limit its ability to implement agricultural policies that diverge from those in England, particularly in areas such as subsidy support and environmental standards.

In conclusion, while the Welsh administration has made significant progress in developing and implementing agricultural policies that reflect the unique needs of Welsh farmers, its efforts continue to be influenced by broader UK and EU frameworks. The transition from the CAP to new common frameworks presents opportunities and challenges for Wales as it seeks to balance traditional practices with modern sustainability goals. The ongoing evolution of Welsh agricultural policy will depend on the interplay between devolved powers and the constraints imposed by UK-wide legislation, highlighting the importance of effective intergovernmental relations and balanced power distribution (Hooghe & Marks, 2016).

8.2.3 Agricultural Policy Scotland

The Scottish Office oversaw agricultural policy delivery until 1999, when the Scottish Parliament assumed responsibility for this area. At the same time, the Common Agricultural

Policy (CAP) underwent significant reforms, transitioning from a policy focused on production to a holistic 'rural affairs' approach aimed at improving rural communities and environmental outcomes. This shift in CAP policy is crucial for understanding the changes in Scottish agricultural policy and its administration. The CAP initially aimed to increase agricultural productivity, ensure a fair standard of living for agricultural communities, stabilise markets, secure the availability of supplies, and provide reasonable prices for consumers. Reforms in the CAP in the 1990s sought to address criticism of the policy for encouraging overproduction, leading to surplus and environmental damage. These issues are addressed by shifting focus towards rural development and environmental sustainability.

This transition had significant implications for Scotland's agricultural policy. With the establishment of the Scottish Parliament in 1999, responsibility for agricultural policy was devolved from the UK government to the newly formed Scottish Executive. This coincided with the CAP's reorientation, providing an opportune moment for the Scottish Executive to align its agricultural policies with the broader EU rural and environmental improvement objectives. The Scottish Executive leveraged this opportunity by abolishing long-established agricultural boards that had regulated the Scottish Office's policy (Jordan & Halpin, 2006). This move signalled a departure from the traditional, production-focused agricultural policies and embraced the CAP's new direction. The creation of the Scottish Executive Environment and Rural Affairs Department (SEERAD) exemplified this shift. SEERAD was designed to integrate agricultural policies with broader rural affairs, reflecting the CAP's holistic approach to rural development.

The significance of the EEC/EU and CAP in shaping Scottish agricultural policy cannot be overstated. The CAP reforms provided a framework and impetus for Scotland to modernise its agricultural policies, aligning them with contemporary priorities such as environmental sustainability and rural development. The role of the EU and CAP thus facilitated a transformative period in Scottish agricultural policy, enabling the newly devolved government to adopt and implement progressive changes that would benefit rural communities and the environment.

Historical Institutionalism defines a critical juncture as a pivotal moment when a substantial transformation sets an institution on a new course (Mahoney & Thelen, 2010). Introducing a devolved parliament and significant agricultural support policy reforms eliminated many agricultural policy networks. The new Executive created new governance structures around

agricultural policy and shifted policy objectives from purely agricultural to expanding and including rural affairs. These changes in 1999 created substantial changes in Scotland's agricultural support policy, and a new pathway opened.

The Scottish government had introduced a tailored policy to suit the unique farming sector in Scotland. In 2004, SEERAD introduced the Less Favoured Area Support Scheme (LFASS). It was similar to the LFA payment scheme but contained an element that increased funding for areas classed as fragile. These fragile areas were based on location and grazing quality, while those on the islands or mainland were in remote locations (Scottish Government, 2005). These schemes effectively supported farming in less favoured areas, covering 85% of all farming in Scotland. In 2005, the Scottish Executive Environment and Rural Affairs Department (SEERAD) introduced the Scottish Beef Calf Scheme to support farming in less favoured areas (LFA).

Being able to provide subsidies to fit the needs of Scottish Agriculture was crucial. However, in the last block of CAP reforms, the UK government's concerns began to be raised by many in the Scottish Parliament, who believed that the UK was moving towards a set of priorities that would not benefit Scottish agriculture and rural affairs. The UK government introduced the Agricultural Act in 2020, with a policy to phase out subsidies in England. The Scottish Parliament was concerned with introducing the Agriculture Act 2020, the UK Internal Market Act 2020 and the Subsidy Control Act 2022 and how these pieces of legislation could constrain future policy decisions and legislation on agricultural support in Scotland (SPICe, 2022).

The publication of the common framework should have resolved the future of agricultural support as an overarching policy document. However, the final document contains no policy. When the devolved administrations introduce a new policy, it must ensure it does not interact with these new pieces of legislation. This has the potential to constrain the devolved governments, and it might appear that the UK government is trying to re-centralise power and weaken devolution. The new common frameworks, intended to provide a UK bespoke policy framework, have instead produced a generic policy document that outlines processes rather than detailed policy prescriptions, thus limiting the flexibility that the CAP once provided.

8.3 Common Frameworks and ‘Muscular Unionism:’ Principles and Challenges in Post-Brexit UK Governance

8.3.1 The Principles Underpinning the Common Frameworks

The UK and the devolved governments recognised the need for common frameworks to substitute EU frameworks and ensure a unified approach that upholds minimum standards, safeguards the internal market, and enables the UK to forge international trade agreements (Cabinet, 2017). The process was also guided by a set of fundamental principles that were collectively agreed upon, and the subsequent section will assess how well these principles were adhered to.

The first principle agreed that common frameworks would be established on existing “conventions and practices and agreed that the competence of devolved institutions would not normally be adjusted without their consent” (Cabinet Office, 2017). However, the legislative consent motion (Sewel Convention) was tested in the Supreme Court shortly after this principle was agreed. The legislative consent motion in the Memorandum of Understanding established that the UK government would not legislate in the devolved policy area without the consent of the devolved governments. At the Supreme Court in the *R (Miller) v Secretary of State for Exiting the European Union*, the court ruled that the Sewel Conventions held ineffective legal status, allowing the UK government to pass legislation on devolved competencies. "Since the convention is simply constitutional, political convention and accordingly non-justiciable" (Engel & Petetin, 2018, p. 26). The Supreme Court judgment established that devolved governments held no power to prevent the UK government from passing legislation on devolved policy.

The second principle implies that the common framework will “maintain, as a minimum, equivalent flexibility for tailoring policies to the specific needs of each territory, as afforded by current EU rules”(Cabinet Office, 2017). This principle is supposed to offer devolved governments the opportunity to design bespoke agricultural policies and support programmes. However, the Agricultural Act (2020), UK IMA (2020), and Subsidy Control Act (2022) (SCA) could undermine this framework and curtail the possibility of divergence. This is a particular issue for agricultural support in Scotland and Wales because of the substantial amount of farmland classed as less favoured areas (LFA), so dependent on subsidies, as outlined in Chapter 6. Devolved governments consistently expressed their concerns in Chapter 7. Jeremy Miles MS, the Counsel-General and Minister for European Transition for the Welsh

Government, referred to improving the Welsh government's relationship with the UK government, stating:

"With respect to everybody concerned, it is entirely Kafkaesque to talk about the reset in relationships while still pursuing the internal market Bill in its current form" (Miles, 2020, p.20).

The third principle stated that the new common frameworks would lead to an increase in decision-making power. However, it is unclear how this could be achieved. There was no further discussion or agreement on how this principle could be realised during the Joint Ministerial Committee (EU Negotiations). The common framework for agricultural support published in 2022 states that common frameworks "will respect the devolution settlements and the democratic accountability of the devolved legislatures, and will therefore lead to a significant increase in decision-making powers for the devolved administrations" (Cabinet Office, 2022, p.25). However, there are no specific details on how this will be achieved.

8.3.2 Muscular Unionism

Two discourses emerged throughout the Brexit withdrawal period and when the common frameworks were being developed. The first centres around 'parity of esteem', and both Scottish and Welsh ministers suggested that if the UK government adopted this approach and fully engaged in the commitment to cooperation, collaboration and respect for devolution, then IGR would improve. However, Mike Russell noted:

"I go back to this issue of different roles and responsibilities for the Governments, but no hierarchy of Governments. Regrettably, that is because the UK Government has not fully recognised the principle of equity. I hope it will be because, when it is recognised, it is possible to put something in place that will work. It will not work if it is simply a mish-mash of what we presently have" (Russell, 2020, p.17).

This statement underscores the importance of a balanced power distribution in a devolved polity, which should enable autonomy in the subnational regions and ensure adequate machinery for power and decision-sharing. However, with the UK introducing legislation that could undermine the common framework, devolved government members involved in the development process repeatedly expressed their frustrations and fears about the future of devolution. The legally non-binding nature of the UK's intergovernmental agreements further complicates this issue, highlighting the need to understand how power is distributed and maintained.

The second theme centred around the notion of 'taking back control' and reviving old parliamentary sovereignty debates. Hunt (2017) posed the question that, with the emergence of

devolved governments, where control would be restored in the UK that had been transformed by multi-level governance and enhanced devolution. Andrews (2021) noted the shift from the early devolution settlement's 'devolve and forget' unionism of the early devolution settlement. There are indications that the UK government is deliberately working to undermine devolution by employing 'muscular unionism' to bypass the Scottish and Welsh governments, particularly with funding that once came from the EU (Andrews, 2021).

Additionally, Brexit has intensified the challenges within the UK's intergovernmental relations. The loss of EU frameworks has removed a layer of shared governance that previously mediated central-devolved relations and prompted the UK government to assert greater control over areas like agricultural policy. This shift underscores the need for robust mechanisms to maintain the balance of power and support meaningful collaboration post-Brexit, ensuring that devolved administrations can effectively participate in designing policies that meet their unique needs (McEwen & Schakel, 2016).

This approach may explain why the UK government is willing to introduce legislation that has the potential to undermine devolution and create political tension. The Sewel Convention, which states that the UK government will not legislate on devolved matters without the consent of the devolved governments, is only a convention and not legally enforceable (McHarg, 2017). Wincott, Murray, and Davis (2022) noted the return of the language of the unitary state as a de facto victory for the central state in asserting its power (McHarg, 2017). This highlights the importance of robust power distribution and decision-sharing mechanisms to maintain the autonomy of subnational regions.

Sandford and Gormley-Heenan (2020) proposed that if new structures were established to enable the UK government and devolved administrations to negotiate joint competencies and implement more effective dispute-resolution mechanisms, it might be feasible to redefine the constitutional relationship. However, during the development of the intergovernmental review, the UK government had the opportunity to introduce robust mechanisms to protect the intergovernmental relationship but chose not to. This decision underscores the central government's preference to maintain control, reflecting a persistent power asymmetry that challenges the balance necessary for effective and respectful devolution.

8.4 Conclusion

In conclusion, this chapter has highlighted the complexities and challenges in the evolution of intergovernmental relations (IGR) in the UK, particularly in the context of agricultural policy.

The initial institutional design, characterised by path dependency and power asymmetry, has profoundly influenced the development and performance of IGR. The persistence of these dynamics demonstrates that mechanisms of reproduction, like layering, contribute to maintaining the status quo and have created a framework resistant to significant change, perpetuating existing power imbalances.

The Common Agricultural Policy's flexibility allowed devolved administrations in Scotland and Wales to tailor agricultural policies to their unique needs, fostering divergence within a unified EU framework. However, in a post-Brexit UK, the introduction of the Agriculture Act 2020, the UK Internal Market Act 2020, and the Subsidy Control Act 2022 has raised concerns about the potential re-centralization of power and the constraints on policy divergence. These legislative changes threaten to undermine the devolved administrations' ability to develop and implement region-specific agricultural policies, thus challenging the principle of subsidiarity that underpins effective devolution.

The principles of shared decision-making and shared rules are critical for fostering a collaborative governance environment. Effective IGR should ensure that devolved administrations have a meaningful role in shaping policies that affect their regions, promoting autonomy while maintaining coherence within the UK's broader political structure. The findings emphasise the need for robust mechanisms to protect the spirit of devolution and ensure meaningful collaboration. Creating a multi-tiered dispute resolution process and a standing IGR secretariat, as outlined in the 2022 intergovernmental review, are steps in the right direction. These structures aim to facilitate shared decision-making and establish clear rules for resolving conflicts, thus supporting a more balanced power distribution. However, without legally binding commitments to respect devolved competencies, these structures may fall short of addressing the underlying power imbalances and ensuring equitable decision-making.

The concept of 'muscular unionism' encapsulates the UK government's approach to asserting control over devolved matters, reflecting a shift from cooperative to more centralised governance. This tension between maintaining devolved autonomy and the central government's efforts to 'take back control' underscores the ongoing challenges in achieving a balanced and collaborative intergovernmental relationship. The divergence in approaches and priorities between the UK government and the devolved administrations highlights the fragility of the current IGR framework.

This chapter provides a comprehensive synthesis of the key findings from the preceding chapters, setting the stage for the final chapter, which will directly address the research questions, discuss the original contribution to knowledge, and offer suggestions for further areas of research.

Chapter 9: Conclusion

9.1 Introduction

This final chapter revisits this thesis's overall aims and research questions, synthesising the findings and drawing comprehensive conclusions. It also highlights the original contributions to knowledge made by this research and reflects on the study's limitations. The chapter concludes with recommendations for future research, addressing the gaps identified and proposing directions for further investigation.

9.2 Aims of the Thesis

This thesis aimed to critically examine the institutional interactions of the UK government and the Devolved Administrations (DAs) of Scotland and Wales and how the intergovernmental framework enabled the common framework for agricultural support that replaces the European Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). No other state has left the EU, and the UK and devolved governments had never jointly developed a UK-wide policy framework. Therefore, there was a lack of empirical knowledge about how a member state negotiates with devolved or regional administrations to replace EU policy frameworks, and no state has had to create an alternative to the CAP. This complex process raised questions about how the intergovernmental framework would perform during such a challenging and unprecedented period.

This research examined the institutional interactions of the UK government and the DAs, focusing on how the IGR mechanisms support the fundamental principles of cooperation, coordination, and consent agreed upon in the JMC communique (EN) to underpin the development of the New Common Framework for Agricultural Support. This project critically examines how the intergovernmental framework can support the development of new common frameworks to replace the European Common Agricultural Policy.

9.3 Addressing the Research Questions

Primary Research Question: To what extent does the intergovernmental relationship enable Scottish and Welsh administrations to participate in designing a new common framework for agricultural support?

Supplementary Questions:

1. What are the fundamental principles and structures underpinning the UK's intergovernmental frameworks?

2. To what extent have they developed since the introduction of devolution?
3. To what extent has previous engagement with the UK government in developing agricultural support policy shaped the current intergovernmental relationship?
4. To what extent is the experience different for Scottish and Welsh administrations?

The primary research question aims to understand how the devolved administrations and the UK government collaborated to develop a new common framework for agricultural support between 2016 and 2022. The supplementary questions were designed to construct a historical context of intergovernmental relationships from 1999 to 2016, exploring the principles that underpin the IGR and how they have evolved as the development and implementation of the CAP and the differing experiences between Scotland and Wales due to their distinct devolution settlement.

This thesis examined how the intergovernmental relationship (IGR) enabled the devolved governments in Scotland and Wales to participate in developing a new common framework for agricultural support. As the UK transitioned to withdraw from the EU, the UK and devolved governments agreed that replacement policy frameworks would be required before returning competencies to the devolved governments (Cabinet Office, 2017). They decided to ensure the process would be cooperative and collaborative with respect to devolution. Additionally, they agreed to review intergovernmental relations to develop machinery to enhance joint decision-making and resolve disputes (Cabinet Office, 2018). Under these circumstances, the devolved governments in Scotland and Wales had some expectations that they would be treated with 'parity of esteem' (Fabiani, 2016; Russell, 2020).

The devolved governments agreed that developing a common framework at the official level was productive. However, due to delays in details released by DEFRA, ministers had less engagement in the process, and parliamentary scrutiny was significantly delayed. The House of Lords Common Frameworks Scrutiny Committee, appointed to scrutinise all matters related to common frameworks, identified three issues: lack of transparency in the development process, political tensions between the UK and devolved governments, and UK legislation, which has exacerbated tensions. All of these factors have impeded intergovernmental relations across the UK. The devolved governments also agreed that the actions of the UK government overshadowed the process. They believed the common frameworks would fail and be 'sidestepped' by the UK government.

The provisional common framework for agricultural support was published in 2022, two years after it was expected to be operational. This common framework shares a generic format with all National Common Frameworks (NCFs) designed using DEFRA. Therefore, this intergovernmental agreement has limited policy implications. This framework was introduced to replace the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), a significant policy that enabled the devolved governments to determine their priorities in agricultural support. This resulted in 'four CAPs' in the UK. Divergence was possible within the EU, and the UK is an excellent example of a member state that has benefited from this flexible approach. Each part of the United Kingdom has begun to develop a new support policy to replace the CAP. However, the Scottish government is the only one likely to continue applying similar EU subsidy support systems. It is unclear how new subsidy support policies will interact with the UK Internal Market Act 2020 (UKIMA) and the Subsidy Control Act 2022 (SCA), which could undermine this framework and curtail the possibility of divergence. The framework document contains information on the process of agricultural support and sets out a new three-level structure that would manage policy divergence and resolve disputes. However, it will not be tested until the Scottish government produces its agricultural support policy in 2024. The document introduced two other elements that would solve the previous criticism of the IGR: transparency and consistency in engagement. This document clarifies the roles and responsibilities of officials and details regular engagement from the official to the ministerial level.

The UK and devolved governments agreed that the process would be cooperative, collaborative, and respectful of devolution. However, the UK government introduced new legislation throughout the development process: the Agriculture Act 2020, the UK Internal Market Act 2020, and the Subsidy Control Act 2022. The Scottish and Welsh governments have raised many concerns about the legislation and its impact on devolution and policy divergence. Both devolved governments believe that this legislation undermines the spirit of the JMC (EN) principles and the framework's function. The intergovernmental relationship functioned such that the devolved governments could participate in developing a common framework for agricultural support. However, no intergovernmental machinery is available to the devolved governments to compel the UK government to consider their objections to the legislation they believe undermines devolution and the common frameworks.

9.4 Conclusion

The research presented in this thesis provides a detailed analysis of how intergovernmental relationships have evolved in the UK and how these relationships have influenced the

development of a new common framework for agricultural support. It highlights the complexity of intergovernmental interactions and the challenges devolved administrations face in influencing UK-wide policies. The findings underscore the importance of clear, transparent, and cooperative intergovernmental mechanisms to support effective governance and respect for devolution.

The study reveals that significant challenges remain while there have been productive engagements at the official level. These challenges include a lack of transparency, political tensions, and the impact of UK legislation on devolution. The introduction of the Agriculture Act 2020, the UK Internal Market Act 2020, and the Subsidy Control Act 2022 has created concerns about the potential centralisation of power and the undermining of devolved competencies. These legislative changes suggest a shift towards 'muscular unionism', where the UK government seeks to assert greater control over devolved areas, raising questions about the future of devolution and intergovernmental relations.

In conclusion, the intergovernmental relationship in the UK has enabled the participation of devolved administrations in developing a new common framework for agricultural support. However, the process has been hindered by delays, lack of transparency, and the imposition of UK legislation that threatens to undermine devolution. In improving intergovernmental relations and ensuring effective governance, it is essential to address these challenges by enhancing transparency, fostering genuine cooperation, and respecting the principles of devolution. These findings and recommendations provide a foundation for future research and policy development, addressing the identified gaps and proposing directions for further investigation.

9.5 Contribution to Knowledge

9.5.1 Introduction

This PhD thesis makes significant contributions to addressing critical gaps in existing literature. The thesis employs innovative research methods, such as case-oriented process tracing and thematic analysis within a critical realist framework, enhancing the depth of analysis and advancing qualitative research methodologies. Data collection methods resulted in governmental reviews and transcripts employed to generate rich empirical material and shed light on unexplored intergovernmental relations and policy development. Additionally, the thesis expands on historical institutionalism, particularly regarding exercising power to maintain the status quo. By integrating empirical findings, innovative methods, and theoretical

insights, this thesis advances our understanding of governance dynamics post-Brexit, shaping scholarly discourse and informing future research.

9.5.2 Empirical Contribution

This thesis significantly advances the empirical understanding of Brexit's impact on UK governance and policy frameworks. It addresses a critical gap in the literature by examining how the UK government navigated the intricate process of replacing EU policies post-Brexit. As the first member state to withdraw from the EU, the UK's experience provides a unique and underexplored field of study. This research project commenced before Brexit and concluded upon its implementation, offering a comprehensive examination of this transformative period. Moreover, the UK's status as a decentralised state due to devolution added complexity to the Brexit process, necessitating the involvement of devolved governments in Scotland and Wales. This study contributes to the literature on common frameworks and explores explicitly their application in agricultural policy, an area previously unexplored in published research. It offers novel insights into the development of these frameworks, the influence of devolved administrations, and the outcomes achieved in agricultural support policy under the new arrangements.

This thesis also contributes to the study of intergovernmental relations (IGR) within the UK context. Due to its informal nature, the existing literature faces challenges in operationalising and collecting empirical data in this field. This study overcomes these limitations by providing a comprehensive empirical review from 1999 to 2022 and contextualising these relationships' evolution over time by analysing UK government-commissioned reviews of devolution and IGR. It highlights historical nuances in how intergovernmental dynamics functioned in Scotland and Wales, particularly in agricultural policy implementation and divergence within the EU framework.

Furthermore, this study highlights the implications of recent UK legislation, such as the Internal Market Act 2020 and the Subsidy Control Act 2022, on the autonomy of devolved administrations post-Brexit. It underscores concerns in Scotland and Wales regarding potential constraints on their policy divergence capabilities, emphasising the evolving nature of devolution within the UK constitutional framework. This thesis advances scholarly understanding by offering empirical insights into Brexit's implications for UK governance and policy frameworks, particularly in agricultural policy and intergovernmental relations. It fills crucial gaps in existing literature and provides a nuanced historical analysis of UK devolution

and intergovernmental dynamics, contributing to broader debates on governance, autonomy, and constitutionalism in a post-Brexit era.

9.5.3 Research Methods Contribution: Data Collection and Analysis

This study encountered significant challenges, particularly regarding access to data through interviews and documentation on intergovernmental relations. Due to these constraints, conventional data collection methods were impractical. However, a novel approach emerged during the House of Lords Scrutiny Committee's review of the common framework process. Rich transcripts were generated through 22 in-depth sessions with Scottish, Welsh, and UK government officials. These detailed insights, from the inception to the conclusion of the process, provided invaluable data that surpassed what might typically be available to a post-graduate researcher. This innovative solution addressed a critical gap in empirical data and enhanced the originality and depth of this research.

Due to the informal nature of intergovernmental relations, operationalising a study can be challenging. This study turned to existing UK government commission reviews. These documents provided historical context and systematic insights into the perspectives of past ministers and officials on intergovernmental dynamics. By synthesising and analysing this data, the study enriched its understanding of how intergovernmental relations have evolved and functioned within the UK's constitutional framework.

This research also contributes to the methodological literature on case-oriented process tracing, specifically in the context of the Scottish and Welsh governments' interactions with the UK government. Unlike the more commonly used hypothesis testing method of process tracing, case-oriented process tracing allows for detailed examination and comparison across cases, which may limit exploration in lesser-known areas; by adopting this approach, the study offers a nuanced understanding of policy development and implementation dynamics within devolved contexts, contributing to methodological advancements in comparative process tracing methodologies.

This study advances the growing use of the critical realism approach to thematic analysis. Thematic analysis is traditionally versatile but can sometimes lack depth in causal inference. By integrating critical realism, which emphasises identifying underlying causal mechanisms, the study goes beyond describing patterns to explore why and how these patterns emerge. This approach enhances the explanatory power of thematic analysis, providing a more profound understanding of the social phenomena under study. By contributing to the application of

critical realism in thematic analysis, this research enhances the methodological toolkit available to qualitative researchers, particularly in exploring complex social interactions and structural influences.

9.5.4 Theoretical Contribution to Knowledge

This PhD thesis enriches the theoretical landscape of historical institutionalism by departing from conventional perspectives focused on institutional stability or abrupt change triggered by exogenous critical junctures. While recent literature has explored how endogenous pressures can lead to incremental change, this research introduces a nuanced perspective. It posits that change can also occur gradually as those in power strategically manoeuvre to preserve the status quo in their favour. By examining these dynamics within the context of Brexit and the evolution of UK governance post-EU membership, this study contributes to a deeper understanding of how institutional arrangements adapt over time.

Central to this theoretical contribution is exploring power distribution and its influence on modes of institutional change aimed at maintaining vested interests. Rather than viewing power as a zero-sum game where veto power dominates, this study applies and expands on the concept of veto possibilities. These possibilities represent nuanced mechanisms through which actors with limited power can still shape outcomes in their favour within institutional settings. By unpacking these dynamics, the research sheds light on how actors navigate and influence institutional evolution amid complex political environments. This study builds upon the limited existing literature, providing empirical insights and a deeper understanding of how veto possibilities function in practice. Thus, it contributes to the broader discourse on institutional change and power dynamics.

9.6 Reflections & Limitations

Every research endeavour encounters limitations, and this study is no exception, particularly in navigating the complexities of studying unfolding events. This project commenced in September 2017, just before the UK and devolved governments agreed on the foundational principles of new common frameworks at a Joint Ministerial Committee (EN). Initial expectations included the UK's withdrawal from the EU by 2020 and the timely development of a comprehensive common framework for agricultural support. This framework was anticipated to catalyse substantial discussions between the UK government and devolved administrations toward establishing a unified UK agricultural policy post-Brexit. However, these expectations were not met. The UK's departure from the EU did not occur until 2020, and

the provisional common frameworks document was not published until February 2022. Even then, it contained limited specifics on agricultural support and mostly outlined procedural frameworks rather than detailed policy prescriptions.

A second significant limitation stemmed from the challenges of studying intergovernmental relations (IGR). Access to detailed information on formal IGR mechanisms has been restricted, with much of the process conducted behind closed doors within Joint Ministerial Committee meetings. Recent efforts by the UK government to enhance transparency, such as publishing limited meeting details and participant lists, have only partially addressed this issue. Moreover, the literature on devolution and IGR remains sparse, particularly concerning the Welsh administration's interactions with the UK government. Unlike Scotland's more distinct devolution settlement, early Welsh devolution was ambiguous, necessitating predominantly informal dialogues among ministers and officials. These informal discussions are not widely documented in the public domain, further limiting the scope of existing academic literature.

Additionally, the COVID-19 pandemic and Brexit's evolving nature posed challenges. The continuous changes in political and legislative contexts required ongoing adjustments to the research focus and methodology. This fluid situation introduced unpredictable elements that complicated long-term planning and data collection.

9.7 Recommendations for Future Research

The study of common frameworks offers multiple streams of opportunities for further investigation. This study raises many questions that could be considered for further research. The first relates specifically to the Common Framework for Agricultural Support. The second refers to common frameworks in other policy areas. The third considers the future of devolution, intergovernmental relationships, and the impact of the Internal Market Act 2020 and the Subsidy Control Act 2022.

This study concludes in 2022 with the publication of the provisional Common Framework for Agricultural Support, an agreement still in its early stages. The new structures for managing divergence and disputes have yet to be thoroughly tested. During the study, the UK government introduced the Agriculture Act 2020 and policy documents to end direct support for farmers in England. Each UK member developed agricultural support frameworks, aligning Wales broadly with England's approach. The Scottish government retained EU CAP support frameworks and plans to introduce a new support framework in 2024/25, likely retaining some form of direct farmer support. Future research should empirically analyse how the Common

Framework for Agricultural Support is tested when Scotland implements its new agricultural policy. The likely retention of subsidies in Scotland, contrasting with policies in England and Wales, could create political tensions. Research should investigate whether the Scottish policy faces tests for excessive divergence through the common framework mechanisms or if the UK government challenges it via the UK Internal Market Act 2020 or the Subsidy Control Act 2022. Additionally, examining how these potential challenges test intergovernmental relationships and the effectiveness of the new intergovernmental framework would provide valuable insights into UK intergovernmental relations and the practical implementation of new policy frameworks.

Secondly, this study focused on the Common Framework for Agricultural Support. DEFRA oversaw the development of 14 frameworks and admitted they had used a generic format with limited policy details, mainly containing process information. Due to the pressures of the pandemic and the urgency of leaving the EU, DEFRA had to abandon plans for a bespoke agricultural support policy initially discussed at the start of the framework creation. Consequently, all frameworks under DEFRA's remit became generic for expedience. Future research could benefit from a comparative analysis between DEFRA and another Whitehall department that had the opportunity to design a new common framework in conjunction with the devolved governments in Scotland and Wales. Investigating how another department managed the creation of bespoke frameworks despite challenges could provide valuable empirical insights into the intergovernmental relationship and the effectiveness of different framework design approaches. Such a comparison could reveal how different policy areas and departmental strategies influence the development and implementation of common frameworks. It could also show how collaboration between the UK government and devolved administrations varies across policy sectors, contributing to a deeper understanding of intergovernmental dynamics and offering practical lessons for future framework development.

Thirdly, the empirical analysis of the common framework revealed that the UK Internal Market Act 2020 and the Subsidy Control Act 2022 dominated discussions, with devolved governments expressing intense concern about their impact on devolution. Several ministers argued that these Acts could roll back devolution settlements, aligning with the 'taking back control' rhetoric of some UK Ministers supporting Brexit. These legislative changes present significant research opportunities, particularly in studying their impact on intergovernmental relationships within the theoretical framework of path dependency. Path dependency suggests that institutional decisions set trajectories that are difficult to alter, often favouring those in

power. By examining the UK Internal Market Act 2020 and the Subsidy Control Act 2022 through this lens, we can gain valuable insights into how these laws influence the balance of power between the UK government and devolved administrations. Future research should explore whether these Acts allow the UK government to centralise control, potentially disrupting the devolution settlement. Detailed study of these Acts could illuminate whether they reinforce existing power structures or prompt meaningful changes in the governance of devolved nations. This focus is crucial for understanding power dynamics, governance, and the future of devolution in the UK, addressing critical issues that warrant academic attention and new literature.

In conclusion, this section highlights several critical areas for future research on common frameworks and intergovernmental relations in the UK. These studies will provide a deeper understanding of the dynamics of UK governance, the balance of power, and the evolving nature of devolution. Addressing these research areas will contribute significantly to the literature on intergovernmental relations and path dependency and provide valuable insights to guide future policy development.

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Appendix

Appendix A. Chapter 5 Coding Example

<p>Question: What are the fundamental principles and structures underpinning the UK's intergovernmental frameworks? To what extent have they developed since the introduction of devolution? To what extent is the experience different for Scottish and Welsh administrations?</p>
<p>Theme 1: UK GOVERNMENT SETS THE PARAMETERS FOR THE RELATIONSHIP Subtheme 1.1 Devolution Structure Codes: Transfer of powers from Scottish/Welsh Office, Asymmetrical power distribution, continuation and continuity, devolution nested within existing structures Subtheme 1.2 Devolved Engagement in Process Codes: Lack of devolved parliamentary engagement, UK design IGR architecture, Legacy of the previous arrangement before devolution</p>
<p>Theme 2: AGREED INITIAL UNDERPINNINGS OF IGR Subtheme 2.1 Agreed Principles Codes: Communication, Confidentiality, Cooperation, non-legally binding</p>
<p>Theme 3: FEATURES OF DEVOLUTION THAT IMPACT ON IGR Subtheme 3.1 Devolution changed the political structure of the UK Codes: Anomaly of England, Asymmetrical devolution, Party (In)Congruence, Devolution is an evolving process, Devolution has little impact on UK institutions, Devolution radical change difficult, Devolution settlement is problematic, devolved should know their limits</p>
<p>Theme 4: ISSUES FOR SCOTLAND Subtheme 4.1 Issues for the UK Codes: Role of civil service, Role of Sec of state, Resistance to Independence, Support for Independence, demand for more powers, More devolution, stronger UK Subtheme 4.2 Issues for Scottish Administration Codes: Anti-independence cross-party agreement, Joint working, Joint decision-making, dispute resolution, Support for more powers</p>
<p>Theme 5: ISSUES FOR WALES Subtheme 5.1 Issues for the UK Codes: Confusion over responsibilities, making space at the House of Commons, Role of civil service, Role of Sec of state, committee multiplicity. Subtheme 5.2 Issues for Wales Codes: Role of civil service, Role of Secretaries of State, confusion over responsibility, powerlessness, multiplicity, delays waiting for HoC,</p>
<p>Theme 6: ASSESSING THE IGR Subtheme 6.1 Ineffectiveness or misuse of IGR mechanisms Codes: Critic of IGR, Dispute escalation effectiveness, JMC does not resolve disputes, JMC is not fit for purpose, UK not legally bound, Lack of legal agreement, Legislative consent, Request for more formality Subtheme 6.2 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR UNDERPINNING OF IGR AFTER REVIEWS Codes: Ensuring DA Consent, Constitutional reform, More Consultation, Departments in regular contact, development of cooperation, Devolution evolves, Enhanced powers, Fairness, Future of Devolution, Improved guidelines for the relationship, Institutional cooperation, multi-level engagement, Multi-level engagement, request for more transparency to each parliament, Respect for all four parts, Respect for devolution, Increased scrutiny, joint decision-making, Transparency, Improve Trust Subtheme 6.3 PROMISES OF REFORM Codes: Agreement of Priorities, Improved Department multi-level working JMC should support relationships, Possible IGR reforms, and Pragmatic IGR working Refine mechanisms, Reform within existing structures</p>

Appendix B. Retained EU laws – Basic Acts.

Regulation 1305/2013 ("the Rural Development Regulation"): This Regulation establishes support for Rural Development by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development,

Regulation 1303/2013 ("the common provisions Regulation"): This Regulation lays down common provisions on EU funds, and in particular on the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development

Regulation 1306/2013 ("the Horizontal Regulation"): This Regulation covers the financing, management and monitoring of the Common Agricultural Policy, and in particular, it provides for cross-cutting measures that apply to all areas of the CAP.

Regulation 1307/2013 ("the Direct Payments Regulation"): This Regulation establishes rules for Direct Payments to farmers under support schemes within the framework of the CAP.

Regulation 1308/2013 ("The Single CMO Regulation"): This Regulation establishes a common organisation of the markets in agricultural products ("CMO")

(DEFRA, 2022)

Appendix C. The UK Agricultural Policy Collaboration Group (PCG)

Share thinking about ideas and plans for new policies, schemes, and standards or changes to existing ones.
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Review recommendations coordinated by the MMG and identify and evaluate possible intervention measures.

Consider whether a new or changing policy where divergence occurs in one party will have an unwanted impact on another party and make recommendations to ministers or senior officials accordingly.

Agree recommendations for buying and selling prices and amount of product to be bought in cases of a UK-wide PI/PSA scheme or parallel schemes; and Agricultural Support Provisional Common Framework 48
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Share the information needed to meet obligations to each other and to third parties.
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(DEFRA, 2022, p.47).

Appendix D. The UK Agriculture Market Monitoring Group (MMG)

Review and analysis of market information from government, industry, and other sources.
Determine the main drivers affecting market development and assess whether they have short- or long-term effects.
Identifying and assessing cross-sector impacts of market development.
Identification of specific regional issues or variations should be considered.
Providing advice to senior officials and Ministers on developments in the market; Agricultural Support Provisional Common Framework 52
Providing a forum for discussion of market impacts across the UK Kingdom
Providing a platform for Policy Leads to consider UK MMG evidence at the separate UK Agriculture Market Policy Group (UKAMPG) to: - assess potential problems/issues; - follow up on intelligence outside UK MMG meetings to assess the impact of possible solutions, including any delivery issues; and
Providing residual reporting information to the EC.

(DEFRA, 2022, p.51).

Appendix E. Responsibilities of Inter-Ministerial Group (IMG-EFRA)

Support the IMG EFRA to discharge its responsibilities in line with its scope and purpose and the activities set out in the IMG EFRA program of work.
Ensure that effective structures and governance are in place to support and monitor the delivery of work programs.
The four administrations' engagement and working groups to examine matters arising, provide a paper or update on the work program progress, and join SOPB meetings to participate in discussions on relevant topics. Agricultural Support Provisional Common Framework 33
On behalf of the IMG EFRA, the Board will ensure that information is shared with both existing and any future wider intergovernmental forums if required and with external stakeholders if it agrees to do so.
Each member is responsible for ensuring information flow and joining their own administration.
Recommend the direction and benefits of any new future activities for the IMG EFRA.
The monitor progresses and provides direction for the ongoing development, implementation, operation, review, and adjustments of any agreed common framework.
Provide a dispute resolution mechanism for common frameworks and a wider EFRA policy prior to the escalation of any disagreements with IMG EFRA.
Respond to any unforeseen matters, such as civil contingency issues arising from disease outbreaks, where joint action is agreed to be beneficial and/or necessary. This will not replace or interrupt the responsibilities of each administration nor other agencies who may be responding to civil contingency matters, e.g., arm's length bodies such as the APHA.
Identify interdependencies and risks to the effectiveness of IMG EFRA or joint working underway between UK administrations and consider and implement preventive and mitigating measures.

(DEFRA, 2022, pp.32-33).